

Inherit

Second INHERIT Assessment & Monitoring Framework / D3.2

WP3 – T3.1, T3.2, T3.3, T3.4, T3.5

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Technical references

Project Acronym	INHERIT
Project Title	Next Generation Solutions for Sustainable, Inclusive, Resource-efficient and Resilient Cultural Heritage
Project Coordinator	Stamatia Rizou SingularLogic srizou@singularlogic.eu
Project Duration	October 2023 – March 2027 (42 months)
Deliverable No.	D3.2
Dissemination level*	PU - Public
Work Package	WP3 – Framework for assessment and monitoring of CH, and catalogue of solutions towards sustainability and resource-efficiency
Tasks	T3.1 – INHERIT heritage resource-efficient technical inspection T3.2 – INHERIT assessment and monitoring framework T3.3 – Web-based application for multi-dimensional assessment T3.4 – INHERIT Hub of measures inventory for efficient, inclusive, resilient and low-emission CH T3.5 – Financial sustainability and risk assessment methodology for sustainable and inclusive CH
Lead beneficiary	3 (CARTIF)
Contributing beneficiary/ies	1 (SLG), 2 (ICCS), 4 (UPCR), 5 (ZSI), 6 (ICLEI), 7 (ISSO), 9 (REGEA), 10 (BOUYGUES), 11 (ELLET), 12 (RPR), 13 (Fasada), 14 (CEMOSA), 15 (UU), 16 (IBB), 17 (UCL), 18 (EAHTR).
Due date of deliverable	30 June 2025
Actual submission date	30 June 2025

* PU = Public -fully open

Funded by
the European Union

The INHERIT project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101123326.

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v	Date	Beneficiary	Author	Comment
0.1	08/01/2025	CARTIF	Carla Rodríguez Alonso	Table of Content (to be agreed with task leaders)
0.2	03/02/2025	CARTIF	Carla Rodríguez Alonso, Víctor Iván Serna González	Introduction and section 3 of the Assessment and monitoring framework (normalisation of KPIs)
0.3	14/04/2025	CARTIF, ICCS, SLG, CEMOSA, UPRC	...	Structure and content of all sections related to the different tasks.
0.4	10/06/2025	CARTIF, SLG, CEMOSA, UPRC	...	Complete content for all sections.
0.5	16/06/2025	CARTIF	Carla Rodríguez Alonso	Consolidated version to send for internal review
0.6	23/06/2025	UPRC, BOUYGUES	Dimitra Tzani, Xavier Gauvin	Internal review
1.0	30/06/2025	CARTIF	Carla Rodríguez Alonso	Final version for submission

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Abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Description
AENOR	<i>Asociación Española de Normalización y Certificación</i> (Spanish Association for Standardisation and Certification)
AHP	Analytic Hierarchy Process
API	Application Programming Interface
BIM	Building Information Model
CDD	Cooling Degree Days
CEAP	Circular Economy Action Plan
CEN	European Committee for Standardisation (French: Comité Européen de Normalisation)
CH	Cultural Heritage
CI/CD	Continuous Integration and Continuous Delivery/Deployment
CRPD	Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities
D	Deliverable
DHW	Domestic Hot Water
EC	European Commission
EN	European Standard
EP	Energy Performance
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EU	European Union
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GWP	Global Warming Potential
H-BIM	Heritage/Historic Building Information Model
HDD	Heating Degree Days
HVAC	Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning
IAQ	Indoor Air Quality
ICCROM	International Centre for the Study of the Preservation and Restoration of Cultural Property
IEA	International Energy Agency
IEQ	Indoor Environmental Quality
IFC	Industry Foundation Classes
IPCE	<i>Instituto del Patrimonio Cultural de España</i> (Spanish Cultural Heritage Institute)
ISM	Interpretive Structural Modelling
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
JRC	Joint Research Centre (from the European Commission)
KPI	Key Performance Indicator

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Acronym	Description
LCA	Life-Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Cost
NEB	New European Bauhaus
NPV	Net Present Value
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
OEC	Operational Energy Costs
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
PBT	Payback Time
RED	Renewable Energy Directive
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
RMP	Risk Management Plan
RII	Relative Importance Index
s	Service
SRI	Smart Readiness Indicator
T	Task
TI	Technical Inspection
TC	Technical Committee
TWC	Total Water Consumption
UI	User Interface
UNE	Spanish Association for Normalisation (<i>Una Norma Española</i>)
UNESCO	United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organisation
UX	User Experience
WEI	Water Exploitation Index
WFD	Water Framework Directive
WISE	Water Information System for Europe
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This deliverable (D3.2) presents the second version of the INHERIT Assessment and Monitoring Framework, developed under Work Package 3 of the INHERIT project. Building on the foundations laid in D3.1, this document introduces significant enhancements and operational tools designed to support the sustainable transformation of cultural heritage (CH) buildings across Europe. It responds to the need for integrated methodologies that balance conservation imperatives with the objectives of climate resilience, circularity, social value, and long-term viability.

The document is structured around four core contributions:

- 1. Technical Inspection Methodology:** the deliverable presents a refined methodology for the preventive and diagnostic inspection of CH buildings, aligned with European standards and adapted to heritage-specific materials and construction systems. A Digital Inspection Form has been developed to systematise data collection and facilitate future integration into Heritage Building Information Models (H-BIM) models and service workflows.
- 2. Multidimensional Assessment Framework:** a robust set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) across four thematic pillars (1- Energy Performance and Indoor Environmental Quality, 2- Resource Efficiency and Circularity, 3- Climate Resilience, and 4- Accessibility and Socioeconomic Sustainability) has been further developed. Normalisation criteria and tailored weighting schemes support flexible, context-sensitive assessments, enabling prioritisation based on INHERIT criteria and pilot-specific inputs.
- 3. Web-Based Assessment Tool:** a second prototype of the INHERIT digital tool is introduced, operationalising the KPI framework. The tool offers a structured user interface including flexible scoring and visualisation features and enables practitioners to perform multidimensional assessments using pre-defined or custom evaluation schemes.
- 4. INHERIT Hub of Measures:** a structured catalogue of conservation, sustainability, and resilience strategies for CH buildings is presented. Measures are aligned with the four KPI pillars and classified according to their eligibility across different national protection levels, enabling users to identify context-appropriate interventions.
- 5. Financial Sustainability and Risk Assessment Methodology:** a methodology is proposed to evaluate the economic viability and implementation risks of CH interventions. It includes tools for analysing life-cycle costs, financing options, risk exposure, and stakeholder acceptability, supporting strategic planning and informed decision-making.

Combined, these components deliver a comprehensive and user-oriented framework, integrating technical inspection, performance assessment, and actionable planning. The outputs are designed to be tested and validated across INHERIT pilot sites and integrated into digital services, contributing to the broader aims of the New European Bauhaus (NEB) and the European Green Deal.

1 Introduction

The INHERIT project promotes sustainable, inclusive and resource-efficient solutions for CH buildings. These buildings, with diverse ages, construction methods and architectural styles, require tailored approaches for preservation and adaptation to modern standards. INHERIT enhances sustainability while maintaining cultural significance through socially innovative and economically viable interventions at various urban levels, covering the full life cycle of CH buildings.

INHERIT establishes a systematic methodology for sustainable CH solutions, promoting energy efficiency, resource conservation and inclusiveness while respecting historical value. It evaluates potential interventions considering architectural, regulatory, and technical constraints, along with social acceptance and financial viability, supporting the New European Bauhaus values.

This deliverable, the second version of the INHERIT Assessment and Monitoring Framework, further develops the methodology of the technical inspection, complements the monitoring and assessment framework with normalised and weighted KPIs across four pillars, integrates pilot feedback, updates the web-based tool and expands the catalogue of conservation measures. It also outlines financial sustainability and risk assessment methods. The work is connected to INHERIT's decision support services and pilot demonstrations, ensuring solutions are technically sound, socially accepted and adaptable across diverse cultural contexts through continuous stakeholder engagement and iterative refinement across project work packages.

The following Table 1 summarises the services (s.0 to s.10) according to the Heritage Building life cycle phase and indicates the pilots where they will be demonstrated, either as a complete service or in a later stage as early replication.

Table 1: INHERIT pilots and services relation

Heritage Building Lifecycle	INHERIT services	Demonstration and Validation								
		Pilot 1 Croatia	Pilot 2 France	Pilot 3 Greece	Pilot 4 Latvia	Pilot 5 Poland	Pilot 6 Spain	Pilot 7 Sweden	Pilot 8 Turkey	
	Smartification & Data Exchange Platform	s.0								
Design & Renovation	Interactive screen use & AR-VR interfaces	s.1					Repl.			
	Modelling & simulation environment	s.2						Repl.		
	Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	s.3				Repl.		Repl.		Repl.
Monitoring, operation & management	Indoor environmental quality & comfort optimisation	s.4	Repl.							
	Energy forecasting & data-driven intelligent management	s.5			Repl.					
	Digital Twin for heritage facilities' real-time monitoring	s.6					Repl.			
	Real-time insights on activity and mobility patterns	s.7								Repl.
Preservation & maintenance	Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	s.8								
	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	s.9				Repl.				
	Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	s.10								Repl.

1.1 Background and objective

As the energy transition accelerates, the need to harmonise climate neutrality targets with the preservation of World Heritage properties has become increasingly critical. These CH buildings, integral to our historical and cultural fabric, are often energy inefficient and vulnerable to deterioration. Despite their prominence, the role of CH buildings in the broader cultural, social, environmental and economic context is frequently overlooked, underscoring the necessity for innovative assessment and monitoring frameworks (UNESCO, 2009 [01]).

The European Union reports that approximately 35% of buildings are over 50 years old, and nearly 75% of the building stock is energy inefficient. However, renovation of these structures offers a promising opportunity for significant energy and CO₂ savings (European Commission, 2019 [02]). Recent advancements in codes and standards reveal that current structures consume only half the energy of their 1980s counterparts, indicating substantial room for improvement. These findings highlight the urgent need for a holistic approach to upgrading CH buildings.

While prior studies have explored energy retrofitting of CH buildings, gaps remain in critical areas such as accessibility, climate resilience, and decision-making tools. For instance, Polo López et al. (2021 [03]) emphasised the importance of integrating solar panels in line with heritage guidelines, and Franco and Mauri (2024 [04]) highlighted the potential of achieving near-zero energy standards without compromising historical value. However, comprehensive methodologies that address accessibility and multidimensional resilience remain scarce.

To address these challenges, the INHERIT project aims to deliver an integrated framework for the assessment and monitoring of energy renovation in CH buildings. The framework emphasises four pillars:

- 1.** Energy Efficiency and Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ), for enhancing the energy performance while maintaining comfort and preserving heritage value.
- 2.** Resource efficiency, circularity and Life-Cycle Costing (LCC), to ensure sustainable use of resources and cost-effectiveness solutions.
- 3.** Climate resilience and human-made hazards, to safeguard CH buildings against climate change impacts and natural disasters.
- 4.** Accessibility, inclusion, transparency and socio-economic sustainability, to promote inclusiveness and ensure equitable access for all, including people with disabilities.

This deliverable, building on the foundational framework introduced in D3.1 “First INHERIT Assessment and Monitoring Framework”, refines the pillars and complements the overall assessment. It also introduces a novel web-based application to support multidimensional CH site assessment, integrating tools like the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) and offering stakeholders an intuitive platform for data analysis and decision-making.

By aligning with the objectives of the New European Bauhaus, this deliverable seeks to transform CH renovation practices, balancing historical preservation with energy efficiency, resilience and inclusiveness. In doing so, it provides a robust methodology to navigate the complexities of CH building retrofitting, ensuring their sustainability and accessibility for generations to come.

1.2 Deliverable structure

This deliverable is structured into eight main sections and supporting annexes, reflecting the comprehensive scope of WP3 in advancing the INHERIT Assessment and Monitoring Framework. Each section corresponds to a major task within the work package and builds upon the foundation work established in Deliverable 3.1. The structure is as follows:

- **Section 1 – Introduction** sets the context for the deliverable. **Subsection 1.1** provides the **background and objective** of the work, justifying the need for a comprehensive and integrated assessment framework for CH buildings. **Subsection 1.2** (present section) describes the **structure of the document** and how it reflects the organisation of WP3 activities.
- **Section 2 – Technical Inspection methodology** presents the second iteration of the inspection methodology initiated in D3.1. It is structured as follows:
 - **Subsection 2.1** outlines the **core principles** of the methodology, including its normative alignment, adaptive inspection logic tailored to heritage contexts, and risk-based prioritisation model.
 - **Subsection 2.2** delves into **historical materials, techniques and pathologies**, providing typological classification of traditional construction systems and identifying deterioration mechanisms based on European (CEN) and national (UNE) standards.
 - **Subsection 2.3** introduces the **Digital inspection form**, a structured tool to guide inspections in the field, with input-output fields, logic for symptom classification, and integration with H-BIM for service 8.
- **Section 3 – Assessment and monitoring framework** builds on the structure presented in D3.1, offering an expanded and operational framework centred on KPIs across four pillars. This section includes:
 - **Subsection 3.1** provides an **overview of the four KPIs pillars**: Energy Performance & IEQ; Resource Efficiency & Circularity; Climate Resilience; and Accessibility & Socioeconomic Sustainability.
 - **Subsection 3.2** focuses on the **normalisation of KPIs**, presenting criteria and target values tailored to geographic, climatic and contextual variables. It is broken down by pillar:
 - 3.2.1 – Pillar 1 (Energy & Comfort)
 - 3.2.2 – Pillar 2 (Resource & Circularity)
 - 3.2.3 – Pillar 3 (Resilience)
 - 3.2.4 – Pillar 4 (Accessibility & Socioeconomic sustainability)
 - **Subsection 3.3** presents the **weighting and prioritisation** methodologies:
 - 3.3.1 introduces weighting schemes based on a multi-criteria analysis rooted in INHERIT’s core principles.
 - 3.3.2 describes how weighting schemes were refined using input from INHERIT pilot sites through participatory activities.
- **Section 4 – Web-based application for the multi-dimensional assessment** presents the second release of the INHERIT assessment tool, structured as follows:

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- **Subsection 4.1** details the **key features** of the tool, including support for both pre-defined and custom weighting schemes.
- **Subsection 4.2** outlines the **user workflow**, demonstrating how users navigate through the assessment process using the digital platform.
- **Subsection 4.3** provides an overview of the **technical architecture**, including backend components and system interoperability.
- **Section 5 – INHERIT Hub of measures** introduces an evolving inventory of conservation, sustainability and resilience strategies for CH buildings. This section includes:
 - **Subsection 5.1** presents the **first set of validated measures**, structured by stage and linked to specific KPIs.
 - **Subsection 5.2** analyses the **alignment of intervention eligibility** across European protection levels, detailing terminology, legislation, and applicability of the measures catalogued.
- **Section 6 – Financial sustainability and risk assessment methodology** complements the technical and assessment tools with an economic and risk-oriented perspective. It includes:
 - **Subsection 6.1** the **methodological framework**, structured in:
 - 6.1.1 – Financing assessment
 - 6.1.2 – Risk identification and evaluation
 - 6.1.3 – Stakeholder acceptability analysis
 - **Subsection 6.2** identifies the **next steps** for testing and integrating the approach in pilot implementations.
- **Section 7 – Conclusions** summarise the key outcomes of the deliverable, including methodological advancements, tool development, and recommendations for the next stages of INHERIT implementation.
- **Section 8 – References** provides all bibliographic sources cited throughout the deliverable.
- **Annexes** offer essential complementary information and supporting material, including:
 - Expert contributions to inspection criteria (**Annex 1**).
 - Scoring catalogue for materials, pathologies and elements (**Annex 2**).
 - KPI weighting results by criteria (**Annex 3**) and pilot (**Annex 4**).
 - Detailed datasheets of the measures included in the INHERIT Hub (**Annex 5**).

2 Technical Inspection methodology

This section represents the second phase in the development of the Technical Inspection methodology for heritage buildings. Developing upon the foundations established in Deliverable 3.1, this report delves deeper into the main characteristics of these buildings by addressing not only the diversity of **historical materials**, but also the **traditional construction techniques** and **systems**. Many of these elements are often forgotten in contemporary construction practices, and their conservation is further complicated by the scarcity of skilled professionals with knowledge of such techniques.

The conservation and sustainable management of Europe's CH buildings is a shared priority across member states. These buildings face specific challenges due to their age, complexity of materials, construction techniques, and their frequently protected status under national and international heritage regulations.

A key contribution of this report is the integration of a comprehensive understanding of the materials and construction systems used in historic buildings, and their relationship to typical deterioration mechanisms. The document introduces practical inspection criteria tailored to the specific characteristics of traditional architecture, aiming to improve the accuracy and relevance of technical assessments, and to **provide a robust basis for systematic inspection and conservation planning**.

To ensure technical soundness and harmonisation, the developed methodology integrates recognised European (CEN) and national (UNE) standards, ensuring alignment with accepted regulatory and technical frameworks. The result is a unified, flexible, and scalable approach to heritage building inspection, adaptable to various typologies and contexts, and suitable for future integration with digital models.

In addition, this report presents the **Digital Inspection Form** (Excel tool)¹, a spreadsheet-based tool designed to support fieldwork with structured data entry, classification of findings, and progressive interoperability with the H-BIM environment proposed in INHERIT Service 8.

The strategic value of **preventive conservation** is central to this methodology. Rather than reacting to severe damage, it promotes early detection, minimal intervention, and sustainability. As stated by UNESCO, *“Preventive conservation must be seen as a priority... not only to reduce risks but to preserve the authenticity and integrity of cultural heritage”* (UNESCO, 2013 [05]). Aligning the Technical Inspection methodology with this philosophy transforms it from a mere diagnostic tool into a foundational element of proactive heritage management across Europe. The main objectives of this section are:

- To expand and specify the inspection methodology by including detailed classifications of historical materials, construction techniques, systems, and the main pathological symptoms associated with each.

¹ Using Microsoft Excel as the primary tool offers a compelling combination of flexibility, accessibility, and precision. Its customizable structure allows for the creation of tailored templates that can accommodate the unique requirements of heritage buildings. With features like data validation, conditional formatting, and pivot tables, Excel enables inspectors to systematically record, analyse, and visualize inspection data, facilitating informed decision-making. Moreover, its widespread availability ensures that team members and stakeholders can collaborate effectively without the need for specialized software, streamlining communication and reducing training overhead.

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- To support this methodology with a robust normative basis, including the UNE 41805 [06] series and relevant European CEN standards identified in D3.1.
- To document the development and structure of the Digital Inspection Form, which operationalises the methodology and ensures consistency in inspection and data collection.
- To provide a benchmark based on the level of risk of deterioration in terms of cost and priority of intervention to support decision-making and define effective conservation plans.

2.1 Core principles of the TI methodology

The work presented in this document is based on three fundamental axes:

- **Normative alignment:** this includes the analysis and application of national (UNE 41805 [06] series) and European standards (primarily CEN/TC 346 [07]) to ensure that the methodology respects recognized criteria for building diagnostics and CH conservation.
- **Pathological and technical characterisation:** a comprehensive review of materials and construction systems typically found in historical buildings has been carried out. These elements are classified according to their typology and associated deterioration symptoms, making it possible to guide the inspection in a structured and traceable manner.
- **Digital inspection tool development:** a functional spreadsheet-based tool has been created to guide field inspections, record findings, and classify pathologies under standardised criteria. This tool also embeds the inspection logic and facilitates interoperability with other documentation and future H-BIM integrations.

Before going further into the development of the methodology, the main updates and strategies that support and justify the work described in this section are compiled and presented below.

2.1.1 Methodological evolution

Deliverable 3.1 introduced the general structure of the inspection methodology, organised around five initial inspection headings: **foundations and structures, façades and roofs, installations, accessibility, and functional behaviour**. It also presented a "pyramidal" prioritisation model to address critical structural stability first and progressively incorporate performance and usability criteria.

Figure 1: Technical inspection headings focused on building construction and functional and user systems

Building on this framework, the current deliverable introduces a new inspection heading (sixth): **finishes and partitions** (Figure 1). This addition reflects the reality observed in many historic buildings, particularly those built with traditional techniques, where structural, envelope, and internal elements often form an inseparable whole. For example, timber frame interior partitions may have become load-bearing over time, and historic finishes (ceramic tiles, plasterwork, decorative wood elements) often possess an intrinsic heritage and cultural value and require specific conservation actions. This new heading addresses architectural elements that do not clearly

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fall under the original categories, yet demand differentiated and sometimes complex maintenance or conservation strategies.

This decision is in line with the ICOMOS Principles for the Analysis, Conservation and Structural Restoration of Architectural Heritage, according which *"Partitions, wall finishes and decorative elements often contribute to the overall significance of the heritage value of a building and should be treated with the same rigour as structural elements."* (ICOMOS, 2003 [07]).

Figure 2, presents a hierarchical pyramid illustrating the six technical inspection headings, organized from foundational structural elements to functional performance, reflecting their importance in the conservation process of CH buildings.

Figure 2: Hierarchical structure of the six technical inspection headings in CH building conservation

2.1.2 Adaptive approach: tailoring inspection to historical construction

The Technical Inspection methodology is designed to be flexible and context-sensitive, adapting to the specific materiality and construction systems of the building under assessment. This adaptability is essential for heritage buildings, where variability in techniques, stylistic and architectural disparities, materials, and pathologies are the norm rather than the exception.

Instead of applying a rigid checklist, the methodology relies on **interactive logic embedded in the Digital Inspection Form**, which guides the user through typology-specific criteria based on the characteristics of the building. Upon initial configuration, the user selects relevant features (e.g., masonry structure, timber frame, presence of vaults or mixed partitions), and the tool dynamically adjusts the required inspection items, risk indicators, and recommended documentation.

This adaptive process is grounded in:

- The typological classification of materials and systems.
- UNE 41805 [06] standards, which address each building component based on its constructive nature.

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- Practical recommendations from European representative conservation entities such as the Spanish Cultural Heritage Institute (IPCE)², which states: *“The Preventive Conservation Plan must adapt to the specific characteristics of the property and allow for periodic monitoring and prioritisation of non-invasive interventions”* (IPCE, 2014 [09]).

Furthermore, the approach considers that the **interdependency of elements in traditional buildings** (e.g., timber partitions acting structurally, or integrated façades) challenges modern notions of separated structural and non-structural roles. Therefore, the inspection adapts not only to risk but also to **historical logic and architectural function**, as recommended by the ICOMOS principles. (ICOMOS, 2003[07]).

Figure 3 shows examples of traditional mixed-material construction, highlighting the challenges that arise in heritage inspections. In such cases, the distinction between structural and non-structural elements, such as façades, infill walls or load-bearing members, is blurred, making it difficult to assess load distribution or structural function. This ambiguity is often the result of prolonged material decay and the complex transformations the building has undergone over time, thus reinforcing the need for an adaptive, context-sensitive inspection approach.

Figure 3: Case examples of historic masonry and timber construction supporting the adaptive inspection approach

At this stage of development, the methodology focuses primarily on the three inspection headings related to the building fabric and construction (foundations & structure, façades & roofs, finishes & partitions), due to their essential role in ensuring structural integrity, preserving material authenticity, and enabling the reliable interpretation of heritage pathologies. In traditional buildings, material degradation and morphological changes often blur the distinction between load-bearing and non-load-bearing elements, making a clear understanding of the physical fabric an essential prerequisite for any subsequent assessment of functional performance or user-oriented systems. Prioritising these components aligns with the risk-based inspection model and lays the

² The IPCE (*Instituto del Patrimonio Cultural de España*) is a representative institution at the European level in the field of preventive conservation of historical heritage due to its long-standing expertise, interdisciplinary research approach, and active participation in international networks and collaborative projects. As part of the Spanish Ministry of Culture, the IPCE develops and promotes advanced methodologies, standards, and technologies for the preservation of cultural assets, while also providing training and technical support to institutions and professionals across Europe. Its work serves as a benchmark for best practices in heritage conservation and contributes significantly to the development of European strategies in this domain.

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groundwork for evaluating installations, accessibility, and functional behaviour in subsequent phases.

The inspection headings related to functional and user systems will be developed in a subsequent phase, building upon the foundation provided by the analysis of the building fabric. This will ensure continuity and coherence across the methodology. Their definition will take into account the applicable international, European, and national standards governing building performance, safety, usability, and habitability, ensuring full normative alignment within the adaptive logic of the inspection framework.

2.1.3 Prioritisation logic: phased and risk-based intervention

While the methodology adapts to each building's characteristics, it also maintains a risk-based prioritisation logic to organise the inspection and intervention sequence. This logic follows a pyramidal structure, where safety and stability are addressed first, ensuring that structural integrity is preserved before considering aesthetic, functional or secondary concerns.

The pyramid model, introduced in D3.1 and updated in the present document with the new Finishes and Partitions heading, allows inspection teams to:

- Identify urgent structural threats (e.g., settlements, cracking, decay in timber trusses, etc.).
- Address envelope issues (e.g., roof leaks, façade detachment, etc.).
- Assess serviceability (e.g., electrical, HVAC, plumbing, etc.), accessibility and usability.
- Evaluate interior elements with cultural or structural significance such as historic plasterwork, joinery, or partition walls that may have acquired load-bearing roles.

The prioritisation model does not override the adaptive logic but complements it. It ensures that decisions in CH buildings are sequenced logically and justified technically, supporting conservation plans aligned with available resources, protection status, and cultural values.

2.2 Historical materials, techniques and pathologies

A solid understanding of the traditional European construction materials and techniques is essential for accurate and meaningful inspections of heritage buildings. Unlike modern structures, historic buildings rely on materials and systems with distinct structural behaviours, decay patterns and conservation needs.

As highlighted in D3.1, much of this knowledge has been progressively lost due to modern industrial standardisation. With the rise of reinforced concrete and steel as dominant structural materials, many age-old trades and local techniques were abandoned in favour of faster and more economical construction processes driven by industrialisation.

Spanish architect and restoration scholar Rafael Manzano Martos, a member of the Royal Academy of Fine Arts of San Fernando³, and an internationally recognised authority in monumental

³ The Royal Academy of Fine Arts of San Fernando plays a crucial role in the conservation of Spanish heritage, which is recognized as one of the richest and most diverse in the world. As one of the oldest and most prestigious cultural institutions in Spain, it has historically been a center of excellence for the study, protection, and promotion of the arts and cultural heritage. Through its academic work, expert committees, and contributions to preservation policies, the Academy has significantly influenced national conservation strategies and fostered a deep appreciation for Spain's historical legacy. Its efforts help safeguard artistic and architectural treasures for future generations, reinforcing Spain's leading position in global heritage conservation.

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restoration, warned about this loss: “*The progressive replacement of historic construction systems and their associated trades by modern technologies -faster but less durable- has contributed to the erosion of vernacular knowledge.*” (Manzano, R., 2002 [10]) Similarly, UNESCO warns that “*Traditional knowledge systems are being lost at a rapid rate due to globalisation and the dominance of modern construction techniques.*” (UNESCO, 2001 [11]).

Traditional architecture is intimately linked to local resources, climatic adaptation, and centuries of empirical knowledge. As the IPCE states “*Traditional materials such as stone, lime, earth or timber, far from being obsolete, remain alive and relevant today for their sustainability, compatibility, and reversibility.*” (IPCE, 2020 [12]).

The TI methodology draws upon this body of knowledge, offering a technical and operational framework that enables high-quality preventive maintenance and enhances the long-term sustainability and viability of historic buildings.

2.2.1 Architectural typologies overview

It is essential to understand the diversity and complexity of historic architecture across Europe, where typologies resist simple standardisation. The evolution of construction systems, materials and cultural expressions has produced a rich and varied built heritage, shaped over centuries of renovations, adaptations and repairs.

While the historical evolution of architectural styles is well documented in the academic literature, usually linked to artistic styles, which are studied in depth by the field of art history, the technical inspection of historic buildings requires a more pragmatic framework, based on construction systems and material performance rather than aesthetics.

Table 2 is a reference that does not attempt to standardise the history of architecture, but to categorise somewhat the most relevant combinations of traditional building techniques and materials found in four broad historical periods.

It is intended as a general reference. In practice, most heritage buildings do not belong to a single architectural typology. Their current state is the result of multiple construction phases, additions, repairs, and material substitutions over time. Therefore, while the table provides a useful framework, inspection should always be grounded in the specific physical and historical characteristics of the building in question.

Table 2: Evolution of construction materials and techniques in historical architecture

Historical period	Predominant materials	Common construction systems and techniques
Classical Antiquity (8th c. BC – 5th c. AD) 	Stone, ceramics, lime, timber, <i>Opus Caementicium</i> , glazed ceramics	Load-bearing walls of stone, brick, and <i>opus caementicium</i> , stone columns, masonry and brick vaults, timber roofs and floors, decorative stone lintels, mortar coatings, painted finishes, and ceramic tile decorations.
Middle Ages (5th – 15th c.) 	Stone, ceramics, timber, earth, lime, gypsum, glazed ceramics	Load-bearing walls of stone, brick, earth, and timber or mixed frameworks, timber trusses and roofs, vaults and arches of stone, brick, and earth, lime mortars and plaster coatings, ceramic tilework, stuccoes, carved stone and gypsum elements.

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Historical period	Predominant materials	Common construction systems and techniques
Renaissance / Baroque / Neoclassicism (15th – 18th c.) 	Ceramics, earth, timber, lime, gypsum, glazed ceramics, stone	Brick, earth, and framed load-bearing walls, stone plinths, brick and stone arches and vaults, timber roofs and floors, lime and gypsum coatings, stucco mouldings, <i>sgraffito</i> , ceramic baseboards, and carved stone and wood ornamentation.
Industrial Age / Avant-garde / Modernism (19th – 20th c.) 	Wrought and cast iron, metal profiles, ceramics, concrete, cement, glass, timber, earth, stone	Structures of iron, concrete, and timber, walls of brick, concrete, earth, and stone, glazed enclosures, cement and gypsum coatings, ceramic tile finishes.

2.2.2 Historic materials and traditional techniques

A rigorous knowledge of traditional materials and their associated construction techniques is essential for understanding the structural and physical behaviour of historic buildings. This understanding is a prerequisite for carrying out effective technical inspections aimed at preventive conservation and risk identification.

Traditional architecture is defined by the use of natural, locally sourced materials, crafted with techniques passed down through generations. The selection of materials and construction methods followed a logic of sustainability, durability, climate adaptation, and empirical knowledge. As stated in Spain's National Plan for Traditional Architecture: *“Traditional construction systems are the result of centuries of experience, environmental adaptation, and use of local resources, and their understanding is essential for their proper conservation and transmission.”* (Ministerio de Cultura y Deporte, 2024 [13]).

Far from being obsolete, materials such as stone, earth, lime, wood, gypsum, and fired ceramics have demonstrated long-term performance, and their inspection requires a technical approach tailored to their physical, chemical, and mechanical properties.

This subsection aims to characterise the main traditional construction materials, describing not only their composition and behaviour but also the common application techniques, associated structural systems, and the geographical and cultural contexts in which they are most frequently found (Table 3). The goal is to provide a solid technical foundation for the formulation of material-specific inspection criteria.

Table 3: Traditional building materials: properties, techniques, and historical applications

Material group	Main characteristics (chemical, physical, mechanical)	Construction techniques (application)	Traditional uses (according to TI headings)
Earth 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Composed of clay, silt, and sand - Hygroscopic, low mechanical strength - High thermal inertia, regulates humidity 	Rammed earth, adobe, half-timbering, mixed with vegetal elements	Vertical structure, arches and vaults, façades, interior partitions
Stone	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inorganic, high resistance - Very durable - Low thermal conductivity (some types) 	Ashlar, masonry, slabs, voussoirs	Vertical structure, Arches and vaults,

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Material group	Main characteristics (chemical, physical, mechanical)	Construction techniques (application)	Traditional uses (according to TI headings)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regional varieties: limestone, sandstone, granite 		Foundations, Façades
Wood 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organic, anisotropic - High tensile/compressive strength along fibres - Lightweight, elastic - Biodegradable, sensitive to moisture and insects 	Timber framing, logs, half-timbering	Vertical and horizontal structure, façades, roofs interior partitions
Ceramics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clay-based and fired - Hard, resistant, brittle - Variable porosity - Good thermal insulation depending on type 	Solid/hollow bricks, tiles	Vertical structure, arches and vaults, façades, interior partitions
Iron 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High tensile and compressive strength - Prone to corrosion - Forged (wrought iron) or cast (cast iron) 	Forging, casting	Vertical and horizontal structure, façade, roofs,
Lime 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aerial or hydraulic binder - Carbonates with CO₂ - Breathable, compatible with porous materials 	Mixed with aggregates to make mortars, coatings, limewash	Finishes
Gypsum 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Calcium sulphate hemihydrate - Hardens by hydration - Fragile, good workability, moisture-absorbing 	Thin coats or sculpted application (profiles), mixed with aggregates to make mortars, coatings, limewash	Finishes
Glazed ceramics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ceramic body with vitreous coating - Impermeable, decorative - Moderately fragile 	Tiles, mosaic tesserae	Finishes
Glass 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Amorphous, brittle, transparent material - Limited mechanical resistance - Good weather resistance 	Leaded stained glass, pane fitting	Façades

2.2.3 Main pathologies and symptoms

A precise understanding of deterioration mechanisms is essential for accurate inspection and diagnosis of heritage buildings. Unlike modern structures, historic buildings are exposed to specific types of degradation stemming from the intrinsic nature of their materials, traditional construction techniques, and long-term exposure to environmental and anthropic factors. This subsection serves

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as a baseline to implement the TI methodology, summarising the main pathological processes associated with traditional building elements. It provides inspectors with a structured diagnostic framework based on the UNE 41805 IN “Building Diagnosis” standards [06].

2.2.3.1 Typology of the deterioration process

The pathological analysis of historic buildings requires a clear and structured understanding of the various deterioration processes that affect traditional materials. As defined by UNE 41805-3 [06], a pathological process includes the sequence of mechanisms (physical, chemical or biological) that, through one or several external factors, alter the properties of a material and give rise to observable damage.

In parallel, the ICCROM framework classifies risks into ten major deterioration agents. This internationally accepted model is widely used for vulnerability assessments and preventive conservation planning. Its strength lies in focusing not only on damage already visible but on the root risk factors that cause it. (ICCROM, 2007 [14]).

The TI methodology integrates both perspectives: the UNE technical-symptomatic model for damage identification and recording, and the ICCROM risk-based environmental model as a guide for maintenance strategies.

The deterioration processes considered in the inspection protocol are:

- **Physical processes:** Caused by environmental conditions (e.g., moisture, temperature, wind, solar radiation, etc.). These primarily affect material surfaces but can compromise deeper layers over time.
 - Common subtypes:
 - Dampness: capillary rise, infiltration, surface or interstitial condensation.
 - Fouling: deposition of suspended particles or differential runoff (streaking).
 - Physical erosion: progressive wear due to wind, rain or freezing.
 - Main vehicles:
 - Capillarity and suction of water from the ground.
 - Uncontrolled runoff due to defects in copings or drip pits.
 - Freezing of water absorbed by porous materials (ice effect).
 - Accumulation of polluting particles in low-ventilation or sheltered areas.

- **Mechanical processes:** Result from tensions, movements, or forces that produce cracks, deformations, or displacements in materials and finishes.
 - Common subtypes:
 - Fissures: linear cracks in surface coatings, without affecting full depth.
 - Fractures: cracks extending through the full thickness of the element.
 - Deformations: warping, buckling, collapse, sagging.
 - Detachment: loss of adhesion of coatings or attached elements.

- Mechanical erosion: wear from impact, abrasion, or repeated use.
- Main vehicles:
 - Absence or poor sizing of expansion joints.
 - Inadequate or missing structural supports.
 - Differences in stiffness between adjoining elements (structure/façade).
 - Failure in metallic anchors or bonding mortars.
 - Accidental loads or impacts, especially near ground level.
-
 - **Chemical and biological processes:** Originate from chemical reactions with external agents (e.g., salts, pollutants, water) or biological growth (e.g., fungi, insects, vegetation).
 - Common subtypes:
 - Efflorescence and subflorescence: migration and crystallisation of soluble salts.
 - Oxidation and corrosion: loss of section in metallic elements.
 - Chemical erosion: selective dissolution, decementation, crusts, black patinas.
 - Biological growth: moulds, lichens, algae, plants, animal nesting.
 - *Discoloration*: alteration of surface colour due to UV exposure or humidity.
 - Main vehicles:
 - Continuous presence of moisture (essential condition).
 - Interaction with pollutants (SO₂, CO₂, NO_x).
 - Hygroscopic nature of the material.
 - Open porosity and internal structure favourable to moisture retention.
 - Lack of ventilation and shaded environments.

Each process is broken down into common symptoms, underlying mechanisms, and typical effects, providing a technical vocabulary and logic for the inspector.

2.2.3.2 Pathologies: symptoms and risk of degradation

The identification of pathologies in historic buildings should not be reduced to a simple catalogue of visible damage. As stated in UNE 41805-14 [06], technical inspection must include a qualitative assessment of the risk of degradation that each symptom entails for the affected architectural element. This approach is key to evaluating not only the nature of the damage but also its severity, potential impact, and the urgency of intervention.

The same symptom may have very different implications depending on the material and structural role of the affected element. A superficial crack in a lime plaster might represent minor aesthetic damage, while an identical crack in a load-bearing earthen wall could indicate serious structural risk.

Assessing degradation risk enables the prioritisation of actions based on objective criteria: loss of function, loss of stability, exposure of the substrate, erosion of original material, or impact on heritage value. This material-specific, risk-oriented approach aligns with preventive conservation

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methodologies promoted by ICCROM and IPCE, advocating for proportionate interventions that favour compatibility and reversibility.

Thus, the classification of damage presented in this section—structured by type of deterioration process, visible symptom, affected materials, and associated risk—serves as a core operational tool for the application of the TI methodology. It supports more accurate inspections, informed technical decision-making, and sustainable conservation in alignment with heritage values.

- **Pathology table – physical processes**

Table 4: Visible symptoms, associated degradation risks, and affected materials in physical degradation processes

Visible Symptom	Degradation Risk	Most Affected Materials
Moisture stains	Salt crystallisation, biological growth, material weakening	Unfired earth, stone, lime mortars, gypsum
Streaking	Premature material ageing and loss of aesthetic uniformity	Lime renders, glazed ceramics, porous stone
Surface erosion	Loss of functional thickness and protective capacity	Soft stone, fired brick, unprotected mortars
Powdering/granulation	Exposure of inner layers and weakening of load-bearing elements	Sandstone, stabilised earth, lime plasters
Lamination (layer flaking)	Risk of detachment and loss of integrity of surface coatings	Wall paintings, gypsum, ceramics with firing defects

- **Pathology table – mechanical processes**

Table 5: Visible symptoms, associated degradation risks, and affected materials in mechanical degradation processes

Visible symptom	Degradation risk	Most affected materials
Linear cracks or fissures	Structural compromise if affecting load-bearing walls or vaults	Masonry, mixed wall systems, earth and ceramic finishes
Deformations or buckling	Permanent deformation and functional failure of the element	Timber floors, earthen or framed walls
Detachments	Loss of coatings, risk of exposing the substrate	Lime plasters, mortars, gypsum, ceramic finishes
Falling elements	Risk of falling parts, endangering people or property	Stone cornices, ceramic ornaments, iron grilles

- **Pathology table – chemical processes**

Table 6: Visible symptoms, associated degradation risks, and affected materials in chemical degradation processes

Visible symptom	Degradation risk	Most affected materials
Efflorescence	Material disintegration, loss of strength and cohesion	Stone (limestone), ceramic and lime mortar
Subflorescence	Internal cracking, formation of additional internal stresses	Ceramic, stone, lime plasters
Black crusts	Progressive chemical decay, aesthetic and functional loss	Calcareous stone in urban environments

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Visible symptom	Degradation risk	Most affected materials
Discoloration	Loss of original colour and alteration of decorative finishes	Glazed ceramics, paints, treated wood
Decementation	Surface cohesion loss, progressive flaking	Stone (sandstone), lime plasters, mortars

- **Pathology table - biological processes**

Table 7: Visible symptoms, associated degradation risks, and affected materials in biological degradation processes

Visible symptom	Degradation risk	Most affected materials
Fungi and mould	Biological degradation, material loss, and deterioration of indoor environment	Wood, gypsum, earthen mortars, wall coatings
Vegetation colonisation	Structural damage to walls, cracking, disintegration	Stone, wood, mortar joints
Insect infestation	Loss of structural cross-section in timber elements	Wood
Nests and droppings	Loss of hygiene, damage to roofs and facades	Stone, Wood, Lime mortar

The classification of pathologies presented here (Table 4-Table 7), structured by deterioration process, observable symptoms, affected materials and associated risk, constitutes a fundamental operational tool for the application of the inspection methodology. This approach will allow for more rigorous, comparable inspections adapted to the material diversity of built heritage.

In the following section, the structure and contents of the digital inspection form will be described, showing how the principles detailed above have been applied in its design.

In this context, a data collection sheet was prepared and distributed among the technical partners responsible for this task, to gather expert knowledge from diverse European national contexts. The purpose of this exercise was to identify what type of information and documentation is considered essential by professionals in the built heritage field to carry out an effective diagnostic inspection.

The table included in **Annex 1** is structured into several thematic blocks. The first section gathers the type of **preliminary documentation** deemed necessary to **prepare the inspection** (e.g., plans, H-BIM models, previous reports, etc.). Subsequently, experts were asked to specify, for each inspection heading (e.g., structure, façade, roof, installations, accessibility, and functional performance), which **symptoms or pathologies are commonly observed, what types of lesions are most frequent, and what inspection frequency is considered appropriate in preventive maintenance routines.**

This exploratory collection has not only helped to **validate the inspection** criteria defined in the digital form but has also **highlighted the value of accumulated technical knowledge** from professionals across different regions. The information gathered strengthens the methodological robustness of the inspection system and provides a realistic basis for its operational implementation in varied heritage contexts.

2.3 Digital inspection form: design, operation and strategic role

The form developed within the framework of this methodology represents a significant advancement to allow for a technical inspection of historic buildings from a European perspective, supported by preventive conservation and not by corrective actions. Its design responds to the specific challenges of built heritage, such as the diversity of traditional materials, the structural and morphological complexity of historical assets, and the need to implement respectful, non-intrusive interventions that preserve authenticity and cultural value.

This tool goes beyond simple data collection. It constitutes a structured, adaptive, and progressive instrument that enables each inspection to be contextualised according to the building's condition, history of interventions, and previously identified risks. In doing so, it addresses one of the most urgent needs in heritage conservation: the construction of cumulative, traceable knowledge to support proportionate, sustainable, and informed technical decisions.

The innovation of the form lies in several core aspects, developed in detail in the following subsections:

- **Phase-based logic:** The inspection process is structured into successive stages, from contextual documentation and typological classification to symptom recording and diagnostic analysis. This approach enhances both consistency and traceability.
- **Adaptive inspection headings:** The form allows a flexible selection of relevant building components (structure, roof, finishes, etc.), enabling both partial and comprehensive inspections while avoiding unnecessary data entry.
- **Diagnostic support and risk-based prioritisation:** Through the registration of symptoms and localisation of deterioration, the form enables predictive analysis and facilitates the identification of pathological patterns across inspection cycles.
- **Digital integration and preventive management:** The data structure is compatible with H-BIM, enabling progressive enrichment of the digital model and integration into long-term maintenance strategies.

Ultimately, the form defines a preventive, multidisciplinary, risk-informed and heritage-sensitive approach to built heritage inspection. It not only systematises technical observation, but also transforms the inspection process into an iterative, data-driven, and sustainability-oriented practice aligned with the physical and cultural integrity of the asset.

2.3.1 General structure and functional blocks of the digital TI form

The digital inspection form developed within the INHERIT project framework is a core component of the preventive technical inspection methodology for heritage buildings. It has been designed with an intuitive and user-oriented interface with a technically robust structure that facilitates systematic, adaptive, and context-sensitive data collection.

- **Welcome interface and initial access**

Upon opening, the form presents a start screen consistent with the project's visual identity, displaying the project name, EU funding acknowledgement, and INHERIT logo. It includes the project coordinator's name, authorship credits, and a contact email for user support.

A central button, "**Start Technical Inspection**", initiates the process and redirects the user to the first data entry module: "First Step Technical Inspection" (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Welcome interface and initial access (mock-up)

- **First step technical inspection**

The first phase of the digital technical inspection form is designed to systematically and traceably collect essential contextual data about the building, the intervention, and the regulatory framework. This information establishes the foundation for appropriate inspection planning, future comparative assessments, damage evolution tracking, and the formulation of preventive conservation strategies. This section is structured into seven thematic blocks, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the building's technical, legal, and heritage context (Figure 5).

- **General inspection data:** records the basic administrative and operational aspects of the intervention:
 - Date of inspection
 - Type of inspection (scheduled / emergency / post-event / initial / periodic)
 - Promoting or commissioning entity
 - Lead technicians
 - Reference to prior inspections (if applicable)
- **Inspector information:** Captures the professional identification of the person responsible for the inspection:
 - Full name
 - Affiliated institution/Company/Organization
 - Professional profile (architect, engineer, conservator, etc.)
 - Contact email
- **Building information:** Collects essential and technical data to accurately characterize the asset:
 - Name or identification code of the building
 - Full address and geographic location
 - Ownership or legal entity (public, private, institutional, ecclesiastical, etc.)
 - Current use and original use (if known)

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- Built area and number of floors
- Year or period of construction
- Documented interventions or renovations (dates/details)
- Link to digital documentation or H-BIM model (if available)
- **Historical and archaeological information:** Provides heritage and architectural context for the building:
 - Construction phases timeline (allowing multiple entries with date and description)
 - Predominant architectural styles
 - Notable heritage elements (structural, decorative, etc.)
 - Official heritage designation (e.g., National Monument, World Heritage Site, regional/local listing)
 - Available documentary or bibliographic sources
- **Regulatory and conservation framework:** Covers the legal and technical constraints applicable to the intervention:
 - Current level of heritage protection
 - Applicable technical regulations (accessibility, energy efficiency, seismic safety, fire safety, etc.)
 - Legal restrictions or requirements for interventions
 - Existence of a Preventive Conservation Plan (Yes/No)
 - Existence of a structured Maintenance Plan (Yes/No)
 - Date and subject of the most recent official inspection or technical review (if applicable)
- **Inspection analysis (preliminary classification):** Defines the construction context by selecting one of three typologies, *Traditional*, *Modern*, or *Mixed*, in order to adapt the structure of the form to the characteristics of the building and the intended scope of the inspection.

The form begins by prompting the user to classify the building according to its predominant construction typology: traditional, modern, or mixed. This distinction is not based solely on the age of the building but reflects deeper differences in constructive logic, material systems, and architectural paradigms.

As a reminder of the criteria established in the in-depth analysis provided in Deliverable 3.1, traditional architecture is typically characterised by material continuity and functional interdependence between structural and envelope elements. Foundations, load-bearing walls, façades, and interior partitions often form an integrated whole, the result of empirical knowledge and local craftsmanship. Consequently, the form groups these elements together under unified inspection headings to reflect their shared behaviour and common deterioration patterns.

In contrast, modern construction, particularly from the 20th century onwards, embodies the paradigm shift introduced by the Modern Movement and architects such as Le Corbusier. The widespread use of reinforced concrete, steel frames, and industrialised materials enabled a clear separation between structure, envelope, and interior layout. This decoupling allows for flexible floor plans and the use of non-load-bearing façades (e.g., curtain walls), and justifies the disaggregation of inspection categories within the form.

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For hybrid or altered buildings, where traditional elements coexist with modern additions or modifications, the form enables custom configuration of the inspection interface, ensuring that the resulting assessment accurately reflects the complexity and layered nature of the building.

When the construction typology is defined, the form generates a tailored inspection structure, activating only the relevant categories. When available, these are linked to architectural drawings or digital twin models, where each building component is coded using its HBIM identifier to ensure traceability and consistency across inspection cycles.

1st STEP TECHNICAL INSPECTION

1 GENERAL INFO
 Inspection date (year/month/day):
 Reason for inspection:
 Inspection orderer:

2 INSPECTOR DATA
 Full name: ID:
 Expertise: e-mail:
 Company:

3 BUILDING INFORMATION
 Name of the heritage building:
 Main use: Location:
 Address:
 Plot number: m² plot: m² built:
 Rights of ownership:

4 HISTORICAL AND ARCHEOLOGICAL INFORMATION
 Date: Construction phase/Relevant intervention:
 Building Typology: Architectural Style:
 Cultural / Historical Significance:

5 REGULATORY FRAMEWORK
 Heritage Protection level:
 Energy Efficiency Class:

6 INSPECTION ANALYSIS
 Historical Context: Modern Construction We will choose this option when it is a building constructed with modern materials or one that is modified with new materials.
 What is to be inspected:
 Foundations and Structure
 Facade
 Roof
 Insulations
 Accessibility
 Functional behaviour

Finish

Figure 5: Interface of the first step in the TI form to fill-in contextual data and inspection analysis setup (mock-up)

● Second step technical inspection

Once the inspection planning is complete and the available digital documentation of the building has been reviewed, the technician carries out the on-site visual inspection, optionally supported by diagnostic tools such as thermographic cameras, hygrometers, or endoscopes, depending on the material characteristics and accessibility conditions.

The findings are documented in a structured data table integrated into the form, following a logic that links physical observations with technical evaluation and intervention prioritisation (Figure 6).

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The screenshot shows the Inherit assessment form interface. At the top left is the Inherit logo and 'Co-Funded by the European Union'. A metadata table includes fields for Inspection date, Company inspection, Building name, Location, Building Typology, and Main Use. A legend defines four priority codes (P) from 1 (Very Major Deficiency) to 4 (Very Mild Deficiency). The main part of the form is a table with columns: ELEMENT CODE, HEADING, CONSTRUCTION SYSTEM, MATERIAL, MAIN SYMPTOM, DETAILED SYMPTOM, LOCATION, LESION, PRIORITY, and CAUSE. The first row has 'Brick' under MATERIAL.

Figure 6: Interface to the second step of the TI form for registering visual symptoms and diagnostic data during on-site inspection (mock-up)

Once the visual inspection is underway, the form becomes an operative tool for capturing both symptoms and contextual parameters. To ensure clarity, consistency, and diagnostic precision, the interface organises input and output data in a standardised structure (Table 8). This structure not only guides the technician during fieldwork but also ensures that the collected data is interoperable and suitable for subsequent analysis, integration into H-BIM environments, and long-term conservation planning.

Table 8: Input and output fields of the inspection form for symptom registration and assessment processing

Item	Description
INPUT	
Element code	A unique identifier linked to architectural documentation or digital models (e.g., H-BIM). It enables precise traceability between the physical inspection and the design data, ensuring that observed pathologies are accurately localised within the documented geometry.
Inspection heading	This field classifies the element within the functional or spatial categories identified in the project, such as Structure, Facade, Roof, or Facilities. Since the inspection can be performed under multiple headings, the technician must identify which one of the elements described in the previous box belongs to. This facilitates comparative evaluation of similar components.
Construction system	Describes the structural or assembly logic to which the element belongs, such as load-bearing walls, porticoes, vaulted ceilings, or trusses. This classification is crucial for understanding how each element contributes to the building's overall stability and for anticipating potential damage propagation within the structural system.
Material	Records the dominant material of the component (e.g., stone, timber, lime mortar, clay). Material properties directly affect an element's durability, compatibility with conservation treatments, and vulnerability to specific types of deterioration. Accurate identification is key for selecting appropriate interventions.
Main symptom	Identifies the general category of damage observed (e.g., moisture, cracking, biological growth). It provides a first-level diagnosis that frames the inspection in terms of pathological patterns, helping to group and prioritise issues by type.
Detailed symptoms	Offers a more precise description of the defect within the broader symptom category. Standardising this terminology ensures consistency across reports and facilitates the aggregation of data for larger-scale analysis and pattern detection.

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Location of the defect	Indicates the specific position of the damage within the element. This spatial information is critical for interpreting the origin and progression of deterioration, assessing risks to surrounding elements, and planning targeted repairs.
OUTPUT	
Lesion	Describes the identified deterioration mechanism affecting the element (e.g., filtration, corrosion, deformation). Understanding the nature of the lesion is fundamental for evaluating the urgency of action and defining technical solutions.
Priority	An urgency level calculated as explained in section 2.3.3 helps technicians classify interventions according to risk and resource optimization, distinguishing between critical structural problems and non-urgent aesthetic concerns.
Suspected cause and diagnosis	A hypothesis generated from the symptom and lesion data, suggesting the most likely origin of the problem. This preliminary diagnosis aids in expert validation and feeds into long-term maintenance strategies.

- **Technical backbone of the form**

The underlying logic of the form is built on a structured approach where each field plays a defined role in guiding the assessment process. Below is a breakdown of the components and the design considerations behind each:

- **Element code attribution**

Each individual element is associated with a unique code. This code is not pre-determined but rather provided by the technician familiar with the specific building. It ensures traceability and context-specific accuracy in the evaluation.

- **Heading categories and scoring system**

The heading field is structured around seven distinct categories. Each of these has been assigned a specific criterion and a corresponding score, which are detailed in Table 10.

- **Construction system Input**

For the construction system field, the form allows free-text entry initially. Once the user begins typing, an autocomplete dropdown is activated. For instance, if the technician types “arc”, the system dynamically searches through a predefined list of **58 recognised items** and displays suggestions that begin with the entered characters.

HEADING	CONSTRUCTION SYSTEM	M...
Foundations and Structure	arc	▼
	Arch	

Figure 7. Operation of the construction system box

The full list of construction systems and their respective criticality levels, as used in the form, is provided in **Annex 2** with the scoring logic further clarified in Table 10.

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These 58 items are the result of a detailed analysis based on UNE 41805 [06], the Spanish standard for building diagnostics, provided by AENOR (*Asociación Española de Normalización y Certificación*). Additionally, the list has been enriched through expert evaluation carried out by the project's technical team, who considered the variety of construction systems commonly found in existing buildings.

- **Material selection**

The material is chosen from a dropdown menu consisting of **17 items**. This closed list ensures standardised inputs and facilitates downstream processing and categorisation.

Similarly, an analysis of the relevant regulations has been carried out to identify the 17 most common materials, complemented by the expert judgment of the technical team. However, it is important to note that this list is not final and may be expanded progressively throughout the course of the project.

- **Symptoms: classification and input complexity**

The form incorporates a large dataset of **519 symptoms**, **this list is entirely based on the standard for non-heritage buildings, whose diagnostic criteria can be reasonably extrapolated to our context. As with the material selection, this symptom list is subject to updates and may be expanded as new types of damage or pathologies are identified over the course of the project.** To streamline user interaction with such a vast dataset, the input field is split into two levels:

- **Main symptom:** This field groups symptoms into broader categories. A dropdown menu is used to present these groups, significantly reducing the list's length and supporting faster, more intuitive searches.
- **Detailed symptom:** Once the main category is selected, the second dropdown becomes available. It enables the user to specify the symptom with greater precision within the selected group.

Although this dual-layer structure is still under development, a practical example can be provided to illustrate how it facilitates symptom identification and input accuracy.

Table 9. Example of operational levels in symptom classification

Main symptom	Detailed symptom
Fissures or cracks	Vertical cracks
	Horizontal cracks
	Inclined cracks
	Cracks and fissures in arches
	Cracks and fissures in barrel vaults, groin vaults, ribbed vaults, etc.
	Fissures on map
	Various fissures
	Fissures according to surface reinforcement

- **Location field**

Location is also selected via a dropdown menu. Its contents are filtered based on the previously selected symptom to reduce noise and improve searchability. Additionally, the entries are sorted alphabetically to further support ease of navigation.

- **Output: lesion and cause prediction**

After all required data are inserted, the form conducts a query against the full dataset of 519 symptom-location combinations. Based on this, it returns the most likely lesion and its probable cause.

A total of **188 distinct lesions** have been identified and categorised according to their level of criticality. This classification stems from a detailed analysis of the applicable building regulations, ensuring alignment with established diagnostic standards. The methodology used follows the approach previously described and is detailed further in **Annex 2**.

- **Strategic contribution and future integration**

This form not only supports structured and consistent real-time inspections but also contributes to the long-term management and conservation of historic buildings. The digitisation of technical findings in a standardised format facilitates the progressive creation of a cumulative inspection history, which is vital for tracking degradation trends, guiding maintenance planning, and informing conservation strategies.

The form is designed to ensure compatibility with digital models, facilitating its future integration into digital twin environments and building information systems (e.g., H-BIM). In this way, technical inspection is framed not as an isolated tool, but as a core component of an ongoing, data-driven maintenance cycle that adapts over time.

Moreover, by enabling the systematic collection of building pathology data, the form contributes to the creation of a robust and interoperable knowledge base. This digital infrastructure can act as a facilitator for the optimisation of maintenance workflows, the prioritisation of interventions, and the long-term preservation of cultural value.

In essence, the form provides a bridge between traditional on-site technical assessment and the strategic digitalisation of heritage asset management.

2.3.2 Technical workflow and field operation

This section describes the general operational logic that guides the use of the digital form throughout a technical inspection. It complements the form's internal structure by detailing the external workflow experienced by users, from the initial request to the post-inspection processing of information.

The workflow (Figure 8) comprises three main phases:

- **Phase 1. Inspection planning (offline)**

Initiated by an inspection request, either scheduled or on demand. The technician accesses the system, locates the building, and reviews whether existing inspection records or documentation are available.

- **If no prior data exist**, a new record is initiated and filled with:

- Contextual and administrative information
- Inspector credentials
- Building identity and ownership details
- Heritage background and conservation regulations

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- **If prior data are available:** the form skips directly to the configuration of the inspection, activating only the relevant components. The availability of drawings or an H-BIM model is verified to guide element selection.
- **Phase 2. On-site inspection (field phase)**
 The user conducts the visual assessment using the inspection form, ideally on a tablet or laptop. Each element is identified by a unique code from the plans or H-BIM. Observations, materials, and symptoms are registered directly.
- **Phase 3 – Post-inspection risk analysis (offline processing)**
 The data recorded in the field is reviewed and used to generate the final output of the form. This includes:
 - Lesion type
 - Risk and priority level
 - Probable cause and preliminary diagnosis

This output informs future conservation measures, and the results are optionally re-integrated into the H-BIM model.

Figure 8: User workflow for the INHERIT digital technical inspection form

2.3.3 Diagnostic logic and risk-based prioritisation

In the final stage of the inspection workflow, once data has been collected during both the planning and on-site phases, the form activates a structured evaluation system that transforms observations into objective technical decisions. This methodology supports both individual diagnoses and broader conservation strategies based on risk and proportionality. It provides a common technical basis for different professional profiles (e.g., inspectors, architects, conservators), promoting consensual and transparent decisions. Furthermore, its modular design allows it to be implemented digitally or manually, facilitating its integration into assisted inspection platforms or portable forms for field technicians.

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The system was developed with a dual purpose:

- To facilitate the work of the field technician, offering a clear and systematic tool to assess the severity of the symptoms detected and assign intervention priorities.
- To support owners and public administrations in optimising resource allocation, enabling actions to be planned based on urgency, impact, and long-term sustainability.

In heritage contexts, where conservation requirements are demanding, resources are scarce and many buildings have experienced long-term neglect, it is essential to prioritise actions carefully and base decisions on sound technical reasoning. This diagnostic outcome of the form is therefore designed to support technicians in making reasoned, sustainable, and high-impact decisions, ensuring that available resources are directed toward the most critical interventions.

The evaluation method used by the tool is based on a multifactorial matrix, in which each deterioration symptom is assessed according to five key criteria:

- **Heading inspected** (structure, facade, installations, etc.).
- **Role of the element within the construction system** (primary load, secondary load, non-mechanical function, etc.).
- **Material** (and its behaviour in the face of deterioration and external agents).
- **Lesion type** (provided thanks to the form after recording the symptoms detected).
- **Priority code**, calculated as a result of the combined analysis of the above factors.

Each factor is rated on a **scale from 1 (lowest criticality) to 4 (highest)**, and the total score translates into one of four **intervention priority levels**, ranging from preventive maintenance to urgent action.

To support this logic, a technical catalogue was developed that includes:

- A comprehensive typology of lesions (from structural failures to superficial or biological damage).
- A classification of common heritage materials (e.g., stone, wood, brick, traditional mortar).
- A range of construction systems, both historical (vaults, load-bearing walls, timber frames) and modern (modular structures, light frames).

This shared technical framework ensures consistent interpretation of symptoms and facilitates collaboration across professional profiles. This logic allows disparate technical observations to be transformed into a quantifiable and actionable result, which directly guides decision-making and the prioritisation of interventions.

The following tables (Table 10 and Table 11) provide a detailed breakdown of the scoring system applied. The first presents the criteria and associated point values used to assess each inspection variable, from the structural role and construction system to the material type and lesion severity. The second consolidates these scores into defined risk categories, establishing corresponding intervention priorities.

Table 10: Assessment matrix for evaluating element criticality based on their conservation status

Criteria	Heading	Scoring
Structural principal	Foundations and Structure	3
	Foundations, Facade and Structure	
Surrounding	Façade	2
	Roof	

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Criteria	Heading	Scoring
Compartmentalization or finishes	Installations	1
	Accessibility	
	Functional behaviour	
	Construction System	Scoring
Critical stresses (compression, tension, active bending)	e.g.: Wooden frame structure, solid slab, concrete shell, timber truss...	4
Transfer of non-main loads	e.g.: Arch, wooden joist floor, timber floor slab, dome...	3
Non-structural but affects sealing or thermal stability	e.g.: Lightweight infill blocks, modular system, sandwich panel	2
Passive or without direct mechanical function	e.g.: Ruled surface, structural glazing system, ruled structure	1
	Material	Scoring
Critical material	High risk of structural degradation e.g.: Steel, earth, concrete	4
Sensitive material	May degrade if not controlled e.g.: Timber, brick, Metal, Lime mortar	3
Stable material	Limited or superficial damage e.g.: Stone, tiles, ceramic, slate	2
Surface material	Without structural involvement e.g.: Plaster, other	1
	Lesion	Scoring
Critical / Structural Injuries	Injuries that directly affect structural stability, mechanical integrity, or pose a risk to user safety.	4
Moderate / Progressive Injuries	Injuries that do not pose an immediate risk, but if left untreated, can lead to major failures or compromise durability.	3
Minor / Cosmetic or Superficial Injuries	Injuries that affect the appearance, hygiene, or minor functionality of the item, without mechanical impact.	2
Biological Injuries / External Agents	Attacks by living organisms (fungi, insects, vegetation) that can be very mild or even structurally compromised if not controlled.	1

Table 11: Risk and priority levels derived from cumulative assessment scores for heritage building elements

Total	Risk Level	Priority Level	Description	Code	
17-20	Very high	Urgent intervention	The element is essential for stability; the damage is severe, active, and affects a material with progressive deterioration.	SEVERE DEFICIENCY	4
13-16	High	Medium-term intervention	Significant damage to a secondary or passive structural element, or to enclosing elements with medium risk.	MAJOR DEFICIENCY	3
9-12	Medium	Delayed monitoring or control	Minor damage, stable materials, no immediate risk. Monitoring or deferred action required.	MILD DEFICIENCY	2
5-8	Low	Preservation or maintenance	Cosmetic alterations, with no structural or functional impact.	MINOR DEFICIENCY	1

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The innovative nature of this methodology lies in its specific adaptation to the context of built heritage, where simply detecting damage is not enough: it is essential to understand its structural, historical, material and even symbolic significance. To achieve this, traditional technical and construction criteria (e.g., load-bearing walls, vaults, structural timber) are integrated with contemporary elements (e.g., sandwich panels, modular systems). The evolutionary and systemic nature of deterioration is considered, paying special attention to the cumulative effects of moisture, material incompatibility, and loss of original functionality.

The implementation of this tool contributes to:

- Prioritising interventions based on technical criteria, not just visual urgency or budget availability;
- Reducing unnecessary or reactive repairs by identifying critical issues early;
- Extending the useful life of heritage buildings through preventive conservation;
- Empowering managers with structured, traceable, and evidence-based data.

2.3.4 Integration with the H-BIM model for preventive maintenance (INHERIT service 8)

A distinctive feature of this methodology is its capacity for seamless integration with H-BIM. The inspection form has been conceived not only as a standalone data collection tool, but as an operational component in a broader digital ecosystem that enables proactive conservation and intelligent asset management.

The relationship between the inspection form and the H-BIM model is articulated in three key moments:

- **Pre-inspection phase: digital input from the H-BIM**
 - Element codes, nomenclatures, and architectural references (e.g. Revit Element ID or IFC GUID) are extracted from the H-BIM model.
 - These identifiers are embedded in the inspection form and guide the configuration of its interface, ensuring spatial consistency and semantic coherence.
 - Available model visualisations (plans, sections, or 3D views) assist in defining the scope of work and the inspection path.
- **On-site inspection: data capture linked to model geometry**
 - During fieldwork, each observed element is assigned to its corresponding H-BIM element using preloaded codes.
 - Symptoms, materials, conditions, and location data are collected using semantic fields in the form aligned with IFC attribute definitions.
 - Inspectors use tablets or portable devices to cross-reference visual model data with the inspection interface. While the connection is not dynamic, the preloaded structure ensures on-site coherence.
- **Post-inspection phase: feeding the model with technical findings**
 - Data is exported to an intermediate structured database, storing condition states, lesion types, and priority levels.

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- This database acts as a semantic bridge to the HBIM model, from which updates to object properties can be performed via Dynamo scripts or similar visual programming tools in Revit.
- In this way, all information collected during the inspection becomes spatially and semantically linked to the 3D representation of the asset.

The integration process is summarised in Figure 9, which outlines the step-by-step connection between the technical inspection data and the H-BIM environment, including data flow direction, database use, and processing stages.

Figure 9: Integration of technical inspection data into the H-BIM model to support preventive maintenance strategies

Over time, this bidirectional workflow contributes to the creation of a dynamic, cumulative dataset that enhances the H-BIM model with operational intelligence.

This enriched model supports:

- **Monitoring:** tracking deterioration across time and space.
- **Forecasting:** Identifying risk patterns and simulating future degradation.
- **Planning:** Prioritising interventions and optimising maintenance resource allocation.
- **Transparency:** Facilitating access for stakeholders, public authorities, and conservation teams.

The integration transforms the H-BIM model from a passive repository into a proactive management tool aligned with the objectives of INHERIT Service 8 that supports the long-term sustainability of historic buildings.

Figure 10 below illustrates how the data model used in Service 8 of INHERIT is structured across seven distinct but interrelated information levels. These levels allow the H-BIM model to store and manage both physical and semantic data, including material type, construction system, pathologies, historical significance, maintenance actions, and monitoring conditions. This structured approach makes it possible to connect inspection findings with long-term conservation strategies and supports effective maintenance planning.

Figure 10: Structure of the data model for preventive maintenance with H-BIM (Service 8)

2.3.5 Conclusions and future outlook

The development of the digital technical inspection form represents a strategic step forward in the construction of methodologies oriented toward the preventive conservation of built heritage. Far from being a static tool, its design follows a progressive and adaptive logic, conceived to be improved and refined as it is implemented in different contexts, by various technical profiles, and across diverse heritage realities.

The **main achievements** of this version include:

- The **validation** of a hierarchical inspection logic, structured around six fundamental headings that reflect the **physical and functional organization** of historic buildings.
- The **development of a versatile digital form**, capable of adapting to different levels of intervention, construction typologies, and conservation conditions.
- The **integration of a risk-based prioritisation matrix** that transforms qualitative observations into quantifiable decisions, facilitating both technical and economic management of heritage assets. While no cost estimation is directly integrated at this stage, the system enables prioritisation and can be linked to institutional cost frameworks in future iterations.
- **Alignment with national and international standards**, ensuring methodological coherence with recognised reference frameworks.
- Specific attention to the **knowledge and study of historical construction techniques and materials** is considered a fundamental condition for realistic, effective, and innovative inspection. This approach enables symptoms to be interpreted according to a coherent constructive logic, allowing conservation strategies to be tailored to the specific characteristics of each heritage asset.

Looking ahead, several lines of development are foreseen:

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- **Consolidation as an operational field tool:** Validation through local pilot cases will continue, to incorporate improvements derived from real use and ensure interoperability with other digital tools.
- **Progressive development of pending inspection headings:** During the next phase of the project, the inspection protocols for installations, accessibility, and functional behaviour will be completed, thereby addressing all aspects defined in the hierarchical structure of the form.
- **Strengthened integration with H-BIM models:** Efforts will focus on consolidating data flows between the form and H-BIM models, enabling traceability of elements, automated updates of their conservation status, and long-term monitoring of pathological symptoms, in line with the objectives of INHERIT Service 8, which is focused on preventive conservation through H-BIM environments.

These lines of work will reinforce the system's multidisciplinary and preventive approach, helping to transform technical inspections into a continuous, traceable practice, oriented toward informed decision-making across the life cycle of historic buildings.

3 Assessment and monitoring framework

The **Assessment and Monitoring Framework** developed in the INHERIT project is a cornerstone for evaluating the current status of CH buildings and monitoring their performance across four critical pillars. These pillars address key areas essential for sustainable management and preservation of CH sites (see Figure 11).

Figure 11: INHERIT pillars for the assessment and monitoring framework

The first pillar, **Energy performance and indoor environmental quality**, focuses on enhancing energy efficiency and indoor conditions, such as thermal comfort, air quality, lighting and acoustics, while respecting the unique conservation needs of CH sites. The second pillar, **Resource efficiency, circularity and life cycle cost**, emphasises sustainable building practices by aligning with circular economy principles, optimising resource use and evaluating long-term financial viability through life cycle costing. The third pillar, **Resilience to climate and human-made hazards**, addresses the protection of CH sites from risks such as extreme weather events, climate change impacts and human-induced hazards, employing risk assessment methodologies to guide adaptation strategies. Lastly, the fourth pillar, **Accessibility, inclusiveness, openness and socioeconomic sustainability**, ensures that CH buildings remain accessible and inclusive while contributing positively to social and economic well-being, balancing modern safety and comfort requirements with the preservation of historical integrity. Combined, these pillars provide a comprehensive framework for assessing and monitoring the sustainable management of CH buildings.

This framework complements the technical inspection methodology (section 2) and is underpinned by macro-objectives and a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) tailored to each pillar. These KPIs were developed through an extensive literature review, leveraging methodologies like Level(s) and the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI), and validated through expert input and pilot feedback in the project's Social Labs activities. The framework will be applied in the INHERIT pilots to perform ex-ante and ex-post assessments, providing a robust tool for evaluating the impact of implemented services.

While **D3.1** detailed the macro-objectives and the KPIs for each pillar (including their definitions, criteria and assessment methods), **D3.2** advances the framework by focusing on two critical enhancements:

- **Normalisation**: ensuring that KPIs are comparable across diverse contexts, such as countries, regions and pilots. This involves setting justified targets and applying normalisation criteria, enabling equitable assessments and clear visualisations.

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- **Weighting and prioritisation:** allowing KPIs to be tailored to specific priorities through context-sensitive weighting schemes. This supports decision-making by emphasising goals or characteristics unique to each CH site.

This section provides an overview of the pillars (subsection 3.1) and the refined approach to normalisation (subsection 3.2) and weighting (subsection 3.3). For detailed descriptions of the KPIs, including their units, assessment criteria and examples, readers are referred to D3.1. The enhancements in current D3.2 ensure the framework's applicability and adaptability, empowering stakeholders to monitor and optimise CH building performance effectively.

The development of the framework was a collaborative effort, led by CARTIF with contributions from designated partners for each pillar (i.e., ICCS for Pillar 1, CARTIF for Pillars 2 and 3, and FASADA for Pillar 4). This process involved defining macro-objectives, establishing assessment criteria and selecting KPIs through iterative feedback rounds with pilot leaders and task partners. The result is a practical and validated framework designed to evaluate the impact of INHERIT services based on baseline conditions of CH sites.

KPIs are central to this framework, serving as quantifiable measures to track progress toward objectives. They provide valuable insights for design optimisation, decision-making, and stakeholder communication, ensuring that the framework supports performance evaluation and fosters informed decision-making throughout the lifecycle of CH buildings.

3.1 Overview of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The KPIs form the backbone of the assessment and monitoring framework, offering a structured approach to evaluating CH buildings across four interconnected pillars. These indicators ensure a comprehensive assessment that aligns with conservation needs, sustainability goals and the socioeconomic significance of CH sites.

The **first pillar** emphasises enhancing energy efficiency and improving indoor conditions in CH buildings while safeguarding their historical integrity. Thermal comfort, air quality, lighting and acoustics are key focus areas, with the incorporation of smart technologies, assessed through the SRI, to optimise energy use and promote sustainability. This approach aims to create efficient and healthier spaces that balance occupant comfort and environmental performance. A high-level summary of the KPIs in the Pillar 1 is presented in the following Table 12, including key information such as the description and measurement units. Readers are encouraged to consult the detailed Annex 2 of D3.1 for an in-depth description of each KPI.

Table 12: Overview of the Pillar 1 “Energy Performance and Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ)” KPIs

ID	KPI Name	Description	Unit
1.1-EP	Total energy intensity	It evaluates the overall energy efficiency of the building, as it quantifies its overall energy consumption against its floor area. It provides a standardised measure that enables comparison both across different buildings and over time for the same buildings. It includes heating energy intensity, cooling energy intensity, lighting energy intensity and appliances energy intensity.	kWh/m ² /year
1.1.1-EP	Heating energy intensity	It measures the energy efficiency of a building’s heating system by normalising heating energy consumption against floor area and heating degree days (HDD). It provides insights into heating performance, insulation effectiveness and opportunities for energy savings.	kWh/(m ² · HDD)/year
1.1.2-EP	Cooling energy intensity	It assesses the energy efficiency of a building’s cooling systems by relating cooling energy consumption to floor area and cooling degree days (CDD). It helps evaluate cooling performance, ventilation efficiency and potential improvements in thermal comfort.	kWh/(m ² · CDD)/year
1.1.3-EP	Lighting energy intensity	It evaluates the efficiency of artificial lighting by normalising lighting energy consumption per floor area. It reflects the impact of lighting technologies, daylight utilisation and energy-saving measures such as sensors and controls.	kWh/m ² /year
1.1.4-EP	Appliances energy intensity	It quantifies the energy used by appliances, plug loads and miscellaneous equipment relative to floor area. It provides an overview of non-HVAC and non-lighting energy consumption, helping identify efficiency improvements through technology upgrades and behavioural change.	kWh/m ² /year
1.2-EP	Energy autonomy	This measure is effectively the proportion of energy consumed by a building over the energy produced from RES, thus assessing its overall autonomy and sustainability. It quantifies the share of energy derived from RES, relative to the total energy consumed by the building. Expressed as a percentage, it provides a measure of the building’s reliance on clean energy.	%
1.3-EP	Energy performance and operation	It is an SRI-based KPI that assesses a building’s energy consumption and operational performance, focusing on reducing excessive energy use and associated emissions. By leveraging smart services and technologies, it ensures optimal energy use through dynamic adaptation to prevailing conditions. Additionally, it enhances the maintenance and operational efficiency of technical systems, minimising energy losses and preventing breakdowns.	Score (SRI: “1-Building”)

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ID	KPI Name	Description	Unit
1.4-EP	Response to the needs of occupants	It is an SRI-based KPI that evaluates a building's ability to use smart, user-friendly technologies to autonomously predict, adapt to, and meet occupants' comfort and convenience needs. By coordinating building functions, it enhances occupant satisfaction and well-being, fostering an environment that prioritises user comfort.	Score (SRI: "2-User")
1.5-EP	Energy flexibility assessment	It is an SRI-based KPI that evaluates a building's capacity to adapt its energy consumption and production in response to changing conditions, enhancing resilience and efficiency. By measuring this flexibility, it aims to optimise energy use, ensure reliable supply during peak demand or renewable variability, and improve overall building resilience.	Score (SRI: "3-Grid")
1.1-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	It evaluates the indoor air temperature to ensure it is typically maintained at levels conducive to general population's comfort and satisfaction. It aims to ensure that indoor environments maintain optimal temperature levels for occupant comfort and productivity.	%
1.2-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	It evaluates the indoor humidity of the building to ensure it is typically maintained at levels conducive to general population's comfort and satisfaction. Its objective is to ensure that humidity levels are maintained in the optimal range to support occupant health, comfort and productivity.	%
1.3-IEQ	Air quality	This KPI, focused on CO ₂ concentration, assesses the overall cleanliness of indoor air to ensure that occupants are typically within a healthy and safe environment. Its objective is to ensure that indoor environments are free of harmful pollutants, thereby protecting the health of occupants and improving overall well-being.	%
1.4-IEQ	Visual comfort	It evaluates the quality of lighting inside a building to ensure it is typically conducive to its intended use. It aims to enhance occupant well-being, productivity and overall satisfaction by providing an environment that minimises eye strain and discomfort. It includes identifying lighting solutions that meet both the aesthetic and functional requirements of building users.	%
1.5-IEQ	Acoustic comfort	It assesses the quality of the building's acoustic environment to ensure occupant well-being and productivity in most hours of the day. High acoustic comfort ensure that spaces are free from excessive noise and disturbing sounds, providing a peaceful and functional environment fit for the purpose of the building.	%

Building on the principles of sustainability, the **second pillar** addresses resource efficiency, circular economy strategies and life cycle costing (LCC). It aims to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, optimise material use and manage water resources while preserving the historical and architectural integrity of CH sites. Life cycle costing ensures decisions support both economy efficiency and environmental sustainability over the long term. The KPIs for Pillar 2 are summarised in Table 13 below, providing an overview of their descriptions and measurement units. For a more comprehensive understanding, readers can refer to the detailed explanations available in Annex 3 of D3.1.

Table 13: Overview of the Pillar 2 "Resource Efficiency, Circularity and Life Cycle Cost (LCC)" KPIs

ID	KPI Name	Description	Unit
2.1-TWC	Total Water Consumption	It measures the water consumption of sanitary fitting, devices and water-using appliances, considering consumption rates, usage factors and the potential substitution of potable water with alternative sources like rainwater or greywater. It provides detailed insights through periodic meter readings and can disaggregate data into potable and non-potable use,	Residential: m ³ /occupant/year

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ID	KPI Name	Description	Unit
		supporting sustainable water management, especially in water-stressed areas.	Non-residential: m ³ /m ² /year
2.2-GWP	Global Warming Potential	It measures the greenhouse gas emissions associated with a building's life cycle, including energy use, water consumption and construction materials, to assess its contribution to global warming. It evaluates both operational and embodied carbon, reflecting the emissions from processes like production, construction, maintenance and deconstruction. GWP quantifies the warming effect of different gases relative to CO ₂ , using conversion factors to estimate CO ₂ equivalent emissions, supporting efforts to reduce a building's carbon footprint.	Kg CO ₂ eq./m ² /year
2.3-OEC	Operational Energy Costs	It represents the total costs of a building's energy services, including consumption, operation and maintenance, including all costs arising from the use of energy sources. It is calculated as the energy usage per fuel type multiplied by its cost. It provides critical economic insights for energy renovation planning, enabling comparisons of baseline and planned energy costs.	€/m ² /year
2.4-PBP	Payback Period	The payback period is the time required to recover investment costs, particularly for energy retrofitting in buildings, by calculating the number of years until cumulative savings offset the initial investment and operating costs. Shorter payback periods are considered lower risk, while longer periods may involve greater uncertainty. PBP is a key criterion for assessing the feasibility and risk of energy renovations, with the goal of reducing it through improved energy performance and cost-effective solutions.	Years
2.5-LCC	Life Cycle Cost	It measures the total cost of a building over its life cycle, including construction, operation, maintenance, refurbishment and disposal, reported in €/m ² /year. It helps optimise long-term performance by balancing initial investments with lower running costs and improved value. LCC supports informed decision-making for investors, asset managers and occupants, promoting sustainable, cost-effective building management.	€/m ² /year
2.6-ECI	Energy Circularity Indicator	It measures the proportion of circular energy -renewable energy produced onsite or nearby and energy savings from passive measures- relative to the building's total life cycle energy consumption. It excludes grid-supplied renewable energy and provides straightforward metric to evaluate energy circularity.	%
2.7-WCI	Water Circularity Indicator	It measures the proportion of circular water -recycled/reused water, greywater, blackwater and rainwater- relative to the building's total life cycle water consumption. It offers a clear metric to evaluate water circularity in building operations and end-of-life phases.	%
2.8-MCI	Material Circularity Indicator	It measures the proportion of circular materials -such as recycled, renewable or cyclable materials used during construction, operation and end-of-life phases- relative to total material use in a building. It evaluates the use of materials that are either reusable, recyclable or biodegradable, providing insights into the material circularity of the building.	%

The **third pillar** focuses on enhancing resilience to climate and human-made hazards, acknowledging the growing threats of climate change and other risks to CH sites. Through the evaluation of hazards, vulnerabilities and exposure, KPIs in this pillar guide strategies to protect CH from risks such as extreme weather events, flooding and pollution while maintaining their identity and functionality. Table 14 offers a concise summary of the KPIs for Pillar 3, including their

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descriptions and units of measurement. For further details on each KPI, please consult Annex 4 in D3.1.

Table 14: Overview of the Pillar 3 “Resilience to Climate and Human-made Hazards” KPIs

ID	KPI Name	Description	Unit
3.1-IoH	Inventory of relevant Hazards	It assesses whether a CH site maintains an inventory of relevant hazards, including climate change risks, geological incidents and human-made hazards. It aims to evaluate the site's awareness and documentation of past hazards, helping to understand their potential impacts and responses, as part of a broader risk assessment methodology.	Score (1 to 5)
3.2-HI	Hazards Identification	It lists the main climate or human-made hazards that could affect a CH site, considering risks like climate change, geological incidents, and human-made threats. It aims to identify and document relevant hazards based on location, historical context and potential impacts on the site's integrity, significance and visitor experience. The list should be supported by evidence such as historical records, studies or expert knowledge, and include future trends, especially regarding climate change.	Score (1 to 5)
3.3-RMP	Risk Management Plan(s)	It evaluates the presence, quality and effectiveness of management plans addressing risks, hazards and vulnerabilities at CH sites, particularly those related to climate change and human-made threats. It focuses on whether the site has plans for adaptation, mitigation and response, outlining strategies, protocols and resource allocation. The plans should be integrated into the overall site management, regularly updated and communicated to stakeholders, ensuring actionable measures for risk management.	Score (1 to 5)
3.4-RI_VxE	Risk Impact assessment: Vulnerability and Exposure	It evaluates the qualitative risk impact of climate change, geological incidents and human-made hazards on CH sites, using a matrix of vulnerability and exposure. Vulnerability refers to the site's predisposition to damage, while exposure assesses the extent to which the site is at risk from potential hazards. Each hazard is scored on a 1-5 scale (very high to very low), considering factors such as structural integrity, historical value, location, and the frequency and severity of risks. The goal is to prioritise risks and inform mitigation and adaptation strategies.	Score (1 to 5)
3.5-RL_SxL	Risk impact Level evaluation: Severity of consequences and Likelihood of occurrence	It assesses the risk impact level of climate change, geological incidents and human-made hazards through a matrix of severity of consequences and likelihood of occurrence. The severity is evaluated based on potential damage to the CH site, including physical, historical and financial impacts. The likelihood assesses the probability of the hazard occurring. Both factors are scored on a 1-5 scale, allowing for risk prioritisation and informing risk management strategies for adaptation, mitigation and response.	Score (1 to 5)

Finally, the **fourth pillar** underscores the importance of making CH buildings accessible, inclusive and socially sustainable. KPIs address critical aspects such as fire safety, universal design principles and socioeconomic contributions, ensuring that heritage sites remain usable and valuable to local communities while preserving their cultural significance. The KPIs for Pillar 4 are outlined in Table 15, providing key details such as descriptions and units of measurement. More detailed information is available in Annex 5 of D3.1 for further reference.

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Table 15: Overview of the Pillar 4 “Accessibility, Inclusiveness, Openness and Socioeconomic Sustainability” KPIs

ID	KPI Name	Description	Unit
4.1-AL	Accessibility Level	It evaluates the accessibility of a CH building by identifying architectural barriers and suggesting improvements. It evaluates 11 functional areas, such as access roads, entrances, communication systems, rooms for people with disabilities, and evacuation paths. The assessment is based on universal design principles, considering the needs of users with disabilities and other diverse requirements. The final score is the percentage of criteria met in a standardised audit, focusing on removing critical barriers and improving accessibility.	%
4.2-I&OL	Inclusiveness and Openness Level	It evaluates a building's design, features and policies that promote accessibility, safety and diversity. It considers aspects such as universal design, accessibility features (e.g., ramps, Braille signage), security measures, community engagement, and affordability. The assessment ensures the building is welcoming to people of all abilities, ages and backgrounds, fostering inclusivity and openness. The result is a percentage score, where 100% indicates maximum inclusivity. This KPI helps identify barriers and plan improvements to make the space more accessible and supportive for all users.	%
4.3-RT	Direct Revenue from Tourism	It measures the income generated by a monument or historic building through activities like entry fees, guided tours and souvenir sales. It assesses the financial self-sufficiency of the monument by comparing the tourism revenue to its operational and maintenance costs. The KPI helps to determine how much the monument's upkeep is supported by its own income, highlighting the extent of reliance on external funding. The revenue is categorised into three levels: significant, moderate or minimal, based on the percentage it covers of the total O&M costs.	Score (P, Q, R)
4.4-IRT	Indirect Revenue through Tourism attraction	It measures the economic benefits that local businesses experience due to the popularity of a nearby monument. It includes increased spending at hotels, restaurants and shops, driven by visitors to the monument. This KPI assesses the monument's contribution to the local economy, highlighting its impact on business revenue and growth in the surrounding area. The impact is categorised into three levels: significant, moderate or minimal, based on surveys and estimations of the economic effect on local establishments.	Score (P, Q, R)
4.5-IPV	Increased Property Value	It measures the rise in real estate values near a monument or historic building, often driven by factors like tourism, improved infrastructure and increased demand. This KPI assesses the economic impact of the monument on the local real estate market, indicating how the monument contributes to the area's prosperity. It is categorised into three levels: significant, moderate or minimal, reflecting the degree to which the monument influences local property values.	Score (P, Q, R)
4.6-LJC	Number of Local Jobs Created	It measures the employment opportunities generated by a monument or historic building, both directly (e.g., staff at the monument) and indirectly (e.g., jobs in local businesses benefiting from tourism). It assesses the monument's impact on the local community's economic well-being. The impact is categorised into three levels: significant, moderate or minimal, reflecting the extent to which the monument supports local employment and community engagement.	Score (P, Q, R)
4.7-IPi	Investment in Public Infrastructure	It measures the financial investments made in the surrounding area of a monument, including improvements in transportation, utilities and public spaces, driven by the monument's presence and tourism appeal. It evaluates how the monument stimulates local development through infrastructure	Score (P, Q, R)

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ID	KPI Name	Description	Unit
		enhancements, with impacts categorised into significant, moderate or minimal, reflecting the scale of infrastructure improvements linked to the monument.	
4.8-CE	Cultural Enrichment	It measures the extent to which a monument or historic building contributes to the local cultural scene, including its influence on events, festivals and community engagement. It evaluates the monument's role in enhancing local cultural identity and fostering a vibrant atmosphere, with impacts categorised into significant, moderate and minimal.	Score (P, Q, R)
4.9-PP	Public Perception	It measures the sentiment of the local community and visitors toward a monument or historic building, assessing how it is viewed in terms of cultural, economic and social impact. It categorises sentiment into three levels: positive, neutral and negative. This helps understand the monument's role in the community and guides efforts to improve its reception.	Score (P, Q, R)

3.2 Normalisation of KPIs

The normalisation is the process of transforming KPIs values to a common scale, making them comparable across diverse contexts such as countries, regions or other conditioning characteristics. This process ensures equitable assessment by accounting for contextual differences in performance standards, resource availability and environmental or socio-economic factors. It provides a consistent framework for identifying performance gaps, establishing priorities and supporting clear and transparent visualisation of results.

Without normalisation, disparities in local conditions -such as climatic variations, building typologies and regulatory baselines- could lead to misinterpretation of data. By applying normalisation, KPIs can be harmonised to a standardised range, typically between 0 (representing the least desirable performance) and 100 (representing the target performance), enabling fair comparison and aggregation.

The process of normalising KPIs requires careful definition of the criteria and target values for each indicator. The criteria and values are informed by:

- **Scientific literature and standards:** reference values derived from existing research, building certifications or EU and national regulations.
- **Contextual relevance:** adjustments for geographic, climatic and socio-economic differences (e.g., comparing water consumption in arid regions versus temperate zones).
- **Alignment with European goals:** target values often reflect broader European objectives, such as those established by the European Green Deal, Renovation Wave or energy efficiency directives.
- **Stakeholder input:** insights from pilot projects, stakeholders and experts to ensure practicality and applicability.

The normalisation range for each KPI typically includes:

- **Target value (100%):** the ideal or desired performance level.
- **Average value:** a central reference point based on European or regional data.
- **Maximum/Minimum value (0%):** the least desirable performance level within the established range.

The following sections 3.2.1 to 3.2.4 (one for each Pillar's KPIs) provide an overview of the normalisation framework for KPIs, focusing on European-level criteria and values. In the column "context criteria", various parameters are outlined depending on the specific characteristics and requirements of each KPI. For example, in the case of the energy intensity indicator, the country is a crucial factor, as variations in climate significantly influence the energy consumption of buildings. Conversely, for KPIs related to Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ), external climatic conditions are less relevant. Instead, the focus shifts to parameters such as the type of building and its standardised categorisation, which better reflect the internal conditions and performance requirements.

3.2.1 Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 1 "Energy & Comfort" KPIs

The normalisation criteria for Pillar 1 "Energy Performance and Indoor Environmental Quality" aim to establish a consistent framework for evaluating energy performance and IEQ in CH buildings. The approach considers national and EU-level benchmarks, climate variations, and applicable European standards such as EN 16798-1:2019 for IEQ parameters.

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Where applicable, regional adjustments have been incorporated, particularly for energy intensity KPI, to account for climatic differences across European countries. IEQ KPIs are assessed based on acceptable thresholds defined in EN 16798-1:2019 for Category III, which is suitable for existing CH buildings where full modernisation is constrained.

3.2.1.1 KPI 1.1-EP Total Energy Intensity

In the following Table 16, the criteria and data used for the normalisation and establishment of the target and maximum values for the indicator **1.1-EP of Total Energy Intensity** are depicted. As energy consumption varies a lot from country to country and also from residential to non-residential buildings, the regions have been specified for the INHERIT countries for the Total energy intensity per square meter, as well as the EU level for a wider reference value.

Table 16: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 1 KPI 1.1-EP

KPI	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Climate (Table 17 & Table 18) sets a % reduction for the Target value	Average value	Target (100%)	Max. (0%)	Source
1.1-EP	Total Energy Intensity (RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS)	kWh/m ² /year	Croatia	Moderate climate (68%)	207.80	141.0	252.3	Average values from: • ODYSSEE-MURE ⁴
			France	Moderate climate (68%)	178.40	151.0	196.7	
			Greece	Extreme hot climate (75%)	151.90	114.0	177.2	
			Latvia	Extreme cold climate (75%)	238.90	179.0	278.8	
			Poland	Moderate climate (68%)	252.70	172.0	306.5	
			Spain	Moderate climate (68%)	99.60	68.0	120.7	
			Sweden	Extreme cold climate (75%)	171.10	128.0	199.8	
			Turkey	Extreme hot climate (75%)	151.90	114.0	177.2	
			EU level	Moderate climate (68%)	173.70	118.0	210.8	
	Total Energy Intensity (NON-RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS)	kWh/m ² /year	Croatia	Moderate climate (68%)	250.00	170.0	303.3	
			France	Moderate climate (68%)	280.00	190.0	340.0	
			Greece	Extreme hot climate (75%)	300.00	225.0	350.0	
			Latvia	Extreme cold climate (75%)	300.00	225.0	350.0	
			Poland	Moderate climate (68%)	190.00	129.0	230.7	
			Spain	Moderate climate (68%)	250.00	170.0	303.3	
			Sweden	Extreme cold climate (75%)	220.00	165.0	256.7	
			Turkey	Extreme hot climate (75%)	300.00	225.0	350.0	
			EU level	Moderate climate (68%)	280.00	190.0	340.0	

⁴ ODYSSEE-MURE: <https://www.indicators.odyssee-mure.eu/online-indicators.html> (Indicator: Average energy consumption per dwelling: <https://www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/efficiency-by-sector/households/average-energy-consumption-dwelling.html>)

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To establish the normalisation criteria for the total energy intensity, average consumption values from the literature at country and EU levels are used as a baseline. The target value (100%) was set as a percentage of improvement over the average consumption, informed by the heating and cooling degree days (HDD and CDD) at the country level, and NUTS 3 region when available. The HDD and CDD are weather-based technical indices used to estimate the energy demand in buildings for heating and cooling. HDD reflects the need for heating, while CDD indicates the demand for cooling (air conditioning). These indices are derived from meteorological air temperature observations, interpolated to a 25km resolution grid for Europe. The calculated gridded HDD and CDD values are then aggregated to the corresponding level (either country level or NUTS-3 level). The HDD and CDD values for the INHERIT countries and NUTS 3 regions, and at an EU level are depicted in following Table 17.

Table 17: Heating and Cooling Degree Days (HDD and CDD) values for the normalisation criteria for Pillar 1 KPI 1.1-EP both at country level and at NUTS 3 level where available (source: Eurostat⁵ and IEA⁶)

KPI	KPI Name	Region (country)	HDD (2023 data)	CDD (2023 data)	Region (NUTS 3 Region)	HDD (2023 data)	CDD (2023 data)
1.1-EP	Total Energy Intensity	Croatia	1,957.53	181.67	Zagrebačka županija – Croatia	2,116.83	134.43
		France	2,045.12	87.22	-	-	-
		Greece	1,375.80	387.33	Kentrikos Tomeas Athinon – Greece	864.79	640.42
		Latvia	3,755.06	8.77	Rīga – Latvia	3,418.73	9.20
		Poland	2,972.75	26.08	Trójmiejski – Poland	3,099.34	2.30
		Spain	1,481.64	338.23	Valladolid – Spain	2,047.83	102.40
		Sweden	5,180.32	0.02	Gotlands län – Sweden	3,331.88	0.00
		Turkey* *2020 year	1,534.00	443.00	Turkey	-	-
		EU level	2,820.92	121.47	EU level	-	-

Taking these factors into account, the target values were set approximately 75% of the average intensity for countries with an extreme climate, approx. 68% for those with a moderate climate, and 60% for countries with a mild climate, according to the classification below.

Table 18: Criteria used to establish target values for the different pilot countries and regions, considering the climate (HDD and CDD)

Improvement (reduction) of average value to Target value	Climate	Criteria	Regions (country or NUTS-3 Region)
75%	Extreme climate	HDD > 3200 or CDD > 400	- Kentrikos Tomeas Athinon – Greece (extreme hot climate) - Rīga – Latvia (extreme cold climate) - Gotlands län – Sweden (extreme cold climate) - Turkey (extreme hot climate)

⁵ Eurostat, Cooling and heating degree days by country - annual data: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/nrg_chdd_a/default/table. Eurostat, Cooling and heating degree days by NUTS 3 region - annual data: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/nrg_chddr2_a/default/table

⁶ IEA data used for Turkey, Heating degree days in Türkiye, 2000-2020: <https://www.iea.org/data-and-statistics/charts/heating-degree-days-in-turkiye-2000-2020>. Cooling degree days in Türkiye, 2000-2020: <https://www.iea.org/data-and-statistics/charts/cooling-degree-days-in-turkiye-2000-2020>

Improvement (reduction) of average value to Target value	Climate	Criteria	Regions (country or NUTS-3 Region)
68%	Moderate climate	2000 < HDD < 3200 or 150 < CDD < 400	- Zagrebačka županija – Croatia - France - Trójmiejski – Poland - Valladolid – Spain - EU level
60%	Mild climate	HDD < 2000 or CDD < 150	-

The maximum value (0%) was calculated based on the relationship between the target value as 100%, the average value as 40%, and the maximum value as 0%, ensuring a consistent framework for normalisation.

3.2.1.2 KPI 1.1-1-EP Heating Energy Intensity

In the following Table 19, the criteria and data used for the normalisation and establishment of the target and maximum values for the indicator **1.1.1-EP of Heating Energy Intensity** are depicted. As heating consumption varies a lot from country to country, the regions have been specified for the INHERIT countries for the heating energy intensity per square meter and considering HDD, as well as the EU level for a wider reference value.

To establish the normalisation criteria for the heating energy intensity, average consumption values from the literature at country and EU levels are used as a baseline. The target value (100%) was set as a 70% improvement over the average consumption, as the indicator itself is already informed by the heating degree days (HDD) at the country level, and NUTS 3 region when available (from previous Table 17). The maximum value (0%) was calculated based on the relationship between the target value as 100%, the average value as 40%, and the maximum value as 0%, ensuring a consistent framework for normalisation.

Table 19: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 1 KPI 1.1.1-EP

KPI	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value [kWh/m ²]	Average value [kWh/(m ² ·HDD)]	Target (100%)	Max. (0%)	Source
1.1.1-EP	Heating Energy Intensity (RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS)	kWh/(m ² ·HDD)/year	Croatia	140.70	0.066	0.047	0.080	Average values from: • ODYSSEE-MURE ⁷ • Turkey data from Kazanasmaz et al. (2014) ⁸ HDD from Table 17.
			France	121.00	0.059	0.041	0.071	
			Greece	71.10	0.082	0.058	0.099	
			Latvia	151.20	0.044	0.031	0.053	
			Poland	161.70	0.052	0.037	0.063	
			Spain	41.30	0.020	0.014	0.024	
			Sweden	93.30	0.028	0.020	0.034	
			Turkey	71.10	0.046	0.032	0.056	
			EU level	111.20	0.039	0.028	0.047	
			Croatia	70.00	0.033	0.023	0.040	

⁷ ODYSSEE-MURE: <https://www.indicators.odyssee-mure.eu/online-indicators.html> (Indicator: Heating consumption per m² and per dwelling: <https://www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/efficiency-by-sector/households/heating-consumption-per-m2.html>)

⁸ Kazanasmaz et al. (2014): <https://gcris.iyte.edu.tr/bitstream/11147/5531/1/5531.pdf>

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KPI	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value [kWh/m ²]	Average value [kWh/(m ² ·HDD)]	Target (100%)	Max. (0%)	Source
	Heating Energy Intensity (NON-RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS)	kWh/(m ² ·HDD)/year	France	120.00	0.059	0.041	0.070	
			Greece	95.00	0.110	0.077	0.132	
			Latvia	180.00	0.053	0.037	0.063	
			Poland	90.00	0.029	0.020	0.035	
			Spain	80.00	0.039	0.027	0.047	
			Sweden	120.00	0.036	0.025	0.043	
			Turkey	95.00	0.062	0.043	0.074	
			EU level	130.00	0.046	0.032	0.055	

3.2.1.3 KPI 1.1.2-EP Cooling Energy Intensity

In the following Table 20, the criteria and data used for the normalisation and establishment of the target and maximum values for the indicator **1.1.2-EP of Cooling Energy Intensity** are depicted. As cooling consumption varies a lot from country to country and also from residential to non-residential buildings, the regions have been specified for the INHERIT countries for the cooling energy intensity per square meter and considering CDD, as well as the EU level for a wider reference value.

To establish the normalisation criteria for the cooling energy intensity, average consumption values from the literature at country and EU levels are used as a baseline. The target value (100%) was set as a 70% improvement over the average consumption, as the indicator itself is already informed by the cooling degree days (CDD) at country level, and at NUTS 3 region when available (from previous Table 17). The maximum value (0%) was calculated based on the relationship between the target value as 100%, the average value as 40%, and the maximum value as 0%, ensuring a consistent framework for normalisation.

Table 20: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 1 KPI 1.1.2-EP

KPI	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value [kWh/m ²]	Average value [kWh/(m ² ·CDD)]	Target (100%)	Max. (0%)	Source
1.1.2-EP	Cooling Energy Intensity (RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS)	kWh/(m ² ·CDD)/year	Croatia	4.10	0.030	0.021	0.037	Average values from: • ODYSSEE-MURE ⁹ CDD from Table 17.
			France	1.00	0.011	0.008	0.014	
			Greece	5.40	0.008	0.006	0.010	
			Latvia	0.10	0.011	0.008	0.013	
			Poland	0.30	0.130	0.091	0.157	
			Spain	1.00	0.010	0.007	0.012	
			Sweden	0.00	0.000	0.000	0.000	
			Turkey	5.40	0.012	0.009	0.015	
			EU level	0.80	0.007	0.005	0.008	
	Cooling Energy			Croatia	15.00	0.112	0.078	
			France	10.00	0.115	0.080	0.138	

⁹ ODYSSEE-MURE: <https://www.indicators.odyssee-mure.eu/online-indicators.html> (Indicator: Unit consumption of air conditioning: <https://www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/efficiency-by-sector/households/unit-consumption-air-conditioning.html>)

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KPI	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value [kWh/m ²]	Average value [kWh/(m ² -CDD)]	Target (100%)	Max. (0%)	Source
	Intensity (NON-RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS)	kWh/(m ² -CDD)/year	Greece	25.00	0.039	0.027	0.047	
			Latvia	0.00	0.000	0.000	0.000	
			Poland	0.00	0.000	0.000	0.000	
			Spain	20.00	0.195	0.137	0.234	
			Sweden	5.00	0.000	0.000	0.000	
			Turkey	25.00	0.056	0.040	0.068	
			EU level	25.00	0.206	0.144	0.247	

3.2.1.4 KPI 1.1.3-EP Lighting Energy Intensity

In the following Table 21, the criteria and data used for the normalisation and establishment of the target and maximum values for the indicator **1.1.3-EP of Lighting Energy Intensity** are depicted. As lighting consumption varies a lot from country to country and also from residential to non-residential buildings, the regions have been specified for the INHERIT countries for the lighting energy intensity per square meter, as well as the EU level for a wider reference value.

To establish the normalisation criteria for the lighting energy intensity, average consumption values from the literature at country and EU levels are used as a baseline. The target value (100%) was set as a 70% improvement over the average consumption. The maximum value (0%) was calculated based on the relationship between the target value as 100%, the average value as 40%, and the maximum value as 0%, ensuring a consistent framework for normalisation.

Table 21: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 1 KPI 1.1.3-EP

KPI	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Max. (0%)	Source
1.1.3-EP	Lighting Energy Intensity (RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS)	kWh/m ² /year	Croatia	4.30	3.00	5.17	Average values from: • ODYSSEE-MURE ¹⁰
			France	5.10	3.50	6.17	
			Greece	4.50	3.00	5.50	
			Latvia	7.00	4.50	8.67	
			Poland	7.40	5.00	9.00	
			Spain	4.90	3.50	5.83	
			Sweden	5.00	3.50	6.00	
			Turkey	4.50	3.00	5.50	
			EU level	3.30	2.00	4.17	
	Lighting Energy Intensity (NON-RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS)	kWh/m ² /year	Croatia	25.00	17.50	30.00	
			France	15.00	10.50	18.00	
			Greece	35.00	24.50	42.00	
			Latvia	15.00	10.50	18.00	
			Poland	10.00	7.00	12.00	
Spain			35.00	24.50	42.00		

¹⁰ ODYSSEE-MURE: <https://www.indicators.odyssee-mure.eu/online-indicators.html> (Indicator: Electricity consumption per dwelling for electrical appliances and lighting; <https://www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/efficiency-by-sector/households/electricity-consumption-dwelling-electrical-appliances-lighting.html>)

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KPI	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Max. (0%)	Source
			Sweden	10.00	7.00	12.00	
			Turkey	35.00	24.50	42.00	
			EU level	30.00	21.00	36.00	

3.2.1.5 KPI 1.1.4-EP Appliances Energy Intensity

In the following Table 22, the criteria and data used for the normalisation and establishment of the target and maximum values for the indicator **1.1.4-EP of Appliances Energy Intensity** are depicted. As other energy consumption from appliances, equipment, plug loads and other miscellaneous sources within the building vary a lot from country to country, and also from residential to non-residential buildings, the regions have been specified for the INHERIT countries for the appliances energy intensity per square meter, as well as the EU level for a wider reference value.

To establish the normalisation criteria for the appliances' energy intensity, average consumption values from the literature at country and EU levels are used as a baseline. The target value (100%) was set as a 70% of the average consumption. The maximum value (0%) was calculated based on the relationship between the target value as 100%, the average value as 40%, and the maximum value as 0%, ensuring a consistent framework for normalisation.

Table 22: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 1 KPI 1.1.4-EP

KPI	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Max. (0%)	Source
1.1.4-EP	Appliances Energy Intensity (RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS)	kWh/m ² / year	Croatia	58.70	41.00	70.50	Average values from: • ODYSSEE-MURE ¹¹
			France	51.30	36.00	61.50	
			Greece	71.00	49.50	85.33	
			Latvia	80.60	56.50	96.67	
			Poland	83.30	58.50	99.83	
			Spain	52.40	36.50	63.00	
			Sweden	72.80	51.00	87.33	
			Turkey	71.00	49.50	85.33	
			EU level	58.50	41.00	70.17	
	Appliances Energy Intensity (NON-RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS)	kWh/m ² / year	Croatia	140.00	98.00	168.00	
			France	135.00	94.50	162.00	
			Greece	145.00	101.50	174.00	
			Latvia	105.00	73.50	126.00	
			Poland	90.00	63.00	108.00	
			Spain	115.00	80.50	138.00	
			Sweden	85.00	59.50	102.00	
			Turkey	145.00	101.50	174.00	
EU level	95.00	66.50	114.00				

¹¹ ODYSSEE-MURE: <https://www.indicators.odyssee-mure.eu/online-indicators.html> (Indicators: Energy consumption of large appliances per dwelling: <https://www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/efficiency-by-sector/households/energy-consumption-large-appliances-dwelling.html>, and Changes in energy consumption and value added of services: <https://www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/efficiency-by-sector/services/>)

3.2.1.6 KPI 1.2-EP Energy Autonomy

The normalisation criteria outlined in Table 23 for indicator **1.2-EP of Energy Autonomy** evaluate the percentage of energy produced from RES compared to total consumption, providing a standardised measure of energy independence.

A score of 100% (target value) signifies that the building produces all its consumed energy from RES, achieving full energy autonomy. A score of 0% (minimum value) reflects no energy autonomy, as most buildings (especially heritage ones) have no energy production or cover a very small part of their energy demand through RES.

Table 23: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 1 KPI 1.2-EP

KPI	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Min. (0%)	Source
1.2-EP	Energy Autonomy	%	EU level	-	100%	0%	• Same referenced as D3.1.

This normalisation approach aligns with EU energy policies and sustainable goals, such as the European Green Deal¹², the Renewable Energy Directive (RED II – 2018/2001/EU)¹³, and the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD 2018/844/EU)¹⁴, which all emphasise the importance of increasing the share of renewables in building to achieve carbon neutrality by 2050. Additionally, ISO 52000-1:2017¹⁵ provides a framework for assessing energy performance in buildings, including the share of renewable energy in total energy consumption.

3.2.1.7 KPI 1.3-EP Energy Performance & Operation

This indicator evaluates a building's energy consumption and operational efficiency based on its ability to reduce excessive energy use, minimise emissions, and enhance technical system performance through smart technologies. The KPI is computed using the SRI-ENACT tool¹⁶, specifically the "1-Building" aggregate score, which averages the impact of energy efficiency and fault protection across different technical domains.

In the following Table 24, the criteria and data used for the normalisation and establishment of the target and maximum values for the indicator **1.3-EP of Energy Performance & Operation** are depicted.

A score of 100% (target value) represent high smart readiness, where the building effectively minimises energy waste and optimises system performance through fault detection and energy-efficient operations. A score of 0% (minimum value) indicates poor energy performance and lack of smart operational strategies, resulting in excessive energy consumption and higher emissions.

Table 24: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 1 KPI 1.3-EP

KPI	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Min. (0%)	Source
1.3-EP	Energy Performance & Operation	- (score)	EU level	-	100%	0%	• References for SRI methodology

¹² https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

¹³ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2018/2001/oj/eng>

¹⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2018/844/oj/eng>

¹⁵ <https://www.iso.org/standard/65601.html>

¹⁶ <https://www.srienact-tool.eu/login>

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3.2.1.8 KPI 1.4-EP Response to the Needs of Occupants

This indicator assesses a building’s ability to autonomously predict, adapt and meet the comfort and convenience needs of its occupants through user-friendly smart technologies. It is calculated using the SRI-ENACT tool, specifically the “2-User” aggregate score, which considers the impact of comfort, convenience, health and well-being, accessibility and information provision to occupants.

In Table 25 the criteria and data used for the normalisation and establishment of the target and maximum values for the indicator **1.4-EP of Response to the needs of occupants** are depicted.

A score of 100% (target value) indicates that the building effectively utilises smart technologies to enhance occupant comfort and well-being, ensuring seamless adaptation to user preferences. A score of 0% (minimum value) reflects low smart readiness, where the building provides little or no automated response to occupant needs.

Table 25: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 1 KPI 1.4-EP

KPI	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Min. (0%)	Source
1.4-EP	Response to the needs of occupants	- (score)	EU level	-	100%	0%	● References for SRI methodology

3.2.1.9 KPI 1.5-EP Energy Flexibility Assessment

This indicator evaluates a building’s capacity to dynamically adjust its energy consumption and production in response to changing conditions, enhancing energy efficiency and resilience. It is calculated using the SRI-ENACT tool, specifically the “3-Grid” aggregate score, which reflects the impact of energy flexibility and storage across technical domains.

Table 26 includes the criteria and data used for the normalisation and establishment of the target and maximum values for the indicator **1.5-EP of Energy Flexibility Assessment** are depicted.

A score of 100% (target value) represents high energy flexibility, meaning that the building can efficiently adjust energy use in response to grid conditions, optimise self-consumption of renewable energy, and participate in demand-response strategies. A score of 0% (minimum value) indicates low flexibility, where the building lacks the capacity to adapt energy use to external fluctuations, reducing its efficiency and resilience.

Table 26: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 1 KPI 1.5-EP

KPI	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Min. (0%)	Source
1.5-EP	Energy Flexibility Assessment	- (score)	EU level	-	100%	0%	● References for SRI methodology

3.2.1.10 KPI 1.1-IEQ Thermal Comfort in terms of Air Temperature

The normalisation criteria for **KPI 1.1-IEQ Thermal Comfort in terms of Air Temperature** establish a standardised framework for assessing thermal conditions across different building types at the EU level. Since indoor environmental quality (IEQ) is not significantly influenced by the location, the normalisation values remain consistent across countries.

The normalisation is based on the EN 16798-1:2019 standard, which defines acceptable temperature ranges for different building types according to three comfort categories:

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- **Category I:** High level of expectation (e.g., spaces occupied by sensitive individuals).
- **Category II:** Normal level of expectation (e.g., new buildings and renovations).
- **Category III:** Moderate level of expectation (e.g., existing buildings).

Since CH buildings are subject to conservation constraints, the minimum acceptable thresholds from category III have been selected as the basis for normalisation.

Table 27 presents the criteria and data used for the normalisation and establishment of the target and minimum values for the indicator.

The target value (100%) represents optimal thermal comfort, meaning that the indoor air temperature remains within the acceptable range for 100% of the occupancy hours. The minimum value (0%) represents poor thermal comfort, meaning that the indoor air temperature remains outside the acceptable range for less than 50% of the occupancy hours.

Table 27: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 1 KPI 1.1-IEQ

KPI	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Min. (0%)	Source
1.1-IEQ	Thermal Comfort in terms of Air Temperature	%	EU level	-	100%	50%	● EN 16798-1:2019 (Category III)

Table 28 details the temperature thresholds considered for thermal comfort assessment according to EN 16798-1:2019. The values for category III are used as the baseline for normalisation.

Table 28: Temperature ranges for the normalisation of Pillar 1 KPI 1.1-IEQ (based on EN 16798-1:2019)

KPI	KPI Name	IEQ aspect	Building/ space type	Category		
				I	II	III
1.1-IEQ	Thermal Comfort in terms of Air Temperature	Temperature range winter	Residential buildings (bedrooms)	21-25 °C	20-25 °C	18-25°C
			Offices (landscape layout)	21-23 °C	20-24 °C	19-25°C
			Schools (classrooms)	21-23 °C	20-24 °C	19-25°C
		Temperature range summer	Residential buildings (bedrooms)	23.5-25.5 °C	23-26 °C	22-27°C
			Offices (landscape layout)	23.5-25.5 °C	23-26 °C	22-27°C
			Schools (classrooms)	23.5-25.5 °C	23-26 °C	22-27°C

3.2.1.11 KPI 1.2-IEQ Thermal Comfort in terms of Indoor Humidity

The normalisation criteria for KPI **1.2-IEQ Thermal Comfort in terms of Indoor Humidity** establish a consistent evaluation framework for assessing indoor humidity conditions in buildings. As humidity is a crucial factor influencing occupant comfort, air quality and building material preservation, this KPI ensures that humidity levels remain within acceptable thresholds.

The normalisation is based on the EN 16798-1:2019 standard, which defines acceptable indoor humidity ranges across the three comfort categories:

- **Category I:** High level of expectation (e.g., spaces occupied by sensitive individuals).
- **Category II:** Normal level of expectation (e.g., new buildings and renovations).
- **Category III:** Moderate level of expectation (e.g., existing buildings).

Since CH buildings often face constraints that limit the feasibility of precise indoor humidity control, the thresholds of category III (20-70%) are used as the reference for normalisation.

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Table 29 presents the normalisation values and data used for the establishment of the target and minimum values for the indicator.

The target value (100%) represents optimal humidity comfort, meaning that humidity remains within the acceptable range for 100% of the occupancy hours. The minimum value (0%) represents poor humidity control, meaning that humidity is outside the acceptable range for more than 50% of the occupancy hours.

Table 29: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 1 KPI 1.2-IEQ

KPI	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Min. (0%)	Source
1.2-IEQ	Thermal Comfort in terms of Indoor Humidity	%	EU level	-	100%	50%	● EN 16798-1:2019 (Category III)

Table 30 details the humidity thresholds defined by EN 16798-1:2019, which are used to assess indoor humidity conditions in buildings.

Table 30: Humidity ranges for the normalisation of Pillar 1 KPI 1.2-IEQ (based on EN 16798-1:2019)

KPI	KPI Name	IEQ aspect	Building/ space type	Category		
				I	II	III
1.1-IEQ	Thermal Comfort in terms of Indoor Humidity	Humidity range	All types of building	30-50 %	25-60 %	20-70 %

3.2.1.12 KPI 1.3-IEQ Air Quality

The normalisation criteria for KPI **1.3-IEQ Air Quality** (CO₂ concentration) establish a structured approach to evaluating indoor air quality (IAQ) in buildings, ensuring that CO₂ levels remain within acceptable thresholds for occupant health and well-being. The normalisation is based on the EN 16798-1:2019 standard, which provides **CO₂ concentration limits** for different building types and comfort categories:

- **Category I:** High level of expectation (e.g., spaces occupied by sensitive individuals).
- **Category II:** Normal level of expectation (e.g., new buildings and renovations).
- **Category III:** Moderate level of expectation (e.g., existing buildings).

Given the constraints of CH buildings, the thresholds of category III (CO₂ levels <1,350 ppm in offices and schools) are used for normalisation.

Table 31 presents the normalisation criteria and data used to establish the target and minimum values for the indicator.

The target value (100%) represents good air quality, meaning that CO₂ levels remain within the acceptable range for 100% of occupancy hours. The minimum value (0%) represents poor air quality, meaning that CO₂ levels exceed the acceptable range for more than 50% of occupancy hours.

Table 31: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 1 KPI 1.3-IEQ

KPI	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Min. (0%)	Source
1.3-IEQ	Air Quality (CO ₂ concentration)	%	EU level	-	100%	50%	● EN 16798-1:2019 (Category III)

Table 32 details the CO₂ concentration thresholds defined by EN 16798-1:2019; which are used to assess indoor air quality in different building types.

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Table 32: CO₂ thresholds for the normalisation of Pillar 1 KPI 1.3-IEQ (based on EN 16798-1:2019)

KPI	KPI Name	IEQ aspect	Building/ space type	Category		
				I	II	III
1.3-IEQ	Air Quality (CO ₂ concentration)	Maximum CO ₂ level (ppm)	Residential buildings (bedrooms)	380	550	950
			Offices (landscape layout)	550	800	1,350
			Schools (classrooms)	550	800	1,350

3.2.1.13 KPI 1.4-IEQ Visual Comfort

The normalisation criteria for KPI **1.4-IEQ Visual Comfort** (illuminance levels) establish a structured approach to assess indoor lighting conditions, ensuring adequate visual comfort for building occupants. Proper lighting enhances well-being, productivity and satisfaction, while preventing eye strain and visual discomfort. The normalisation is based on EN 16798-1:2019, which provides **minimum illuminance levels** for different building spaces and functional needs. The standard defines 500 lux as the minimum acceptable illuminance for offices and similar workspaces.

Since visual comfort is not climate-dependent, normalisation values are established at the EU level, ensuring consistent assessment across different building types.

Table 33 presents the normalisation criteria and data used to establish the target and minimum values for the indicator.

The target value (100%) represents optimal visualisation comfort, meaning that illuminance is higher than 500 lux for 100% of occupancy hours. The minimum value (0%) represents poor visual comfort, meaning that illuminance is higher than 500 lux for more than 50% of occupancy hours.

Table 33: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 1 KPI 1.4-IEQ

KPI	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Min. (0%)	Source
1.4-IEQ	Visual Comfort (illuminance levels)	%	EU level	-	100%	50%	● EN 16798-1:2019

Table 34 details the minimum illuminance levels defined by EN 16798-1; which serve as the basis for evaluating visual comfort in different building spaces.

Table 34: Illuminance thresholds for the normalisation of Pillar 1 KPI 1.4-IEQ (based on EN 16798-1:2019)

KPI	KPI Name	IEQ aspect	Building/ space type	Minimum illuminance (Lux)
1.4-IEQ	Visual Comfort (illuminance levels)	Minimum lighting level (Em)	Residential buildings (living rooms)	-
			Offices (landscape layout)	500 lux
			Schools (classrooms)	500 lux

3.2.1.14 KPI 1.5-IEQ Acoustic Comfort

The normalisation criteria for KPI **1.5-IEQ Acoustic comfort** (noise levels) provide a structured framework for assessing indoor noise conditions, ensuring optimal occupant well-being and productivity. High acoustic comfort minimises disturbances and enhances concentration, making it essential for workspaces, educational environments and residential settings.

The normalisation approach is based on EN 16798-1:2019, which defines **maximum noise levels** for different building types and functional spaces in three comfort categories:

- **Category I:** High level of expectation (e.g., spaces occupied by sensitive individuals).

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- **Category II:** Normal level of expectation (e.g., new buildings and renovations).
- **Category III:** Moderate level of expectation (e.g., existing buildings).

For existing (and CH) buildings, category III is selected as the benchmark, which sets a maximum acceptable noise level of 45 dB for offices and similar environments.

Since acoustic comfort is not climate-dependent, values are offered at the EU level, ensuring consistent assessment across different buildings and regions.

Table 35 outlines the normalisation criteria and data used to establish the target and minimum values for the indicator.

The target value (100%) represents optimal acoustic comfort, meaning that noise level is lower than 45 dB for 100% of occupancy hours. The minimum value (0%) represents poor acoustic comfort, meaning that the noise level is lower than 45 dB for more than 50% of occupancy hours.

Table 35: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 1 KPI 1.5-IEQ

KPI	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Min. (0%)	Source
1.5-IEQ	Acoustic Comfort (noise levels)	%	EU level	-	100%	50%	• EN 16798-1:2019 (Category III)

Table 36 presents the maximum allowable noise levels (LAeq) from EN 16798-1:2019, serving as the basis for normalisation.

Table 36: Maximum allowable noise levels for the normalisation of Pillar 1 KPI 1.5-IEQ (based on EN 16798-1:2019)

KPI	KPI Name	IEQ aspect	Building/ space type	Category (dB)		
				I	II	III
1.5-IEQ	Acoustic Comfort (noise levels)	Maximum system noise level (LAeq)	Residential buildings (bedrooms)	25 dB	30 dB	35 dB
			Offices (landscape layout)	35 dB	40 dB	45 dB
			Schools (classrooms)	30 dB	34 dB	38 dB

3.2.2 Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 2 “Resource & Circularity” KPIs

The Pillar 2 “Resource Efficiency, Circularity and Life Cycle Cost” normalisation criteria are established for each indicator to enable consistent benchmarking and comparison across diverse contexts, with targets aligned to EU sustainability objectives such as the Green Deal and Circular Economy Action Plan. Key data inputs and calculations supporting these criteria are provided in each of the following sub-sections (3.2.2.1 to 3.2.2.8) devoted to every indicator in Pillar 2.

The normalisation criteria for the indicators of Total Water Consumption, Global Warming Potential and Operational Energy Costs have been specified for each INHERIT country, as these values can vary significantly from one country to another since they depend on the climate and weather conditions (e.g., for the use of energy for space heating or cooling, for the use of water in swimming pools...). The remaining indicators in Pillar 2 are assigned single EU-wide targets and maximum values. This approach simplifies the framework while ensuring alignment with overarching EU sustainability goals such as the Green Deal and Circular Economy Action Plan. These indicators are less influenced by regional disparities and instead reflect shared objectives, enabling consistent benchmarking and comparability across all countries.

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3.2.2.1 KPI 2.1-TWC Total Water Consumption

In the following Table 37, the criteria and data used for the normalisation and establishment of the target and maximum values for the indicator **2.1-TWC of Total Water Consumption** are depicted. In order to make water consumption comparable, the TWC per occupant has been specified for the INHERIT countries, as well as the EU level for wider reference values. In addition, TWC per square meter has been also added at EU level.

Table 37: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 2 KPI 2.1-TWC

KPI	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Max. (0%)	Source
2.1-TWC	Total Water Consumption (PER OCCUPANT)	m ³ / occupant/ year	Croatia	66.43	45.0	80.7	Average values from: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> European Parliament¹⁷ Eurostat¹⁸
			France	46.72	35.0	54.5	
			Greece	64.61	40.0	81.0	
			Latvia	28.11	20.0	33.5	
			Poland	35.77	25.0	43.0	
			Spain	47.45	30.0	59.1	
			Sweden	54.02	40.0	63.4	
			Turkey	44.00	30.0	53.3	
			EU level	43.80	30.0	53.0	
	Total Water Consumption (PER SQUARE METRE)	m ³ /m ² / year	EU level	0.76	0.55	0.90	Statista ¹⁹

To establish the normalisation criteria for the total water consumption, average consumption values from the literature at country and EU levels are used as a baseline. The target value (100%) was set as a percentage of improvement over the average consumption, informed by the **Water Exploitation Index plus (WEI+)**. The WEI+ is an indicator used to assess water stress by measuring the ratio of total water abstraction to renewable freshwater resources in a given area over a specific period. Unlike the traditional water exploitation index (WEI), which only considers annual water abstraction, WEI+ accounts for seasonal variations and environmental flow requirements, providing a more dynamic and accurate assessment of water scarcity. A WEI+ value above 20% indicates more water stress, while values above 40% suggest severe water stress, signalling potential risks to water availability for ecosystems and human activities, implying unsustainable use of freshwater resources. The WEI+ values for the INHERIT regions and at an EU level are depicted in following Table 38.

Table 38: Water Exploitation Index, plus (WEI+) values for the normalisation criteria for Pillar 2 KPI 2.1-TWC

KPI	KPI Name	Unit	Region	WEI+	Average value (TWC)
2.1-TWC	Total Water Consumption (PER OCCUPANT)	m ³ /occupant/ year	Croatia	0.17	66.43
			France	2.80	46.72
			Greece	13.27	64.61
			Latvia	0.39	28.11
			Poland	8.70	35.77

¹⁷ <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/topics/en/article/20181011STO15887/drinking-water-in-the-eu-better-quality-and-access>

¹⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Water_statistics

¹⁹ <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1312154/water-intensity-of-real-estate-by-type-europe/>

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KPI	KPI Name	Unit	Region	WEI+	Average value (TWC)
			Spain	8.10	47.45
			Sweden	0.22	54.02
			Turkey	14.03	44.00
			EU level	3.60	43.80

WEI+ (Water Exploitation Index plus) is expressed as a decimal ratio (e.g., 0.17 = 17%), not as a percentage in the Table 38. Values above 0.2 (20%) indicate water stress, and values above 0.4 (40%) reflect severe water stress. For consistency and comparability, WEI+ values are shown in decimal form as per Eurostat convention.

Taking these factors into account, the target values were set at approximately 75% of the average consumption for countries with a WEI+ below 7%, approx. 68% for those with a WEI+ between 7% and 12%, and 60% for countries with a WEI+ above 13%. The maximum value (0%) was calculated based on the relationship between the target value as 100%, the average value as 40%, and the maximum value as 0%, ensuring a consistent framework for normalisation.

The methodology reflects regional differences in water stress, enabling fair comparisons and supporting efforts to prioritise improvements where water resources are under great strain.

3.2.2.2 KPI 2.2-GWP Global Warming Potential

Table 39 summarises the normalisation criteria, including region-specific data, the derived average values and the targets and maximum thresholds for the indicator **2.2-GWP of Global Warming Potential**. These values are essential and support to compare the suitability performance of CH buildings across different countries and within the EU.

The normalisation criteria are based on two key components, the energy intensity (taken from KPI 1.1-EP, Table 16) and the water consumption (derived from KPI 2.1-TWC, Table 37). These values, per m², are converted into CO₂ equivalent emissions using established GHG emission factors.

The target value (100%) represents approximately 70% of the average GWP value. This is aligned with ambitious European sustainability goals. The maximum value (0%) is calculated based on a framework where the average value corresponds to 40% and the target value to 100%, ensuring consistency across all countries and at the EU level.

Table 39: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 2 KPI 2.2-GWP

ID	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Max. (0%)	Source
2.2-GWP	Global Warming Potential	Kg CO ₂ eq./m ² /year	Croatia	30.49	21.0	36.8	KPIs: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1.1-EP (Table 16) ● 2.1-TWC (Table 37) D3.1 Annex 3 (detailed KPI 2.2-GWP in Annex A3.2) Eurostat ²⁰
			France	12.72	9.0	15.2	
			Greece	23.62	16.0	28.7	
			Latvia	30.75	21.0	37.3	
			Poland	61.69	43.0	74.2	
			Spain	9.87	7.0	11.8	
			Sweden	10.03	7.0	12.1	
			Turkey	28.42	20.0	34.0	
			EU level	19.42	13.5	23.4	

²⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Energy_consumption_in_households

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The final GWP value for each country and EU level is calculated as the sum of the GWP from energy and water.

The average values for the **GWP from water** are directly calculated by multiplying the TWC per square meter and the GHG factor for tap water, which corresponds to 0.378 Kg CO₂ eq./m³. The calculation can be seen in Table 40, resulting in 0.29 Kg CO₂ eq./m².

Table 40: Calculation of the average values for the GWP from water (for Pillar 2 KPI 2.2-GWP)

ID	KPI Name	Unit	Region	2.1-TWC	GHG emission factor from tap water	Average value
2.2-GWP water	Global Warming Potential from water	Kg CO ₂ eq./m ² /year	EU level	0.76 m ³ /m ² /year	0.378 Kg CO ₂ eq./m ³	0.29

The calculation of the average **GWP from energy** is more complex, since it requires different data:

- the energy intensity data (kWh/m²/year) from KPI 1.1-EP in Pillar 1 from previous section 3.2.1.1,
- the share of fuels in each country (see Table 41)
- that are then multiplied by the total energy intensity to obtain the intensity per fuel type in each region (see Table 42),
- the GHG emission factors for each of the fuels (Table 43). These are collected mainly from the information for the KPI 2.2-GWP reported in D3.1 (Annex A3.2), based on JRC data on emission factors. As can be seen in Table 43, while emission factors are by default (at EU level) for most of the energy carriers and renewable energy, the emission factor for the GHG emissions of the electricity consumption is different per country, as it depends on the country energy mix.
- Finally, Table 44 includes the calculation of the GWP from energy, which is done as the summary of the energy intensity of each fuel multiplied by the corresponding emission factor.

Table 41: Share of fuels from the energy consumption in the EU and pilot's countries (input for Pillar 2 KPI 2.2-GWP) (source: Eurostat²¹)

Region	Natural gas	Electricity	Renewables and biofuels	Oil and petroleum products	Heat	Solid fossil fuels
Croatia	21.40%	24.31%	45.06%	4.34%	4.83%	0.07%
France	25.54%	35.89%	25.75%	9.40%	3.36%	0.07%
Greece	10.79%	33.03%	25.75%	29.76%	0.63%	0.04%
Latvia	9.41%	12.93%	39.91%	4.87%	32.88%	0.11%
Poland	20.88%	12.43%	26.49%	2.87%	17.51%	19.83%
Spain	21.84%	44.24%	16.41%	17.31%	0.00%	0.20%
Sweden	0.36%	49.48%	11.99%	2.10%	36.07%	0.00%
Turkey	55.87%	20.02%	14.16%	1.43%	0.00%	8.51%
EU level	30.89%	25.10%	22.64%	10.88%	8.15%	2.26%

²¹ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Energy_consumption_in_households

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Table 42: Energy intensity in total and per fuel type (input for Pillar 2 KPI 2.2-GWP) (calculated from KPI 1.1-EP and previous table on share of fuels) in kWh/m²/year

Region	TOTAL (Energy intensity)	Natural gas	Electricity	Renewables and biofuels	Oil and petroleum products	Heat	Solid fossil fuels
Croatia	208	44.51	50.56	93.72	9.03	10.05	0.15
France	178	38.09	43.27	80.21	7.73	8.60	0.12
Greece	152	32.53	36.95	68.49	6.60	7.34	0.11
Latvia	239	51.15	58.10	107.69	10.37	11.54	0.17
Poland	253	54.14	61.50	114.00	10.98	12.22	0.18
Spain	100	21.40	24.31	45.06	4.34	4.83	0.07
Sweden	171	36.59	41.57	77.05	7.42	8.26	0.12
Turkey	152	32.53	36.95	68.49	6.60	7.34	0.11
EU level	174	37.24	42.30	78.40	7.55	8.40	0.12

Table 43: Emission factors of the different fuels (input for Pillar 2 KPI 2.2-GWP) in tonnes of CO₂ eq./MWh (source: D3.1 Annex A3.2)

Region	Natural gas	Renewables and biofuels	Oil and petroleum products	Solid fossil fuels (e.g., anthracite)	Electricity		
	Standard approach (source: IPCC, 2006 ²²)				Activity-based approach, IPCC	Source	
Croatia	0.202	0.000	0.227	0.356	0.378	IPCC (JRC) ²³	
France					0.068		
Greece					0.412		
Latvia					0.305		
Poland					0.779		
Spain					0.175		
Sweden					0.015		
Turkey					0.542		Climatiq ²⁴
EU level					0.233		IEA ²⁵

Table 44: Calculation of the average values for the GWP from energy (for Pillar 2 KPI 2.2-GWP)

ID	KPI Name	Region	GWP from energy [Kg CO ₂ eq./m ² /year]						TOTAL GWP from energy [Kg CO ₂ eq./m ² /year]
			Natural gas	Electricity	Renewables and biofuels	Oil and petroleum products	Heat	Solid fossil fuels	
2.2-GWP energy	Global Warming Potential	Croatia	8.991	19.113	0.000	2.049	0.000	0.052	30.21
		France	7.695	2.942	0.000	1.754	0.000	0.044	12.44
		Greece	6.571	15.224	0.000	1.497	0.000	0.038	23.33
		Latvia	10.331	17.721	0.000	2.355	0.000	0.060	30.47

²² <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC136272>

²³ <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC136272>

²⁴ <https://www.climatiq.io/data/emission-factor/d56e798f-2094-40af-9ab2-1367f9c98b1f>

²⁵ <https://www.iea.org/data-and-statistics/data-product/emissions-factors-2024>

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ID	KPI Name	Region	GWP from energy [Kg CO ₂ eq./m ² /year]					TOTAL GWP from energy [Kg CO ₂ eq./m ² /year]	
			Natural gas	Electricity	Renewables and biofuels	Oil and petroleum products	Heat		Solid fossil fuels
	from energy	Poland	10.937	47.912	0.000	2.493	0.000	0.063	61.40
		Spain	4.323	4.254	0.000	0.985	0.000	0.025	9.59
		Sweden	7.392	0.624	0.000	1.685	0.000	0.043	9.74
		Turkey	6.571	20.028	0.000	1.497	0.000	0.038	28.13
		EU level	7.522	9.856	0.000	1.714	0.000	0.043	19.14

3.2.2.3 KPI 2.3-OEC Operational Energy Costs

Table 45 summarises the normalisation criteria for the indicator **2.3-OEC of Operational Energy Costs**. It includes region-specific data, as well as the average values and the targets and maximum thresholds.

Table 45: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 2 KPI 2.3-OEC

ID	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Max. (0%)	Source
2.3-OEC	Operational Energy Costs	€/m ² /year	Croatia	20.14	14.0	24.2	KPI 2.2-GWP (Table 42) Energy prices per energy fuel: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Natural gas (Eurostat²⁶) ● Electricity (Eurostat²⁷) ● Renewables (adapted and estimated from IRENA²⁸)
			France	21.13	15.0	25.2	
			Greece	14.53	10.0	17.6	
			Latvia	26.11	18.0	31.5	
			Poland	24.95	17.5	29.9	
			Spain	10.08	7.0	12.1	
			Sweden	19.32	13.5	23.2	
			Turkey	8.26	6.0	9.8	
			EU level	20.66	14.5	24.8	

The normalisation criteria are based on two key components, the energy intensity per energy fuel (taken from KPI 2.2-GWP, Table 42) and the energy prices for the fuels.

The target value (100%) represents approximately 70% of the average OEC value. The maximum (0%) is calculated based on a framework where the average value corresponds to 40% and the target value to 100%, ensuring consistency across all countries.

The energy prices for the different fuels are difficult to find and thus, only natural gas, electricity and renewable energy have been taken into consideration, which in turn have the highest share of consumption. Both the natural gas and electricity prices are available in the Eurostat database and can be checked in Table 46 for 2024 prices by types of user, and average values calculated to be used in the calculation of the average OEC. For the renewable energy, an adaptation has been done based on data from IRENA to estimate the price of **renewable energy** at the European level, which stands for **0.044€/kWh**.

²⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ten00117/default/table?lang=en&category=t_nrg.t_nrg_indic

²⁷ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ten00118/default/table?lang=en&category=t_nrg.t_nrg_indic

²⁸ <https://www.irena.org/Publications/2024/Sep/Renewable-Power-Generation-Costs-in-2023>

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Table 46: Energy prices of fuels in 2024 for the EU and pilot's countries (input for Pillar 2 KPI 2.3-OEC)

(source: Eurostat) in €/kWh

Region	Natural gas (medium size households)	Natural gas (non-households, medium-size consumers)	Electricity (medium size households)	Electricity (non-households, medium-size consumers)	Natural gas (average)	Electricity (average)
Croatia	0.0524	0.1472	0.2169	0.0486	0.1821	0.0524
France	0.0581	0.2776	0.1555	0.0881	0.2166	0.0581
Greece	0.0376	0.2173	0.1279	0.0549	0.1726	0.0376
Latvia	0.0538	0.2546	0.1451	0.0730	0.1999	0.0538
Poland	0.0707	0.2112	0.1275	0.0695	0.1694	0.0707
Spain	0.0424	0.2436	0.1217	0.0622	0.1827	0.0424
Sweden	0.0682	0.2434	0.0937	0.1221	0.1686	0.0682
Turkey	0.0315	0.0488	0.0898	0.0239	0.0693	0.0315
EU level	0.0530	0.2889	0.1558	0.0817	0.2224	0.0530

Then, as can be seen in Table 47, the energy prices per fuel are multiplied by the corresponding energy intensity fuel, and the summary of those three values constitutes the total energy cost. To consider the maintenance and other energy-related costs in the OEC indicator average, an increase of 30% has been added to the energy costs.

Table 47: Cost of energy per fuel, in total and 30% increase for considering maintenance and other energy-related costs (input for Pillar 2 KPI 2.3-OEC) in €/m²/year

Region	Natural gas	Electricity	Renewables	Total energy cost	Maintenance and other energy-related costs (30%)	Total (average OEC)
Croatia	2.162	9.205	4.124	15.49	4.65	20.14
France	3.355	9.371	3.529	16.25	4.88	21.13
Greece	1.786	6.378	3.014	11.18	3.35	14.53
Latvia	3.735	11.611	4.739	20.09	6.03	26.11
Poland	3.761	10.416	5.016	19.19	5.76	24.95
Spain	1.330	4.440	1.983	7.75	2.33	10.08
Sweden	4.468	7.007	3.390	14.86	4.46	19.32
Turkey	0.777	2.561	3.014	6.35	1.91	8.26
EU level	3.041	9.405	3.450	15.90	4.77	20.66

3.2.2.4 KPI 2.4-PBP Payback Period

Table 48 contains the normalisation criteria, including the average value, the target and the maximum value for the indicator **2.4-PBP Payback Period**.

Table 48: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 2 KPI 2.4-PBP

ID	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Max. (0%)	Source
2.4-PBP	Payback Period	Years	EU level	8	5	12	Reference from EPBD, European Guide on EE...

The normalisation criteria are based on typical payback periods for energy retrofitting projects in Europe, which often range from 6 to 10 years. The target value is set at an optimal timeframe to

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enhance investment attractiveness and align with EU energy efficiency goals, while the maximum value is set at 12 years, as longer payback periods are generally considered financially unviable due to higher risks and uncertainties.

Although specific payback periods are not detailed in EU regulations, the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD)²⁹ emphasises cost-effective renovations to improve energy efficiency, indirectly supporting shorter payback periods for energy retrofitting investments. The European Energy Efficiency Guide 2024³⁰ and the Commission Guidance on Implementing the EPBD (2019)³¹ highlight the need for financially feasible investments to achieve EU energy reduction targets, such as a 16% reduction by 2030. These criteria ensure consistency in assessing retrofitting projects' financial viability, encouraging investments aligned with EU sustainability objectives.

3.2.2.5 KPI 2.5-LCC Life Cycle Cost

Table 49 contains the normalisation criteria, including the average value, the target and the maximum value for the indicator **2.5-LCC Life Cycle Cost**.

Table 49: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 2 KPI 2.5-LCC

ID	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Max. (0%)	Source
2.5-LCC	Life Cycle Cost	€/m ² /year	EU level	25	15	35	Reference from EPBD, Level(s) framework...

The normalisation criteria are based on typical life cycle costs for retrofitted buildings in Europe, which often range from 20 to 30 €/m²/year, depending on the scope of retrofitting measures, operational efficiency and building type. The target value is set at 15 €/m²/year, representing an optimised cost achieved through energy-efficient renovations, effective maintenance strategies and sustainable materials. This aligns with EU objectives to balance initial investments with reduced long-term operational costs. The maximum value is set at 35 €/m²/year, reflecting poorly optimised life cycle costs that are financially unsustainable due to high operational or maintenance expenses.

While specific benchmarks are not detailed in EU regulations, the EPBD³² emphasises cost-effective renovations, and the Level(s) EU framework³³ provides methodologies to assess and optimise life cycle costs. The EC's guidance on Life Cycle Costing in construction³⁴ emphasises the importance of considering all costs over a building's life span to ensure economic feasibility and sustainability. Additionally, studies such as the one by Santos et al. (2023)³⁵ highlight the role of life cycle costing in supporting sustainable decision-making in the construction sector, aligning with EU sustainability objectives.

²⁹ https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficient-buildings/energy-performance-buildings-directive_en?prefLang=es

³⁰ <https://build-up.ec.europa.eu/en/resources-and-tools/publications/european-energy-efficiency-guide-2024>

³¹ https://commission.europa.eu/news/commission-guidance-how-implement-revised-energy-performance-buildings-directive-provisions-building-2019-05-16_en

³² https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficient-buildings/energy-performance-buildings-directive_en?prefLang=es

³³ https://susproc.jrc.ec.europa.eu/product-bureau/sites/default/files/2021-01/UM3_Indicator_6.1_v1.1_21pp.pdf

³⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/5060/attachments/1/translations/en/renditions/pdf>

³⁵ <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/16/20/8959>

3.2.2.6 KPI 2.6-ECI Energy Circularity Indicator

Table 50 contains the normalisation criteria, including the average value, the target and the minimum value for the indicator **2.6-ECI Energy Circularity Indicator**.

Table 50: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 2 KPI 2.6-ECI

ID	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Min. (0%)	Source
2.6-ECI	Energy Circularity Indicator	%	EU level	25%	60%	10%	Reference from EPBD, RED, European Green Deal...

The normalisation criteria are based on estimated energy circularity levels achievable in retrofitted buildings across Europe, considering the extent of on-site renewable energy production and the implementation of passive energy-saving measures. The target value is set at 60%, representing an optimised level of energy circularity achieved through significant adoption of on-site renewable energy systems and advanced passive strategies, aligning with EU goals for increased energy efficiency and renewable energy integration. The minimum value is set at 10%, reflecting minimal or no integration of renewable energy and negligible use of passive measures.

Although specific benchmarks for energy circularity are not detailed in EU regulations, the EPBD emphasises the importance of reducing energy consumption and increasing reliance on renewable energy systems, indirectly supporting higher levels of energy circularity. Additionally, the Renewable Energy Directive (RED)³⁶ promotes decentralised renewable energy adoption, and the European Green Deal³⁷ reinforces the importance of improving energy efficiency to achieve climate neutrality by 2050. The normalisation criteria ensure consistency in assessing energy circularity across retrofitted buildings, encouraging investments aligned with EU sustainability objectives and circular economy principles.

3.2.2.7 KPI 2.7-WCI Water Circularity Indicator

Table 51 contains the normalisation criteria, including the average value, the target and the minimum value for the indicator **2.7-WCI Water Circularity Indicator**.

Table 51: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 2 KPI 2.7-WCI

ID	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Min. (0%)	Source
2.7-WCI	Water Circularity Indicator	%	EU level	25%	60%	10%	Reference from WFD, WISE, Ellen MacArthur Foundation...

The average value of 25% for the 2.7-WCI reflects the estimated level of water circularity currently achievable in retrofitted CH buildings. Many CH buildings face challenges in implementing large-scale water reuse systems, such as greywater and blackwater recycling or rainwater harvesting, due to design constraints and preservation requirements. Existing examples from retrofitted buildings across Europe suggest that 20-30% circular water can typically be achieved with moderate integration of water reuse and rainwater harvesting systems. This aligns with the objectives of the EU Water Framework Directive (WFD)³⁸, which promotes sustainable water management practices

³⁶ https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/renewable-energy/renewable-energy-directive-targets-and-rules/renewable-energy-directive_en

³⁷ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

³⁸ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/water/water-framework-directive_en

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and encourages reducing freshwater demand through reuse and recycling (also in Freshwater Information System for Europe, WISE³⁹).

The target value of 60% represents an optimised level of water circularity that can be achieved through the substantial integration of advanced water reuse systems (e.g., greywater and blackwater recycling) and rainwater harvesting technologies. This aligns with the Ellen McArthur Foundation’s circularity principles⁴⁰ and the European Green Deal, which emphasise resource efficiency and the circular economy as critical pathways to achieving environmental sustainability. Achieving this target supports reduced reliance on freshwater resources and aligns with EU-wide goals for reducing water stress and improving circular water practices. The minimum value of 10% reflects minimal or no integration of circular water systems, which is a baseline scenario often observed in un-retrofitted or poorly optimised CH buildings. This threshold underscores the importance of implementing water reuse systems as part of sustainable retrofitting strategies.

3.2.2.8 KPI 2.8-MCI Material Circularity Indicator

Table 52 contains the normalisation criteria, including the average value, the target and the minimum value for the indicator **2.8-MCI Material Circularity Indicator**.

Table 52: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 2 KPI 2.8-MCI

ID	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Min. (0%)	Source
2.8-MCI	Material Circularity Indicator	%	EU level	30%	70%	10%	Reference from Ellen MacArthur Foundation, CEAP, Cradle to Cradle certification...

The average value of 30% of the **2.8-MCI Material Circularity Indicator** reflects the estimated level of material circularity achievable in retrofitted buildings, including CH sites. Many CH buildings face constraints in integrating recycled or renewable materials and designing for material recovery at the end of life due to preservation requirements and construction challenges. However, existing retrofitted examples suggest that integrating 20-40% circular materials is feasible with moderate efforts, such as incorporating recycled metals, renewable materials like timber or bamboo, and design for extended material lifespans. This estimate aligns with the Ellen MacArthur Foundation’s circularity principles⁴¹, which emphasise maximising resource recovery, and the European Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP)⁴², which promotes the use of secondary raw materials in construction.

The target value of 70% represents an ambitious yet achievable level of material circularity, where a significant portion of materials used are recycled, renewable or designed for reuse or biodegradation. Achieving this target aligns with EU objectives under the CEAP and the European Green Deal, which prioritise resource efficiency and circularity as key strategies for achieving climate neutrality by 2050. It reflects the integration of advanced material circularity strategies, such as using Cradle to Cradle-certified products⁴³, designing for disassembly and prioritising renewable and cyclable materials. The minimum value of 10% reflects minimal material circularity, such as scenarios where little to no effort is made to use recycled, renewable or cyclable materials.

³⁹ <https://water.europa.eu/freshwater>

⁴⁰ <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/> and <https://emf.thirdlight.com/link/blnz4r55tme1-dpouou/@/preview/1?o>

⁴¹ <https://www.ellenmacarthurfoundation.org/circular-economy-principles>

⁴² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1583933814386&uri=COM:2020:98:FIN>

⁴³ <https://c2ccertified.org/certified-products>

3.2.3 Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 3 “Climate Resilience” KPIs

The normalisation criteria for the indicators under Pillar 3 “Resilience to Climate and Human-made Hazards” establish a consistent framework for assessing resilience in CH buildings, ensuring comparability across different sites. Unlike the KPIs in previous pillars, these indicators were designed with a predefined **1 to 5 scoring scale**, inherently normalising the evaluation, where higher scores indicate better preparedness, risk management and resilience.

Since these indicators evaluate **qualitative aspects** -such as the presence, completeness and effectiveness of risk-related documentation and strategies- no additional EU-wide average is calculated. The predefined scoring methodology itself provides a **standardised and qualitative evaluation framework**. The normalisation process primarily ensures alignment with international and European risk management frameworks, such as those outlined by IPCC, the EU Adaptation Strategy, and UNESCO guidelines for CH risk management.

This approach reflects best practices in resilience planning, allowing sites to benchmark their performance and identify areas for improvement. The following sub-sections (3.2.3.1 to 3.2.3.5) detail the normalisation criteria and targets for every indicator in Pillar 3.

3.2.3.1 KPI 3.1-IoH Inventory of relevant Hazards

This indicator evaluates whether a CH site maintains a **systematic record of past hazards**, ensuring awareness and preparedness for future threats. A well-documented inventory enables site managers to track historical hazards, understand their impacts and develop effective mitigation strategies. The normalisation criteria outlined in Table 53 for indicator **3.1-IoH Inventory of relevant Hazards**, evaluate the completeness, accessibility and level of detail of hazard inventories at CH sites.

Table 53: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 3 KPI 3.1-IoH

ID	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Min. (0%)	Source
3.1-IoH	Inventory of relevant Hazards	Score (1 to 5)	EU level	-	5	1	Same references as D3.1.

A score of 5 (target value) represents a comprehensive, well-maintained inventory that documents all major past hazards, including dates, impacts and mitigation responses. This ensures that the site is well-prepared for potential future risks. Conversely, a score of 1 (minimum value) indicates no documentation of past hazards, reflecting a high vulnerability to unforeseen risks and a lack of structured risk management.

3.2.3.2 KPI 3.2-HI Hazards Identification

This indicator assesses whether a CH site has a **clear and well-documented list of potential hazards** that may affect it in the future. Identifying relevant hazards is a fundamental step in risk management, allowing site managers to proactively assess and mitigate potential threats related to climate change, geological events and human-made hazards.

The normalisation criteria outlined in Table 54 for indicator **3.2-HI Hazards Identification** evaluate the completeness and documentation quality of hazard identification at CH sites.

Table 54: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 3 KPI 3.2-HI

ID	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Min. (0%)	Source
3.2-HI	Hazards Identification	Score (1 to 5)	EU level	-	5	1	Same references as D3.1.

A score of 5 (target value) reflects a comprehensive hazards list that is well-documented, supported by evidence and considers future trends. This ensures that all major risks are identified and accounted for in the site's risk management strategies. In contrast, a score of 1 (minimum value) indicates no formal identification of potential hazards, leaving the site vulnerable to unanticipated threats.

3.2.3.3 KPI 3.3-RMP Risk Management Plan(s)

This indicator evaluates whether a CH site has a **structured risk management plan (RMP)** that outlines strategies for mitigating, adapting to and responding to identified hazards. A well-developed RMP ensures that CH sites have clear procedures in place to address potential risks effectively.

The normalisation criteria outlined in Table 55 for indicator **3.3-RMP Risk Management Plan(s)** assess the existence, comprehensiveness and implementation of risk management plans at CH sites.

Table 55: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 3 KPI 3.3-RMP

ID	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Min. (0%)	Source
3.3-RMP	Risk Management Plan(s)	Score (1 to 5)	EU level	-	5	1	Same references as D3.1.

A score of 5 (target value) represents a comprehensive and regularly updated risk management plan, covering adaptation, mitigation and response strategies while being fully integrated into the CH site's overall management framework. A score of 1 (minimum value) signifies no formalised risk management plan, indicating an absence of preparedness and response mechanisms.

3.2.3.4 KPI 3.4-RI_VxE Risk Impact assessment: Vulnerability and Exposure

This indicator measures a CH site's **susceptibility (vulnerability) and level of exposure** to identified hazards. By assessing these factors, site managers can prioritise risks and tailor mitigation strategies accordingly.

The normalisation criteria outlined in Table 56 for indicator **3.4-RI_VxE Risk Impact assessment: Vulnerability and Exposure** ensure a consistent assessment of risk impact across different CH sites, using a structured evaluation of vulnerability and exposure.

Table 56: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 3 KPI 3.4-RI_VxE

ID	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Min. (0%)	Source
3.4-RI_VxE	Risk Impact assessment: Vulnerability and Exposure	Score (1 to 5)	EU level	-	5	1	Same references as D3.1.

A score of 5 (target value) represents a detailed, evidence-based assessment of vulnerability and exposure, ensuring that risks are well-documented and prioritised. A score of 1 (minimum value) indicates no assessment, leaving the site unprepared to prioritise risk and implement hazard mitigation measures.

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3.2.3.5 KPI 3.5-RL_SxL Risk impact Level evaluation: Severity of consequences and Likelihood of occurrence

This indicator assesses the **potential severity of hazard consequences** and the **likelihood of their occurrence**, allowing sites to quantify and prioritise risks. This approach supports informed decision-making and targeted mitigation strategies.

The normalisation criteria in Table 57 for indicator **3.5-RL_SxL Risk impact Level evaluation: Severity of consequences and Likelihood of occurrence** provide a structured framework for assessing risk impact levels at CH sites.

Table 57: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 3 KPI 3.5-RL_SxL

ID	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Min. (0%)	Source
3.5-RL_SxL	Risk impact Level evaluation: Severity of consequences and Likelihood of occurrence	Score (1 to 5)	EU level	-	5	1	Same references as D3.1.

A score of 5 (target value) indicates a thorough, well-documented assessment of severity and likelihood, ensuring that mitigation plans are prioritised based on risk magnitude. A score of 1 (minimum value) means no formal assessment, leaving the CH site exposed to unanticipated threats.

3.2.4 Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 4 “Accessibility & Sustainability” KPIs

The normalisation criteria for the indicators under Pillar 4 “Accessibility, Inclusiveness, Openness and Socioeconomic Sustainability” ensure a consistent evaluation framework for CH buildings. Like the indicators in Pillar 3, these KPIs are largely predefined with a normalised scale, eliminating the need for additional adjustments or EU-wide average calculations.

These indicators assess **qualitative and semi-quantitative aspects** related to accessibility, inclusiveness, socioeconomic impact and community perception. Their inherently structured and standardised scoring systems allow for comparability across different CH sites without requiring further normalisation.

The normalisation approach aligns with international and European frameworks, including EN 17210:2021 (European Accessibility Standard)⁴⁴, the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD)⁴⁵, the European Disability Strategy⁴⁶, and the EU Green Deal⁴⁷. This ensures that CH sites can benchmark their performance, identify accessibility and inclusivity gaps, and implement targeted improvement strategies while considering conservation constraints.

The following sub-sections (3.2.4.1 to 3.2.4.9) detail the normalisation criteria and targets for every indicator in Pillar 4.

3.2.4.1 KPI 4.1-AL Accessibility Level

This indicator assesses the **level of accessibility** in a CH building, ensuring that **architectural and functional barriers** are identified and addressed through accessibility audits. It evaluates whether

⁴⁴ https://accessible-eu-centre.ec.europa.eu/content-corner/digital-library/en-172102021-accessibility-and-usability-built-environment-functional-requirements_en

⁴⁵ <https://social.desa.un.org/issues/disability/crpd/convention-on-the-rights-of-persons-with-disabilities-crpd>

⁴⁶ <https://www.inclusion-europe.eu/european-disability-strategy/>

⁴⁷ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

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the building complies with **universal design principles**, providing **equitable access** for all users, including people with disabilities, seniors, and caregivers with small children.

The normalisation criteria outlined in Table 58 for indicator **4.1-AL Accessibility Level** evaluate the percentage of accessibility criteria met during an audit, reflecting the extent to which the building supports inclusive access.

Table 58: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 4 KPI 4.1-AL

ID	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Min. (0%)	Source
4.1-AL	Accessibility Level	%	EU level	-	100%	30%	Same references as D3.1.

A score of 100% (target value) represents full compliance with accessibility requirements, ensuring barrier-free access and adherence to universal design standards. A score of 30% indicates low accessibility, acknowledging that even heritage buildings with constraints often include some accessibility adaptations (e.g., ramps, alternative routes, assistance services, etc.).

3.2.4.2 KPI 4.2-I&OL Inclusiveness and Openness Level

This indicator evaluates a CH building's **degree of inclusiveness and openness**, measuring factors such as **universal design, safety, community engagement, affordability, and diversity-friendly policies**. It considers whether the building fosters an inclusive environment for all users, regardless of background, abilities or socioeconomic status.

The normalisation criteria outlined in Table 59 for indicator **4.2-I&OL Inclusiveness and Openness Level** assess the extent of inclusiveness based on a checklist approach, providing a percentage score.

Table 59: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 4 KPI 4.2-I&OL

ID	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Min. (0%)	Source
4.2-I&OL	Inclusiveness and Openness Level	%	EU level	-	100%	30%	Same references as D3.1.

A score of 100% (target value) indicates that the building meets all inclusivity and openness criteria, ensuring a welcoming and fully inclusive and engagement space for all users. A score of 30% indicates a non-inclusive environment, where significant barriers limit engagement and participation.

Inclusiveness goes beyond physical accessibility to policies, affordability and engagement strategies, which many CH sites provide at least partially.

3.2.4.3 KPI 4.3-RT Direct Revenue from Tourism

This indicator measures the **percentage of operational and maintenance costs (O&M)** covered by **direct tourism revenue**, such as entry fees, guided tours and souvenir sales. It reflects the **financial self-sufficiency** of the CH building and its ability to sustain operations without relying on external funding.

The normalisation criteria outlined in Table 60 for indicator **4.3-RT Direct Revenue from Tourism** categorise revenue coverage into three levels: **significant (P), moderate (Q) and minimal effect (R)**, according to criteria in Annex A5.3 from D3.1.

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Table 60: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 4 KPI 4.3-RT

ID	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Min. (0%)	Source
4.3-RT	Direct Revenue from Tourism	Score (P, Q, R)	EU level	-	P (>50%)	R (<20%)	Same references as D3.1.

A score of P – significant effect (target value) indicates that the CH site generates enough revenue to cover at least 50% of its O&M costs, ensuring high financial sustainability.

3.2.4.4 KPI 4.4-IRT Indirect Revenue through Tourism

This indicator assesses how the **CH site contributes to local businesses** by attracting tourists who spend money on **hotels, restaurants and shops**.

The normalisation criteria outlined in Table 61 for indicator **4.4-IRT Indirect Revenue through Tourism** categorise the monument's economic impact based on business surveys and estimated contributions, according to criteria in Annex A5.4 from D3.1.

Table 61: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 4 KPI 4.4-IRT

ID	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Min. (0%)	Source
4.4-IRT	Indirect Revenue through Tourism	Score (P, Q, R)	EU level	-	P (strong effect)	R (minimal)	Same references as D3.1.

A score of P – significant effect (target value) indicates that the CH site drives substantial local economic activity, boosting local businesses and employment. A score of Q – moderate effect - indicates that the CH site has a moderate influence on the revenues of the zone, and this value will take the value of 50%.

3.2.4.5 KPI 4.5-IPV Increased Property Value

This indicator measures the **impact** of the CH site **on real estate prices** in the surrounding area due to increased attractiveness and tourism demand.

The normalisation criteria outlined in Table 62 for indicator **4.5-IPV Increased Property Value** classify the impact based on property **value growth percentages**, according to criteria in Annex A5.5 from D3.1.

Table 62: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 4 KPI 4.5-IPV

ID	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Min. (0%)	Source
4.5-IPV	Increased Property Value	Score (P, Q, R)	EU level	-	P (>15%)	R (<5%)	Same references as D3.1.

A score of P – significant effect (target value) reflects a significant increase in property values, indicating a strong economic influence from the CH site.

3.2.4.6 KPI 4.6-LJC Number of Local Jobs Created

This indicator evaluates the CH site's **role in supporting community employment**, measuring the proportion of **jobs filled by local residents**.

The normalisation criteria in Table 63 for indicator **4.6-LJC Number of Local Jobs Created** define three levels of employment impact, according to criteria in Annex A5.6 from D3.1.

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Table 63: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 4 KPI 4.6-LJC

ID	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Min. (0%)	Source
4.6-LJC	Number of Local Jobs Created	Score (P, Q, R)	EU level	-	P (>70%)	R (<40%)	Same references as D3.1.

A score of P – significant effect (target value) indicates that more than 70% of jobs are held by local residents, demonstrating a strong community employment impact.

3.2.4.7 KPI 4.7-IPI Investment in Public Infrastructure

This indicator measures **public and private investment in infrastructure projects** linked to the presence of the CH site, such as transport, utilities and public spaces, benefiting both local communities and visitors.

The normalisation criteria in Table 64 for indicator **4.7-IPI Investment in Public Infrastructure** classify the impact based on financial contributions, according to Annex A5.7 from D3.1.

Table 64: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 4 KPI 4.7-IPI

ID	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Min. (0%)	Source
4.7-IPI	Investment in Public Infrastructure	Score (P, Q, R)	EU level	-	P (>50%)	R (<20%)	Same references as D3.1.

A score of P – significant effect (target value) means that infrastructure investments exceed 10 million € or represent over 50% of local projects, reflecting a strong economic boost.

3.2.4.8 KPI 4.8-CE Cultural Enrichment

This indicator assesses how a CH site **contributes to local cultural activities**, such as events, festivals, exhibitions and artistic programmes. It measures the role of the site in fostering cultural identity and engagement.

The normalisation criteria outlined in Table 65 for indicator **4.8-CE Cultural Enrichment** classify the impact based on participation in cultural events, according to Annex A5.8 from D3.1.

Table 65: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 4 KPI 4.8-CE

ID	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Min. (0%)	Source
4.8-CE	Cultural Enrichment	Score (P, Q, R)	EU level	-	P (>50%)	R (<20%)	Same references as D3.1.

A score of P – significant effect (target value) reflects that the CH site directly contributes to over 50% of cultural events, strengthening local identity and engagement in the area.

3.2.4.9 KPI 4.9-PP Public Perception

This indicator evaluates **public sentiment** towards the CH site based on surveys, media coverage and stakeholder feedback. It reflects **how the site is perceived in terms of cultural, economic and social impact**.

The normalisation criteria in Table 66 for indicator **4.9-PP Public Perception** classify the results based on the percentage of positive responses, according to Annex A5.9 from D3.1.

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Table 66: Normalisation criteria and targets for Pillar 4 KPI 4.9-PP

ID	KPI Name	Unit	Region	Average value	Target (100%)	Min. (0%)	Source
4.9-PP	Public Perception	Score (P, Q, R)	EU level	-	P (>70%)	R (<40%)	Same references as D3.1.

A score of P – significant effect (target value) indicates that more than 70% of surveyed respondents have positive views about the CH site, demonstrating strong cultural and social appreciation.

3.3 Weighting and prioritisation of KPIs

The weighting and prioritisation of KPIs are fundamental steps in enhancing the flexibility and applicability of the INHERIT assessment and monitoring framework. This process enables the creation of tailored **weighting schemes** that reflect the specific goals, challenges and unique characteristics of CH buildings and sites. By assigning relative importance to the four pillars and the KPIs within them, the framework supports more context-sensitive assessments, aiding stakeholders in making informed decisions aligned with their conservation, sustainability and management objectives.

The prioritisation approach is designed to accommodate diverse needs through pre-defined weighting schemes, which are categorised into two types:

- **Schemes based on** the unique contest and characteristics of **INHERIT pilots**, reflecting site-specific priorities identified through collaborative activities with pilot leaders.
- **Schemes based on defined criteria** that were established during the workshop at the INHERIT Meeting in Valladolid, where key factors influencing the performance of CH buildings were identified and ranked.

These schemes will be integrated into the INHERIT web-based tool (under development in Task 3.3, see section 4), allowing users to input indicator data and select the most appropriate weighting strategy for their specific context (see mock-up idea in Figure 12). This tool ensures that the assessment will remain dynamic and adaptable, supporting both ex-ante and ex-post evaluations across different CH sites.

Figure 12: Mock-up for the INHERIT assessment tool with the pre-defined weighting schemes that the user can choose to apply to their assessment

To ensure methodological rigour, the **Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP)**, developed by Thomas L. Saaty (Saaty 1980 [15], Saaty, 2008 [16]), has been used to assign weights. AHP is a widely recognised multi-criteria decision-making technique that relies on structured pairwise comparison to determine the relative importance of various criteria. This process involves:

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- **Pairwise comparison of pillars:** evaluating the relative importance of the four pillars against each other based on specific decision-making criteria.
- **Pairwise comparison within each pillar:** assessing the significance of each KPI relative to others within the same pillar to refine intra-pillar weighting.

The results of these comparisons are transformed into quantitative weights using AHP formulas, ensuring a transparent and consistent prioritisation process. The following sections detail the prioritisation outcomes at both the INHERIT criteria (section 3.3.1) and the INHERIT pilots (section 3.3.2).

3.3.1 Weighting schemes based on INHERIT criteria

The INHERIT assessment and monitoring framework integrates diverse perspectives to ensure that CH buildings are managed sustainably, with a balance between conservation, performance and community value. To support this, weighting schemes based on INHERIT criteria have been developed, reflecting key priorities identified during the project's collaborative activities, particularly the Valladolid Workshop. These schemes provide a flexible approach for users to emphasise specific objectives when assessing and monitoring CH sites, ensuring that the framework can adapt to various contexts and stakeholder needs.

The criteria underpinning these schemes represent fundamental dimensions of CH management. They were defined through expert discussions, capturing the multifaceted nature of CH conservation and use. Each criterion reflects a critical area where decision-makers often face trade-offs, helping guide the weighting process according to the unique priorities of each assessment.

The five criteria are as follows:

- **Criteria 1. Preservation of cultural and historical value.** This criterion prioritises interventions that maintain and protect the historical and cultural integrity of CH buildings. It emphasises the need to minimise alterations to the original structure and appearance while preventing damage from environmental stressors.
- **Criteria 2. Energy efficiency and operational performance.** Focusing on sustainability, this criterion prioritises improving the building's energy performance, reducing consumption and enhancing operational efficiency without compromising historical features. It also aims to maintain indoor comfort and reduce operational costs.
- **Criteria 3. Resilience to environmental and human-made hazards.** This criterion highlights the importance of protecting CH buildings from climate-related risks (e.g., floods, extreme temperatures) and human-made hazards (e.g., vandalism, unsustainable tourism). It supports strategies that enhance the building's adaptive capacity and risk management.
- **Criteria 4. Socioeconomic and community engagement.** Recognising CH sites as vital socio-cultural assets, this criterion prioritises accessibility, inclusiveness and the building's role in fostering community engagement and generating economic benefits, particularly for public or multi-purpose buildings.
- **Criteria 5. Longevity and life cycle cost management.** This criterion focuses on optimising the building's durability and managing costs over its entire life cycle. It aims to reduce long-term maintenance expenses, ensure structural resilience, and promote cost-effective investments that support sustainable conservation.

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These criteria serve as the foundation for the weighting schemes introduced in this section and fully detailed in Annex 3. Each scheme reflects different prioritisation scenarios, enabling users to tailor KPI assessment to align with specific conservation goals, sustainability targets and management strategies. The following Figure 13 illustrates the criteria developed during the workshop, capturing their core principles and intended focus areas.

Figure 13: Criteria set for the weighting schemes that were defined during a participatory workshop

The prioritisation exercise was conducted during the workshop with INHERIT consortium partners. Participants were divided into five groups, each corresponding to one of the defined INHERIT criteria. To ensure a balanced and comprehensive perspective, the groups were formed to be heterogeneous in terms of expertise and skills, bringing together participants with diverse backgrounds related to CH, sustainability and building performance.

Each group was provided with the criteria cards (Figure 13) to serve as a constant reference, ensuring that the prioritisation process remained aligned with the specific objectives of their assigned criterion. The activity involved pairwise comparisons, where participants assessed two elements at a time -either pillars or indicators within a pillar- to determine which was more relevant in the context of their assigned criterion.

For each comparison, participants used a standardised comparison scale (Figure 14), which allowed them to rate the relative importance of one element over another. The scale ranged from equal importance to varying degrees of preference, guiding the decision-making process with clear, consistent criteria. Participants discussed each comparison collaboratively, leveraging their collective expertise to reach a consensus on the appropriate rating (see also example in Figure 15).

Figure 14: Scale for the pairwise comparison of elements and example for pillar comparison

Figure 15: Example of KPI pairwise comparison within Pillar 2

Following the completion of the pairwise comparisons, the data were processed using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) method to calculate the final weights for both the pillars and KPIs within each pillar. The results of the prioritisation exercise for each criterion are presented below, with additional details provided in Annex 3.

Results obtained for criteria 1. Preservation of cultural and historical value.

Table 67: Weight distribution of INHERIT Pillars based on prioritisation results for criteria 1

WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation		
Pillar 1	Energy Performance and Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ)	6.57%
Pillar 2	Resource Efficiency, Circularity and Life Cycle Cost (LCC)	13.77%
Pillar 3	Resilience to Climate and Human-made Hazards	48.31%
Pillar 4	Accessibility, Inclusiveness, Openness and Socioeconomic Sustainability	31.36%

Figure 16: Pie chart of Pillar weights based on prioritisation for criteria 1

The prioritisation of KPIs within each pillar following criteria 1 is detailed in Annex A3.1, where the specific weights assigned to individual indicators are provided to support more granular decision-making.

Results obtained for criteria 2. Energy efficiency and operational performance.

Table 68: Weight distribution of INHERIT Pillars based on prioritisation results for criteria 2

WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation		
Pillar 1	Energy Performance and Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ)	52.34%
Pillar 2	Resource Efficiency, Circularity and Life Cycle Cost (LCC)	33.61%
Pillar 3	Resilience to Climate and Human-made Hazards	8.98%
Pillar 4	Accessibility, Inclusiveness, Openness and Socioeconomic Sustainability	5.07%

Figure 17: Pie chart of Pillar weights based on prioritisation for criteria 2

The detailed prioritisation of KPIs within each pillar based on criteria 2 is presented in Annex A3.2. It provides the specific weights assigned to each indicator, offering insights into relative importance and supporting more targeted, data-driven decision-making for energy efficiency and operational performance assessments.

Results obtained for criteria 3. Resilience to environmental and human-made hazards.

Table 69: Weight distribution of INHERIT Pillars based on prioritisation results for criteria 3

WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation		
Pillar 1	Energy Performance and Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ)	6.79%
Pillar 2	Resource Efficiency, Circularity and Life Cycle Cost (LCC)	23.00%
Pillar 3	Resilience to Climate and Human-made Hazards	63.42%
Pillar 4	Accessibility, Inclusiveness, Openness and Socioeconomic Sustainability	6.79%

Figure 18: Pie chart of Pillar weights based on prioritisation for criteria 3

The KPI prioritisation results within each pillar for criteria 3 are outlined in Annex A3.3. This Annex details the assigned weights for each indicator, highlighting their relevance in enhancing the resilience of CH sites against environmental and human-made hazards, and providing a robust basis for risk-focused decision-making.

Results obtained for criteria 4. Socioeconomic and community engagement.

Table 70: Weight distribution of INHERIT Pillars based on prioritisation results for criteria 4

WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation		
Pillar 1	Energy Performance and Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ)	21.67%
Pillar 2	Resource Efficiency, Circularity and Life Cycle Cost (LCC)	12.50%
Pillar 3	Resilience to Climate and Human-made Hazards	5.83%
Pillar 4	Accessibility, Inclusiveness, Openness and Socioeconomic Sustainability	60.00%

Figure 19: Pie chart of Pillar weights based on prioritisation for criteria 4

The prioritisation of KPIs within each pillar under criteria 4 is available in Annex A3.4. Here, the indicator weights reflect the emphasis on social inclusiveness, community value, and socioeconomic impact, supporting informed decisions that enhance the cultural and social role of heritage buildings.

Results obtained for criteria 5. Longevity and life cycle cost management.

Table 71: Weight distribution of INHERIT Pillars based on prioritisation results for criteria 5

WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation		
Pillar 1	Energy Performance and Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ)	23.96%
Pillar 2	Resource Efficiency, Circularity and Life Cycle Cost (LCC)	60.77%
Pillar 3	Resilience to Climate and Human-made Hazards	9.35%
Pillar 4	Accessibility, Inclusiveness, Openness and Socioeconomic Sustainability	5.92%

Figure 20: Pie chart of Pillar weights based on prioritisation for criteria 5

The specific weights within each pillar following the prioritisation for criteria 5 are presented in Annex A3.5. This section provides insights into how different indicators contribute to optimising building durability and cost efficiency over the life cycle, facilitating strategic planning for sustainable long-term management.

3.3.2 Weighting schemes based on INHERIT pilots

In addition to the weighting schemes based on thematic criteria, the INHERIT assessment and monitoring framework integrates pilot-specific weighting schemes to reflect the unique characteristics, priorities and contextual needs of the INHERIT pilot sites. These schemes are essential for ensuring that the framework is adaptable to diverse CH environments, allowing assessments to be tailored to specific site conditions, conservation goals and operational challenges. The development of these weighting schemes relied on input from pilot site leaders and key stakeholders, collected through a structured Excel-based questionnaire. This tool, designed with clear instructions, guided participants through exercises for both pillar-level and KPI-level prioritisation, ensuring clarity and consistency across all pilot sites. An introduction to the assessment and monitoring framework was provided to set the context (Figure 21).

CONTEXT AND INTRODUCTION TO THE ACTIVITY

Task 3.2 INHERIT Assessment and Monitoring Framework has developed a framework structured in **four pillars** in which **KPIs have been defined and detailed** for assessing and monitoring CH buildings.

The list of indicators (and overview with some details) in each pillar can be checked: [Indicators list \(PILLARS\)!](#)

Every KPI has been detailed (including ID, definition, objective, assessment criteria, references and examples) in the **Annexes of the D3.1 First INHERIT Assessment & Monitoring Framework**. [INHERIT_D3.1_V1.0_CARTIF.pdf](#)

The prioritisation of KPIs allows the creation of tailored weighting schemes that reflect specific goals or unique characteristics of cultural heritage (CH) buildings. These schemes enable end-users to select options aligned with their objectives.

Pre-defined schemes will be of two types:

- based on the **INHERIT pilots** unique context and characteristics
- ✓ based on defined **criteria** (already defined during the Valladolid Meeting Workshop):

Through the INHERIT Assessment and Monitoring framework, that will be accessible via web-based tool (being developed under T3.3), users can input indicator data and choose suitable weighting schemes. Collaboration with the INHERIT pilots is essential to **define these schemes based on the PILOTS** by prioritising pillars and indicators according to pilot-specific characteristics.

Continue to the tab: [INSTRUCTIONS!](#) to read the instructions before start the exercise!

Figure 21: Overview of the context and activity introduction tab from the Excel sheet used for the Pilot prioritisation exercise

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The clear instructions also guided pilot partners across the different exercises and tabs of the Excel sheet (Figure 22).

INSTRUCTIONS

Exercises of the **prioritisation through pair-wise comparison**:

→ Simply go to the pointed tab in this Spreadsheet and decide **which of the two items being compared** (the one on the left or the one on the right) **is more relevant and to what degree**. The scale assigns "0" for equal importance, and then values of "2", "4", "6" and "8" for the greater importance of the element on the right or on the left side.

Scale for the comparison:
Equal importance (0), 2, 4, 6, 8

1 2 3 4 5

Once you have decided, write a "1" in the corresponding cell.

If you have any doubts about the meaning or definition of any pillar or indicator, short explanation can be found in 'Indicators list (PILLARS)' tab, and detailed information can be found in the D3.1:

You can also go to the 'PILOT description' tab to check the description of the pilot, and feel free to provide any **feedback and suggestions about YOUR pilot** to improve the description about the key characteristics.

Exercise 1 Do the **PILLARS** prioritisation exercise: [PILLARS - Weighting!](#)

Exercise 2 Do the prioritisation exercise of the **KPIs in Pillar 1**: [Pillar 1 - Weighting!](#)

Exercise 3 Do the prioritisation exercise of the **KPIs in Pillar 2**: [Pillar 2 - Weighting!](#)

Exercise 4 Do the prioritisation exercise of the **KPIs in Pillar 3**: [Pillar 3 - Weighting!](#)

Exercise 5 Do the prioritisation exercise of the **KPIs in Pillar 4**: [Pillar 4 - Weighting!](#)

Figure 22: Overview of the instructions tab from the Excel sheet used for Pilot prioritisation exercise

An indicators list is provided in a dedicated tab, allowing participants to easily consult the definitions and details of the KPIs being compared (Figure 23).

ASSESSMENT AND MONITORING FRAMEWORK (T3.2, Deliverable 3.1)
[INHERIT_D3.1_V1.0_CARTIF.pdf](#)

PILLAR 1 - Energy Performance and Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ)

The pillar 1 focuses on improving the energy efficiency and indoor conditions in cultural heritage (CH) buildings, while respecting their conservation needs. This pillar addresses key aspects like thermal comfort, air quality, lighting and acoustics, ensuring that buildings are both energy-efficient and conducive to occupant health and well-being. The framework emphasises the importance of balancing energy performance with occupant comfort, applying relevant IEQ standards. It also incorporates smart technologies, assessed through the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI), to optimise energy use, enhance comfort and support sustainability goals. The objective is to achieve healthier, more efficient spaces that contribute positively to occupant satisfaction and environmental performance.

ID	Name	Definition
1.1-EP	Total energy intensity	It evaluates the overall energy efficiency of the building, as it quantifies its overall energy consumption against its floor area. It provides a standardised measure that enables comparison both across different buildings and over time for the same buildings. It includes: heating energy intensity, cooling energy intensity, lighting energy intensity and appliances energy intensity.
1.2-EP	Energy autonomy	This measure is effectively the proportion of energy consumed by a building over the energy produced from RES, thus assessing its overall autonomy and sustainability. It quantifies the share of energy derived from RES, relative to the total energy consumed by the building. Expressed as a percentage, it provides a measure of the building's reliance on clean energy.
1.3-EP	Energy performance and operation	It is a SRI-based KPI that assesses a building's energy consumption and operational performance, focusing on reducing excessive energy use and associated emissions. By leveraging smart services and technologies, it ensures optimal energy use through dynamic adaptation to prevailing conditions. Additionally, it enhances the maintenance and operational efficiency of technical systems, minimising energy losses and preventing breakdowns.
1.4-EP	Response to the needs of occupants	It is a SRI-based KPI that evaluates a building's ability to use smart, user-friendly technologies to autonomously predict, adapt to, and meet occupants' comfort and convenience needs. By coordinating building functions, it enhances occupant satisfaction and well-being, fostering an environment that prioritises user comfort.
1.5-EP	Energy flexibility assessment	It is a SRI-based KPI that evaluates a building's capacity to adapt its energy consumption and production in response to changing conditions, enhancing resilience and efficiency. By measuring this flexibility, it aims to optimise energy use, ensure reliable supply during peak demand or renewable variability, and improve overall building resilience.
1.1-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of air	It evaluates the indoor air temperature to ensure it is typically maintained at levels conducive to general population's comfort and satisfaction. It aims to ensure that indoor environments maintain

Figure 23: Overview (partial as an example) of the Indicators' list tab from the Excel sheet used for Pilot prioritisation exercise

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The Excel sheet also included a “Pilot Description” tab summarising key information about their site, including historical background, architectural features, current usage and specific sustainability challenges (Figure 24, Figure 25, Figure 26), from the information already collected for D5.1. This will also be how the pilots will be presented in the assessment tool for other end-users to identify themselves with pilot characteristics and context. Participants could review and update this information to ensure the assessment reflected the most accurate and relevant data.

1 City Administration Headquarters in Jastrebarsko, CROATIA

Located in the protected historical core of Jastrebarsko, Croatia, this pilot focuses on a late 19th-century classical-style building that serves as the City Administration Headquarters. Key cultural assets include its ornate façade and a historically significant chandelier. The building's infrastructure blends traditional elements, such as brick walls and clay tile roofs, with modern updates such as PVC windows but lacks advanced energy systems. Planned upgrades in INHERIT focus on sustainable modernisation, including thermal insulation, energy-efficient windows, improved HVAC systems, and digital technologies to enhance comfort and air quality, balancing heritage preservation with innovation to inspire revitalisation of historic buildings.

Country	Croatia
Year of construction	1915
Major renovation	Complete reconstruction in 1987
Main façade material	Brick wall
Number of floors	3 floors (ground floor + two floors)
Building area	570 m ²
Current use	City administration offices (public building)
Daily usage	18 employees and ~15 visitors
Key focus	Energy efficiency in public office buildings
Key assets	Profiles and ornaments of the main street façade, and luxurious historical chandelier with incandescent bulbs

2 Noisiel La Chocolaterie in Noisiel, FRANCE

Located in Noisiel near Paris, this pilot is part of the transformation of a former industrial complex into “La Cité du Goût,” a 34,000 m² mixed-use hub dedicated to gastronomy. Several buildings are protected as historic monuments, and the project aims to create an exceptional living environment that fosters social connection and biodiversity. The pilot focuses on converting two office buildings, La Verrière and Colonnades, into around 60 housing units. Existing systems include gas boilers, electric heaters, and hot water tanks. Planned interventions involve double-glazing while preserving wooden frames, new roof windows, replacement of air conditioning with a renewable-ready district heating system, thermodynamic tanks, and flood-resilient interior partitions. The renovation will prioritise thermal comfort, natural light, and sustainability, respecting the site's architectural heritage.

Country	France
Year of construction	Late 19th to early 20th century
Major renovation	Ongoing transformation into housing and cultural hub
Main façade material	Brick and industrial masonry
Number of floors	2-3 floors
Building area	~3,600 m ²
Current use	Former office buildings, now pending transformation
Daily usage	No currently in active use, planned for ~60 housing units
Key focus	Sustainable housing transformation and heritage preservation
Key assets	Historic industrial architecture, protected façades and integration into "La Cité du Goût" cultural and gastronomic district.

3 ELLET Building in Tripodon Street in Athens, GREECE

Located under the Acropolis on Tripodon Street, this early 19th-century building reflects Athenian heritage through its traditional architecture and significant cultural artifacts, including remnants of ancient Tripodon Street and an ancient water supply network. The two-story structure features a ground floor used for events and seminars, while the upper floor serves as office space. Retaining its original stone walls, wooden beams, and ceramic tile roofing, the building has undergone updates to improve energy efficiency. Planned renovations in INHERIT will integrate smart technologies to enhance sustainability and functionality while preserving its historical and cultural significance, setting a model for heritage conservation in Athens.

Country	Greece
Year of construction	Early 19th century
Major renovation	Significant upgrades in 1990 (last major renovation)
Main façade material	Stone walls
Number of floors	4 floors (underground + ground floor + two floors)
Building area	503 m ²
Current use	Office for NGO (private building)
Daily usage	12 employees and occasional meetings, events and educational programmes hosting up to 50 participants
Key focus	Heritage conservation with modern energy solutions
Key assets	Ancient wall, murals and antiquities from the street of the Tripods, including a historic water network and jars

Figure 24: Description of pilots (1, 2 and 3) in the PILOT tab of the Excel tool used for the prioritisation exercise

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4 Ave Sol Concert Hall in Riga, LATVIA

Located in the historic centre of Riga, this 18th-century building, originally St. Peter and Pavel Church, showcases classicism architecture and has been a cultural hub since its transformation into the Ave Sol Concert Hall in 1977. The three-story structure retains its original masonry, wooden elements, and historical doors, though updates have been minimal. Planned renovations in INHERIT aim to balance heritage preservation with modernisation, including improvements to accessibility, stage facilities, and technical systems. Energy efficiency measures, such as roof insulation and heating systems upgrades, will also be implemented. This initiative aspires to enhance the building's functionality while safeguarding its architectural and cultural significance.

Country	Latvia
Year of construction	1780
Major renovation	Reconstructed in 1980
Main façade material	Strip-shaped block and clay bricks
Number of floors	4 floors (basement + three floors)
Building area	763 m ²
Current use	Concert hall (public building)
Daily usage	5 employees + 40 musicians + up to 250 concert visitors
Key focus	Sustainable energy in cultural buildings
Key assets	Façade, windows and structural elements, internal and external doors, stairs, interior decoration and wall/ceiling paintings

5 Social residential building in Gdynia, POLAND

This social residential building in Gdynia, constructed in 1928, is a prominent example of Gdynia Modernism and is protected under the Municipal Register of Monuments. Managed by the city of Gdynia and supervised by the Municipal Cultural Heritage Conservator, the building features key heritage elements such as its façade divisions, original staircase windows, and detailed balcony railings. The renovation within INHERIT aims to enhance energy efficiency while preserving these historic features, using advanced technologies like H-BIM, Digital Twin, and AR/VR to evaluate renovation scenarios. The project will also explore the integration of renewable energy sources, providing a model for sustainable, heritage-sensitive building upgrades.

Country	Poland
Year of construction	1928
Major renovation	Minor renovations in 2011 and 2019, including central heating replacement and roof/chimney hatch
Main façade material	Brick walls
Number of floors	5 floors (basement + ground floor + three floors)
Building area	1168 m ²
Current use	Residential social building (public building)
Daily usage	32 residents (3-4 per apartment, 10 apartments)
Key focus	Retrofitting and energy efficiency in social housing
Key assets	Front façade divisions, window frames in the staircase, balcony railings detail

6 Monastery 'Ntra. Sra. Del Prado' in Valladolid, SPAIN

The Monastery of 'Nuestra Señora del Prado' in Valladolid was built in 1440 and declared a national historical and artistic monument in 1877. It combines Classicist and Baroque styles and has served various purposes over the centuries, including as a royal printing office and psychiatric hospital, and is now the headquarters of the Castilla y León Regional Government. Notable heritage features include the Praves Cloister and Imperial Staircase. The renovation through INHERIT will enhance energy efficiency using H-BIM, Digital Twin and AR/VR technologies, while preserving its cultural and historical value. This pilot will serve as a model for sustainable conservation in heritage buildings.

Country	Spain
Year of construction	1440
Major renovation	Minor renovation in 2020, including boiler replacement
Main façade material	Load-bearing wall of limestone masonry, and brickwork
Number of floors	7 floors (basement + ground floor + mezzanine + 4 floors)
Building area	55,258 m ²
Current use	Regional government offices (public building)
Daily usage	600 employees + ~25 visitors
Key focus	Sustainable energy solutions for historic religious building
Key assets	Praves cloister, Martínez cloister, Bulas cloister, Fray Pío room, imperial staircase, church, north doorway, church paintings, church polychrome capitals

Figure 25: Description of pilots (4, 5 and 6) in the PILOT tab of the Excel tool used for the prioritisation exercise

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7 City of Visby, UNESCO World Heritage Site, in Gotland, SWEDEN

The City of Visby, a UNESCO World Heritage Site on the island of Gotland, is a remarkable example of a medieval northern European walled trading town. Its historic district, dating back to the 12th-13th centuries, features a unique well-preserved townscape with high-quality buildings that offer a vivid representation of medieval urban life. The pilot focuses on the "Kulturrum" office building, a cultural hub for creative industries. With recent upgrades to its energy efficiency, the INHERIT project aims to test innovative solutions while preserving cultural heritage. The insights gained will guide future conservation efforts, promoting sustainable energy practices across Visby's historic structures.	
Country	Sweden
Year of construction	13th - 21th century, Kulturrum: 13th - 17th century
Major renovation	Replacement of windows in 1979
Main façade material	Kulturrum: Lime stone walls
Number of floors	Visby: approx. 200 buildings, Kulturrum: 3 floors
Building area	Kulturrum: 978 m ²
Current use	Kulturrum: office (for cultural and creative sector businesses) and public space (public-private building)
Daily usage	~20 users from cultural association
Key focus	Renewable energy systems in UNESCO-listed historic town
Key assets	Highest level of protection of the building, medieval walls, immovable interior and exterior

8 Ahmet Piriştina İzmir City Archive and Museum (APIKAM) in İzmir, TURKEY

The APIKAM is a historically significant building, originally constructed as İzmir fire station in 1930, following the Great Fire of İzmir in 1922. It now serves as a city archive and museum, offering a variety of spaces including exhibition areas, offices, a research library, and a meeting room. Notably, it retains its architectural features from the Early Republican period, such as the fire observation tower and original wooden doors and windows. The pilot in INHERIT aims to enhance its energy performance by incorporating smart technologies and renewable energy while preserving its cultural heritage. By improving accessibility and promoting cultural exchange, APIKAM will continue to serve as a vibrant community hub in İzmir.	
Country	Turkey
Year of construction	1932
Major renovation	Major renovations in 2001, including removal of added utility rooms, walls and doors, restoration of original façades and features, and creation of new office spaces
Main façade material	Masonry system
Number of floors	3 floors (ground floor + 2 floors)
Building area	2,921 m ²
Current use	City Archive, Museum, Book café (public building)
Daily usage	70 personnel + 7 security + ~55 visitors exhibition + 7 other workers
Key focus	Heritage preservation with energy efficiency for cultural buildings
Key assets	Building's original characteristics, tower, stairs and stair railings, original cement tiles, original wooden doors and windows, original iron entrance door

Figure 26: Description of pilots (7 and 8) in the PILOT tab of the Excel tool used for the prioritisation exercise

Then, the core activity consisted of pairwise comparison exercises, conducted separately for:

- Pillar prioritisation:** participants compared the four pillars in pairs, deciding which was more relevant for their pilot and to what extent, using a standardised comparison scale from 0 (equal importance) to 8 (strong preference) (Figure 27, Figure 28).
- KPI prioritisation within each pillar:** similar pairwise comparisons were conducted for KPIs within each pillar (example in Figure 29 and Figure 30), allowing participants to assess the relative importance of indicators based on their pilot's unique context.

The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is an extensively used technique for multi-attribute decision-making. It is applied here to obtain weights for each KPI within the four Pillars of the Assessment and Monitoring framework. The exercise consists on a pair-wise comparison among the different KPIs: compare the KPIs, one to another, within the pillar, using the individual view on what of them is more important and in which degree (equal importance (0) or 2 - 4 - 6 - 8), or according to an agree topic or concept.

Activity		8	6	4	2	0	2	4	6	8	
Pillar 1	Energy & Comfort									Pillar 2	Resource & Circularity
Pillar 1	Energy & Comfort									Pillar 3	Climate Resilience
Pillar 1	Energy & Comfort									Pillar 4	Accessibility & Sustainability
Pillar 2	Resource & Circularity									Pillar 3	Climate Resilience
Pillar 2	Resource & Circularity									Pillar 4	Accessibility & Sustainability
Pillar 3	Climate Resilience									Pillar 4	Accessibility & Sustainability

WEIGHTS Pillars prioritisation					Pairwise comparison Matrix 0				
Pillar 1	Energy Performance and Indoor Environmental Qual	#DIV/0!			Pillar 1	Pillar 2	Pillar 3	Pillar 4	
Pillar 2	Resource Efficiency, Circularity and Life Cycle Cost (#DIV/0!			1	FALSO	FALSO	FALSO	
Pillar 3	Resilience to Climate and Human-made Hazards	#DIV/0!			#DIV/0!	1	FALSO	FALSO	
Pillar 4	Accessibility, Inclusiveness, Openness and Socioecon	#DIV/0!			#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	1	FALSO	
		#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	1	
Added value #DIV/0! #DIV/0! #DIV/0! 1					Normalised Matrix 0				
Pillar 1	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	Pillar 1	Pillar 2	Pillar 3	Pillar 4	
Pillar 2	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0
Pillar 3	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	0
Pillar 4	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	#DIV/0!	1
Added value #DIV/0! #DIV/0! #DIV/0! 1					Added value #DIV/0! #DIV/0! #DIV/0! 1				
λ max #DIV/0! CI #DIV/0!					λ max #DIV/0! CI #DIV/0!				
n 4 RI (4x4) 0.90 CR #DIV/0!					n 4 RI (4x4) 0.90 CR #DIV/0!				

Figure 27: Template for the PILLARS weighting tab from the Excel sheet used for Pilot prioritisation exercise

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The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is an extensively used technique for multi-attribute decision-making. It is applied here to obtain weights for each KPI within the four Pillars of the Assessment and Monitoring framework. The exercise consists on a pair-wise comparison among the different KPIs: compare the KPIs, one to another, within the pillar, using the individual view on what of them is more important and in which degree (equal importance (0) or 2-4-6-8), or according to an agree topic or concept.

Activity												
MATRIX 0: PILLARS prioritisation												
* Please, put only a 1 in each row												
Pillar 1 Energy & Comfort			8	6	4	2	0	2	4	6	8	Pillar 2 Resource & Circularity
Pillar 1 Energy & Comfort				1								Pillar 3 Climate Resilience
Pillar 1 Energy & Comfort					1							Pillar 4 Accessibility & Sustainability
Pillar 2 Resource & Circularity						1						Pillar 3 Climate Resilience
Pillar 2 Resource & Circularity							1					Pillar 4 Accessibility & Sustainability
Pillar 3 Climate Resilience								1				Pillar 4 Accessibility & Sustainability

Figure 28: Example of a completed PILLARS weighting tab from the Excel sheet used for Pilot prioritisation

The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is an extensively used technique for multi-attribute decision-making. It is applied here to obtain weights for each KPI within the four Pillars of the Assessment and Monitoring framework. The exercise consists on a pair-wise comparison among the different KPIs: compare the KPIs, one to another, within the pillar, using the individual view on what of them is more important and in which degree (equal importance (0) or 2-4-6-8), or according to an agree topic or concept.

Activity												
MATRIX 1: PILLAR 1 - Energy Performance and Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ)												
* Please, put only a 1 in each row												
1.1-EP Total energy intensity			8	6	4	2	0	2	4	6	8	1.2-EP Energy autonomy
1.1-EP Total energy intensity												1.3-EP Energy performance and operation
1.1-EP Total energy intensity												1.4-EP Response to the needs of occupants
1.1-EP Total energy intensity												1.5-EP Energy flexibility assessment
1.1-EP Total energy intensity												1.1-IEQ Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature
1.1-EP Total energy intensity												1.2-IEQ Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity
1.1-EP Total energy intensity												1.3-IEQ Air quality
1.1-EP Total energy intensity												1.4-IEQ Visual comfort
1.1-EP Total energy intensity												1.5-IEQ Acoustic comfort
1.2-EP Energy autonomy												1.3-EP Energy performance and operation
1.2-EP Energy autonomy												1.4-EP Response to the needs of occupants
1.2-EP Energy autonomy												1.5-EP Energy flexibility assessment
1.2-EP Energy autonomy												1.1-IEQ Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature
1.2-EP Energy autonomy												1.2-IEQ Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity

Figure 29: Template for the Pillar 1 weighting tab from the Excel sheet used for the Pilot prioritisation

The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is an extensively used technique for multi-attribute decision-making. It is applied here to obtain weights for each KPI within the four Pillars of the Assessment and Monitoring framework. The exercise consists on a pair-wise comparison among the different KPIs: compare the KPIs, one to another, within the pillar, using the individual view on what of them is more important and in which degree (equal importance (0) or 2-4-6-8), or according to an agree topic or concept.

Activity												
MATRIX 3: PILLAR 3 - Resilience to Climate and Human-made Hazards												
* Please, put only a 1 in each row												
3.1-IoH Inventory of relevant Hazards			8	6	4	2	0	2	4	6	8	3.2-HI Hazards Identification
3.1-IoH Inventory of relevant Hazards												3.3-RMP Risk Management Plan(s)
3.1-IoH Inventory of relevant Hazards												3.4-RI_VxI Risk Impact assessment: Vulnerability and Exposure
3.1-IoH Inventory of relevant Hazards												3.5-RI_SxI Risk Impact Level evaluation: Severity of consequences and Likelihood of occurrence
3.2-HI Hazards Identification												3.3-RMP Risk Management Plan(s)
3.2-HI Hazards Identification												3.4-RI_VxI Risk Impact assessment: Vulnerability and Exposure
3.2-HI Hazards Identification												3.5-RI_SxI Risk Impact Level evaluation: Severity of consequences and Likelihood of occurrence
3.3-RMP Risk Management Plan(s)												3.4-RI_VxI Risk Impact assessment: Vulnerability and Exposure
3.3-RMP Risk Management Plan(s)												3.5-RI_SxI Risk Impact Level evaluation: Severity of consequences and Likelihood of occurrence
3.4-RI_VxI Risk Impact assessment: Vulnerability and Exposure												3.5-RI_SxI Risk Impact Level evaluation: Severity of consequences and Likelihood of occurrence

Figure 30: Example of a completed Pillar 3 weighting tab from the Excel sheet used for Pilot prioritisation

Upon completion of the exercises, the collected priorities were processed using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) methodology, as can be seen on the right side of the previous figures. AHP enabled the systematic transformation of qualitative judgements from the pairwise comparisons into quantitative weights, ensuring consistency and methodological rigour in the prioritisation results.

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These pilot-specific weighting schemes are integrated into the INHERIT web-based tool (within T3.3), allowing users to select a weighting scheme that aligns with the characteristics of their CH site or to customise assessment based on similar profiles.

The results of the prioritisation exercises for each INHERIT pilot are presented below, with detailed KPI weighting schemes provided in Annex 4.

Results obtained for Pilot 1: City Administration Headquarters in Jastrebarsko, CROATIA

Table 72: Weight distribution of INHERIT Pillars based on prioritisation results for Pilot 1

WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation		
Pillar 1	Energy Performance and Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ)	61.23%
Pillar 2	Resource Efficiency, Circularity and Life Cycle Cost (LCC)	23.01%
Pillar 3	Resilience to Climate and Human-made Hazards	11.19%
Pillar 4	Accessibility, Inclusiveness, Openness and Socioeconomic Sustainability	4.58%

Figure 31: Pie chart of Pillar weights based on prioritisation for Pilot 1

The specific weights per pillar following the prioritisation for Pilot 1 are presented in Annex A4.1.

Results obtained for Pilot 2: Noisiel La Chocolaterie, Noisiel, FRANCE

Table 73: Weight distribution of INHERIT Pillars based on prioritisation results for Pilot 2

WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation		
Pillar 1	Energy Performance and Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ)	26.25%
Pillar 2	Resource Efficiency, Circularity and Life Cycle Cost (LCC)	19.79%
Pillar 3	Resilience to Climate and Human-made Hazards	47.17%
Pillar 4	Accessibility, Inclusiveness, Openness and Socioeconomic Sustainability	6.79%

Figure 32: Pie chart of Pillar weights based on prioritisation for Pilot 2

The specific weights per pillar following the prioritisation for Pilot 2 are presented in Annex A4.2.

Results obtained for Pilot 3: ELLET Building in Tripodon Street in Athens, GREECE

Table 74: Weight distribution of INHERIT Pillars based on prioritisation results for Pilot 3

WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation		
Pillar 1	Energy Performance and Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ)	17.60%
Pillar 2	Resource Efficiency, Circularity and Life Cycle Cost (LCC)	7.58%
Pillar 3	Resilience to Climate and Human-made Hazards	47.32%
Pillar 4	Accessibility, Inclusiveness, Openness and Socioeconomic Sustainability	27.51%

Figure 33: Pie chart of Pillar weights based on prioritisation for Pilot 3

The specific weights per pillar following the prioritisation for Pilot 3 are presented in Annex A4.3.

Results obtained for Pilot 4: Ave Sol Concert Hall in Riga, LATVIA

Table 75: Weight distribution of INHERIT Pillars based on prioritisation results for Pilot 4

WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation		
Pillar 1	Energy Performance and Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ)	51.73%
Pillar 2	Resource Efficiency, Circularity and Life Cycle Cost (LCC)	7.49%
Pillar 3	Resilience to Climate and Human-made Hazards	16.84%
Pillar 4	Accessibility, Inclusiveness, Openness and Socioeconomic Sustainability	23.94%

Figure 34: Pie chart of Pillar weights based on prioritisation for Pilot 4

The specific weights per pillar following the prioritisation for Pilot 4 are presented in Annex A4.4.

Results obtained for Pilot 5: Social residential building in Gdynia, POLAND

Table 76: Weight distribution of INHERIT Pillars based on prioritisation results for Pilot 5

WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation		
Pillar 1	Energy Performance and Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ)	37.63%
Pillar 2	Resource Efficiency, Circularity and Life Cycle Cost (LCC)	11.49%
Pillar 3	Resilience to Climate and Human-made Hazards	18.81%
Pillar 4	Accessibility, Inclusiveness, Openness and Socioeconomic Sustainability	32.07%

Figure 35: Pie chart of Pillar weights based on prioritisation for Pilot 5

The specific weights per pillar following the prioritisation for Pilot 5 are presented in Annex A4.5.

Results obtained for Pilot 6: Monastery 'Nuestra Señora del Prado' in Valladolid, SPAIN

Table 77: Weight distribution of INHERIT Pillars based on prioritisation results for Pilot 6

WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation		
Pillar 1	Energy Performance and Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ)	12.22%
Pillar 2	Resource Efficiency, Circularity and Life Cycle Cost (LCC)	5.56%
Pillar 3	Resilience to Climate and Human-made Hazards	28.89%
Pillar 4	Accessibility, Inclusiveness, Openness and Socioeconomic Sustainability	53.34%

Figure 36: Pie chart of Pillar weights based on prioritisation for Pilot 6

The specific weights per pillar following the prioritisation for Pilot 6 are presented in Annex A4.6.

Results obtained for Pilot 7: City of Visby, UNESCO World Heritage Site, in Gotland, SWEDEN

Table 78: Weight distribution of INHERIT Pillars based on prioritisation results for Pilot 7

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
Pillar 1	Energy Performance and Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ)	32.34%
Pillar 2	Resource Efficiency, Circularity and Life Cycle Cost (LCC)	26.83%
Pillar 3	Resilience to Climate and Human-made Hazards	31.00%
Pillar 4	Accessibility, Inclusiveness, Openness and Socioeconomic Sustainability	9.83%

Figure 37: Pie chart of Pillar weights based on prioritisation for Pilot 7

The specific weights per pillar following the prioritisation for Pilot 7 are presented in Annex A4.7.

Results obtained for Pilot 8: Ahmet Prishtina İzmir Archive and Museum (APIKAM) in İzmir, TURKEY

Table 79: Weight distribution of INHERIT Pillars based on prioritisation results for Pilot 8

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
Pillar 1	Energy Performance and Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ)	23.89%
Pillar 2	Resource Efficiency, Circularity and Life Cycle Cost (LCC)	16.94%
Pillar 3	Resilience to Climate and Human-made Hazards	19.72%
Pillar 4	Accessibility, Inclusiveness, Openness and Socioeconomic Sustainability	39.44%

Figure 38: Pie chart of Pillar weights based on prioritisation for Pilot 8

The specific weights per pillar following the prioritisation for Pilot 8 are presented in Annex A4.8.

4 Web-based application for the multi-dimensional assessment

The INHERIT Assessment Tool implements a web-based application for the assessment and monitoring framework introduced in Section 3. The tool leverages on the first release of the application that was delivered as part of the initial version of the assessment framework and includes updates and extensions to make the application more user-friendly and efficient. The tool is accessible under the URL: <https://assesstool-inherit.euinno.eu/>.

4.1 Key features of the INHERIT Assessment Tool

This second release of the web-based application for the multi-dimensional assessment includes the following key high-level features aimed at assessing CH buildings.

- **User Management:** The tool includes user registration, secure authentication, profile management, and password recovery options.
- **Assessment Capabilities:** Users can create building portfolios, input assessment data, view detailed results, and track historical assessments, along with a public registry option for completed assessments.

The high-level features are further detailed in Table 80, which provides an overview of the key updates of the application.

Table 80: Overview of the key features of the second release of the INHERIT assessment tool

Feature category	Key features	Description
User Management	User Registration	Online registration capability for new users
	Secure Authentication	Login system with username & password credentials
	Profile Management	Change password and modify personal data
	Password Recovery	Retrieve forgotten passwords
Assessment & Building Management	Building Portfolio Creation	Assessors can create and manage their building portfolios
	Comprehensive Assessment Input	Input all required data to calculate assessment scores across the four pillars of the INHERIT framework
	Assessment Scoring	View detailed assessment results across all the four different pillars
	Historical Tracking	View previous assessments for buildings and track changes in assessment scores over time
	Public Building Registry	Make buildings publicly visible to all tool users (optional, when assessment is complete)

Feature category	Key features	Description
Programmability	CI/CD environment	Separation of frontend/backend through RESTful API and creation of CI/CD pipeline to facilitate updates and evolution of the application
	RESTful API	Complete API for user authentication, building management, assessment operations, and public building access

4.2 User workflow

User workflows are essential as they define the step-by-step processes users follow to achieve their goals. A clear and simple workflow helps users move through tasks more easily, making the app smooth and easy to use. It also improves user satisfaction and retention by aligning the app's functionality with real-world needs and behaviours. By understanding and optimising user workflows, developers can create a more seamless experience, minimize errors, and ensure that the app delivers value at every stage of use.

Figure 39: INHERIT Assessment Tool user workflow

A more detailed table outlining each step in the workflow, along with descriptions and supporting images, can be found below. Table 81 is designed to provide a deeper understanding of the user journey and highlight key interactions at each stage.

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Table 81: Step-by-step users' workflow

Step	Description	Screenshot
Login	Enables access to a secure dashboard	
Dashboard overview	Display of building metrics and status	
Add building	Create new building entries	
Perform assessment	Complete comprehensive evaluation across 4 pillars	

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Step	Description	Screenshot
Get score & visualization	View assessment results with data visualization	
Historical data	Track building performance over time	
Status tracking	Monitor buildings by status (Not Assessed, Assessment In Progress, Assessment Done)	
Public registry	Optionally share completed assessments with all users	

4.3 Assessment Tool architecture

To assess the multi-dimensional data across all different pillars, the following architecture was proposed as an implementation of the tool. This architecture enables the web application to facilitate assessors to create and manage their CH buildings portfolio.

The web application is based on Remix.js, an open source, full stack framework. Remix.js lets developers focus on the user interface to deliver a great user experience for the assessors. By using this framework, a RESTful API was developed to achieve interoperability and data exchange by complying with the REST design principles. For the Frontend of the web application, a React-based

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user interface was implemented, promoting a clean and user-friendly UI and UX. For the authentication layer, a user credential management system was implemented, to provide a secure and fast log in mechanism.

The database that was chosen for this particular use case is the battle-tested SQLite, an open source, lightweight database with massive adoption and use on various open-source projects like Android. SQLite provides a minimal, yet highly performant database that makes it a perfect fit for the developed web application.

The application code was hosted on GitHub to enable easier integration with other tools and for release versioning. Also, the application was containerized with Docker and the produced image was uploaded to DockerHub registry. Containerization was used to make the web application easier to deploy in the selected environment. The environment that was used to host the web application is the Kubernetes cluster. Kubernetes provides automated rollout and rollbacks for smooth application deployment, service discovery and load balancing to efficiently handle user traffic, self-healing in case an app instance fails, secret and configuration management in a secure manner.

To facilitate a smooth end-to-end deployment, from a code push to a new Kubernetes release, a CI/CD pipeline was implemented based on Jenkins. The pipeline is triggered from a Github WebHook to the Jenkins agent. From there, the agent retrieves the updated code with the new feature, builds the Docker image, pushes it to DockerHub and schedules a rollout release on Kubernetes. With this process, the implemented pipeline minimizes manual operations and automates the deployment of new releases, ultimately giving more features and better insights to the users of the Assessment tool for CH buildings.

The architecture can also be visualized in the following Figure 40.

Figure 40: Technical architecture of the INHERIT Assessment Tool

5 INHERIT Hub of measures

This section continues the work developed in deliverable D3.1. The **INHERIT Hub of Measures** is an inventory of solutions for the prevention, monitoring, management and renovation of CH sites. The catalogue is conceived as a decision support tool, offering a preliminary selection of interventions to be considered in the modernization processes of these sites. In this new version, a classification of measures is presented according to the level of heritage protection under which they can be applied. This effort contributes to the creation of a comparative basis for the standardization of intervention strategies in different national contexts.

In the previous deliverable a methodology was defined, which has been applied again in this phase of the work. This methodology is shown in Figure 41.

Figure 41. Inventory of measures. Methodology for development

Furthermore, as planned, we are currently in the **enrichment stage of the wave**. Once the information is collected, it is refined to retain only the most relevant details and any necessary additional data is added. At this stage, the most effective and meaningful way to present the information is also defined.

Figure 42. Implementation waves of the methodology for the Hub of Measures development

In the previous version, an initial list of measures was established. In this version, this list has been optimized through a process of revision, consolidation and expansion, which has resulted in the **83 measures** presented below. To facilitate the consultation of these measures in relation to each pillar, they have been organized into four sections, corresponding to the following pillars: **Pillar 1** (Energy Performance and IEQ), **Pillar 2** (Resource efficiency, Circularity and LCC), **Pillar 3** (Resilience to climate and human-made hazards), and **Pillar 4** (Accessibility, Inclusiveness, Openness and

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Socioeconomic sustainability). It is important to note that a single measure may be associated with multiple pillars, as it can address different aspects simultaneously.

The tables corresponding to these sections (Table 82 to Table 85) include the following aspects:

- **ID**
 - **Name** of the measure
 - **Group of measures** it belongs to: ● *Insulation system*, ● *Window system*, ● *Shadow system*, ● *Lighting system*, ● *Control system*, ● *HVAC system*, ● *DHW system*, ● *Appliances*, ● *RES integration*, ● *Digitalization system*, ● *Materials*, ● *Water system*, ● *Electrical system*, ● *Structural system*, ● *Accessibility*, ● *Socioeconomic and* ● *Others*.
 - **CH protection level**: ● *Low*, ● *Medium* and ● *High*. Heritage buildings are categorized by their level of protection, with higher levels imposing greater restrictions on permissible interventions. This column indicates the level of protection under which the measure can be applied.
- **Pillar 1: Energy Performance and IEQ**

This group of measures includes solutions under *Pillar 1*. A total of 57 measures are included in this group, characterized by a comprehensive approach to improving the building's energy performance. They cover interventions in the thermal envelope, such as insulation of façades, roofs, and floors, as well as window upgrades, in addition to solar shading solutions, efficient lighting, HVAC systems, control systems, RES, digitalization, and other complementary measures. The main objective is to improve energy efficiency, provide thermal comfort, and reduce heating and cooling costs. Table 82 summarizes this group of measures:

Table 82. Set of measures for Pillar 1

ID	Name	Group of measures	CH protection level
#01	Façade external insulation	Insulation system	Low
#02	Façade internal insulation	Insulation system	Medium
#03	Façade intermediate insulation	Insulation system	Low
#04	Roof external insulation	Insulation system	Low
#05	Roof internal insulation	Insulation system	Medium
#06	Green Roof Installation	Insulation system	Low
#07	Floor insulation	Insulation system	Medium
#08	Natural lighting prioritization	Window system	Low
#09	Window and door restoration	Window system	High
#10	Windows sealing	Window system	High
#11	Windows with a low emissivity coating	Window system	Medium
#12	Aluminium carpentry with thermal break	Window system	Medium
#13	Windows with double glazing (air chamber)	Window system	Medium
#14	Windows with triple glazing (air chamber)	Window system	Medium
#15	Windows with double glazing (argon gas)	Window system	Medium
#16	Windows with triple glazing (argon gas)	Window system	Medium
#17	Windows new all	Window system	Low
#18	Sun protection	Shadow system	Medium

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ID	Name	Group of measures	CH protection level
#19	LED lighting	Lighting system	High
#20	Lighting sensors	Lighting system	High
#21	Occupancy sensors	Lighting system	High
#22	Lighting Controls	Lighting system	High
#23	District Heating System	HVAC system	Medium
#24	Boiler - Natural Gas Condensing	HVAC system	Medium
#25	Boiler - Biomass	HVAC system	Medium
#26	Heat pump - Direct expansion	HVAC system	Medium
#27	Heat pump - Geothermal (ground source)	HVAC system	Medium
#28	Radiant heating system	HVAC system	Medium
#29	Reconstruction of the heating system and thermostat for control of heating according to system scheduling	HVAC system	High
#30	Energy-Efficient HVAC Systems	HVAC system	High
#31	Heat recovery	HVAC system	High
#32	Mechanical ventilation with recuperation	HVAC system	High
#33	Variable airflow fans	HVAC system	High
#34	High-efficiency filters	HVAC system	High
#35	Variable water flow pumps	HVAC system	High
#36	Storage systems	HVAC system	Medium
#37	Increase the design temperature of the chilled water	HVAC system	High
#38	Solar thermal panels	DHW system	Medium
#39	White appliances replacement	Appliances	High
#40	Prevent excessive use of air conditioning since it is threatening the energy supply	Appliances	Medium
#41	Temperature sensors	Control system	High
#42	EQ sensors	Control system	High
#43	Implementation of a system for remote measurement of energy consumption	Control system	High
#44	Implementation of a system for remote measurement of water consumption	Control system	High
#45	PV (+/- storage)	RES integration	Medium
#46	PV panels in the parking lot	RES integration	Medium
#47	EV chargers	RES integration	Medium
#48	Modelling & simulation environment	Digitalization system	High
#49	IEQ and thermal comfort optimisation	Digitalization system	High
#50	Energy forecasting and intelligent management	Digitalization system	High
#51	Digital Twin for Heritage facilities real time monitoring operation & management	Digitalization system	High

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ID	Name	Group of measures	CH protection level
#52	Real-time insights on activity and mobility partners	Digitalization system	High
#53	Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	Digitalization system	High
#54	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	Digitalization system	High
#55	Bike infrastructure (parking)	Others	High
#56	Energy advice and leaflets	Others	High
#80	Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	Digitalization system	High

- **Pillar 2: Resource efficiency, Circularity and LCC**

This group of measures corresponds to *Pillar 2* and includes 20 solutions focused on resource efficiency, circularity, and life cycle costing (LCC). It covers interventions related to control, digitalization, materials, water management, and other sustainability aspects.

Table 83 summarizes this group of measures:

Table 83. Set of measures for Pillar 2

ID	Name	Group of measures	CH protection level
#20	Lighting sensors	Lighting system	High
#21	Occupancy sensors	Lighting system	High
#22	Lighting Controls	Lighting system	High
#29	Reconstruction of the heating system and thermostat for control of heating according to system scheduling	HVAC system	High
#33	Variable airflow fans	HVAC system	High
#43	Implementation of a system for remote measurement of energy consumption	Control system	High
#44	Implementation of a system for remote measurement of water consumption	Control system	High
#47	EV chargers	RES integration	Medium
#48	Modelling & simulation environment	Digitalization system	High
#49	IEQ and thermal comfort optimisation	Digitalization system	High
#51	Digital Twin for Heritage facilities real time monitoring operation & management	Digitalization system	High
#53	Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	Digitalization system	High
#54	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	Digitalization system	High
#57	Reclaimed Materials	Materials	High
#58	Local Materials Sourcing	Materials	High
#59	Efficient use of water	Water system	High
#60	Replacement of the cold water and sewage system.	Water system	Low

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ID	Name	Group of measures	CH protection level
#61	Assessment of building resource efficiency through thermography Infrared (IRT)	Others	High
#62	See Pillar 1	Others	Low
#80	Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	Digitalization system	High

- **Pillar 3: Resilience to climate and human-made hazards**

This group of measures corresponds to *Pillar 3* and includes 15 solutions aimed at enhancing resilience to climate and human-made hazards. It covers interventions in structural systems, electrical systems, RES, and digitalization. Table 84 summarizes this group of measures:

Table 84. Set of measure for Pillar 3

ID	Name	Group of measures	CH protection level
#47	EV chargers	RES integration	Medium
#48	Modelling & simulation environment	Digitalization system	High
#49	IEQ and thermal comfort optimisation	Digitalization system	High
#51	Digital Twin for Heritage facilities real time monitoring operation & management	Digitalization system	High
#54	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	Digitalization system	High
#63	Modernization of the lightning protection system	Electrical system	High
#64	Replacement of the electricity supply and fire suppression system	Electrical system	High
#65	Reinforcement of load-bearing structure	Structural system	High
#66	Moisture protection	Structural system	High
#67	Protection of the metal structure	Structural system	High
#68	Reducing thrust in arches and vaults	Structural system	High
#69	Reducing slab deformation	Structural system	High
#70	Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	Digitalization system	High
#79	Interactive screen use & AR-VR interfaces	Digitalization system	High
#80	Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	Digitalization system	High

- **Pillar 4: Accessibility, Inclusiveness, Openness and Socioeconomic sustainability**

This group of measures corresponds to Pillar 4 and includes solutions focusing on accessibility, inclusion and socio-economic sustainability. The 14 measures address accessibility, digitalisation, lighting and socio-economic impact improvements. Table 85 summarises this group of measures:

Table 85. Set of measure for Pillar 4

ID	Name	Group of measures	CH protection level
#21	Occupancy sensors	Lighting system	High
#51	Digital Twin for Heritage facilities real time monitoring operation & management	Digitalization system	High
#52	Real-time insights on activity and mobility partners	Digitalization system	High
#54	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	Digitalization system	High
#71	Elevator	Accessibility	Medium
#72	Ramp	Accessibility	Medium
#73	Handrail	Accessibility	High
#74	Audible signage in customer service and elevators	Accessibility	High
#75	Podotactile pavement	Accessibility	Low
#76	ISA signal	Accessibility	High
#77	Offering educational programs	Socioeconomic	High
#78	Improving public perception	Socioeconomic	High
#79	Interactive screen use & AR-VR interfaces	Digitalization system	High
#80	Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	Digitalization system	High

5.1 First round of measures

In addition to optimizing the full list of measures, a subset of 40 was selected for detailed completion. This selection was made in collaboration with all partners, identifying the measures most closely aligned with their areas of work and ensuring representation of all four pillars within the subset. The goal was to identify weaknesses in the templates and to evaluate the final outcome of a representative sample. Figure 43 shows the template used to document the measures, highlighting its sections and corresponding fields. The datasheet includes the following headings:

- **ID:** Numeric identifier that lists the measures from #1 to #83.
- **Application:** Encompasses the methods, resources and field to which this measure applies.
- **Photo:** Image linked to the measure, it can be a photograph of a component that is part of the measure, or of some process or activity related to it.
- **Generic information:** Covers the most global aspects of a measure. This section includes details such as implementation conditions, advantages, disadvantages, limitations, social impact, visual impact, physical impact, and with what level of CH protection it is compatible.
- **Technical information:** This section includes relevant technical data for the measure, especially when it involves changes to architectural, structural, or systems aspects. The information is organized into technical characteristics, geometric and material data, as well as data related to installation, maintenance, and operation.
- **Impact:** This comprises a set of indicators that demonstrate the impact of the measure. These indicators are related to the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined in section 3.

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- **Costs:** This section covers the costs related to the measure. It includes information such as the initial investment cost, the savings involved in implementing the measure, and the time it takes to recover the initial investment.
- **Others:** Includes additional information. This section details the phase in which the measure is implemented, the maturity level of the technology, and the scale of implementation of the measure, i.e., the different levels at which it can be applied.
- **References:** Name of the references from which the measurement information was obtained.

Figure 43. Final version of measure datasheet template (with guidance)

The process was structured in the following stages:

- 1. Selection and assignment:** Forty measures were selected and distributed among project partners, who were asked to contribute based on their expertise or by researching the assigned limitations measures.
- 2. Review:** Once completed, each measure was assigned two reviewers to provide feedback and suggestions for improvement.
- 3. Unification and validation:** After the review phase, the measures were refined and standardized to ensure consistency in format and quality.

Figure 44 illustrates the tracking system used during the first two stages to monitor progress and ensure that each step was properly followed.

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ID	Measure Name	Partner	Status	Reviewer 1	Status	Reviewer 2	Status
#51	Digital Twin for Heritage facilities real time monitoring operation & management	CEM	Filled	UPRC	Reviewed	CARTIF	Reviewed
#52	Real-time insights on activity and mobility partners	SLG	Filled	ICCS	Reviewed	FASADA	Reviewed
#53	Preventive maintance with H-BIM	CARTIF	Filled	RPR	Reviewed	SLG	Reviewed
#54	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	ICCS	Filled	FASADA	Reviewed	CEM	Reviewed

Figure 44. Example of the tracking document for the documentation of measures

The selected measures are: ● 01, ● 02, ● 03, ● 08, ● 11, ● 15, ● 18, ● 19, ● 20, ● 21, ● 22, ● 23, ● 26, ● 29, ● 31, ● 32, ● 33, ● 34, ● 36, ● 41, ● 43, ● 44, ● 45, ● 47, ● 48, ● 49, ● 50, ● 51, ● 52, ● 53, ● 54, ● 65, ● 66, ● 70, ● 71, ● 73, ● 76, ● 79 and ● 82.

These measures have been classified according to the INHERIT pillars to which they are applicable. It should be noted that a single measure can be linked to multiple pillars. Out of the 40 selected measures, 28 address the pillars of energy efficiency and IEQ, 14 relate to resources and circularity, 10 to resilience, and 7 to accessibility and sustainability.

Energy & IEQ	Resources & Circularity	Resilience	Accessibility & Sustainability
• 32 measures	• 18 measures	• 10 measures	• 9 measures

Four measures are presented below as illustrative examples (Figure 45 – Figure 52). They were selected from the full catalogue for their relevance to different pillars of the Inherit project and because they address a diverse set of challenges—ranging from energy efficiency and resource management to structural resilience and social inclusion. These examples showcase the variety and applicability of the measures developed in the project. The complete set of measures is included in Annex 5 Detailed datasheets of INHERIT Hub of measures.

- **Measure #02. Façade internal insulation.** A widely applicable energy efficiency solution, especially important for heritage buildings where external interventions are often restricted. It also provides significant benefits in terms of energy performance.
- **Measure #44. Systems for remote measurement of water consumption.** Contribute to resource efficiency and sustainability through improved monitoring and management of water use.
- **Measure #65. Reinforcement of load – bearing structure.** Essential for enhancing the structural resilience of historic buildings, particularly against seismic activity and other physical risks.
- **Measure #71. Elevator.** Although considered an invasive measure, elevators can be integrated into heritage buildings in respectful ways. They not only improve accessibility but also add social value and symbolize the connection between heritage and contemporary society.

Inherit

FAÇADE INTERNAL INSULATION

ID #02

Interior Thermal Insulation system to improve the energy efficiency of buildings by thermally insulating them from the inside.

APPLICATION

This measure involves adding a layer of thermal insulation (XPS, EPS, PIR, mineral wool or polyurethane, cellulose, fiberboard) to the inner side of the wall. This layer is fixed using a fastening system and covered with plasterboard or wooden panels and coating. This intervention reduces the wall's thermal conductivity, improves the building's energy efficiency, and enhances indoor thermal comfort.

MEASURE GROUP
Insulation system.

INHERIT PILLAR
Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

Heading of Technical Inspections
Façades and roofs.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS
Walls must be dry and free from mold or dirt to prevent moisture -related problems. Ensure good ventilation, ideally mechanical, to manage indoor moisture levels. Install a vapor barrier on the room side to stop moisture from entering the insulation layer. The insulation must meet local building regulations for thermal and moisture protection.

ADVANTAGES

- Preserves the building's external appearance.
- Quick installation.
- Low initial costs.
- Improved indoor comfort.
- Improved energy efficiency.

PHOTO^[1]

- No impact on neighbours.
- It can be installed regardless of external weather conditions.

DISADVANTAGES

- Risk of condensation.
- Reduced room size.
- Thermal bridges.
- Limited thermal mass benefits.

LIMITATIONS
Nos suitable for:

- Buildings with high indoor humidity.
- Heritage buildings with restrictions on making internal modifications.
- Poorly ventilated spaces.
- Limited space.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE
Medium.

VISUAL IMPACT
Medium.

PHYSICAL IMPACT
Medium.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL
Medium.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES
Example of the technical specifications of a wall with mineral wool thermal insulation.^[2]

Figure 45. Measure #02. Page 1

Figure 46. Measure #02. Page 2

Inherit

SYSTEMS FOR REMOTE MEASUREMENT OF WATER CONSUMPTION

Installation of systems for remote water consumption measurement which consists of four main components: a water meter, impulse emitter, impulse splitter, and communication equipment.

APPLICATION

This is a measure feasible regardless the level of protection of the building and with low technical requirements. It enables accurate monitoring and control of water consumption, contributing to resource saving and more efficient water management.

MEASURE GROUP

Control system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 2: Resources and Circularity.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Installations.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

To install, commission, and test the remote measurement system, the water meter must be compatible with the installation of additional equipment for integration of communication equipment. Otherwise, a new meter should be installed.

ADVANTAGES

- Indirect (behavioural) reduction of water consumption.
- Increase water consumption awareness.
- Gain insights into the operation of the building.

DISADVANTAGES

- Cost of initial investment.
- Stable communication must be ensured.

ID #44

PHOTO

LIMITATIONS

- Type of existing water meter.
- It may not be compatible with the system

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

VISUAL IMPACT

Low.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

Low.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

High.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

- Communication protocol: NB-IOT
- Communication with devices: impulse
- Power battery (Li 3,6V)
- Type of SIM card: MFF2
- Working temperature range: -25 / +55
- IP65 protection
- Measurement interval: ≥ 1 min

Figure 47. Measure #44. Page 1

Figure 48. Measure #44. Page 2

Inherit

REINFORCEMENT OF LOAD – BEARING STRUCTURE

This measure involves reinforcing the load-bearing structure of a building by repairing cracks or weaknesses that could compromise the building's structural stability, ensuring safety and longevity.

APPLICATION

The cracks will be repaired using materials identical to those originally used in construction and techniques like fiber-reinforced polymers or steel supports.

MEASURE GROUP
Structural system.

INHERIT PILLAR
Pillar 3: Climate Resilience.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS
Foundations and Structure

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

- Bureaucratic requirements.

ADVANTAGES

- Preserves the building.
- Enhances safety and security.
- Increases the value of the building.
- Extends the building's functional lifespan.

DISADVANTAGES

- Potential loss of historical authenticity.
- High implementation cost.

LIMITATIONS
Technical complexity of the repair process.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE
Medium.

VISUAL IMPACT
High.

ID #65

PHOTO

PHYSICAL IMPACT
High.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL
High.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES
A materials study of the structural element must be conducted before reinforcement to ensure compatibility.

GEOMETRY DATA
Accurate documentation of the building's geometry is essential, using tools like laser scanning or photogrammetry to guide reinforcement design.

INSTALLATION DATA
Reinforcement involves assessing structural integrity, selecting compatible materials and applying appropriate techniques like fiber-reinforced polymers or steel supports. Installations should be made in the right environment or weather conditions (ideally when it is not raining, and temperatures are neither too high nor too low).

Figure 49. Measure #65. Page 1

Inherit

MAINTENANCE DATA

Type of maintenance | Visual inspection

OPERATION DATA

No operation is required after implementation.

IMPACT

PILLAR 3 KPIS: Climate Resilience

Hazards Identification	KPI (-)
Risk Management Plan(s)	
Risk Impact assessment: Vulnerability and Exposure	
Risk impact Level evaluation: Severity of consequences and Likelihood of occurrence	

COSTS

INVESTMENT

Costs depend on building size, required reinforcement and materials, typically involving significant investment due to specialized work.

SAVINGS

Prevents future structural deterioration and costly repairs while preserving the building's value and functionality over time.

ROI

Though initial costs are high, benefits include extended building lifespan, enhanced safety and cultural heritage preservation.

OTHERS

PHASE

Design and Renovation
Preservation and maintenance

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

Medium – High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Only on items require intervention.

Figure 50. Measure #65. Page 2

Inherit
ELEVATOR

ID #71

Installing an elevator as an alternative to stairs aims to ensure accessible vertical circulation for people with reduced mobility. This intervention can be addressed either by installing a single-person lift attached to an existing wall, or through a larger-scale construction that allows the installation of a higher-capacity elevator suitable for multiple passengers.

APPLICATION

Conservators often prefer the external placement of the elevator to avoid damaging the interior. However, even an external solution must be carefully designed to blend with the façade's style.

MEASURE GROUP

Accessibility.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 4: Accessibility & Inclusiveness.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Accessibility.

GENERIC INFORMATION**IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS**

It is necessary to request approval from the conservation authorities. They will assess how the elevator could impact the building's preservation.

ADVANTAGES

- Improved accessibility.
- Reduces the risk of falls (on stairs).
- Increased property value.

DISADVANTAGES

- High cost.
- Impact on the preservation of original elements.
- Additional bureaucracy.
- Structural challenges.
- Visual impact.

PHOTO^[1]

**Photographs of the construction of an elevator at the Cathedral of Santa Maria, in Vitoria-Gasteiz (Spain), integrated within a tower. This cylindrical tower, built with sandstone masonry, was designed to blend visually with the monument.*

LIMITATIONS

- Design and placement restrictions.
- Space limitations.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

VISUAL IMPACT

High.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

Medium (to high).

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

High.

Figure 51. Measure #71. Page 1

Inherit

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

Power [kW]	4 - 15
------------	--------

GEOMETRY DATA ^[2]

Standard cabin dimensions (wheelchair accessible):

Height [mm]	2100 – 2300
Width [mm]	1100 – 1400
Depth [mm]	1400 – 1600

INSTALLATION DATA

Installation time [h]	500 - 1000
-----------------------	------------

MAINTENANCE DATA

Routine inspections, lubrication and cleaning, control system calibration, emergency, and safety tests.

Lifespan [Years]	20 - 30
------------------	---------

OPERATION DATA

Operational needs: energy efficiency and power supply, access control and security, temperature and humidity control, vibration and noise reduction, user accessibility and interface, routine maintenance scheduling.

IMPACT

PILLAR 4 KPIS: Accessibility & Inclusiveness

Accessibility level	KPIs (%)
Inclusiveness and openness level	KPIs (-)
Public perception	KPIs (%)

COSTS

INVESTMENTS

Investing in an elevator for a CH building is a significant financial commitment that requires careful planning, heritage-compatible design, and collaboration with conservation experts. The total cost can range from € 100.000 to over € 1 million, depending on the complexity of the project

and the building's structural and heritage needs.

SAVINGS - ROI

There is no direct energy savings or payback period associated with this measure, as it does not lead to a reduction in consumption. However, it does contribute to the increased value of the property, allowing for an indirect return on investment.

OTHERS

PHASE

Design and Renovation.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

The scale of implementation is influenced significantly by the type of building, with residential buildings typically requiring smaller solutions and commercial or institutional buildings needing larger, more complex systems.

Figure 52. Measure #71. Page 2

5.2 Alignment of protection level across European countries

CH buildings are a concrete expression of a country's historical, social, and artistic legacy. Preserving them is not only a cultural obligation but also a legal and patrimonial responsibility. Although many countries have specific laws aimed at protecting heritage buildings, these regulations are typically shaped by national legal frameworks and local contexts. As a result, comparing protection levels and permissible interventions across countries is often difficult.

In response to this challenge, a common standard was proposed to unify and systematize information about the regulatory frameworks governing the conservation of built heritage. The main objective of this standard is to establish comparable protection levels across countries, facilitating cross-country analysis of conservation policies, the identification of best practices, and the design of coherent intervention strategies at the regional or international scale. These protection levels will also serve as a basis to classify intervention measures according to the protection status of CH sites, making it easier to determine whether a specific measure can be applied to a site with a given level of protection.

To implement this approach and allow for a consistent comparison between national regulatory frameworks, a structured methodology has been developed and applied throughout this exercise.

The process began by identifying the core issue and exploring different approaches to address it. Based on this analysis, the decision was made to conduct a mapping of existing legal frameworks in the project's pilot countries: Croatia, Greece, Latvia, Poland, Spain, Sweden, and Turkey.

Three protection levels were defined to enable comparison across countries:

- **Level P0. No special protection:** Buildings under this level are not covered by any heritage-specific regulations and are subject only to the general building codes of each country.
- **Level P1. Intermediate protection:** These buildings are partially protected under local or regional regulations, which impose certain restrictions aimed at preserving their character, though not to the highest degree.
- **Level P2. Maximum protection:** These buildings fall under strict national legislation that heavily regulates their use, limits interventions, and ensures preservation in accordance with heritage laws.

Once these levels were established, **two working groups** were formed: one tasked with completing the data and another with reviewing and validating the information submitted.

Project partners were then asked to review their local and national regulations and align them with the protection levels defined above. To that end, they were requested to complete a document including the following information:

1. For each protection level, the **specific terminology used in national regulations** to classify buildings falling within that level.
2. The **applicable legislation** in each country that corresponds to or can be associated with each protection level.
3. A general overview of how the identified regulations affect key structural elements of the building, for each protection level.
4. For each country, the maximum protection level at which various types of intervention measures are permitted.

5.2.1 Terminology

This section presents the **specific terminology** used in the national regulations of the participating countries to classify buildings according to their level of heritage protection. The classification is organized into three levels (PO, PI, and PII), and it allows for the identification of how each country formally refers to protected buildings in its respective legislation.

Table 86. Terminology used to classify buildings according to their level of protection

Protection Level	PO	PI	PII
Croatia	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kulturno - povijesna cjelina (Part of Cultural-Historical ensembles) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kulturno dobro (Individually Protected Cultural Properties)
Greece	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • διατηρητέων κτιρίων (Listed/preserved building) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • μνημείο (Monument)
Latvia	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vietējas nozīmes kultūras pieminekļi (Local Importance Monuments) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Valsts nozīmes kultūras pieminekļi (National Importance Monuments)
Poland	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Obszar objęty ochroną konserwatorską (Areas under conservation protection) • Ochrona konserwatorska w miejscowym planie (Protection through a Local Spatial Development Plan) • Wpis do gminnej ewidencji zabytków (Listing in the Municipal Register of Monuments) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pomnik historii (Historic Monument) • Wpis do rejestru zabytków (Inclusion in the Register of Monuments)
Spain	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patrimonio Histórico Español (Andalucía) (Spanish Historical Heritage) • Bien Cultural de Interés Local, BCIL (Cataluña) (Cultural Asset of Local Interest) • Bien de Relevancia Local, BRL (Comunidad Valenciana) (Assets of local relevance) • Bien Cultural Inventariado, BCI (País vasco) (Inventoried Cultural Asset) • Bien de Interés Patrimonial, BIP (Comunidad de Madrid y Castilla-La Mancha) (Asset of Patrimonial Interest) • Bien Catalogado (Galicia) (Listed Asset) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bien Interés Cultural, BIC (Asset of Cultural Interest)
Sweden	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Särskilt värdefull byggnad (Specific heritage interest) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Byggnadsminne (Listed buildings)
Turkey	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • II. Grup Tescilli Korunması Gereklî Taşınmaz Kültür Varlığı (Group II - Registered Immovable Cultural Property to be Protected) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I. Grup Tescilli Korunması Gereklî Taşınmaz Kültür Varlığı (Group I - Registered Immovable Cultural Property to be Protected)
Netherlands	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gemeentelijke monumenten (Municipal Monument) • Provinciale monumenten (Provincial Monument) • Beschermde stads- en dorpsgezichten (Protected urban and village conservation areas) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rijksmonument (National Monument)
United Kingdom	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Locally Listed Buildings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Listed Buildings (Grade I, Grade II* and Grade II)

5.2.2 Legislation

This section presents **the legislation applicable to heritage buildings** in the participating countries, intending to map regulations and understanding which legal provisions influence the different levels of protection. The classification is organized into three levels (PO, PI and PII), and makes it possible to identify which regulations govern each of these levels.

Table 87. Regulations applied at each level of protection in participating countries

Protection Level	PO	PI	PII
Croatia	No special CH regulations apply. It is regulated by the country's state regulations.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>NN 145/2024, Zakon o zaštiti i očuvanju kulturnih dobara</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>NN 145/2024, Zakon o zaštiti i očuvanju kulturnih dobara</i>
Greece	No special CH regulations apply. The building must simply comply with general planning and building legislation (e.g., the Greek Building Regulation, Law 4067/2012 , and other applicable codes for seismic safety, energy efficiency, accessibility, etc.).	<p>It is subject to a series of laws, presidential decrees and ministerial decisions. These include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Νόμος 4067/2012 – Νέος Οικοδομικός Κανονισμός • Νόμος 3028/2002 – Περί Προστασίας των Αρχαιοτήτων και εν γένει της Πολιτιστικής Κληρονομιάς 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Νόμος 4858/2021 – Ελληνικός Κώδικας Πολιτιστικής Κληρονομιάς
Latvia	No special CH regulations apply. All buildings are subject to the Planning and Building Act.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Kultūras pieminekļu aizsardzības likums.</i> (Law on the Protection of Cultural Monuments) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Kultūras pieminekļu aizsardzības likums.</i> (Law on the Protection of Cultural Monuments)
Poland	No special CH regulations apply. It is regulated by the country's state regulations.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Ustawa o planowaniu i zagospodarowaniu przestrzennym</i> (The Act on Spatial Planning and Development,) • <i>Ustawa o ochronie zabytków i opiece nad zabytkami</i> (The Act on the Protection and Care of Monuments) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Ustawa o ochronie zabytków i opiece nad zabytkami</i> (The Act on the Protection and Care of Monuments)
Spain	No special CH regulations apply. It is regulated by state, regional and municipal regulations. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Ley de Ordenación de la Edificación (LOE) – Ley 38/1999</i> • <i>Código Técnico de la Edificación (CTE) – Real Decreto 314/2006.</i> • <i>Plan General de Ordenación Urbana de Valladolid.</i> 	<p>Each region has its own historical heritage laws and has the competence to manage its heritage assets in accordance with these laws.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Ley 14/2007, del Patrimonio Histórico de Andalucía.</i> • <i>Ley 7/2024, de Patrimonio Cultural de Castilla y León.</i> 	<p><i>It is regulated not only by the regional laws of each region, but also by national legislation.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Ley 16/1985, del Patrimonio Histórico Español</i>

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Protection Level	P0	PI	PII
Sweden	No special CH regulations apply. The building must simply comply with general planning and building legislation (e.g., Plan och bygglag (2010:900))	No special cultural-heritage regulations apply. The building must simply comply with general planning and building legislation (e.g., Plan och bygglag (2010:900))	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kulturmiljölag (1988:950) (National Heritage legislation)
Turkey	No special CH regulations apply. It is regulated by the country's state regulations.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kültür ve Tabiat Varlıklarını Koruma Kanunu (Law on the Conservation of Cultural and Natural Property (Law 2863 / 23.07.1983)) • Taşınmaz Kültür Varlıklarının Gruplandırılması, Bakım ve Onarımları Hakkında İlke Kararı (Grouping, Maintenance and Repairs of Immovable Cultural Properties (Resolution No. 660 / 05.11.1999)) • Korunması Gerekli Taşınmaz Kültür Varlıklarının Yapım ve Denetim Esaslarına Dair Yönetmelik (Regulation on the Principles of Building and Control of Immovable Cultural Property to be Protected (11.06.2005)) • Yıpranan Tarihî ve Kültürel Taşınmaz Varlıkların Yenilenerek Korunması ve Yaşatılarak Kullanılması Hakkında Kanun (Kanun No: 5366) (Law on Conservation by Renovation and Use by Revitalization of the Deteriorated Historical and Cultural Immovable Property (Law 5366 / 16.06.2005)) • Korunması Gerekli Taşınmaz Kültür ve Tabiat Varlıklarının Tespit ve Tescili Hakkında Yönetmelik (Regulation on the Identification and Registration of Immovable Cultural and Natural Property to Be Protected (13.03.2012)) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kültür ve Tabiat Varlıklarını Koruma Kanunu (Law on the Conservation of Cultural and Natural Property (Law 2863 / 23.07.1983)) • Taşınmaz Kültür Varlıklarının Gruplandırılması, Bakım ve Onarımları Hakkında İlke Kararı (Grouping, Maintenance and Repairs of Immovable Cultural Properties (Resolution No. 660 / 05.11.1999)) • Korunması Gerekli Taşınmaz Kültür Varlıklarının Yapım ve Denetim Esaslarına Dair Yönetmelik (Regulation on the Principles of Building and Control of Immovable Cultural Property to be Protected (11.06.2005)) • Yıpranan Tarihî ve Kültürel Taşınmaz Varlıkların Yenilenerek Korunması ve Yaşatılarak Kullanılması Hakkında Kanun (Kanun No: 5366) (Law on Conservation by Renovation and Use by Revitalization of the Deteriorated Historical and Cultural Immovable Property (Law 5366 / 16.06.2005)) • Korunması Gerekli Taşınmaz Kültür ve Tabiat Varlıklarının Tespit ve Tescili Hakkında Yönetmelik (Regulation on the Identification and Registration of Immovable Cultural and Natural Property to Be Protected (13.03.2012))

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Protection Level	P0	PI	PII
Netherlands	No special CH regulations apply. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Omgevingswet (Environmental and Planning Act, 2024) • Bestemmingsplannen (Municipal Zoning Plans) 	• Erfgoedverordening Gemeente (Municipal Heritage Ordinance)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Erfgoedwet (Heritage Act, 2016) • Omgevingswet (Environmental and Planning Act, 2024)
United Kingdom	Buildings that do not have special heritage protection fall under general construction regulations, governed by the Building Regulations 2010 and enforced by local authorities.	Locally Listed Buildings are identified by local planning authorities under the National Planning Policy Framework, which encourages the protection of non-designated heritage assets. These buildings are not legally protected at the national level, but local planning policies may impose constraints on alterations or demolitions to preserve their character.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ancient Monuments and Archaeological Areas Act 1979 • The Planning (Listed Buildings and Conservation Areas) Act 1990

5.2.3 Key elements

This section provides an overview of **how national regulations affect key structural elements** in heritage buildings, organized by protection level (P0, PI, PII) and by participating country. The analysis aims to identify the degree of permitted or restricted intervention for each technical component, according to the applicable legal framework.

The following indicators are used to support interpretation:

- ✓: Intervention permitted with few restrictions
- ✓*: Intervention permitted, conditional on the preservation of cultural value
- X: Intervention not permitted, not regulated, or subject to strict limitations

Table 88. Permitted Interventions by Country and Protection Level

INHERIT Protection Level		Insulation	Windows /Doors	Led Lighting	HVAC	RES	Digital services	Control system	Accessibility
Croatia	P0	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	PI	✓*	✓*	✓	✓*	✓*	✓	✓	✓*
	PII	X	X	✓	✓*	X	✓	✓*	X
Greece	P0	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	PI	✓*	✓*	✓	✓	✓*	✓	✓	✓*
	PII	X	X	✓*	✓*	X	✓	✓*	X
Latvia	P0	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	PI	✓*	✓*	✓	✓*	✓*	✓	✓	✓*
	PII	X	X	✓*	✓*	X	✓	✓*	X
Poland	P0	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	PI	✓*	✓*	✓	✓*	✓*	✓	✓	✓

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INHERIT Protection Level		Insulation	Windows /Doors	Led Lighting	HVAC	RES	Digital services	Control system	Accessibility
	PII	✗	✗	✓	✓*	✗	✓	✓*	✓*
Spain	PO	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	PI	✓*	✓*	✓	✓*	✓*	✓	✓	✓
	PII	✗	✗	✓	✓*	✗	✓	✓*	✓*
Sweden	PO	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	PI	✗	✓*	✓	✓*	✗	✓	✓	✓
	PII	✗	✓*	✓	✓*	✗	✓	✓	✓
Turkey	PO	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	PI	✓*	✓*	✓	✓*	✓*	✓	✓	✓*
	PII	✓*	✓*	✓*	✓*	✓*	✓*	✓*	✓*
Netherlands	PO	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	PI	✓*	✓*	✓	✓*	✓*	✓	✓	✓
	PII	✗	✗	✓	✓*	✗	✓	✓	✓*
United Kingdom	PO	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	PI	✓*	✓*	✓*	✓*	✗	✓	✓*	✗
	PII	✗	✗	✓*	✓*	✗	✓	✓*	✗

5.2.4 Measures

This section presents, for each participating country, the **maximum level of protection at which the measures in the catalogue** are allowed to be applied to heritage buildings. The objective is to identify to what extent technical interventions can be implemented in contexts of higher protection, according to national legislation. This information makes it possible to compare the margin of technical action allowed in buildings with high levels of protection between the different countries.

Due to the size of the table, the following country abbreviations have been used: **C – Croatia, G – Greece, L – Latvia, S – Spain, SW – Sweden, T – Turkey, N – Netherlands**, and **UK – United Kingdom**. Additionally, measures for which no sufficient information is available, or whose estimation is particularly difficult, are marked with the symbol (–).

Table 89. Maximum level of protection per country for the application of catalogue measures in heritage buildings

		C	G	L	P	S	SW	T	N	UK
#01	Façade external insulation	PI	PO	PII	PO	PO	PO	PI	PO	PO
#02	Façade internal insulation	PII	PI	PII	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI
#03	Façade intermediate insulation	PO	PO	PII	PO	PO	PO	PI	-	PI
#04	Roof external insulation	PI	PI	PII	PI	PO	PO	PI	PO	PO
#05	Roof internal insulation	PII	PI	PO	PII	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI
#06	Green Roof Installation	PO	PO	PII	PO	PO	PO	PI	PO	PO

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		C	G	L	P	S	SW	T	N	UK
#07	Floor insulation	PII	PI	PO	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PO
#08	Natural lighting prioritization	PO	PO	PI	PO	PO	PO	PI	PII	PI
#09	Window and door restoration	PII	PII	PII	PII	PII	PI	PI	PII	PII
#10	Windows sealing	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PII
#11	Windows with a low emissivity coating	PI	PI	PO	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI
#12	Aluminium carpentry with thermal break	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PO	PI
#13	Windows with double glazing (air chamber)	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI
#14	Windows with triple glazing (air chamber)	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI
#15	Windows with double glazing (argon gas)	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI
#16	Windows with triple glazing (argon gas)	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI
#17	Windows new all	PO	PO	PII	PI	PO	PO	PI	PO	PI
#18	Sun protection	PI	PI	PII	PO	PI	PI	PI	PII	PI
#19	LED lighting	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PI
#20	Lighting sensors	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PI
#21	Occupancy sensors	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PI
#22	Lighting Controls	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PI
#23	District Heating System	PII	PI	PO	PII	PI	PII	PI	PO	PI
#24	Boiler - Natural Gas Condensing	PII	PI	PII	PII	PI		PI	PO	PII
#25	Boiler - Biomass	PII	PI	PII	PII	PI	PII	PI	PI	PII
#26	Heatpump - Direct expansion	PII	PI	PO	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PO
#27	Heatpump - Geothermal	PII	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI
#28	Radiant heating system	PII	PI	PI	PII	PI	PII	PI	PII	PI
#29	Reconstruction of the heating system and thermostat for control of heating according to system scheduling	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PII
#30	Energy-Efficient HVAC Systems	PII	PII	PI	PII	PII	PII	PI	PI	PI
#31	Heat recovery	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PI	PO
#32	Mechanical ventilation with recuperation	PII	PII	PI	PI	PII	PI	PI	PI	PI
#33	Variable airflow fans	PII	PII	PO	PI	PII	PI	PI	PI	PO
#34	High-efficiency filters	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PI	PO
#35	Variable water flow pumps	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PI	PO

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		C	G	L	P	S	SW	T	N	UK
#36	Storage systems	PI	PI	PO	PI	PI	PI	PI	PO	PO
#37	Increase the design temperature of the chilled water	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PO	PO
#38	Solar thermal panels	PI	PI	PII	PO	PI	PO	PI	PI	PO
#39	White appliances replacement	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PO	PO
#40	Prevent excessive use of air conditioning since it is threatening the energy supply	PII	PO	PO	PO	PO	PO	PI	PII	PO
#41	Temperature sensors	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PO
#42	EQ sensors	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PO
#43	Implementation of a system for remote measurement of energy consumption	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PI
#44	Implementation of a system for remote measurement of water consumption	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PI
#45	PV (+/- storage)	PI	PI	PII	PO	PI	PO	PI	PI	PI
#46	PV panels in the parking lot	PI	PI	PII	PI	PI	PI	PI	PO	PI
#47	EV chargers	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI	PI
#48	Modelling & simulation environment	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PI
#49	IEQ and thermal comfort optimisation	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PI
#50	Energy forecasting and intelligent management	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PI
#51	Digital Twin for Heritage facilities real time monitoring operation & management	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PI
#52	Real-time insights on activity and mobility partners	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PI
#53	Preventive maintenance with H-BIM	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PI
#54	GIS-based solution for sustainable heritage maintenance	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PI
#55	Bike infrastructure (parking)	PII	PI	PII	PI	PI	PII	PI	PI	PI
#56	Energy advice and leaflets	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PO
#57	Reclaimed Materials	PII	PII	PI	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PI
#58	Local Materials Sourcing	PII	PII	PI	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PI
#59	Efficient use of water	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PI
#60	Replacement of the cold water and sewage system.	PI	PO	PO	PI	PO	PII	PI	PI	PI

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		C	G	L	P	S	SW	T	N	UK
#61	Assessment of building resource efficiency through thermography Infrared (IRT)	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PI
#62	See Pillar 1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	PII	-
#63	Modernization of the lightning protection system	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PI
#64	Replacement of the electricity supply and fire suppression system	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PI
#65	Reinforcement of load-bearing structure	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PII
#66	Moisture protection	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PII
#67	Protection of the metal structure	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PII
#68	Reducing thrust in arches and vaults	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PII
#69	Reducing slab deformation	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PII
#70	Heritage buildings environmental climate scenarios	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PII
#71	Improvement wheelchair accessibility (elevator)	PI	PI	PII	PO	PI	PI	PI	PII	PI
#72	Improvement wheelchair accessibility (ramp)	PI	PI	PII	PI	PI	PI	PI	PII	PI
#73	Handrail	PII	PII	PII	PII	PII	PI	PI	PII	PII
#74	Audible signage in customer service and elevators	PII	PII	PI	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PI
#75	Podotactile pavement	PI	PO	PII	PO	PO	PO	PI	PII	PI
#76	ISA signal	PII	PII	PI	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PI
#77	Offering e-learning packages	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PI	PII	PI
#78	Improving public participation	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PII	PII	PI
#79	Interactive screen use & AR-VR interfaces	PII	PII	PI	-	PII	PII	PII	PII	PI
#80	Decision support tool for optimal renovation planning	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PII	PII	PI
#81	Universal Design	PII	PII	PI	PII	PII	PII	PII	PII	PI
#82	Social Lab	PII	PII	PI	PII	PII	PII	PII	PII	PI
#83	NEB Compass self-assessment tool	PII	PII	PO	PII	PII	PII	PII	PII	PI

6 Financial sustainability and risk assessment methodology

The European Union has set a target of climate neutrality by 2050 (European Commission). Improving the energy efficiency of existing buildings is crucial to achieving this goal. However, the process of energy retrofitting in CH buildings is a complex issue. The complexity of managing CH stems not only from its historical and cultural significance but also from the challenges related to securing financing and managing associated risks. These financial and risk-related factors add additional layers of difficulty to the preservation, access, and sustainability efforts (Lidelöw et al., 2019 [17]; Martínez-Molina et al., 2016 [18]; Vieveen, 2015 [19]). To address this multidimensional challenge, three key issues will be assessed in this section:

Financing

The energy renovation of CH buildings requires subsidies along with thorough cost-effectiveness and economic feasibility assessments to ensure their long-term sustainability (Panakaduwa et al., 2024 [20]). Conducting a structured financing analysis is essential, as it enables stakeholders to determine the most suitable financing mechanisms (Jelinčić & Šveb, 2021 [21]). This, in turn, is crucial for ensuring that the proposed renovation measures are not only technically sound but also economically viable and implementable over time.

Risks

An important aspect of the energy retrofitting process for CH buildings is stakeholders' perception of risk. This perception includes the risk of irreversible alterations, damage to cultural value, lengthy bureaucratic procedures, and the complexity of assessing and characterizing the current state of CH buildings. These risks can be a major obstacle to the implementation of measures if a comprehensive assessment framework is not applied (Sodangi, 2024 [22]).

Acceptability

Beyond financial considerations and risk management, energy upgrades must be culturally and socially acceptable to stakeholders. Social acceptance often depends on understanding the impact on the aesthetics of the building, which can be a deterrent to the implementation of interventions (Lucchi et al., 2023 [23]). Several studies have shown the need for acceptability assessment tools to implement balanced retrofit strategies (Eriksson et al., 2014 [24]; Florio et al., 2018 [25]).

Several studies have analysed energy efficiency measures in CH buildings using multi-criteria approaches that consider economic, technical, conservation, and environmental factors. Projects like EFFESUS and CLIC, highlight the importance of integrating heritage conservation with energy performance and user comfort. However, despite some attention to financing, risk, and social acceptance, there is a notable lack of studies that comprehensively combine these three critical dimensions in an integrated framework. The upcoming study of Task 3.5 aims to address this gap by incorporating data from the INHERIT Hub of measures (Task 3.4) on energy retrofit measures for heritage buildings (Egusquiza et al., 2022 [26]; Kutut et al., 2014 [27]; Lucchi, 2016 [28]; Zagorskas et al., 2014 [29]).

6.1 Methodological framework

This section presents the methodological framework that will be applied to accomplish the objectives of this study. Figure 53 shows the steps for implementing the process.

Figure 53. The overarching methodological approach of this study

1. Desk Research

The first step involves an extensive review of the existing literature to identify approaches and methodological frameworks related to financing, risks, and the acceptability of energy retrofits in CH buildings. This step collects reliable and up-to-date studies, which will form the basis for implementing task 3.5. This phase ensures the theoretical background and the alignment of the research with international practices.

2. Methodology Structuring

In this step, the methodologies developed through desk research are identified for the three evaluation categories relevant to this study: financing, risks, and acceptance.

3. Development of the assessment frameworks and data collection

Afterwards, the assessment frameworks are developed for each of the three categories to determine the most important risks, evaluate economic sustainability, and guarantee stakeholder acceptability. Based on the frameworks different data collection methods will be also deployed in order to collect the necessary data to perform the analysis.

4. Case Study Application

Once the frameworks and the data collection methods have been developed, they will be applied to the INHERIT case studies in order to gather insights from relevant stakeholders.

5. Indicators & Strategic Recommendations

Based on the preceding steps, the basic sustainability and financial feasibility indicators will be extracted. Simultaneously, the most critical points in each assessment, as identified through questionnaires and practical application, will be addressed through the development of corresponding strategies.

6.1.1 Financing assessment

Literature Review

Economic viability, long-term investment returns, and the availability of policy-based incentive programs are all emphasized in the literature on financing strategies for energy retrofits in existing buildings. The study of Blecich et al. (2016, [30]) examined the case of an energy retrofit of the HVAC of Krsan Castle, focusing on two key economic performance indicators, Net Present Value (NPV) and Payback Back Time (PBT), evaluating their outcomes across eight retrofit scenarios. Similarly, Ciulla et al. (2016, [31]) analysed PBT and Annual Savings as main economic metrics to assess eight renovation possibilities in historic residential structures. The findings demonstrate the differences in cost-effectiveness by building type and climate zone. According to Zagorskas et al. (2013, [32]), who explored retrofit techniques for historic structures, government subsidies are required for the energy retrofit of historic buildings because of the high cost and technical complexity of solutions like interior insulation. By examining the feasibility of potential façade insulation methods for a historic building using a multi-criteria matrix, Annibaldi et al. (2020, [33]) created a five-step technique for evaluating retrofit strategies in historic structures. The methodological procedure developed in (Nesticò et al., 2015 [34])'s study determines the best option to follow from a technical and financial standpoint, assessing the chosen measures using indicators like NPV, IRR, and PBT. However, a common gap across these studies is that, despite evaluating the cost-effectiveness of energy retrofit measures, they largely overlook the specific financing mechanisms, except for Zagorkas et al. (2013, [32]), who briefly addressed the role of government subsidies. While many studies assess the economic feasibility of energy efficiency measures in historic and CH buildings, few combine these aspects with available financing tools. The proposed methodology aims to bridge this gap by offering a comprehensive approach to financing energy retrofits in CH buildings.

Methodology for the Financing

In this context, the methodology is based on a financial assessment tool with a rating system to evaluate the measures identified in Task 3.4. Particularly, each of the proposed measures will be evaluated against six individual criteria, on a scale of 1 to 5, that comprise a single efficiency index for a full and comparative study. The categories in which they will be graded are listed below, along with a brief description:

- The investment category represents the initial cost of each measure. Although each measure's price may differ from nation to nation, each measure's cost is indicative of how the chosen measures compare.
- Net present value to investment ratio is an indicator that reflects the level of return on unit for an investment. For example, if NPVR = 2, this indicates that for every 1 euro invested, the net present value (NPV) equals 2 euros (Zheng et al., 2021 [35]).
- Payback Time is an economic metric that indicates the number of years it will take to recoup the initial investment from the savings that were created.
- Energy performance is the energy savings resulting from the comparison of the existing building condition with the energy use after the implementation of energy efficiency measures.
- Implementation refers to the impact of the necessary changes to be made to the buildings in order to implement the measure in each case.

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- Heritage level is the highest level of heritage protection that any measure may provide. In particular, level 1 is the highest level of protection, intending to entirely preserve the building's original external and internal appearance, which indicates that the number of measures that can be used is limited. Level 2 is the medium degree of protection, aiming to keep the original external appearance while allowing for alterations to materials, woodwork, and the interior of the structure. Finally, level 3 is the lowest level of protection, allowing most measures to be implemented as long as they do not drastically alter the cultural traits of the structure.

Financing Assessment		
Type	Impact	Rating
Investment	Small investments compared to building size	€€€€€
	Moderate investments compared to building size	€€€€€
	Medium investments compared to building size	€€€€€
	High investments compared to building size	€€€€€
	Very high investments compared to building size	€€€€€
Net Present Value to investment ratio	Above 2	✓✓✓✓✓
	1.5 to 2	✓✓✓✓
	1 to 1.5	✓✓✓✓
	0.5 to 1	✓✓✓✓
	Less than 0.5	✓✓✓✓
Payback Period	Less than 3 years	☺☺☺☺
	3 to 5 years	☺☺☺☺
	5 to 10 years	☺☺☺☺
	10 to 20 years	☺☺☺☺
	Beyond 20 years	☺☺☺☺
Energy Performance	Very high savings, beyond 40%	💡💡💡💡
	High savings, up to 40%	💡💡💡💡
	Medium savings, up to 20%	💡💡💡💡
	Moderate savings, up to 10%	💡💡💡💡
	Small savings, up to 5%	💡💡💡💡
Implementation	Easy to implement, almost no adaptations needed	✗✗✗✗✗
	Small adaptations needed, minor modifications	✗✗✗✗✗
	Medium adaptations needed, interventions in one craft	✗✗✗✗✗
	Large adaptations needed, interventions in some crafts	✗✗✗✗✗
	Very large adaptations needed, interventions in various crafts	✗✗✗✗✗
Heritage	Protection Level 3	III
	Protection Level 2	II
	Protection Level 1	I

Figure 54. Rating Template for the Measures

Figure 54 presents the finance assessment template in six categories, ranging from 1 to 5. In each category, the evaluations correspond to a hierarchical qualitative performance scale:

- The first position indicates "**excellent**" performance.
- The second indicates "**good**" performance.
- Third place indicates "**moderate**" performance
- The fourth indicates "**poor**" performance.
- The fifth indicates "**very poor**" performance.

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For the category "Heritage level", the corresponding scale is from 1 to 3, and the ratings are defined as follows:

1. Protection level 3 indicates "**excellent**" performance.
2. Protection level 2 indicates "**moderate**" performance.
3. Protection level 1 indicates "**very poor**" performance.

6.1.2 Identification and evaluation of potential risks

Literature review

The complexity of evaluating technical, financial, regulatory, and heritage risks is highlighted by recent studies on risk analysis in the field of energy renovations. According to recent research, managing the uncertainty associated with changes to culturally significant buildings is receiving more attention. Panakaduwa et al. (2024, [20]) conducted a review of the barriers to implementing energy measures in CH buildings in the United Kingdom and classified them based on their frequency of occurrence in the literature. Similarly, Sodangi (2024, [22]) identified critical impediments through a literature review and, using the interpretive structural modelling (ISM) technique, studied the complex interrelationships between risks. Bottino-Leone et al. (2024, [36]) investigated the adoption of photovoltaic elements and the risks they may entail in historic buildings, with the use of questionnaires. Lee et al. (2015, [37]) identified the key risks associated with energy performance contracting projects, as a result of two empirical questionnaire surveys in Hong Kong. Şahin et al. (2015, [38]) conducted a risk assessment of energy retrofit measures in CH buildings, taking into account factors such as energy savings, economic, heritage values, durability, moisture, and indoor environment. Sunikka-Blank & Galvin (2016, [39]) conducted interviews with owners of CH buildings to investigate their influence on energy retrofit choices. Similarly, Vassiliades et al. (2023, [40]) investigated the key perspectives of residents in Cyprus regarding sustainable building design through a questionnaire. Some studies examine the risks associated with accessibility in these buildings. Such as the research by Kruczek et al. (2024, [41]), who investigated the reasons why such measures are not implemented in CH sites. As the literature review reveals, there is a significant gap regarding the existence of a comprehensive risk assessment for the implementation of energy efficiency measures, which would cover many aspects that discourage building owners from making such investments, taking accessibility into account. At the same time, the views of stakeholders should be considered, as they provide important insights into addressing these risks.

Methodology for potential risks

The implementation of energy retrofit measures in historic buildings is an important issue, as several barriers prevent it. According to the study by Fouseki & Cassar (2014, [42]) one of the most important reasons that leads owners to hesitate is the threat of alteration of cultural elements. At the same time, Nair et al. (2022, [43]) highlight the lack of technical guidelines and the ambiguity of institutional frameworks, which could reduce the risk taken. Another factor that is a barrier, as pointed out by Herrera-Avellanosa et al. (2024, [44]), is the high upfront costs and the lack of access to financial instruments, such as subsidies or low-interest loans. The present methodology aims to thoroughly explore risks for the integration of energy efficiency technologies and their evaluation. Through this research, important insights will emerge regarding understanding the causes of these risks and exploring mitigation strategies.

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The evaluation is based on a systematic literature review, which includes articles and references from databases such as ScienceDirect, Google Scholar, Zenodo, etc. The selection criteria include articles focusing on heritage buildings and retrofitting, and more specifically, articles that analyse the obstacles and risks related to the topic under discussion. After the literature review, the risks identified were divided into 10 categories relating to: aesthetic, economic, environmental, operational, technical, data and metering, regulatory, institutional, social and behavioural, and accessibility. Table 90-Table 99 below presents the questionnaire used for the evaluation.

Table 90: Aesthetic aspects

Cat.	Which risks do you consider significant in the energy upgrade or accessibility improvement of a CH building?	Not significant at all	Slightly significant	Moderately significant	Significant	Very significant
Aesthetics	Alteration of the building's visual coherence	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Compromise of the building's cultural, artistic, or historical character	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Appearance of unexpected effects following retrofit implementation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Change in the spatial perception of the building	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

The aesthetic risks include all possibilities that may alter the visual harmony or the cultural-historical characteristics of the building. Changes in spatial perception, such as variations in natural lighting or the sense of height, can also be considered aesthetic risks. Moreover, the very uncertainty about the chance of these elements being affected can act as a deterrent to the choice or implementation of specific interventions.

Table 91: Economic aspects

Cat.	Which risks do you consider significant in the energy upgrade or accessibility improvement of a CH building?	Not significant at all	Slightly significant	Moderately significant	Significant	Very significant
Economics	High financial cost of retrofit implementation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Distortion of energy market prices	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Uncertainty in achieving the anticipated energy performance	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Difficulty in obtaining initial capital	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Limited awareness among financiers regarding retrofit benefits	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Extended time required for return on investment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Insufficient economic justification for retrofit investments	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Complexity of emerging technologies and contract structures	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Allocation of resources to other economic sectors	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Higher maintenance needs compared to conventional components	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Economic risks are primarily concerned with the high cost of implementing interventions, which stems from the urgent need for interventions that safeguard the building's cultural value. The high cost causes the investment to have a longer payback period, while external factors such as distorted energy prices, insufficient information for financiers on the benefits of these investments, and the complexity of new technologies add uncertainty. At the same time, the inability to document the investment, combined with the need to reallocate funds to other resources, may result in the

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postponement or cancellation of these interventions. However, uncertainty can also be linked to the results of implementing energy efficiency measures and, more specifically, to achieve the expected energy efficiency and ensuring the lowest maintenance costs for the sustainability of these investments.

Table 92: Environmental aspects

Cat.	Which risks do you consider significant in the energy upgrade or accessibility improvement of a CH building?	Not significant at all	Slightly significant	Moderately significant	Significant	Very significant
Environmental	Emissions generated during the retrofit process	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Challenges related to end-of-life recycling of components	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Emissions associated with manufacturing energy-efficient systems	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

There are some significant environmental risks associated with increasing energy efficiency in heritage buildings. Dioxide emissions from retrofitting (e.g., machinery, material transportation, etc.) and construction can be harmful to the local and wider environment. At the same time, recycling the materials used for the retrofit once they have reached the end of their useful life is another concern for the measures' implementation.

Table 93: Operational aspects

Cat.	Which risks do you consider significant in the energy upgrade or accessibility improvement of a CH building?	Not significant at all	Slightly significant	Moderately significant	Significant	Very significant
Operation	Underperformance of installed systems or equipment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Unpredictable patterns in energy consumption post-retrofit	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Reduced performance due to inadequate design	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Accelerated deterioration of new equipment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Operational risks are potential problems that may arise following the completion of the upgrade interventions. A major issue is equipment underperformance, which can be caused by either the equipment or insufficient design. Obstacles may also arise due to uncertainty about equipment deterioration or energy consumption patterns.

Table 94: Technical aspects

Cat.	Which risks do you consider significant in the energy upgrade or accessibility improvement of a CH building?	Not significant at all	Slightly significant	Moderately significant	Significant	Very significant
Technical	Limited technical expertise and access to appropriate solutions	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Uncertainty about delays in completing the retrofit	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Inaccurate sizing of equipment	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Shortage of skilled technical or managerial staff	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Complexity due to the historic nature of buildings	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Irreversible changes caused by interventions	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Use of substandard construction materials	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Challenges in performing repairs after retrofit	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Insufficient technical capability for implementation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Limited availability of reliable subcontractors	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

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Cat.	Which risks do you consider significant in the energy upgrade or accessibility improvement of a CH building?	Not significant at all	Slightly significant	Moderately significant	Significant	Very significant
	Lengthy duration of the overall implementation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

The technical aspect is another potential source of risk. As previously stated, the primary goal is to achieve a balance between energy efficiency and the building's CH. The lack of specially trained personnel in such constructions may cause additional problems during the implementation of the measures. Such issues include inaccurate equipment sizing, irreversible changes, difficulties repairing new components after retrofitting, and longer implementation times than expected. Other issues that may arise as a result of contractors' unreliability in receiving appropriate training on such projects include access to specialized solutions for these buildings and the use of substandard materials.

Table 95: Data and metering aspects

Cat.	Which risks do you consider significant in the energy upgrade or accessibility improvement of a CH building?	Not significant at all	Slightly significant	Moderately significant	Significant	Very significant
Data and metering	Difficulty in defining a reliable pre-retrofit baseline	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Inaccuracy in methods for determining energy savings	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Inaccuracy in post-retrofit measurement data	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Uncertainty in costs related to monitoring and verification	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Difficulty in assessing the building's existing condition	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Difficulty in processing and combining diverse data sources	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Lack of appropriate energy assessment frameworks for heritage buildings	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Measuring the current and post-retrofit conditions is necessary when implementing energy efficiency measures to guarantee the validity of the upgrade. Naturally, the validity of these measurements could pose concerns for stakeholders. The lack of a widely recognized framework for energy assessment in these buildings is the source of these worries. Nevertheless, the implementation of energy measures may be seriously hampered by the need for a range of data from various sources in order to apply energy assessment properly.

Table 96: Regulatory aspects

Cat.	Which risks do you consider significant in the energy upgrade or accessibility improvement of a CH building?	Not significant at all	Slightly significant	Moderately significant	Significant	Very significant
Regulatory	Length and complexity of required legal procedures	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Difficulty in obtaining permits or authorizations	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Inconsistencies in laws and regulations	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Insufficient legal and policy support for retrofitting	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Another element that might deter prospective investors from making improvements to CH buildings is regulatory risks. More precisely, the process may be made more difficult by the intricacy or ambiguity of the laws as well as the challenge of acquiring permits. Moreover, the implementation of energy efficiency measures may be at risk even if there is no legal or policy backing.

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Table 97: Institutional aspects

Cat.	Which risks do you consider significant in the energy upgrade or accessibility improvement of a CHbuilding?	Not significant at all	Slightly significant	Moderately significant	Significant	Very significant
Institutional	Instability in governmental support or priorities	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Low stakeholder collaboration and coordination	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Increased reliance on imported technologies or components	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Inactivity of local authorities in retrofit planning	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Lack of interdepartmental coordination	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

The success of an energy upgrade can be undermined by critical institutional weaknesses. Instability in government support or policy priorities, combined with low cooperation among stakeholders and limited involvement of local authorities in planning, creates a dysfunctional implementation framework. Furthermore, dependence on imported technologies can be a significant obstacle to the entire process.

Table 98: Social and behavioural aspects

Cat.	Which risks do you consider significant in the energy upgrade or accessibility improvement of a CH building?	Not significant at all	Slightly significant	Moderately significant	Significant	Very significant
Social and behavioural	Unethical behaviour or moral hazard risks	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Complexity in using new energy systems	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Unfamiliarity with retrofit technologies	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Lack of motivation to invest in retrofitting	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Concerns about the reliability of retrofit solutions	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Opposition or complaints from neighbouring property users	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Social and behavioural factors significantly influence the renovation process. Lack of familiarity with new renovation systems can raise doubts about their reliability. In addition, the absence of incentives or interest on the part of owners to invest in such interventions, as well as possible reactions from neighbouring properties, create an environment of inertia. In some cases, moral hazard phenomena can further burden implementation.

Table 99: Accessibility aspects

Cat.	Which risks do you consider significant in the energy upgrade or accessibility improvement of a CH building?	Not significant at all	Slightly significant	Moderately significant	Significant	Very significant
Accessibility	Restrictions from heritage protection regulations	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Limited funding or financial support	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Low demand from users with mobility needs	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Risk of damaging historic features through interventions	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Lack of expressed need for accessibility improvements	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Uncertainty about how to best implement accessibility upgrades	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
	Difficulties in ensuring technical compatibility of solutions	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Interventions to improve accessibility in CH buildings encounter technical, institutional, economic, and social obstacles. Strict restrictions in relevant legislation limit the scope of interventions, while

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the lack of clear design guidelines creates uncertainty. In many cases, low demand from users with mobility needs reduces the priority given to the issue. Furthermore, the difficulty of finding technically compatible solutions that respect the architectural elements of the building, combined with limited funding, leads to accessibility measures being classified as a secondary objective rather than a basic need.

This questionnaire will be evaluated by stakeholders on a scale of 1 (not significant at all) to 5 (very significant), and once all the results have been collected, an analysis will be carried out using the Relative Importance Index (RII). This index will produce a ranking of measures from most important to least important in order to address the most important measures that affect the practical implementation of the measures (Mato et al., 2023 [45]). The method for calculating the index is described below.

Relative Importance Index (RII)

$$RII = \frac{\sum w}{A \times N} = \frac{(5n_5 + 4n_4 + 3n_3 + 2n_2 + 1n_1)}{5N}$$

Where:

W = Weight assigned to each factor by respondents according to Likert scale 1 to 5

*n*₁ to *n*₅ = Number of responses that selected Likert scores 1 to 5 respectively

A = Highest weight on the scale = 5

N = Total number of respondents

The results of this assessment will provide us with an understanding of the most significant risks that pose a dilemma regarding the implementation of measures in CH buildings, as well as ways to deal with them.

6.1.3 Stakeholder acceptability analysis

Literature review

Stakeholder attitudes and cultural values are emphasized as crucial factors in research on the social acceptability of energy-related initiatives in heritage buildings. However, the literature frequently employs behaviour analysis frameworks, stakeholder mapping, and in-depth interviews to pinpoint acceptance barriers and develop contextually sensitive engagement tactics. Broström et al. (2014, [46]) investigated how energy retrofits can be carried out in historic buildings in Sweden, considering the potential impact on cultural value and emphasizing the importance of stakeholder participation in the process. Eriksson et al. (2014, [24]) implemented a methodology that included assessing the significance and impact of four retrofit options. ICOMOS (2011) examines the heritage impact and significance of the measures via an acceptable matrix, although no practical application of the energy measures is mentioned. Şahin et al. (2015, [38]) conducted a thorough investigation of energy retrofit measures in a historic building in Turkey, but do not consider stakeholder participation. Roberti et al. (2017, [47]) developed a quantitative approach to this issue, considering conservation compatibility and the views of relevant stakeholders, even though the number of measures examined is limited. Harrestrup & Svendsen (2015, [48]) conducted research on the energy retrofit of a historic building with a focus on internal insulation and moisture, but without any reference to stakeholder participation or acceptability in the process. Florio et al. (2018, [25]) investigated the visibility of the measures to be implemented in order to close the acceptability gap, but their research was limited to the utilization of photovoltaic elements. The literature review

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reveals research gaps, such as the variety of measures or stakeholder involvement in the process, which the acceptability assessment methodology will address.

Methodology for stakeholders' acceptability

The need to preserve civil heritage buildings while also improving building energy efficiency profiles presents a significant challenge that necessitates extra cautious decision making with acceptability considerations. According to Boeri et al. (2025, [49]), "balancing conservation needs with evolving patterns of use and energy efficiency within heritage" is critical for the long-term sustainability of these buildings. In this context, the assessment seeks to capture stakeholder perceptions, social acceptance, and the measures' compatibility with the specific architectural characteristics of these buildings. The acceptability assessment methodology is divided into two sub-elements: heritage impact and heritage significance, which combine a matrix for selecting the most acceptable measures.

Heritage impact definition

The impact of energy-efficiency measures varies according to their type. Taking this into consideration, the implementation of such measures in heritage buildings is not simply a technical intervention, but an activity that will affect the architectural value of the building if not implemented correctly. Onecha et al. (2021, [50]) emphasize that the integration of new energy efficiency technologies in buildings of historical significance may undermine their distinctive characteristics if not properly evaluated. Based on this, the use of tools to assess the impact of measures is key to balancing the upgrading and preservation of architectural elements (Piderit et al., 2019, [51]). As a result of the above, there is a need for a tool to assess the impact of these measures. The impact assessment ratings are listed below (Figure 55).

Score	Description	Example Interventions	Evaluation Criteria
-3 (Negative High)	Major intervention causing substantial damage or irreversible loss of heritage value.	External insulation covering historic facades, replacing original features with modern equivalents.	Irreversible, highly visible, or destructive to authenticity.
-2 (Negative Medium)	Noticeable intervention that partly compromises cultural significance.	Internal insulation in rooms with some decorative or historical value, minor structural changes to less sensitive areas.	Partial loss of authentic material or appearance, limited reversibility.
-1 (Negative Low)	Minor alteration with negligible loss of authenticity.	Internal insulation in non-visible rooms, replacing non-original elements with neutral modern ones.	Slight visual or material change, low visibility, reversible.
0 (None)	No impact on the cultural value, fully reversible and non-invasive.	Installing wireless sensors or smart controls using adhesive or non-invasive mounting, without altering or drilling into original materials.	No interference with original materials or appearance, complete reversibility.
+1 (Positive)	The measure enhances or restores the cultural value of the heritage element.	Restoration of a lost decorative element using original materials, reconstruction of a historical window based on archival evidence.	Reinforces authenticity, enhances historical understanding, reinstates original appearance.

Figure 55. Impact level definitions

- **-3 (negative high):** This refers to major interventions that cause significant and irreversible changes to heritage value. Such measures may include external insulation covering historic facades or replacing original features with modern equivalents.
- **-2 (negative medium):** Measures in this group result in noticeable changes or a partial loss of the building's heritage value. This category includes measures such as internal insulation

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in rooms with decorative or historical value, as well as minor structural changes to less sensitive areas.

- **-1 (negative low)**: The changes are imperceptible and have little effect on historical data. Measures in this category include internal insulation in non-visible rooms and the replacement of non-original elements with neutral modern ones.
- **0 (none)**: This category includes measures that have no effect on the cultural elements of the buildings and are completely reversible. Wireless sensors or smart controls may be installed using adhesive or non-invasive mounting, without altering or drilling into the original materials.
- **+1 (Positive)**: The measures enhance or restore the cultural value of the building's elements. Measures in this category may include restoring a lost decorative element with original materials or reconstructing a historical window using archival evidence.

Heritage significance definition

The concept of CH goes beyond the historical and architectural dimension. Moreover, what makes CH as significant is the multitude of social, spiritual, and emotional values attributed to it by different actors and communities (de la Torre, 2013 [52]). Local communities should be involved in decision-making processes to ensure effective historical conservation. This strategy allows for the successful integration of heritage values into decision-making processes for conservation (Fredheim & Khalaf, 2016 [53]). The Burra Charter states that any changes should be guided by cultural significance. This means that any retrofit option should aim to minimise cultural significance. Against this backdrop, heritage significance considers 5 levels of significance (Figure 56).

Score	Description	Example Interventions
4 - Very High	Strong historical, architectural, and cultural value. Element is highly visible and contains authentic materials and decorative features. Its loss would seriously harm the building's heritage identity.	A decorated foyer open to the public with authentic materials and elaborate ornamentation, a main facade retaining original design and visible to the public.
3 - High	Important for understanding the building's history. May have some alterations, but retains original features and materials.	An interior space with preserved decorative plasterwork and authentic finishes, still serving its original use (e.g., a main staircase or salon).
2 - Medium	Contributes to the building's function but has limited historic or aesthetic uniqueness. Often includes secondary or altered elements.	A corridor with retained layout but lacking decorative detail, using partially original wall structure.
1 - Low	Limited heritage value, little or no historical or visual contribution. Often not original or significantly altered.	A secondary internal room with simple finishes and no original construction materials remaining.
0 - None	No heritage value. Element is entirely modern or irrelevant to the building's heritage significance.	A modern storage room added during recent renovations with no original materials or design features.

Figure 56. Significance level definitions

- **4 - Very High**: Strong historical, architectural, and cultural value. Element is highly visible and contains authentic materials and decorative features. Its loss would seriously harm the building's heritage identity.
- **3 - High**: Important for understanding the building's history. May have some alterations, but retains original features and materials.

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- **2 – Medium:** Contributes to the building’s function but has limited historic or aesthetic uniqueness. Often includes secondary or altered elements.
- **1 – Low:** Limited heritage value, little or no historical or visual contribution. Often not original or significantly altered.
- **0 – None:** No heritage value. Element is entirely modern or irrelevant to the building’s heritage significance.

Acceptability matrix

The heritage impact and heritage significance form the acceptability matrix, which will determine whether a measure is acceptable or not. More specifically, the measures can be defined as follows: “**unacceptable**”, “**may be acceptable**”, and “**acceptable**”. Through the implementation of this, essentially, the dialogue of feasible measures for the cultural building in question takes place.

Heritage Impact of solution	Heritage Significance of element					
	0 - none	1 - Low	2 - Medium	3 - High	4 - Very High	
-3 (Negative High)	Acceptable	May be Acceptable	May be Acceptable	Unacceptable	Unacceptable	
-2 (Negative Medium)	Acceptable	Acceptable	May be Acceptable	May be Acceptable	Unacceptable	
-1 (Negative Low)	Acceptable	Acceptable	Acceptable	Acceptable	May be Acceptable	
0 (None)	Acceptable	Acceptable	Acceptable	Acceptable	Acceptable	
+1 Positive	Acceptable	Acceptable	Acceptable	Acceptable	Acceptable	

Figure 57. Acceptability matrix

Acceptability questionnaire

The last step of this methodology is creating the Acceptability Questionnaire, through which the stakeholders will rate the proposed measures. Figure 58 shows a small sample of this list, which is guided by the Acceptability Matrix in Figure 57.

Suggested Measures	Heritage Impact of solution	Heritage Significance of element	Acceptance
Façade insulation			
Façade external insulation	-3 (Negative High)	2 - Medium	May be Acceptable
Façade internal insulation	-2 (Negative Medium)	1 - Low	Acceptable
Façade intermediate insulation	-3 (Negative High)	3 - High	Unacceptable

Figure 58. Acceptability questionnaire

6.2 Next steps

A next step for this study is to apply the above assessment frameworks to the **case study applications** of INHERIT and engage with stakeholders relevant to the CH sites.

After collecting the responses and conducting the analysis, the **financial and risk mitigation recommendations** will be developed. Sustainable business models and implementation strategies will be suggested for each pilot site along with more generic conclusions and recommendations in order to replicate the lessons learned to other CH sites.

7 Conclusions

Deliverable 3.2 consolidates and advances the work initiated in D3.1, delivering a robust and operational framework for the assessment and monitoring of CH buildings. Key methodological improvements have been introduced, including an enhanced **Technical Inspection methodology** tailored to heritage-specific pathologies and materials, and the integration of a structured Digital Inspection Form to support standardised fieldwork and future interoperability with H-BIM systems.

The **Key Performance Indicator (KPI) framework** has been expanded through the definition of normalisation criteria and multi-level weighting schemes, enabling tailored assessments across diverse CH contexts and stakeholder priorities. These developments have been implemented into a **second prototype of the INHERIT web-based assessment tool**, which now supports more intuitive user workflows and flexible scoring options for multi-dimensional evaluation.

The deliverable also introduces the **first set of validated measures within the INHERIT Hub**, offering actionable strategies across sustainability, resilience, and conservation domains. In parallel, a methodological foundation has been laid for **evaluating financial viability and risk**, addressing life-cycle costs, implementation barriers, and stakeholder acceptability.

Looking ahead, the outputs of this deliverable will be tested and refined through application in INHERIT pilot sites. Their integration into the digital services under development in WP4 will be essential to ensure practical usability, alignment with end-user needs, and real-world impact in supporting the sustainable transformation of Europe's CH building stock.

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Annex 1. Expert contributions for inspection criteria definition and symptom typology

This annex presents the results of a structured data collection exercise conducted with technical partners of the INHERIT project. The objective was to gather expert knowledge on the identification of pathologies, classification of lesion types, and associated maintenance criteria that inform the design and practical application of technical inspections in historic buildings.

The tables included in this annex were completed independently by two partners, one from Poland and one from Spain, with long-standing experience in architectural conservation and heritage diagnostics. Each table outlines the following components:

- **Pathological Symptoms:** Key observable signs of deterioration based on field expertise.
- **Type of Lesion:** Categorisation of each pathology by severity and impact.
- **Recommended Maintenance Frequency:** Indicative intervals at which the element should be re-inspected or maintained to ensure proper conservation.
- **Additional Comments or Considerations:** Expert annotations on context-specific risks, inspection methods, or material behaviour.

These contributions reflect the diversity of approaches and professional practices across Europe and provide valuable input for refining the inspection logic proposed in this deliverable.

A1.1 Contributions from Polish Partner (Fasada)

Table 100: Pathological processes, observable symptoms, and inspection criteria for structural and foundation elements (Polish contribution)

STRUCTURE & FOUNDATION	Type of information	Main symptom to observe	How can it be collected?	Difficulty level to obtain it	Review frequency
Mechanical process					
	Cracks and Fissures	Location, size, material type	Visual inspection	Low	Yearly
	Deformation and Movements	Deviations from vertical and horizontal, stability of the elements	Visual inspection, 3D scan	Medium in the initial phase	Yearly
	Landslides	Location, process dynamics	Visual inspection, on-site measurements	Low	Yearly
	Mechanical Erosion	Size of damage, location, type of material	Visual inspection, high resolution image	Low	Yearly
Chemical process					
	Efflorescence	Appearance of white powdery residue on masonry, size of staining, appearance of flaking or peeling	Visual inspection	Medium	Yearly
	Organism and Biodegradation	Discoloration, deterioration, odor	visual and olfactory inspection	Medium	Yearly

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STRUCTURE & FOUNDATION	Type of information	Main symptom to observe	How can it be collected?	Difficulty level to obtain it	Review frequency
	Oxidation and Corrosion	Presence of rust, assessment of the degree of corrosion	Visual inspection	Low	Yearly
	Chemical Erosion	Surface deterioration, colour changes, structural weakness	Visual inspection	Medium	Yearly
	Discoloration	Assessment of the degree of discoloration	Visual inspection	Medium	Yearly
Physical process					
	Moisture	Visible dampness, mold and mildew, pilling paint and efflorescence	Sensory inspection	Low	Every 6 months
	Stains and pollution	Surface discoloration, acid rain damage, biological growth, localized corrosion	Visual inspection	Medium	Yearly
	Physical Erosion	Surface wear and tear, cracking, chipping and spalling, loss of detail	Visual inspection	Low	Every 6 months

Table 101: Pathological processes, observable symptoms, and inspection criteria for façades and roofs elements (Polish contribution)

FAÇADES & ROOFS	Type of information	Main symptom to observe	How can it be collected?	Difficulty level to obtain it	Review frequency
Mechanical process					
	Deformation and Movements	Location, size, material type	Visual inspection	Low	Yearly
	Cracks and Fissures	Deviations from vertical and horizontal, stability of the elements	Visual inspection, 3D scan	Medium in the initial phase	Yearly
	Landslides	Location, process dynamics	Visual inspection, on-site measurements	Low	Yearly
	Mechanical Erosion	Size of damage, location, type of material	Visual inspection, high resolution image	Low	Yearly
Chemical Process					
	Efflorescence	Appearance of white powdery residue on masonry, size of staining, appearance of flaking or peeling	Visual inspection	Medium	Yearly
	Organism and Biodegradation	Discoloration, deterioration, odor	visual and olfactory inspection	Medium	Yearly
	Oxidation and Corrosion	Presence of rust, assessment of the degree of corrosion	Visual inspection	Low	Yearly

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FAÇADES & ROOFS	Type of information	Main symptom to observe	How can it be collected?	Difficulty level to obtain it	Review frequency
	Chemical Erosion	Surface deterioration, colour changes, structural weakness	Visual inspection	Medium	Yearly
	Discoloration	Assessment of the degree of discoloration	Visual inspection	Medium	Yearly
Physical process					
	Moisture	Visible dampness, mold and mildew, pilling paint and efflorescence	Sensory inspection	Low	Every 6 months
	Stains and pollution	Surface discoloration, acid rain damage, biological growth, localized corrosion	Visual inspection	Medium	Yearly
	Physical Erosion	Surface wear and tear, cracking, chipping and spalling, loss of detail	Visual inspection	Low	Every 6 months

Table 102: Inspection guidelines for building installations: symptoms, diagnostic methods, and maintenance frequency (*Polish contribution*)

INSTALLATIONS	Type of information	Main symptom to observe	How can it be collected?	Difficulty level to obtain it	Review frequency
Climatization					
Heating system	Boil condition	Noises, inconsistent heating, pilot light issues, pressure fluctuations	visual inspection, auditory clues, thermostat testing	Medium	Yearly
	Circuits and terminals condition	Loose connections, burnt smell, corrosion, system failure	Visual inspection, electrical testing	Low	Yearly
	Energy Efficiency	High energy bills, inconsistent heating, longer operating time	Energy usage monitoring, efficiency tests	High	Yearly
	Leak detection	Water pooling, pressure drop, mold or mildew, rust	Visual inspection, pressure monitoring	Low	Every 6 months
Cooling system	Production equipment condition	Reduced cooling performance, noises, vibration, frequent breakdowns	Visual inspection, performance testing	Medium	Yearly
	Circuits and terminals condition	Power fluctuations, burnt smell, corroded or frayed wires, frequent tripping	Visual Inspection, Electrical Testing	Low	Yearly
	Coolant level	Insufficient cooling, frost build-up, overheating, higher energy use	Pressure testing, visual inspection	High	Yearly
	Energy Efficiency	Higher energy bills, longer cooling times	Energy monitoring, performance audits	High	Yearly

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INSTALLATIONS	Type of information	Main symptom to observe	How can it be collected?	Difficulty level to obtain it	Review frequency
Ventilation	Condition of ducts and vents	Airflow issues, dust build-up, uneven ventilation, noises	Visual inspection, airflow measurement	Medium	Every 2 years
	Mechanical Air Extraction Behaviour and filter	Poor air quality, increased dust, increased humidity, unusual odors	Visual inspection, air quality testing	Low	Every 3-6 months
	Windows characteristics and status	Drafts, condensation, cracks or damage, difficult operation	Visual inspection, thermal imaging	Low	Yearly
Thermal insulation					
	Condition of insulation in walls	Temperature variation, high energy bills, drafts, condensation or dampness	Thermal imaging, visual inspection, blower door test	High	Every 5 years
	Condition of insulation in ceilings	Heat loss or gain, increased energy usage, visible damage, condensation or mold	Thermal imaging, visual inspection	Medium	Every 5 years
	Condition of insulation in windows	Condensation, drafts, cold or warm spot, cracked seals	Thermal imaging, visual inspection	Low	Yearly
	Thermal break	Thermal bridging, condensation, energy inefficiency	Thermal imaging, visual inspection	High	Every 5 years
	Functionality of automation systems	Inconsistent temperature control, erratic system behavior, high energy consumption, system alarms or fault codes	System diagnostics, monitor energy usage	Medium	Yearly
	Check of Sensors	Inaccurate readings, delayed system response, erratic system behavior, fault codes or alarms	Manual testing, system diagnostics	Medium	Yearly
Electricity					
	Condition of the Electric Panels Elements	Frequent tripping, burnt smell, loose or corroded connections, sparking or arcing, unusual noises	Visual inspection, electrical testing, load testing	Medium	Yearly
	Condition of Internal Electrical Installation	Frequent short circuits, flickering lights, overheating outlets, buzzing sounds, sparking or electrical shocks	Visual inspection, electrical testing, thermal imaging	Medium	Every 5 years
Lighting					
	Condition of lighting fixtures	Flickering or dimming, physical damage, overheating, buzzing or humming noises, uneven lighting	Visual inspection, electrical testing	Low	Yearly

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INSTALLATIONS	Type of information	Main symptom to observe	How can it be collected?	Difficulty level to obtain it	Review frequency
	Energy efficiency	High energy bills, outdated technology, excessive heat, inconsistent lighting performance	Energy monitoring, upgrade analysis	Medium	Every 2-3 years
	Functionality of emergency lights	Failure during power outages, dim or flickering lights, delayed activation	Regular testing, visual inspection	Low	Every 6 months
	Battery Autonomy of emergency lights	Short battery life, dimming during extended use, battery failure	Battery load testing	High	Every 6 months
Sound system (PA system)					
	Functionality of speakers	Distorted sound, no sound, uneven sound distribution, physical damage	Sound check, visual inspection, electrical testing	Low	Yearly
	Functionality of controllers	Inconsistent volume control, delayed response, physical damage, signal loss	Manual testing, visual inspection, system diagnostics	Medium	Yearly
	Functionality of microphones and another device	No sound or low volume, distorted sound, battery or power issues, physical damage	Sound check, visual inspection, battery testing	Low	Every 6 months
Fire protection system					
	Condition of alarm systems	false alarms, no sound or poor volume, delayed activation, visual indicators malfunction	System testing, visual inspection	Medium	Yearly
	Condition of smoke detector	Frequent false alarms, failure to activate, physical damage, weak battery warning	Regular testing, visual inspection	Low	Monthly
	Condition of electrical fire extinguishers	No pressure, corrosion or damage, expired certification	Visual inspection, service records	Medium	Yearly
	Condition of fire doors	Difficult to close or seal, visible damage, missing hardware	Physical inspection, functionality test	Low	Yearly
	Charge level of Fire Extinguishers	Low pressure, frequent use	Pressure gauge check	Low	Monthly
	Fire Extinguishers physical conditions	Corrosion or damage, obstructed access	Visual inspection	Low	Monthly
	Functionality of the Smoke/Heat detectors	Failure to alarm, delayed response	Functional tests	Low	Monthly
	Conditions of the sensors and sensibility of Smoke/Heat detectors	Inconsistent sensitivity, frequent alarms	Regular testing	Medium	Monthly

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INSTALLATIONS	Type of information	Main symptom to observe	How can it be collected?	Difficulty level to obtain it	Review frequency
	Condition and functionality of the heads and valves Automatic Sprinkler System	Leaking heads or valves, corrosion or physical damage, failure to activate	Visual inspection, system testing	Low	Yearly
	Condition of Equipped Fire Hose Reels (BIE)	Damaged hose, no water flow, obstructed access	Visual inspection, flow testing	Low	Yearly
Plumbing and drainage system					
	Supply pipes condition	Leaks or drips, discolored water, reduced water pressure, unusual noises	Visual inspection, pressure testing	Medium	Yearly
	Downpipes condition	Visible damage, blockages, rust or corrosion, overflowing gutters	Visual inspection, flow testing	Low	Bi-yearly
	Detection of blockages and leaks	Slow drainage, unpleasant odors, visible signs of water damage, gurgling sounds	Smoke testing, camera inspection, flow tests	Medium	Every 3 months
	Drainage systems condition	Cooling water, soil erosion, weeds or foul smells, visible damage	Visual inspection, water flow tests	Low	Yearly
DHW system					
	Condition of boiler or accumulators	Inefficient heating, strange noises, corrosion or rust, frequent cycling, physical damage	Visual inspection, performance testing	Medium	Yearly
	Energy efficiency	Higher energy bills, long heating times, poor insulation, outdated technology	Energy usage monitoring, heat loss detection	Medium	Yearly
	Water pression	Low water pressure, fluctuating pressure, noisy pipes, boiler shut-off	Pressure gauge check, flow rate tests	Low	Monthly
	Leaks	Visible water, mold growth, lower pressure, rust or corrosion	Visual inspection, moisture sensors	Medium	Quarterly
	Material	Corrosion or rust, cracks or deformation, material fatigue, discolored water	Visual inspection, water quality testing	Medium	Yearly
Renewable energy generators					
	Condition of solar panels, wind turbines, etc.	Reduced energy output, physical damage, dirt or debris, rust or corrosion	Energy monitoring, visual inspection, performance testing	Medium	Bi-yearly

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INSTALLATIONS	Type of information	Main symptom to observe	How can it be collected?	Difficulty level to obtain it	Review frequency
	Energy production efficiency	Lower energy output, increased energy consumption, poor weather sensitivity	Monitoring systems, system calibration	Medium	Quarterly
	Condition of Electric Car Chargers	Charging issues, physical damage, heat build-up, error messages	Visual inspection, functionality test	Medium	Yearly
	Energy efficiency of Electric Car Chargers	Higher energy consumption, slow charging, heat loss	Energy monitoring, heat detection	Medium	Yearly
Overall building consumption					
	Gas consumption	High gas bills, inconsistent heating, gas smell, frequent boiler cycling	Gas meter monitoring, leak detection, system performance tests	Medium	Quarterly
	Water consumption	High water bills, leaks, low water pressure, dampness or mold	Water meter monitoring, leak detection, visual inspection	Medium	Quarterly
	Electricity consumption	Rising energy bills, overheating appliances, frequent circuit breaker trips, energy drain	Electric meter monitoring, energy audits, thermal imaging	Medium	Quarterly

A1.2 Contributions from Spanish Partner (Cemosa)

Table 103: Pathological processes, observable symptoms, and inspection criteria for structural and foundation elements (*Spanish contribution*)

STRUCTURE & FOUNDATION	Type of information	Main symptom to observe	How can it be collected?	Difficulty level to obtain it	Review frequency
Mechanical process					
	Cracks and Fissures	Material. Type. Aperture. Depth. Extent. Structural element. Condition of surrounding material.	Visual inspection. Photography. Crack meter. 3D laser scanner. Infrared thermography. Borescope. Geo-radar. Strain gauge.	Low.	Monthly.
	Deformation and Movements	Material Type Magnitude Structural element State of surrounding material.	Visual inspection. Photography. Optical or digital level. 3D laser scanner. Drone with georeferenced scanning. Inclinometer.	High.	Monthly.

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STRUCTURE & FOUNDATION	Type of information	Main symptom to observe	How can it be collected?	Difficulty level to obtain it	Review frequency
			Extensometer. Strain gauge.		
	Landslides	Material. Type. Magnitude. Extent. Direction. Structural element affected. State of the environment.	Visual inspection. Topographic survey with total station or differential GPS. 3D laser scanning, Drone with photogrammetry. Monitoring with inclinometers. Extensometers. Piezometers. Test pits and geological mapping.	High.	Monthly.
	Mechanical Erosion	Material. Type. Depth. Extend. Causative agent. Structural element. Condition of surrounding material.	Visual inspections. Photography. 3D laser scanning. Digital level. Profilometer. Drone with 3D modelling.	Medium.	Every three months.
Chemical process					
	Efflorescence	Material. Type. Colouring. Texture. Extend. Structural element. State of surrounding material.	Visual inspection. Detailed photographic record with scale. Surface sampling for chemical analysis of salts. Moisture mapping and thermal mapping. pH and surface conductivity measurement.	Low.	Every three months.
	Organism and Biodegradation	Material. Type. Colouring. Texture. Extend. Structural element State of surrounding material.	Visual inspection. Photography with macro or microscopic detail. Sampling for biological analysis. Thermography. Mechanical strength testing. Moisture and pH measurement.	Medium.	Every three months.
	Oxidation and Corrosion	Material. Type. Colouring, Surface condition. Surface condition.	Visual inspection. Photography. Test Pits. Ultrasound.	Medium	Every three months

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STRUCTURE & FOUNDATION	Type of information	Main symptom to observe	How can it be collected?	Difficulty level to obtain it	Review frequency
		Associated cracks. Structural element, condition of surrounding material.	Half-cell corrosion potential. Concrete electrical resistivity meter. Laboratory analysis of carbonation or chlorides.		
	Chemical Erosion	Material Type Colouring Depth Texture Extend Structural element State of surrounding material.	Visual Inspection. High-resolution photography. Surface hardness testing. Core sampling for laboratory analysis. Volume loss measurement (3D laser scanning, photogrammetry). Thermography or moisture mapping to detect active areas.	Medium	Every three months
	Discoloration	Material Type Colouring Extend Persistence Structural element Condition of surrounding material	Visual inspection. Photography with colour scale. Thermal recording. Digital chromatic mapping through photogrammetric analysis. Sampling for composition analysis.	Low	Biannual
Physical process					
	Moisture	Material. Type. Location. Extend. Surface condition. Structural element Condition of surrounding material.	Visual inspection. Measurement with hygrometer or thermos-hygrometer. Infrared thermography. Moisture detection cameras or thermal mapping. Absorption test or sampling for moisture content analysis.	Medium.	Every three months.
	Stains and pollution	Material. Type. Extend. Persistence. Structural element. Condition of surrounding material.	Visual inspection. High-resolution photographic recording. Digital chromatic mapping. Surface sampling for particle analysis.	Low.	Every three months.

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STRUCTURE & FOUNDATION	Type of information	Main symptom to observe	How can it be collected?	Difficulty level to obtain it	Review frequency
			Spectroscopy or chemical analysis		
	Physical Erosion	Material. Type. Depth. Extend. Causative agent. Structural element. Condition of surrounding material.	Visual inspection. Photography. 3D laser scanning. Roughness or profilometry tests. Adhesion or mechanical strength tests.	High.	Every three months.

Table 104: Pathological processes, observable symptoms, and inspection criteria for façades and roofs elements (Spanish contribution)

FAÇADES & ROOFS	Type of information	Main symptom to observe	How can it be collected?	Difficulty level to obtain it	Review frequency
Mechanical process					
	Deformation and Movements	Material. Type. Aperture. Depth. Extent. Structural element. Condition of surrounding material.	Visual inspection. Photography. Crack meter. 3D laser scanner. Infrared thermography. Borescope. Geo-radar. Strain gauge.	Low.	Monthly.
	Cracks and Fissures	Material. Type. Aperture. Depth. Extent. Structural element. Condition of surrounding material.	Visual inspection. Photography. Crack meter. 3D laser scanner. Infrared thermography. Borescope. Geo-radar. Strain gauge.	Low.	Monthly.
	Landslides	Material. Type. Magnitude. Extent. Direction. Structural element affected. State of the environment.	Visual inspection. Topographic survey with total station or differential GPS. 3D laser scanning, Drone with photogrammetry. Monitoring with inclinometers. Extensometers. Piezometers. Test pits and geological mapping.	High.	Monthly.
	Mechanical Erosion	Material. Type. Depth.	Visual inspections. Photography. 3D laser scanning.	Medium.	Every three months.

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FAÇADES & ROOFS	Type of information	Main symptom to observe	How can it be collected?	Difficulty level to obtain it	Review frequency
		Extend. Causative agent. Structural element. Condition of surrounding material.	Digital level. Profilometer. Drone with 3D modelling.		
Chemical process					
	Efflorescence	Material. Type. Colouring. Texture. Extend. Structural element. State of surrounding material.	Visual inspection. Detailed photographic record with scale. Surface sampling for chemical analysis of salts. Moisture mapping and thermal mapping. pH and surface conductivity measurement.	Low.	Every three months.
	Organism and Biodegradation	Material. Type. Colouring. Texture. Extend. Structural element State of surrounding material.	Visual inspection. Photography with macro or microscopic detail. Sampling for biological analysis. Thermography. Mechanical strength testing. Moisture and pH measurement.	Medium.	Every three months.
	Oxidation and Corrosion	Material. Type. Colouring, Surface condition. Surface condition. Associated cracks. Structural element, condition of surrounding material.	Visual inspection. Photography. Test Pits. Ultrasound. Half-cell corrosion potential. Concrete electrical resistivity meter. Laboratory analysis of carbonation or chlorides.	Medium	Every three months
	Chemical Erosion	Material Type Colouring Depth Texture Extend Structural element State of surrounding material.	Visual Inspection. High-resolution photography. Surface hardness testing. Core sampling for laboratory analysis. Volume loss measurement (3D laser scanning, photogrammetry).	Medium	Every three months

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FAÇADES & ROOFS	Type of information	Main symptom to observe	How can it be collected?	Difficulty level to obtain it	Review frequency
			Thermography or moisture mapping to detect active areas.		
	Discoloration	Material Type Colouring Extend Persistence Structural element Condition of surrounding material	Visual inspection. Photography with colour scale. Thermal recording. Digital chromatic mapping through photogrammetric analysis. Sampling for composition analysis.	Low	Biannual
Physical process					
	Moisture	Material. Type. Location. Extend. Surface condition. Structural element Condition of surrounding material.	Visual inspection. Measurement with hygrometer or thermos-hygrometer. Infrared thermography. Moisture detection cameras or thermal mapping. Absorption test or sampling for moisture content analysis.	Medium.	Every three months.
	Stains and pollution	Material. Type. Extend. Persistence. Structural element. Condition of surrounding material.	Visual inspection. High-resolution photographic recording. Digital chromatic mapping. Surface sampling for particle analysis. Spectroscopy or chemical analysis	Low.	Every three months.
	Physical Erosion	Material. Type. Depth. Extend. Causative agent. Structural element. Condition of surrounding material.	Visual inspection. Photography. 3D laser scanning. Roughness or profilometry tests. Adhesion or mechanical strength tests.	High.	Every three months.

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Table 105: Inspection Guidelines for Building Installations: Symptoms, Diagnostic Methods, and Maintenance Frequency (*Spanish contribution*)

INSTALLATIONS	Type of information	Main symptom to observe	How can it be collected?	Difficulty level to obtain it	Review frequency
Climatization					
Heating System	Boil condition	Unusual noises Bubbling Knocking in pipes Unexpected temperature variations. Burner ignition frequency.	Visual and auditory inspection of heat production, piping and heat exchangers. Infrared thermography.	Medium	Weekly
	Circuits and terminals condition	Presence of leaks Corrosion Physical damage in pipes, joints, or terminal units. Pressure problems and calcifications Damage to pipe insulation. Frequency of starts and stops of pumping units	Visual inspection along piping, around valves, radiators, and heat emitters Signs include stains, rust, deformation, wet spots. Pressure tests. Infrared thermography.	Medium	Every three months.
	Energy Efficiency	Excessive power consumption. Slow system response.	Checking bills. Temperatures of the system. Humidity sensors in rooms. Setpoint temperatures and schedules	Low	Monthly and Annual.
	Leak detection	Moisture accumulation. Pressure drops. Water stains, corrosion, or hissing sounds.	Visual inspection. Pressure gauge readings. Acoustic sensors. Infrared thermography.	Medium.	Every three months.
Cooling System	Production equipment condition	Check inlet and outlet temperature and power consumption ('efficiency calculation'). Unexpected temperature variations. Check fans performance. Frequency of starts and stops of compressors.	Visual and auditory inspection of cool production, piping and heat exchangers. Infrared thermography.	Medium	Monthly
	Circuits and terminals condition	Presence of leaks Corrosion Physical damage in pipes, joints, or terminal units. Pressure problems and calcifications Damage to pipe insulation.	Visual inspection along piping, around valves, radiators, and heat emitters Signs include stains, rust, deformation, wet spots. Pressure tests	Medium	Every three months.

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INSTALLATIONS	Type of information	Main symptom to observe	How can it be collected?	Difficulty level to obtain it	Review frequency
		Frequency of starts and stops of pumping units.	Infrared thermography.		
	Coolant level	Check the level indicator.	Visual inspection.	Low	Monthly
	Energy Efficiency	Excessive power consumption. Long cooling cycles. Inconsistent room temperatures.	Checking bills. Temperature and humidity sensors in rooms. Temperatures of the system. Setpoint temperatures.	Medium.	Monthly and Annual.
Ventilation	Condition of ducts and vents	Visible dust Clogging Mold Supply temperature, humidity and velocity conditions. Strange noises. Insulation damage	Visual inspection Thermo-hygrometer Anemometer Endoscopic camera	Medium.	Every three months.
	Mechanical Air Extraction Behaviour and filter	Unusual noise. Low suction. Dust accumulation.	Functional test. Filter check.	Medium.	Monthly.
	Windows characteristics and status	Air leaks. Windows that do not seal properly. Condition of shading elements	Visual inspection. Tightness test. Infrared thermography	Low.	Annual.
Thermal insulation					
	Condition of insulation in walls	Cold spots, mold, heat loss	Thermographic camera Infrared thermography.	Medium	-
	Condition of insulation in ceilings	Uneven temperatures, condensation	Thermographic camera Infrared thermography.	Medium	-
	Condition of insulation in windows	Drafts, high energy loss, fogging	Thermographic camera Infrared thermography.	Medium	-
	Thermal break	Thermal bridging, cold spots, condensation	Thermographic camera Infrared thermography.	High	-
	Functionality of automation systems	Poor thermal comfort, unexpected energy use	Functionality test and system audit	Medium	Weekly

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INSTALLATIONS	Type of information	Main symptom to observe	How can it be collected?	Difficulty level to obtain it	Review frequency
	Check of Sensors	Inaccurate environmental data	Calibration tests and sensor status review	Low	Weekly
Electricity					
	Condition of the Electric Panels Elements	Excessive heat Loose connections Damaged switches Operation of the capacitor bank	Visual inspection. Infrared thermography. Tests: earth resistance, impedance, differential tripping, reactive power, insulation between cables	Medium	Annual
	Condition of Internal Electrical Installation	No operation. Exposed cables. Burning smell.	Visual inspection. Infrared thermography. Multimeter test.	High	Biannual
Lighting					
	Condition of lighting fixtures	Fused lights Dust	Visual inspection.	Low.	
	Energy efficiency	Lighting technology Schedules	Visual inspection.	Low.	Annual
	Functionality of emergency lights	Light operation	Short power failure simulation.	Low.	Monthly
	Battery Autonomy of emergency lights	Battery discharging and charging.	Power failure simulation.	Low.	Annual
Sound system (PA system)					
	Functionality of speakers	No operation.	A signal is sent and checked to see if it arrives.	Low	-
	Functionality of controllers	No operation.	A signal is sent and checked to see if it arrives.	Low	-
	Functionality of microphones and another device	No operation.	A signal is sent and checked to see if it arrives.	Low	-
Fire protection system					
	Condition of alarm systems	No activation, error in acoustic/illuminated signal	Verification of the control panel, push button test, control panel and siren test.	Medium.	Every three months.
	Condition of smoke detector	Fault light, no response to smoke.	Functional test with test gas, signal check at control panel,	Medium.	Every three months.

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INSTALLATIONS	Type of information	Main symptom to observe	How can it be collected?	Difficulty level to obtain it	Review frequency
			acoustic/light verification.		
	Condition of electrical fire extinguishers	No charging, indicators off, no response	Visual inspection	Medium.	Biannual.
	Condition of fire doors	Incomplete sealing, blockages, mechanical damage	Visual Inspection, opening/closing test	Low	Biannual.
	Charge level of Fire Extinguishers	Needle outside green zone	Checking the pressure gauge on each extinguisher	Low	Every three months.
	Fire Extinguishers physical conditions	Corrosion, unreadable labels, physical damage	Visual inspection	Low	Every three months.
	Functionality of the Smoke/Heat detectors	No activation, delayed activation	Observation of response on control panel and siren	Medium.	Every three months.
	Conditions of the sensors and sensibility of Smoke/Heat detectors	No change detection, false alarms	Activation test	High	Annual
	Condition and functionality of the heads and valves Automatic Sprinkler System	Dripping, corrosion, clogging, non-firing	Verification of start/stop pressure of pumps (Jockey/Main), hydraulic test.	High	Annual
	Condition of Equipped Fire Hose Reels (BIE)	Leaks, low pressure, damaged hoses.	Verification of static/dynamic/simultaneous pressure, range test (>5 m), visual inspection.	Medium	Biannual
Plumbing and drainage system					
	Supply pipes condition	Leaks Low pressure in relation to the standards	Flowmeter Pressure gauge	Medium	Annual
	Downpipes condition	Obstructions	Visual inspection Drainage test	Low	Annual
	Detection of blockages and leaks	Standing water, dampness in walls or ceilings	Visual inspection Drainage test Flowmeter Pressure gauge	High	Annual
	Drainage systems condition	Stagnant water Slow drainage	Flowmeter Visual inspection	Medium	Annual
DHW system					

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INSTALLATIONS	Type of information	Main symptom to observe	How can it be collected?	Difficulty level to obtain it	Review frequency
	Condition of boiler or accumulators	Unusual noises Bubbling Unexpected temperature variations. Burner ignition frequency.	Visual and auditory inspection of heat production, piping, heat exchangers and accumulators. Infrared thermography. Check sacrificial anode	Medium	Weekly
	Energy efficiency	Excessive power consumption. Slow system response. Damage to pipe or accumulator insulation.	Checking bills. Temperatures of the system. Setpoint temperatures.	Low	Monthly and Annual.
	Water pressure	Pressure drops.	Pressure gauge readings.	Low.	Monthly
	Leaks	Moisture accumulation. Pressure drops. Water stains, corrosion, or hissing sounds.	Visual inspection. Pressure gauge readings. Acoustic sensors. Infrared thermography.	Medium.	Monthly
	Material	Accumulators' material corrosion.	Check sacrificial anode	Low.	Monthly
Renewable energy generators					
	Condition of solar panels, wind turbines, etc.	Physical damage. Dirt. Worn-out parts.	Visual inspection, temperature and vibration measurement.	Medium	Every 3 months.
	Energy production efficiency	Lower-than-expected production	Inverter/controller analysis.	Low.	Monthly.
	Condition of Electric Car Chargers	Charging faults, loose connectors, error lights.	Physical and functional inspection	Medium.	Monthly
	Energy efficiency of Electric Car Chargers	Excessive consumption, loss of energy.	Measurement with network analyzer.	Medium.	Every 3 Months.
Overall building consumption					
	Gas consumption	Unusual increase in gas consumption	Checking bills. Meter reading	Low	Monthly
	Water consumption	Unusual increase in water consumption	Checking bills. Meter reading	Low	Monthly
	Electricity consumption	Unusual increase in energy consumption	Checking bills. Meter reading	Low	Monthly

Annex 2. Scoring catalogue of elements, materials and pathologies for risk-based technical inspections

Heading	Criteria	Points
Foundations and Structure	Structural principal	3
Foundations, Facade and Structure	Structural principal	3
Facade	Surrounding	2
Roof	Surrounding	2
Installations	Compartmentalization or finishes	1
Accessibility	Compartmentalization or finishes	1
Functional behaviour	Compartmentalization or finishes	1

Construction System	Criteria	Points
Wooden frame structure	Critical stresses (compression, tension, active bending)	4
Timber truss	Critical stresses (compression, tension, active bending)	4
Wooden joist floor	Transfer of non-main loads	3
Steel truss	Critical stresses (compression, tension, active bending)	4
Steel portal frame	Critical stresses (compression, tension, active bending)	4
Steel frame (beam)	Critical stresses (compression, tension, active bending)	4
Timber truss	Critical stresses (compression, tension, active bending)	4
Timber floor slab	Transfer of non-main loads	3
Hollow blocks	Transfer of non-main loads	3
Lightweight infill blocks	Non-structural but affects sealing or thermal stability	2
One-way slab	Transfer of non-main loads	3
One-way floor system	Transfer of non-main loads	3
Two-way ribbed slab	Transfer of non-main loads	3
Waffle slab	Transfer of non-main loads	3
Solid slab	Critical stresses (compression, tension, active bending)	4
Ribbed slab	Transfer of non-main loads	3
Tiled vault	Transfer of non-main loads	3
Catalan vault	Transfer of non-main loads	3
Load-bearing wall structure	Transfer of non-main loads	3
Partitioned wall structure	Non-structural but affects sealing or thermal stability	2
Timber frame with infill walls	Critical stresses (compression, tension, active bending)	4
Vaulted structure	Transfer of non-main loads	3

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Construction System	Criteria	Points
Arch	Transfer of non-main loads	3
Double-curved system or hyperbolic paraboloid	Transfer of non-main loads	3
Load-bearing masonry	Transfer of non-main loads	3
Confined masonry	Transfer of non-main loads	3
Reinforced masonry	Transfer of non-main loads	3
Load-bearing wall	Transfer of non-main loads	3
Lightweight slab	Transfer of non-main loads	3
Reinforced concrete	Transfer of non-main loads	3
Post-tensioned slab	Critical stresses (compression, tension, active bending)	4
Pre-tensioned slab	Critical stresses (compression, tension, active bending)	4
Waffle slab with void formers	Transfer of non-main loads	3
Shear wall system	Critical stresses (compression, tension, active bending)	4
Light steel frame	Critical stresses (compression, tension, active bending)	4
Rolled steel structure	Transfer of non-main loads	3
Pratt truss / Warren truss	Critical stresses (compression, tension, active bending)	4
Space frame structure	Critical stresses (compression, tension, active bending)	4
Light timber frame	Critical stresses (compression, tension, active bending)	4
Rigid frame	Critical stresses (compression, tension, active bending)	4
Cross-Laminated Timber (CLT)	Transfer of non-main loads	3
Structural wood panels	Non-structural but affects sealing or thermal stability	2
Precast concrete	Non-structural but affects sealing or thermal stability	2
Timber joists	Transfer of non-main loads	3
Modular system	Non-structural but affects sealing or thermal stability	2
Sandwich panel	Non-structural but affects sealing or thermal stability	2
3D volumetric modular construction	Non-structural but affects sealing or thermal stability	2
Glued laminated timber (Glulam)	Transfer of non-main loads	3
Barrel vault	Transfer of non-main loads	3
Dome	Transfer of non-main loads	3
Groin vault	Transfer of non-main loads	3
Pneumatic structure	Passive or without direct mechanical function	1
Tensile structure	Passive or without direct mechanical function	1
Ribbed vault	Transfer of non-main loads	3
Concrete shell	Critical stresses (compression, tension, active bending)	4
Ruled surface	Passive or without direct mechanical function	1
Hanging structure	Passive or without direct mechanical function	1
Structural glazing system	Passive or without direct mechanical function	1

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Material	Criteria	Points
Timber	Sensitive material (may degrade if not controlled)	3
Steel	Critical material (high risk of structural degradation)	4
Brick	Sensitive material (may degrade if not controlled)	3
Stone	Stable material (limited or superficial damage)	2
Compressed earth block	Critical material (high risk of structural degradation)	4
Earth	Critical material (high risk of structural degradation)	4
Plaster	Surface material or without structural involvement	1
Lime mortar	Sensitive material (may degrade if not controlled)	3
Concrete	Critical material (high risk of structural degradation)	4
Ceramic	Stable material (limited or superficial damage)	2
Tiles	Stable material (limited or superficial damage)	2
Metal	Sensitive material (may degrade if not controlled)	3
Other	Surface material or without structural involvement	1
Ceramic tile	Stable material (limited or superficial damage)	2
Slate	Stable material (limited or superficial damage)	2
Sheet metal	Sensitive material (may degrade if not controlled)	3
Glazed tile	Stable material (limited or superficial damage)	2

Lesion	Criteria	Points
Collapse	Critical / Structural Injuries	4
Accidental	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Accidental moisture	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Alveolus	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Animal macro-organisms	Biological Injuries / External Agents	1
Anobids (woodworm)	Biological Injuries / External Agents	1
Arrows and slopes	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Bad pressure	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Biipels	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Birds	Biological Injuries / External Agents	1
Bleaching	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Bostrichidae	Biological Injuries / External Agents	1
Breakage of shelves	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Breakdowns	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Breaks in the assembly areas of the parts	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Brittle breakage	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Brown rot or cubic	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Buckling	Critical / Structural Injuries	4

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Lesion	Criteria	Points
Bulging	Critical / Structural Injuries	4
By deposit	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
By differential washing	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Capilar	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Capillary	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Capillary moisture	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Cerambycids (large woodworm)	Biological Injuries / External Agents	1
Chemical attacks	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Chemical corrosion	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Chemical erosion	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Chromogenic fungi This fungus does not affect the cell wall and its impact on mechanical strength is minimal.	Biological Injuries / External Agents	1
Cleaning	Minor / Cosmetic or Superficial Injuries	2
Coating bulging	Critical / Structural Injuries	4
Coating wear	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Collapse	Critical / Structural Injuries	4
Condensation	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Condensation moisture	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Corrosion	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Cracks	Critical / Structural Injuries	4
Cracks in solid slabs	Critical / Structural Injuries	4
Cracks in unidirectional slabs	Critical / Structural Injuries	4
Cracks in waffle slabs	Critical / Structural Injuries	4
Cracks in walls	Critical / Structural Injuries	4
Cracks: Cracking	Critical / Structural Injuries	4
Cracks: Cracks	Critical / Structural Injuries	4
Cracks: Crow's feet or quadrangular cracks	Critical / Structural Injuries	4
Cracks: shrinkage	Critical / Structural Injuries	4
Cracks: Split, starred or open heart	Critical / Structural Injuries	4
Criptotermes brevis Walker	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Crushes	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Crust	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Crypto-florescence	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Curculionidae (wood weevils)	Biological Injuries / External Agents	1
Damage to foundation materials	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3

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Lesion	Criteria	Points
Decementation	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Deformation	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Deformation of the material	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Deformation of the structure	Critical / Structural Injuries	4
Deformations	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Deployments	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Descents	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Detachment	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Detachment of finishing elements	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Detachment of the coating mortar	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Detachments	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Detachments in bonded systems	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Detachments in point anchor systems	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Dirt	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Dirt patina	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Dirty patina	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Disaggregation	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Discoloration	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Dissolution	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Domestic animals	Biological Injuries / External Agents	1
Dust deposit	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Efflorescence	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Electrochemical corrosion	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Erosion	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Erosion mechanics	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Excessive warming	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Excreative deposit	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Fatigue fracture It is a sudden breakage of the material, without plasticisation, produced by variable stresses over time, cyclic loading and unloading, with stresses below the elastic limit.	Critical / Structural Injuries	4
Fibra disorders: Resin pockets (gills)	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Fibre disorders: Diagonal fibre	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Fibre disorders: Double sapwood	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Fibre disorders: Eccentricity of the heartv	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3

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Lesion	Criteria	Points
Fibre disorders: Interbreeding or interlock	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Fibre disorders: Intertwined or twisted fibre	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Fibre disorders: Irregular growth	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Fibre disorders: Knots	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Fibre disorders: Lupias and warts	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Fibre disorders: reaction wood	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Filtration	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Filtration and capillarity moisture	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Filtration moisture	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Filtration Moistures	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Fire action	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Fissures	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Floors	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Foundation error	Critical / Structural Injuries	4
Fungi: moulds	Biological Injuries / External Agents	1
Fungus	Biological Injuries / External Agents	1
Green algae	Biological Injuries / External Agents	1
Hits	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Inadequate temperature	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Inlay	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Inlay and lime	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Insects	Biological Injuries / External Agents	1
Insufficient bracing	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Insufficient section	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Irregular appearance	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Lack of adhesion and lifting of the floor screed	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Lack of continuity of thermal insulation.	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Lack of pond	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Lack of watertightness	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Laminar tearing A tear or crack in the rolling direction that produces a staggered pattern with longitudinal sections much larger than the transverse sections.	Critical / Structural Injuries	4
Landslides	Critical / Structural Injuries	4

D3.2 Second INHERIT Assessment & Monitoring Framework

Lesion	Criteria	Points
Leaks in facilities	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Lichens	Biological Injuries / External Agents	1
Lime	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Linear rupture	Critical / Structural Injuries	4
Localised crushing on metal fasteners	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Loss of coating mass	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Loss of horseshoe	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Loss of section	Critical / Structural Injuries	4
Lyctids (moth)	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Malfunction	Critical / Structural Injuries	4
Marking anchors.	Minor / Cosmetic or Superficial Injuries	2
Marking of joints.	Minor / Cosmetic or Superficial Injuries	2
Material absence	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Material Intexistence	Minor / Cosmetic or Superficial Injuries	2
Mechanical erosion	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Microcracks	Critical / Structural Injuries	4
Microorganisms: bacteria	Biological Injuries / External Agents	1
Missing and cleaning	Minor / Cosmetic or Superficial Injuries	2
Moisture seepage	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Moistures	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Moulds This fungus does not affect the cell wall and its impact on mechanical strength is minimal.	Biological Injuries / External Agents	1
Mushrooms	Biological Injuries / External Agents	1
Natural patina	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Noises	Minor / Cosmetic or Superficial Injuries	2
Obstructions	Minor / Cosmetic or Superficial Injuries	2
Operation	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Oxidation	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Oxidation and corrosion	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Patina	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Photodegradation	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Physical erosion	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Plant micro-organisms (fungi)	Biological Injuries / External Agents	1
Plant organisms (grasses)	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Plant organisms (lichens and mosses)	Biological Injuries / External Agents	1
Plants	Biological Injuries / External Agents	1

D3.2 Second INHERIT Assessment & Monitoring Framework

Lesion	Criteria	Points
Plunge	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Pond	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Praise	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Praise	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Punctual losses and conditions	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Punctual rupture	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Reticulitermes lucifugus Rossi	Biological Injuries / External Agents	1
Rot fungus This fungus affects mechanical properties Classification:	Biological Injuries / External Agents	1
Rot White or fibrous (corrosive or delignifi- cante)	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Rotation or turn	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Rotting and loss of material	Critical / Structural Injuries	4
Rotting fungi	Biological Injuries / External Agents	1
Separation of insulating panels	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Seudo- eflorescencia	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Smells	Minor / Cosmetic or Superficial Injuries	2
Soft rot	Minor / Cosmetic or Superficial Injuries	2
Softening	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Sparks	Minor / Cosmetic or Superficial Injuries	2
Sparks	Minor / Cosmetic or Superficial Injuries	2
Staining	Minor / Cosmetic or Superficial Injuries	2
Structure corrosion	Critical / Structural Injuries	4
Structure degradation	Critical / Structural Injuries	4
Structure fissures	Critical / Structural Injuries	4
Surface deformation.	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Unsheduling	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Upper plants	Biological Injuries / External Agents	1
Voltage	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Warp	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Warping Deformations	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Warps and sags	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Washing differential	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Water action	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Watertightness	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3

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Lesion	Criteria	Points
Wear	Moderate / Progressive Injuries	3
Xylophagous attack	Biological Injuries / External Agents	1
Xylophagous coleopterous insects	Biological Injuries / External Agents	1
Xylophagous insects	Biological Injuries / External Agents	1

Annex 3. KPI prioritisation results based on INHERIT criteria

This annex presents the detailed results of the KPI prioritisation exercise conducted according to the five INHERIT criteria. Using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), weights were assigned to both the pillars and KPIs within each pillar, reflecting the relative importance of different sustainability and heritage management priorities. These results support assessments tailored to specific strategic objectives.

A3.1 KPI Weights based on Criteria 1 – Preservation of cultural and historical value

Results obtained for criteria 1. Preservation of cultural and historical value.

Table 106: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 1 based on prioritisation for criteria 1

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
1.1-EP	Total energy intensity	9.32%
1.2-EP	Energy autonomy	4.12%
1.3-EP	Energy performance and operation	1.43%
1.4-EP	Response to the needs of occupants	1.43%
1.5-EP	Energy flexibility assessment	5.78%
1.1-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	12.61%
1.2-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	23.06%
1.3-IEQ	Air quality	19.69%
1.4-IEQ	Visual comfort	11.28%
1.5-IEQ	Acoustic comfort	11.28%

Figure 59: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 1 following prioritisation for criteria 1

D3.2 Second INHERIT Assessment & Monitoring Framework

Table 107: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 2 based on prioritisation for criteria 1

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
2.1-TWC	Total Water Consumption	2.38%
2.2-GWP	Global Warming Potential	9.53%
2.3-OEC	Operational Energy Costs	3.73%
2.4-PBP	Payback Period	22.05%
2.5-LCC	Life Cycle Cost	34.04%
2.6-ECI	Energy Circularity Indicator	7.81%
2.7-WCI	Water Circularity Indicator	2.60%
2.8-MCI	Material Circularity Indicator	17.87%

Figure 60: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 2 following prioritisation for criteria 1

Table 108: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 3 based on prioritisation for criteria 1

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
3.1-IoH	Inventory of relevant Hazards	3.39%
3.2-HI	Hazards Identification	4.52%
3.3-RMP	Risk Management Plan(s)	39.38%
3.4-RI_VxE	Risk Impact assessment: Vulnerability and Exposure	23.12%
3.5-RL_SxL	Risk impact Level evaluation: Severity of consequences and Likelihood of occurrence	29.60%

Figure 61: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 3 following prioritisation for criteria 1

D3.2 Second INHERIT Assessment & Monitoring Framework

Table 109: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 4 based on prioritisation for criteria 1

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
4.1-AL	Accessibility Level	4.31%
4.2-I&OL	Inclusiveness and Openness Level	21.35%
4.3-RT	Direct Revenue from Tourism (entry fees)	2.12%
4.4-IRT	Indirect Revenue through Tourism attraction	4.54%
4.5-IPV	Increased Property Value	1.85%
4.6-LJC	Number of Local Jobs Created	15.87%
4.7-IPI	Investment in Public Infrastructure	9.26%
4.8-CE	Cultural Enrichment	26.03%
4.9-PP	Public Perception	14.67%

Figure 62: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 4 following prioritisation for criteria 1

A3.2 KPI Weights based on Criteria 2 – Energy Efficiency and Operational Performance

Results obtained for criteria 2. Energy Efficiency and Operational Performance.

Table 110: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 1 based on prioritisation for criteria 2

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
1.1-EP	Total energy intensity	17.86%
1.2-EP	Energy autonomy	2.67%
1.3-EP	Energy performance and operation	4.84%
1.4-EP	Response to the needs of occupants	4.08%
1.5-EP	Energy flexibility assessment	2.83%
1.1-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	21.60%
1.2-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	15.29%
1.3-IEQ	Air quality	16.97%
1.4-IEQ	Visual comfort	5.34%
1.5-IEQ	Acoustic comfort	8.51%

Figure 63: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 1 following prioritisation for criteria 2

D3.2 Second INHERIT Assessment & Monitoring Framework

Table 111: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 2 based on prioritisation for criteria 2

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
2.1-TWC	Total Water Consumption	8.70%
2.2-GWP	Global Warming Potential	6.92%
2.3-OEC	Operational Energy Costs	23.27%
2.4-PBP	Payback Period	5.71%
2.5-LCC	Life Cycle Cost	10.43%
2.6-ECI	Energy Circularity Indicator	22.80%
2.7-WCI	Water Circularity Indicator	12.88%
2.8-MCI	Material Circularity Indicator	9.30%

Figure 64: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 2 following prioritisation for criteria 2

Table 112: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 3 based on prioritisation for criteria 2

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
3.1-IoH	Inventory of relevant Hazards	3.26%
3.2-HI	Hazards Identification	7.75%
3.3-RMP	Risk Management Plan(s)	54.29%
3.4-RI_VxE	Risk Impact assessment: Vulnerability and Exposure	19.06%
3.5-RL_SxL	Risk impact Level evaluation: Severity of consequences and Likelihood of occurrence	15.64%

Figure 65: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 3 following prioritisation for criteria 2

D3.2 Second INHERIT Assessment & Monitoring Framework

Table 113: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 4 based on prioritisation for criteria 2

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
4.1-AL	Accessibility Level	35.04%
4.2-I&OL	Inclusiveness and Openness Level	23.60%
4.3-RT	Direct Revenue from Tourism (entry fees)	9.26%
4.4-IRT	Indirect Revenue through Tourism attraction	5.46%
4.5-IPV	Increased Property Value	1.82%
4.6-LJC	Number of Local Jobs Created	10.15%
4.7-IPV	Investment in Public Infrastructure	6.87%
4.8-CE	Cultural Enrichment	4.12%
4.9-PP	Public Perception	3.68%

Figure 66: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 4 following prioritisation for criteria 2

A3.3 KPI Weights based on Criteria 3 – Resilience to environmental and human-made hazards

Results obtained for criteria 3. Resilience to environmental and human-made hazards.

Table 114: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 1 based on prioritisation for criteria 3

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
1.1-EP	Total energy intensity	2.94%
1.2-EP	Energy autonomy	4.58%
1.3-EP	Energy performance and operation	8.45%
1.4-EP	Response to the needs of occupants	14.97%
1.5-EP	Energy flexibility assessment	5.69%
1.1-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	21.18%
1.2-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	18.27%
1.3-IEQ	Air quality	13.12%
1.4-IEQ	Visual comfort	4.92%
1.5-IEQ	Acoustic comfort	5.89%

Figure 67: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 1 following prioritisation for criteria 3

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Table 115: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 2 based on prioritisation for criteria 3

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
2.1-TWC	Total Water Consumption	15.25%
2.2-GWP	Global Warming Potential	27.46%
2.3-OEC	Operational Energy Costs	9.45%
2.4-PBP	Payback Period	3.48%
2.5-LCC	Life Cycle Cost	13.36%
2.6-ECI	Energy Circularity Indicator	11.42%
2.7-WCI	Water Circularity Indicator	10.76%
2.8-MCI	Material Circularity Indicator	8.82%

Figure 68: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 2 following prioritisation for criteria 3

Table 116: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 3 based on prioritisation for criteria 3

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
3.1-IoH	Inventory of relevant Hazards	4.72%
3.2-HI	Hazards Identification	27.01%
3.3-RMP	Risk Management Plan(s)	38.45%
3.4-RI_VxE	Risk Impact assessment: Vulnerability and Exposure	17.60%
3.5-RL_SxL	Risk impact Level evaluation: Severity of consequences and Likelihood of occurrence	12.23%

Figure 69: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 3 following prioritisation for criteria 3

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Table 117: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 4 based on prioritisation for criteria 3

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
4.1-AL	Accessibility Level	22.92%
4.2-I&OL	Inclusiveness and Openness Level	5.73%
4.3-RT	Direct Revenue from Tourism (entry fees)	14.21%
4.4-IRT	Indirect Revenue through Tourism attraction	6.10%
4.5-IPV	Increased Property Value	9.15%
4.6-LJC	Number of Local Jobs Created	3.79%
4.7-IPV	Investment in Public Infrastructure	25.90%
4.8-CE	Cultural Enrichment	4.96%
4.9-PP	Public Perception	7.23%

Figure 70: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 4 following prioritisation for criteria 3

A3.4 KPI Weights based on Criteria 4 – Socioeconomic and community engagement

Results obtained for criteria 4. Socioeconomic and community engagement.

Table 118: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 1 based on prioritisation for criteria 4

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
1.1-EP	Total energy intensity	2.28%
1.2-EP	Energy autonomy	3.08%
1.3-EP	Energy performance and operation	3.69%
1.4-EP	Response to the needs of occupants	9.27%
1.5-EP	Energy flexibility assessment	2.85%
1.1-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	11.42%
1.2-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	12.48%
1.3-IEQ	Air quality	28.99%
1.4-IEQ	Visual comfort	12.51%
1.5-IEQ	Acoustic comfort	13.43%

Figure 71: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 1 following prioritisation for criteria 4

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Table 119: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 2 based on prioritisation for criteria 4

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
2.1-TWC	Total Water Consumption	16.39%
2.2-GWP	Global Warming Potential	15.76%
2.3-OEC	Operational Energy Costs	6.42%
2.4-PBP	Payback Period	5.13%
2.5-LCC	Life Cycle Cost	8.99%
2.6-ECI	Energy Circularity Indicator	13.57%
2.7-WCI	Water Circularity Indicator	25.45%
2.8-MCI	Material Circularity Indicator	8.28%

Figure 72: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 2 following prioritisation for criteria 4

Table 120: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 3 based on prioritisation for criteria 4

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
3.1-IoH	Inventory of relevant Hazards	4.72%
3.2-HI	Hazards Identification	27.01%
3.3-RMP	Risk Management Plan(s)	38.45%
3.4-RI_VxE	Risk Impact assessment: Vulnerability and Exposure	17.60%
3.5-RL_SxL	Risk impact Level evaluation: Severity of consequences and Likelihood of occurrence	12.23%

Figure 73: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 3 following prioritisation for criteria 4

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Table 121: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 4 based on prioritisation for criteria 4

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
4.1-AL	Accessibility Level	27.79%
4.2-I&OL	Inclusiveness and Openness Level	18.23%
4.3-RT	Direct Revenue from Tourism (entry fees)	2.24%
4.4-IRT	Indirect Revenue through Tourism attraction	4.98%
4.5-IPV	Increased Property Value	4.04%
4.6-LJC	Number of Local Jobs Created	14.77%
4.7-IPI	Investment in Public Infrastructure	9.50%
4.8-CE	Cultural Enrichment	7.55%
4.9-PP	Public Perception	10.90%

Figure 74: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 4 following prioritisation for criteria 4

A3.5 KPI Weights based on Criteria 5 – Longevity and life cycle cost management

Results obtained for criteria 5. Longevity and life cycle cost management.

Table 122: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 1 based on prioritisation for criteria 5

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
1.1-EP	Total energy intensity	20.86%
1.2-EP	Energy autonomy	14.42%
1.3-EP	Energy performance and operation	22.97%
1.4-EP	Response to the needs of occupants	5.01%
1.5-EP	Energy flexibility assessment	12.04%
1.1-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	6.10%
1.2-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	6.10%
1.3-IEQ	Air quality	4.28%
1.4-IEQ	Visual comfort	4.10%
1.5-IEQ	Acoustic comfort	4.10%

Figure 75: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 1 following prioritisation for criteria 5

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Table 123: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 2 based on prioritisation for criteria 5

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
2.1-TWC	Total Water Consumption	2.80%
2.2-GWP	Global Warming Potential	3.70%
2.3-OEC	Operational Energy Costs	21.30%
2.4-PBP	Payback Period	2.44%
2.5-LCC	Life Cycle Cost	31.46%
2.6-ECI	Energy Circularity Indicator	14.64%
2.7-WCI	Water Circularity Indicator	10.98%
2.8-MCI	Material Circularity Indicator	12.68%

Figure 76: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 2 following prioritisation for criteria 5

Table 124: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 3 based on prioritisation for criteria 5

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
3.1-IoH	Inventory of relevant Hazards	25.69%
3.2-HI	Hazards Identification	32.46%
3.3-RMP	Risk Management Plan(s)	22.28%
3.4-RI_VxE	Risk Impact assessment: Vulnerability and Exposure	9.78%
3.5-RL_SxL	Risk impact Level evaluation: Severity of consequences and Likelihood of occurrence	9.78%

Figure 77: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 3 following prioritisation for criteria 5

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Table 125: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 4 based on prioritisation for criteria 5

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
4.1-AL	Accessibility Level	2.92%
4.2-I&OL	Inclusiveness and Openness Level	2.98%
4.3-RT	Direct Revenue from Tourism (entry fees)	37.27%
4.4-IRT	Indirect Revenue through Tourism attraction	17.34%
4.5-IPV	Increased Property Value	16.37%
4.6-LJC	Number of Local Jobs Created	6.96%
4.7-IPV	Investment in Public Infrastructure	9.74%
4.8-CE	Cultural Enrichment	2.58%
4.9-PP	Public Perception	3.84%

Figure 78: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 4 following prioritisation for criteria 5

Annex 4. KPI prioritisation results based on INHERIT Pilots

This annex presents the KPI prioritisation results based on the specific contexts and characteristics of the INHERIT pilot sites. The prioritisation reflects the unique needs, challenges and management priorities of each pilot, as determined through workshops and collaborative activities with pilot leaders and stakeholders. The AHP method was applied to derive the weights, supporting site-specific performance assessments.

A4.1 KPI Weights for Pilot 1 – City Administration Headquarters in Jastrebarsko, Croatia

Results obtained for Pilot 1. City Administration Headquarters in Jastrebarsko, Croatia

Table 126: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 1 based on prioritisation for Pilot 1

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
1.1-EP	Total energy intensity	25.72%
1.2-EP	Energy autonomy	3.27%
1.3-EP	Energy performance and operation	10.74%
1.4-EP	Response to the needs of occupants	3.27%
1.5-EP	Energy flexibility assessment	25.72%
1.1-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	10.74%
1.2-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	3.27%
1.3-IEQ	Air quality	10.74%
1.4-IEQ	Visual comfort	3.27%
1.5-IEQ	Acoustic comfort	3.27%

Figure 79: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 1 following prioritisation for Pilot 1

D3.2 Second INHERIT Assessment & Monitoring Framework

Table 127: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 2 based on prioritisation for Pilot 1

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
2.1-TWC	Total Water Consumption	38.41%
2.2-GWP	Global Warming Potential	17.90%
2.3-OEC	Operational Energy Costs	6.89%
2.4-PBP	Payback Period	6.89%
2.5-LCC	Life Cycle Cost	17.90%
2.6-ECI	Energy Circularity Indicator	2.55%
2.7-WCI	Water Circularity Indicator	2.55%
2.8-MCI	Material Circularity Indicator	6.89%

Figure 80: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 2 following prioritisation for Pilot 1

Table 128: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 3 based on prioritisation for Pilot 1

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
3.1-IoH	Inventory of relevant Hazards	37.24%
3.2-HI	Hazards Identification	14.87%
3.3-RMP	Risk Management Plan(s)	37.24%
3.4-RI_VxE	Risk Impact assessment: Vulnerability and Exposure	5.33%
3.5-RL_SxL	Risk impact Level evaluation: Severity of consequences and Likelihood of occurrence	5.33%

Figure 81: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 3 following prioritisation for Pilot 1

D3.2 Second INHERIT Assessment & Monitoring Framework

Table 129: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 4 based on prioritisation for Pilot 1

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
4.1-AL	Accessibility Level	34.18%
4.2-I&OL	Inclusiveness and Openness Level	12.82%
4.3-RT	Direct Revenue from Tourism (entry fees)	3.64%
4.4-IRT	Indirect Revenue through Tourism attraction	3.64%
4.5-IPV	Increased Property Value	12.82%
4.6-LJC	Number of Local Jobs Created	3.64%
4.7-IPI	Investment in Public Infrastructure	12.82%
4.8-CE	Cultural Enrichment	3.64%
4.9-PP	Public Perception	12.82%

Figure 82: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 4 following prioritisation for Pilot 1

A4.2 KPI Weights for Pilot 2 – Noisiel La Chocolaterie in Noisiel, France

Results obtained for Pilot 2. Noisiel La Chocolaterie in Noisiel, France

Table 130: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 1 based on prioritisation for Pilot 2

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
1.1-EP	Total energy intensity	18.30%
1.2-EP	Energy autonomy	9.55%
1.3-EP	Energy performance and operation	3.87%
1.4-EP	Response to the needs of occupants	23.16%
1.5-EP	Energy flexibility assessment	5.59%
1.1-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	15.98%
1.2-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	5.07%
1.3-IEQ	Air quality	13.61%
1.4-IEQ	Visual comfort	1.38%
1.5-IEQ	Acoustic comfort	3.48%

Figure 83: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 1 following prioritisation for Pilot 2

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Table 131: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 2 based on prioritisation for Pilot 2

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
2.1-TWC	Total Water Consumption	2.57%
2.2-GWP	Global Warming Potential	6.09%
2.3-OEC	Operational Energy Costs	36.77%
2.4-PBP	Payback Period	21.22%
2.5-LCC	Life Cycle Cost	13.97%
2.6-ECI	Energy Circularity Indicator	10.74%
2.7-WCI	Water Circularity Indicator	5.40%
2.8-MCI	Material Circularity Indicator	3.23%

Figure 84: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 2 following prioritisation for Pilot 2

Table 132: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 3 based on prioritisation for Pilot 2

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
3.1-IoH	Inventory of relevant Hazards	3.77%
3.2-HI	Hazards Identification	8.41%
3.3-RMP	Risk Management Plan(s)	16.36%
3.4-RI_VxL	Risk Impact assessment: Vulnerability and Exposure	35.73%
3.5-RL_SxL	Risk impact Level evaluation: Severity of consequences and Likelihood of occurrence	35.73%

Figure 85: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 3 following prioritisation for Pilot 2

D3.2 Second INHERIT Assessment & Monitoring Framework

Table 133: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 4 based on prioritisation for Pilot 2

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
4.1-AL	Accessibility Level	15.12%
4.2-I&OL	Inclusiveness and Openness Level	7.93%
4.3-RT	Direct Revenue from Tourism (entry fees)	2.41%
4.4-IRT	Indirect Revenue through Tourism attraction	7.23%
4.5-IPV	Increased Property Value	39.33%
4.6-LJC	Number of Local Jobs Created	11.62%
4.7-IPI	Investment in Public Infrastructure	2.57%
4.8-CE	Cultural Enrichment	5.32%
4.9-PP	Public Perception	8.46%

Figure 86: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 4 following prioritisation for Pilot 2

A4.3 KPI Weights for Pilot 3 – ELLET Building in Tripodon Street in Athens, Greece

Results obtained for Pilot 3. ELLET Building in Tripodon Street in Athens, Greece

Table 134: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 1 based on prioritisation for Pilot 3

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
1.1-EP	Total energy intensity	7.03%
1.2-EP	Energy autonomy	8.59%
1.3-EP	Energy performance and operation	5.50%
1.4-EP	Response to the needs of occupants	8.99%
1.5-EP	Energy flexibility assessment	6.36%
1.1-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	14.13%
1.2-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	14.96%
1.3-IEQ	Air quality	14.96%
1.4-IEQ	Visual comfort	9.38%
1.5-IEQ	Acoustic comfort	10.10%

Figure 87: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 1 following prioritisation for Pilot 3

D3.2 Second INHERIT Assessment & Monitoring Framework

Table 135: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 2 based on prioritisation for Pilot 3

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
2.1-TWC	Total Water Consumption	18.11%
2.2-GWP	Global Warming Potential	13.29%
2.3-OEC	Operational Energy Costs	10.78%
2.4-PBP	Payback Period	6.94%
2.5-LCC	Life Cycle Cost	7.49%
2.6-ECI	Energy Circularity Indicator	11.07%
2.7-WCI	Water Circularity Indicator	16.16%
2.8-MCI	Material Circularity Indicator	16.16%

Figure 88: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 2 following prioritisation for Pilot 3

Table 136: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 3 based on prioritisation for Pilot 3

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
3.1-IoH	Inventory of relevant Hazards	15.30%
3.2-HI	Hazards Identification	19.75%
3.3-RMP	Risk Management Plan(s)	19.75%
3.4-RI_VxL	Risk Impact assessment: Vulnerability and Exposure	22.60%
3.5-RL_SxL	Risk impact Level evaluation: Severity of consequences and Likelihood of occurrence	22.60%

Figure 89: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 3 following prioritisation for Pilot 3

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Table 137: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 4 based on prioritisation for Pilot 3

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
4.1-AL	Accessibility Level	16.79%
4.2-I&OL	Inclusiveness and Openness Level	12.06%
4.3-RT	Direct Revenue from Tourism (entry fees)	5.69%
4.4-IRT	Indirect Revenue through Tourism attraction	7.71%
4.5-IPV	Increased Property Value	5.63%
4.6-LJC	Number of Local Jobs Created	12.06%
4.7-IPI	Investment in Public Infrastructure	14.18%
4.8-CE	Cultural Enrichment	12.94%
4.9-PP	Public Perception	12.94%

Figure 90: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 4 following prioritisation for Pilot 3

A4.4 KPI Weights for Pilot 4 – Ave Sol Concert Hall in Riga, Latvia

Results obtained for Pilot 4. Ave Sol Concert Hall in Riga, Latvia

Table 138: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 1 based on prioritisation for Pilot 4

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
1.1-EP	Total energy intensity	10.85%
1.2-EP	Energy autonomy	1.77%
1.3-EP	Energy performance and operation	6.17%
1.4-EP	Response to the needs of occupants	11.97%
1.5-EP	Energy flexibility assessment	1.55%
1.1-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	24.20%
1.2-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	11.20%
1.3-IEQ	Air quality	22.79%
1.4-IEQ	Visual comfort	5.74%
1.5-IEQ	Acoustic comfort	3.76%

Figure 91: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 1 following prioritisation for Pilot 4

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Table 139: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 2 based on prioritisation for Pilot 4

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
2.1-TWC	Total Water Consumption	6.59%
2.2-GWP	Global Warming Potential	6.99%
2.3-OEC	Operational Energy Costs	24.94%
2.4-PBP	Payback Period	24.94%
2.5-LCC	Life Cycle Cost	24.94%
2.6-ECI	Energy Circularity Indicator	4.46%
2.7-WCI	Water Circularity Indicator	2.15%
2.8-MCI	Material Circularity Indicator	4.99%

Figure 92: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 2 following prioritisation for Pilot 4

Table 140: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 3 based on prioritisation for Pilot 4

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
3.1-IoH	Inventory of relevant Hazards	14.06%
3.2-HI	Hazards Identification	44.78%
3.3-RMP	Risk Management Plan(s)	7.56%
3.4-RI_VxE	Risk Impact assessment: Vulnerability and Exposure	22.43%
3.5-RL_SxL	Risk impact Level evaluation: Severity of consequences and Likelihood of occurrence	11.16%

Figure 93: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 3 following prioritisation for Pilot 4

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Table 141: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 4 based on prioritisation for Pilot 4

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
4.1-AL	Accessibility Level	3.96%
4.2-I&OL	Inclusiveness and Openness Level	4.35%
4.3-RT	Direct Revenue from Tourism (entry fees)	3.91%
4.4-IRT	Indirect Revenue through Tourism attraction	9.07%
4.5-IPV	Increased Property Value	13.40%
4.6-LJC	Number of Local Jobs Created	6.05%
4.7-IPI	Investment in Public Infrastructure	4.84%
4.8-CE	Cultural Enrichment	34.10%
4.9-PP	Public Perception	20.31%

Figure 94: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 4 following prioritisation for Pilot 4

A4.5 KPI Weights for Pilot 5 – Social residential building in Gdynia, Poland

Results obtained for Pilot 5. Social residential building in Gdynia, Poland

Table 142: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 1 based on prioritisation for Pilot 5

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
1.1-EP	Total energy intensity	10.10%
1.2-EP	Energy autonomy	3.12%
1.3-EP	Energy performance and operation	3.93%
1.4-EP	Response to the needs of occupants	6.23%
1.5-EP	Energy flexibility assessment	4.76%
1.1-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	22.34%
1.2-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	17.82%
1.3-IEQ	Air quality	16.47%
1.4-IEQ	Visual comfort	7.42%
1.5-IEQ	Acoustic comfort	7.82%

Figure 95: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 1 following prioritisation for Pilot 5

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Table 143: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 2 based on prioritisation for Pilot 5

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
2.1-TWC	Total Water Consumption	15.37%
2.2-GWP	Global Warming Potential	8.36%
2.3-OEC	Operational Energy Costs	22.88%
2.4-PBP	Payback Period	14.95%
2.5-LCC	Life Cycle Cost	8.62%
2.6-ECI	Energy Circularity Indicator	9.87%
2.7-WCI	Water Circularity Indicator	10.91%
2.8-MCI	Material Circularity Indicator	9.04%

Figure 96: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 2 following prioritisation for Pilot 5

Table 144: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 3 based on prioritisation for Pilot 5

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
3.1-IoH	Inventory of relevant Hazards	9.06%
3.2-HI	Hazards Identification	5.80%
3.3-RMP	Risk Management Plan(s)	19.84%
3.4-RI_VxE	Risk Impact assessment: Vulnerability and Exposure	32.65%
3.5-RL_SxL	Risk impact Level evaluation: Severity of consequences and Likelihood of occurrence	32.65%

Figure 97: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 3 following prioritisation for Pilot 5

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Table 145: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 4 based on prioritisation for Pilot 5

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
4.1-AL	Accessibility Level	29.30%
4.2-I&OL	Inclusiveness and Openness Level	17.97%
4.3-RT	Direct Revenue from Tourism (entry fees)	1.42%
4.4-IRT	Indirect Revenue through Tourism attraction	5.22%
4.5-IPV	Increased Property Value	13.34%
4.6-LJC	Number of Local Jobs Created	5.40%
4.7-IPI	Investment in Public Infrastructure	7.49%
4.8-CE	Cultural Enrichment	8.94%
4.9-PP	Public Perception	10.92%

Figure 98: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 4 following prioritisation for Pilot 5

A4.6 KPI Weights for Pilot 6 – Monastery ‘Nuestra Señora del Prado’ in Valladolid, Spain

Results obtained for Pilot 6. Monastery ‘Nuestra Señora del Prado’ in Valladolid, Spain

Table 146: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 1 based on prioritisation for Pilot 6

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
1.1-EP	Total energy intensity	9.49%
1.2-EP	Energy autonomy	1.99%
1.3-EP	Energy performance and operation	3.92%
1.4-EP	Response to the needs of occupants	11.23%
1.5-EP	Energy flexibility assessment	2.02%
1.1-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	20.32%
1.2-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	14.21%
1.3-IEQ	Air quality	17.01%
1.4-IEQ	Visual comfort	13.34%
1.5-IEQ	Acoustic comfort	6.45%

Figure 99: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 1 following prioritisation for Pilot 6

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Table 147: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 2 based on prioritisation for Pilot 6

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
2.1-TWC	Total Water Consumption	3.40%
2.2-GWP	Global Warming Potential	34.98%
2.3-OEC	Operational Energy Costs	29.12%
2.4-PBP	Payback Period	14.10%
2.5-LCC	Life Cycle Cost	6.08%
2.6-ECI	Energy Circularity Indicator	4.85%
2.7-WCI	Water Circularity Indicator	3.74%
2.8-MCI	Material Circularity Indicator	3.74%

Figure 100: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 2 following prioritisation for Pilot 6

Table 148: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 3 based on prioritisation for Pilot 6

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
3.1-IoH	Inventory of relevant Hazards	14.53%
3.2-HI	Hazards Identification	21.76%
3.3-RMP	Risk Management Plan(s)	49.23%
3.4-RI_VxL	Risk Impact assessment: Vulnerability and Exposure	5.17%
3.5-RL_SxL	Risk impact Level evaluation: Severity of consequences and Likelihood of occurrence	9.31%

Figure 101: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 3 following prioritisation for Pilot 6

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Table 149: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 4 based on prioritisation for Pilot 6

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
4.1-AL	Accessibility Level	9.72%
4.2-I&OL	Inclusiveness and Openness Level	19.44%
4.3-RT	Direct Revenue from Tourism (entry fees)	1.74%
4.4-IRT	Indirect Revenue through Tourism attraction	11.39%
4.5-IPV	Increased Property Value	2.89%
4.6-LJC	Number of Local Jobs Created	8.24%
4.7-IPI	Investment in Public Infrastructure	2.62%
4.8-CE	Cultural Enrichment	21.13%
4.9-PP	Public Perception	22.82%

Figure 102: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 4 following prioritisation for Pilot 6

A4.7 KPI Weights for Pilot 7 – City of Visby, UNESCO World Heritage Site, in Gotland, Sweden

Results obtained for Pilot 7. City of Visby, UNESCO World Heritage Site, in Gotland, Sweden

Table 150: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 1 based on prioritisation for Pilot 7

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
1.1-EP	Total energy intensity	10.51%
1.2-EP	Energy autonomy	2.51%
1.3-EP	Energy performance and operation	18.94%
1.4-EP	Response to the needs of occupants	8.41%
1.5-EP	Energy flexibility assessment	6.73%
1.1-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	11.47%
1.2-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	10.50%
1.3-IEQ	Air quality	10.50%
1.4-IEQ	Visual comfort	9.93%
1.5-IEQ	Acoustic comfort	10.50%

Figure 103: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 1 following prioritisation for Pilot 7

D3.2 Second INHERIT Assessment & Monitoring Framework

Table 151: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 2 based on prioritisation for Pilot 7

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
2.1-TWC	Total Water Consumption	8.95%
2.2-GWP	Global Warming Potential	11.63%
2.3-OEC	Operational Energy Costs	20.30%
2.4-PBP	Payback Period	8.83%
2.5-LCC	Life Cycle Cost	15.65%
2.6-ECI	Energy Circularity Indicator	13.86%
2.7-WCI	Water Circularity Indicator	14.48%
2.8-MCI	Material Circularity Indicator	6.31%

Figure 104: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 2 following prioritisation for Pilot 7

Table 152: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 3 based on prioritisation for Pilot 7

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
3.1-IoH	Inventory of relevant Hazards	7.27%
3.2-HI	Hazards Identification	28.32%
3.3-RMP	Risk Management Plan(s)	23.37%
3.4-RI_VxE	Risk Impact assessment: Vulnerability and Exposure	20.52%
3.5-RL_SxL	Risk impact Level evaluation: Severity of consequences and Likelihood of occurrence	20.52%

Figure 105: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 3 following prioritisation for Pilot 7

D3.2 Second INHERIT Assessment & Monitoring Framework

Table 153: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 4 based on prioritisation for Pilot 7

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
4.1-AL	Accessibility Level	15.42%
4.2-I&OL	Inclusiveness and Openness Level	19.32%
4.3-RT	Direct Revenue from Tourism (entry fees)	2.17%
4.4-IRT	Indirect Revenue through Tourism attraction	6.69%
4.5-IPV	Increased Property Value	9.42%
4.6-LJC	Number of Local Jobs Created	7.54%
4.7-IPI	Investment in Public Infrastructure	5.77%
4.8-CE	Cultural Enrichment	16.28%
4.9-PP	Public Perception	17.39%

Figure 106: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 4 following prioritisation for Pilot 7

A4.8 KPI Weights for Pilot 8 – Ahmet Piriştina İzmir City Archive and Museum (APIKAM) in İzmir, Turkey

Results obtained for Pilot 8. Ahmet Piriştina İzmir City Archive and Museum (APIKAM) in İzmir, Turkey

Table 154: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 1 based on prioritisation for Pilot 8

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
1.1-EP	Total energy intensity	11.59%
1.2-EP	Energy autonomy	3.52%
1.3-EP	Energy performance and operation	9.44%
1.4-EP	Response to the needs of occupants	6.35%
1.5-EP	Energy flexibility assessment	5.35%
1.1-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	15.40%
1.2-IEQ	Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	15.40%
1.3-IEQ	Air quality	15.40%
1.4-IEQ	Visual comfort	8.77%
1.5-IEQ	Acoustic comfort	8.77%

Figure 107: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 1 following prioritisation for Pilot 8

D3.2 Second INHERIT Assessment & Monitoring Framework

Table 155: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 2 based on prioritisation for Pilot 8

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
2.1-TWC	Total Water Consumption	15.65%
2.2-GWP	Global Warming Potential	18.15%
2.3-OEC	Operational Energy Costs	19.94%
2.4-PBP	Payback Period	9.07%
2.5-LCC	Life Cycle Cost	9.07%
2.6-ECI	Energy Circularity Indicator	9.07%
2.7-WCI	Water Circularity Indicator	9.07%
2.8-MCI	Material Circularity Indicator	9.97%

Figure 108: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 2 following prioritisation for Pilot 8

Table 156: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 3 based on prioritisation for Pilot 8

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
3.1-IoH	Inventory of relevant Hazards	12.36%
3.2-HI	Hazards Identification	12.36%
3.3-RMP	Risk Management Plan(s)	21.86%
3.4-RI_VxE	Risk Impact assessment: Vulnerability and Exposure	24.71%
3.5-RL_SxL	Risk impact Level evaluation: Severity of consequences and Likelihood of occurrence	28.71%

Figure 109: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 3 following prioritisation for Pilot 8

D3.2 Second INHERIT Assessment & Monitoring Framework

Table 157: Weight distribution of KPIs within Pillar 4 based on prioritisation for Pilot 8

	WEIGHTS Pillar prioritisation	
4.1-AL	Accessibility Level	22.91%
4.2-I&OL	Inclusiveness and Openness Level	17.36%
4.3-RT	Direct Revenue from Tourism (entry fees)	3.49%
4.4-IRT	Indirect Revenue through Tourism attraction	4.12%
4.5-IPV	Increased Property Value	4.89%
4.6-LJC	Number of Local Jobs Created	7.72%
4.7-IPV	Investment in Public Infrastructure	7.06%
4.8-CE	Cultural Enrichment	22.91%
4.9-PP	Public Perception	9.57%

Figure 110: Spider chart of KPIs weights within Pillar 4 following prioritisation for Pilot 8

Annex 5. Detailed datasheets of INHERIT Hub of measures

This annex contains the detailed datasheets for the 40 selected measures developed in the current phase of the INHERIT Hub of measures. These measures were chosen as a representative sample to test and refine the documentation process and provide a comprehensive overview of their applicability, technical characteristics, impact and associate costs. Each dataset follows the standardised template described in section 5.1 and includes information on application context, heritage compatibility and contribution to the INHERIT pillars. Together, they demonstrate the diversity and potential of interventions to support the sustainable modernisation of CH buildings.

The following index provides direct hyperlinks to each of the 40 measures included in this Annex, facilitating quick navigation through the detailed datasheets.

No se encontraron entradas de tabla de contenido.

FAÇADE EXTERNAL INSULATION

Exterior Thermal Insulation system to improve the energy efficiency of buildings by thermally insulating them from the outside.

APPLICATION

The main components are: Thermal insulation (XPS, EPS, mineral wool or polyurethane), Fastening system and Coating.

MEASURE GROUP

Insulation system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Façades and roofs.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

Approval of the administrative unit supervising the CH building. It is only possible if it does not disturb the former appearance of the façade, and it is possible to transfer the details to the finished insulation.

ADVANTAGES

- Improve energy efficiency.
- Moisture management.
- Maintenance reduction.
- Reduction of environmental impact.
- Improvement of thermal and noise comfort inside.

DISADVANTAGES

- Aesthetic and historical value impact.
- Technical difficulties and potential for damage.
- Cost considerations.

PHOTO ^[1]

LIMITATIONS

Regulatory and approval challenges.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

Medium.

VISUAL IMPACT

High.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

High.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

Low.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES ^[2]

	Thermal conductivity [W/(m*K)]	Density [kg/m ³]	Specific heat [kJ/(kg*K)]
EPS	0.029-0.041	18-50	1.25
XPS	0.030-0.04	25-45	1.45-1.70
PUR	0.022-0.046	30-100	1.30-1.45
PIR	0.018-0.028	30-45	1.4-1.5
Rock wool	0.029-0.042	40-200	0.8-1.0
Glass wool	0.031-0.037	13-100	0.9-1.0

The maximum thickness of the insulation will be subject to the regulations in force in each country/region. In urban areas, it must align with adjacent buildings. ^[3]

INSTALLATION DATA

Installation time [h/m²] | $\approx 1 - 2$ ^[4]

MAINTENANCE DATA

Type of maintenance	Inspections, cleaning and repairs.
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Lifespan [Years]	$\approx 30-50$ ^[5]
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OPERATION DATA

In order to implement this measurement, it is necessary to have the required permits.

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Total energy intensity	KPIs [kWh/m ² / year]
Heating energy intensity	
Cooling energy intensity	
Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	KPIs (%)
Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	

COSTS

INVESTMENTS ^{[6][7]}

The budget varies according to various factors, such as the type and thickness of the insulation, the adhesive used, the façade accessories (profiles, mouldings), the number of openings and the specific characteristics of the area where it is located. It is estimated that the total cost will be in the range of €65 to €250 per square metre.

SAVING ^[7]

Energy savings depend on the climatic zone where the building is located and the number of surfaces to which this measure is applied. However, it is estimated that it can lead to a total energy consumption reduction of 15% to 40%.

ROI

Each case should be considered individually. Too many variables to estimate the payback time.

OTHERS

PHASE

Design and renovation.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Insulation of the walls of a building can take place on the whole or part of the building.

REFERENCES

- [1] ArchDaily Mexico. (n.d.). *What is EIFS, or how to design an exterior thermal insulation system?* Retrieved from <https://www.archdaily.mx>
- [2] Amir Ali, Anas Issa and Ahmed Elshaer. (2024). *A Comprehensive Review and Recent Trends in Thermal Insulation Materials for Energy Conservation in Buildings*. Retrieved from <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/16/20/8782>
- [3] Normas urbanistas. Ordenanzas. https://www.malaga.eu/recursos/urbanismo/pgou_ap2/pgou_ad1/Documento%20C.%20Normativa,%20ordenanzas%20y%20fichas/2.%20Normas%20urbanisticas.%20Ordenanzas/TITULO%20XII.pdf
- [4] Official College of Quantity Surveyors and Architectural Technicians of Bizkaia. (2022). *Measurement and budgeting of an ETICS - Technical architecture professionals facing climate change*. Retrieved from <https://www.coaatbi.org/tecnicos-edificacion-ante-cambio-climatico/medicion-y-presupuestado-un-sate>
- [5] European Association for ETICS (EAE). (2023). *Long-term performance*. Retrieved from <https://www.ea-etics.com/etics/long-term-performance/>
- [6] Institute for Energy Diversification and Saving (IDAE). (2012). *Guide 002: External Thermal Insulation Systems (ETICS) for the Rehabilitation of Building Thermal Envelopes*. Retrieved from https://www.idae.es/uploads/documentos/documentos_12300_Guia_SATE_A2012_accesibles_edan_df06746b.pdf
- [7] Polytechnic University of Madrid. (2022). *Análisis experimental y simulación del comportamiento térmico del sistema de aislamiento por el exterior (SATE) en un edificio de viviendas rehabilitado: Caso de estudio en Madrid*. From https://oa.upm.es/72742/1/SHEILA_VARELA_LUJAN.pdf

FAÇADE INTERNAL INSULATION

ID #02

Interior Thermal Insulation system to improve the energy efficiency of buildings by thermally insulating them from the inside.

APPLICATION

This measure involves adding a layer of thermal insulation (XPS, EPS, PIR, mineral wool or polyurethane, cellulose, fiberboard) to the inner side of the wall. This layer is fixed using a fastening system and covered with plasterboard or wooden panels and coating. This intervention reduces the wall's thermal conductivity, improves the building's energy efficiency, and enhances indoor thermal comfort.

MEASURE GROUP

Insulation system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

Heading of Technical Inspections

Façades and roofs.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

Walls must be dry and free from mold or dirt to prevent moisture -related problems. Ensure good ventilation, ideally mechanical, to manage indoor moisture levels. Install a vapor barrier on the room side to stop moisture from entering the insulation layer. The insulation must meet local building regulations for thermal and moisture protection.

ADVANTAGES

- Preserves the building's external appearance.
- Quick installation.
- Low initial costs.
- Improved indoor comfort.
- Improved energy efficiency.

PHOTO ^[1]

- No impact on neighbours.
- It can be installed regardless of external weather conditions.

DISADVANTAGES

- Risk of condensation.
- Reduced room size.
- Thermal bridges.
- Limited thermal mass benefits.

LIMITATIONS

Nos suitable for:

- Buildings with high indoor humidity.
- Heritage buildings with restrictions on making internal modifications.
- Poorly ventilated spaces.
- Limited space.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

Medium.

VISUAL IMPACT

Medium.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

Medium.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

Medium.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

Example of the technical specifications of a wall with mineral wool thermal insulation. ^[2]

	Density [kg/m ³]	Thickness [mm]	Thermal Resistance [m ² K/W]
Base Wall			
Mansory brick	1943	348	0.58
Lime mortar	1243	10	0.02
Internal insulation			
Mineral wool	37	100	2.5
Vapour barrier	-	0.2	-
Gypsum board	850	13	0.07
Paint	-	-	-
Total			
		471.2	3.17

INSTALLATION DATA

Installation time [h/m ²]	Precise data on the duration of the installation is not available; however, it is estimated to vary between 0.5 and 1.
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MAINTENANCE DATA

Type of maintenance	Inspections, cleaning and repairs.
Useful life [Years]	≈ 20 - 30

OPERATION DATA

Before installing internal wall insulation, conduct a thorough assessment for moisture and structural damage. Prepare the surface by cleaning and repairing it and ensure the installation of vapor barriers to prevent condensation. Select appropriate insulation materials, organize the place of work, and gather necessary tools and equipment.

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Total energy intensity	KPIs [kWh/m ² / year]
Heating energy intensity	
Cooling energy intensity	
Energy autonomy	KPIs (%)
Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	KPIs (%)

Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	KPIs (%)
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COSTS

INVESTMENTS

The investment in the installation of interior insulation varies considerably depending on the type of insulation used, its thickness and the cost of labour, factors which depend on each country. According to a Spanish company ^[3] specialised in this type of installation, the price can range between 10 and 50 euros/m². However, Dutch sources ^[4] estimate a range of 100 to 130 euros/m².

SAVING ^[5]

If all external walls of the building are insulated, the energy demand can be reduced by 9% to 43% compared to the original (uninsulated) state. The exact percentage depends on factors such as the insulation material, wall thickness, climate conditions, and the overall energy efficiency of the building.

ROI

Each case should be considered individually. There are too many variables to estimate the payback time.

OTHERS

PHASE

Design and renovation.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Insulation of the walls of a building can take place overall or just part of the building.

REFERENCES

[1] County Insulation. (n.d.). Internal wall insulation - County insulation - Loft insulation installer, loft boarding services. Retrieved from <https://countyinsulation.co.uk/internal-wall-insulation/>

[2] Nickolaj Feldt Jensen. (2021) *Robust solutions for internal retrofitting solid masonry walls in historic buildings with regards to hygrothermal performance*. (Doctoral dissertation). Retrieved from [Phd thesis Nickolaj.pdf](#)

[3] Calor y Frío. (2024). *Cost of internal thermal insulation per square meter*. Retrieved from <https://presupuestos.caloryfrio.com/cuanto-cuesta-precios/precio-m2-aislamiento-termico-interior.html>

[4] Regelhulpen voor Bedrijven. (n.d.). *Cost estimates for businesses*. Retrieved from <https://regelhulpenvoorbedrijven.nl/kostenkentallen/>

[5] International Energy Agency – Solar Heating & Cooling Programme. (2018). *Energy savings due to internal facade insulation*. Retrieved from <https://w.iea-shc.org/Data/Sites/1/publications/Energy%20savings%20due%20to%20internal%20facade.pdf>

FAÇADE INTERMEDIATE INSULATION

ID #03

Injected cavity wall insulation improves thermal efficiency by filling the space between inner and outer walls with insulating materials. It is a safe and effective method, ideal for buildings constructed before the 1970s that lack proper insulation.

APPLICATION

Small holes are drilled in the exterior wall to inject materials such as cellulose, fiberglass, or mineral wool. This process is quick, minimally invasive, and reduces heat loss, optimizing energy consumption and indoor comfort.

MEASURE GROUP

Insulation system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

Heading of Technical Inspections

Façades and roofs.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

Stable walls, absence of moisture issues, proper ventilation availability, accessibility of installation, consent of the conservator in the case of heritage buildings.

ADVANTAGES

- Improved energy efficiency.
- Enhanced thermal comfort.
- Moisture and mold reduction.
- Operating cost savings.
- Quick installation.

DISADVANTAGES

- Risk of moisture condensation.
- Potential for structural damage.
- Potential incomplete insulation coverage and thermal bridges.

PHOTO [1]

LIMITATIONS

Regulatory and approval challenges in case CH buildings.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

Medium.

VISUAL IMPACT

Low.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

High.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

Low.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

	Thermal resistance [[m ² *K)/W]	Thermal transmittance [W/(m ² *K)]
EPS	2.6 - 3.3	0.030 - 0.038
PUR	3.6 - 4.5	0.022 - 0.028
Mineral wool	2.5 - 3.3	0.030 - 0.040
Natural fibres	3.5 - 4.5	0.22 - 0.29

GEOMETRY DATA

Depends on the dimensions of the wall to which it is applied (thickness of the air gap).

Thickness of air gap [mm]	30 – 100
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INSTALLATION DATA

Installation time [h]	≈ 2
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MAINTENANCE DATA

Type of maintenance	Inspections and repairs
Useful life [Years]	≈ 25 – 30

OPERATION DATA

In order to implement this measure, it is necessary to work with suitable insulation materials, tools, blowing equipment (if necessary) and ensure that the building is in good repair.

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

	KPIs [kWh/m ² /year]
Total energy intensity	KPIs [kWh/m ² /year]
Heating energy intensity	
Cooling energy intensity	
Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	KPIs (%)
Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	KPIs (%)

COSTS

INVESTMENT

The cost of injected cavity wall insulation ranges from 15 to 35 € (£13 - £30) per square metre but can vary depending on a number of factors. These include the size of the surface to be insulated, the type of material injected (such as foam or mineral wool), the condition of the cavities and the accessibility of the area, which can increase labour costs. In addition, professional installation fees also play a role, as experience is required to do the job properly, which can increase the total cost of the project.

SAVINGS

The installation of insulation significantly reduces heat loss, resulting in savings of up to 10% on energy costs.

ROI

Cavity wall insulation pays for itself over a period of 9 to 12 years, depending on the initial investment and the energy savings generated. With a service life of approximately 25 years, it ensures long-term economic and energy benefits, maximising the return on investment.

OTHERS

PHASE

Design and renovation.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Insulation of the walls of a building can take place overall or just part of the building.

REFERENCES

- [1] GreenMatch. (2024). *Retrofit cavity wall insulation*. Retrieved from <https://www.greenmatch.co.uk/insulation/walls/cavity/retrofit>
- [2] GreenMatch. (2024). *Injection cavity wall insulation*. Retrieved from <https://www.greenmatch.co.uk/insulation/walls/cavity/injection>
- [3] GreenMatch. (2024). *Cavity wall insulation cost*. Retrieved from <https://www.greenmatch.co.uk/insulation/walls/cavity/cost>

ROOF EXTERNAL INSULATION

ID #04

Waterproofing and Roof Insulation System to improve the energy efficiency of buildings.

APPLICATION

On pitched roofs, once the existing ceramic tile has been removed, a vapor barrier, a half sandwich panel (consisting of a waterproof particle board, an XPS core and a self-adhesive waterproofing membrane) is installed and the ceramic tile is reinstalled with polyurethane foam.

MEASURE GROUP

Insulation system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Façades and roofs.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

This measure modifies building envelope, so it may not apply to some CH sites with high protection level.

ADVANTAGES

- Waterproofing.
- Lightweight.
- Cost reduction.
- Reduction of energy consumption.

DISADVANTAGES AND LIMITATIONS

- Invasive.
- Additional weight.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

Low.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

Medium.

PHOTO

VISUAL IMPACT

High.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

High.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION ^{[1] [2] [3]}

TECHNICAL FEATURES

	Unit	Value
Generic property		
Thermal transmittance (U)	[W/m ² K]	[0.89 - 0.27]
Fire reaction		Class E
Insulation properties		
XPS Thickness	[mm]	[30 - 120]
Rock wool Thickness	[mm]	[60 - 140]
Tile properties		
Tile conductivity	[W/m K]	0,04
Vapour barrier film properties		
Length of vapour barrier film	[m]	[20 - 50]
Width of vapour barrier film	[mm]	1500

GEOMETRY DATA

Property	Unit	Value
Length (L)	[mm]	2000
Width (w)	[mm]	[950 - 1030]
Thickness (t)	[mm]	[2.6 - 2.4]
Wave Height (H)	[mm]	[36 - 24]
Wave Pass (P)	[mm]	[95 - 48]

INSTALLATION DATA

Installation time [h/m ²]	0,5
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MAINTENANCE DATA

Useful life [Years]	> 30
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IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Property	KPIs
Total energy intensity	[kWh/m ² /year]
Heating energy intensity	
Cooling energy intensity	
Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	KPIs (%)
Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	KPIs (%)

COSTS

INVESTMENTS ^[4]

This system is widely used in Spain due to the region's climatic conditions, providing an excellent solution for energy efficiency and protection against moisture. While specific data for other countries is not available, the average cost in the Spanish market is around 124 €/m².

SAVING

It is not possible to give an exact value because it depends very much on the type of building, climate, etc.

ROI

Each case should be considered individually. Too many variables to estimate the payback time.

OTHERS

PHASE

Design and Renovation.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

It can only be installed on the roof of a building.

REFERENCES

[1] Onduline. (2024). *SIATE Roof Onduline Catalog*. [PDF]. Retrieved on [access date], from

https://es.onduline.com/sites/onduline_es/files/2025-01/catalogo-siate-cubierta-onduline_2024.pdf

[2] Onduline. (2023). *Technical Sheet Onduline Bajo Teja DRS BT-190*. [PDF]. Retrieved on [access date], from https://es.onduline.com/sites/onduline_es/files/2023-06/ft-onduline-bajo-teja-drs-bt-190_0.pdf

[3] Onduline. (2024). *Onduline Bajo Teja DRS Catalog*. [PDF]. Retrieved on [access date], from https://es.onduline.com/sites/onduline_es/files/2024-05/Catalogo%20Onduline%20Bajo%20Teja%20DRS_1.pdf

[4] Generador de Precios. (n.d.). *SIATE ONDULINE System for Waterproofing Sloped Roofs*. Retrieved on [access date], from https://www.generadordeprecios.info/obra_nueva/Cubiertas/Inclinadas/Sistemas_de_tejados/QTX120_Sistema_SIATE_ONDULINE_de_imperme.html

NATURAL LIGHTING PRIORITISATION

ID #08

Prioritize natural light over artificial light. This measure leads to reduction in energy consumption and increased visual comfort.

APPLICATION

One technique for optimising the use of daylight is daylight control. This method uses sensors and control systems to reduce or switch off artificial lighting when there is sufficient ambient light.

Another technique could be the strategic placement of mirrors to reflect natural light into darker areas of the building.

MEASURE GROUP

Window system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Façades and roofs.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

Careful designs for as windows and skylights.

ADVANTAGES^[4]

- Energy saving for electrical lighting.
- Increasing visual comfort.

DISADVANTAGES

- Sensitive works of art may be damaged by exposure to light.^[3]
- Risk of glare and reflections.

LIMITATIONS

Natural light can damage works of art and wall murals.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

PHOTO^[3]

VISUAL IMPACT

Medium.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

Medium.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

Low.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION^[5]

In this measure, basic methods are proposed to prioritise natural light, due to the strict restrictions governing CH buildings. However, it should be noted that there are other techniques that pursue the same objective:

- Glass prisms and blinds.
- Sun-shading mirror elements.
- Light shelf.
- Glazing with reflective profiles.
- Revolving louvres.
- Solar control glass.
- Solar tube.
- Prismatic panels.

- Transparent light protection system with Holographic Optical Elements.
- Integrated anidolic system.
- Heliostat.

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Total energy intensity	KPIs [kWh/m ² /year]
Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	KPIs (%)
Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	
Visual comfort	

COSTS

INVESTMENT - SAVING - ROI

It is difficult to define the investment, savings, and ROI for this measure due to its ambiguous nature. For more information on installing a control system, refer to measure #22 in this catalog.

OTHERS

PHASE

Design and Renovation.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

All the building.

REFERENCES

[1] Mayorga Pinilla, M. F., & Álvarez, J. L. (2016). Advanced daylighting evaluation applied to cultural heritage buildings and museums: Application to the cloister of Santa Maria El Paular. *Renewable Energy*, 85, 1362–1370. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0960148115301075>

[2] Balocco, C., & Calzolari, R. (2008). Natural light design for an ancient building:

A case study. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 12(6), 1601–1613. Retrieved from [Natural light design for an ancient building: A case study - ScienceDirect](#)

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WINDOWS WITH A LOW EMISSIVITY FILM

ID #11

The use of low-emissivity filming windows helps to reduce heat loss, thereby improving the energy efficiency of a building. By maintaining more stable indoor temperatures throughout the year, these windows provide greater thermal comfort for occupants.

APPLICATION

Once the glass surface has been properly cleaned, the coating will be applied, ensuring uniform coverage across the entire area.

MEASURE GROUP

Window system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Façades & Roofs.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

If this intervention is to be carried out on a building with a certain level of heritage protection, it is essential to obtain approval in accordance with current regulations, as well as authorization from a committee of experts. Additionally, it must be verified that the measure does not compromise the historical or architectural value of the element.

ADVANTAGES

- Non-intrusive.
- Improved thermal comfort.
- Reduce heat loss through glazed areas.
- Reduce the energy consumption of the building.

PHOTO ^[1]

DISADVANTAGES

- High cost.
- Long payback periods.

LIMITATIONS

The incorporation of this film may affect the cultural value and original aesthetics of the window.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

Medium.

VISUAL IMPACT

Low.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

Low.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

Medium.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES ^[2]

	U [W/m ² K]	G (SHGC)
SINGE PANE		
No film	5.9	0.82
TCC 75	3.6	0.53
DOUBLE PANE		
No film	2.6	0.7
TCC 75	2	0.51

A study shows that this measure can reduce heat loss through windows by 36% during the heating season, and decrease heat gain through windows by 35% during the cooling season. ^[1]

GEOMETRY DATA ^{[3][4]}

Thickness [μm]	75
Width [m]	30.5
Height [mm]	1520

INSTALLATION DATA

Installation time	No precise information is available regarding the installation time. However, it is estimated to take approximately 0.5 hours.
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MAINTENANCE DATA

Type of maintenance	Regular cleaning of surfaces.
Lifespan [Years]	30

OPERATION DATA

In order to implement this measurement, it is necessary to have the required permits.

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Total energy intensity	KPIs [kWh/m ² /year]
Heating energy intensity	
Cooling energy intensity	
Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	KPIs (%)
Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	

COSTS

INVESTMENTS ^[5]

Costs may vary depending on the retailer and installer. The company Windowtreat estimates a cost ranging from £150 to £200 per m², which corresponds approximately to €175–235 per m².

SAVING

No specific data is available regarding the economic savings associated with the installation of low-emissivity films.

ROI ^[1]

In some case studies, the payback period is estimated to be approximately 30 years.

OTHERS

PHASE

Design and Renovation.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

All windows.

REFERENCES

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WINDOW WITH DOUBLE GLAZING (ARGON GAS)

ID #15

This type of window incorporates an argon gas chamber between the glass panes. Argon has lower thermal conductivity and higher density than air, resulting in reduced thermal transmittance and improved acoustic insulation.

APPLICATION

Replacement of the original window with a new unit incorporating an argon gas-filled chamber. This measure involves a complete window replacement, as the original frames may be incompatible with the increased thickness of the new glazing. Additionally, it is essential to ensure proper sealing to maintain the integrity of the gas chamber.

MEASURE GROUP

Window system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Façades and roofs.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

This measure can be applied to windows with no conservation value.

ADVANTAGES ^[2]

- Reduce heat transfer through windows.
- Reduced energy consumption for heating and cooling.
- Increased thermal comfort for the occupants.
- Prevent condensation problems.

DISADVANTAGES

- Loss of historical integrity.
- High cost.

PHOTO ^[1]

LIMITATIONS

Space for carpentries.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

Medium.

VISUAL IMPACT

High.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

High.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

Low.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES ^[3]

ARGON CHAMBER GLASS					
COMPOSITION Double glazing	4/6/4	4/8/4	4/10/4	4/12/4	4/16/4
U [(Wm ² *K)]	3,3	3,1	3,0	2,9	2,7
LOW-EMISSIVITY LAMINATED GLASS					
COMPOSITION A normal glass and a low-e glass. e ≤ 0,03	4/6/4	4/8/4	4/10/4	4/12/4	4/16/4
U [(Wm ² *K)]	2,5	2,1	1,8	1,7	1,5

Thermal transmittance (U) [(m ² *K)/W]	[3,3 – 2,7]
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Thermal transmittance with a low emissivity film (U) [(m ² *K)/W]	[2,5 - 1,5]
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GEOMETRY DATA ^[3]

Defining the geometry of a window can be complex, as it must comply with the specific requirements of the opening. However, certain parameters, such as the thickness of the glass and the argon gas chamber, are standardized.

Glass Thickness [mm]	[4 - 12]
Argon chamber thickness [mm]	[6 - 20]

INSTALLATION DATA

Installation time [h]	[3 - 8]
-----------------------	---------

MAINTENANCE DATA

Type of maintenance	Regular cleaning of surfaces.
Lifespan [Years]	Its estimated lifespan with optimal thermal performance is between 20 and 30 years. After this time, its insulating properties may gradually diminish. However, its basic function as a window remains unaffected.

OPERATION DATA

In order to implement this measurement, it is necessary to have the required permits.

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Total energy intensity	KPIs [kWh/m ² /year]
Heating energy intensity	
Cooling energy intensity	
Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	KPIs (%)
Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	

COSTS

INVESTMENTS

The cost depends on the brand and model. If an aesthetic replica of the original joinery is required, this will increase the overall price. For a standard window with double glazing (4 mm glass) and a 16 mm argon gas chamber, the price in Spain is approximately €50.

OTHERS

PHASE

Design and Renovation.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Windows with no conservation value.

REFERENCES

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SUN PROTECTION

ID #18

Use energy-efficient sun protection for the cultural heritage building to reduce solar heat gain and protect materials from UV radiation damage. This can also help regulate the building's heat comfort.

APPLICATION

This can be achieved in two ways: first, outdoors, by using architectural elements such as fixed or retractable awnings, which extend the roof line to create shade, or by integrating vegetation into the environment to provide solar shading; and second, indoors, by installing movable blinds or shades, or by applying UV-filtering window films.

MEASURE GROUP

Shadow system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Façades and roofs.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

It may not apply to some CH sites with high protection level. The installations risk damaging the cultural heritage value of the building and/or its surroundings.

ADVANTAGES

- Reduce the indoor temperature due to the shading effect.
- Reduce cooling consumption in summer.
- Dampen or deflect wind.

DISADVANTAGES

- Obstruction of views.
- Changes in aesthetics.
- Blockage of natural light.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

Low.

PHOTO

VISUAL IMPACT

High.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

High.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

Low.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

INSTALLATION DATA

Installation time of roller shutters [h]	[0.5 - 3]
Awning installation time [h]	[2 - 8]
Vegetation installation time [day]	[1 - 2]

MAINTENANCE DATA

Type of maintenance (Awning / Roller Shutter)	Clean every 6 - 12 [months]
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IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Cooling energy intensity	KPIs [kWh/m ² /year]
Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	KPIs (%)

COSTS

INVESTMENTS

The investment varies significantly depending on the chosen solar protection system. Additionally, for awnings and shutters, there is a wide range of prices, as the cost may change based on the type of operation system. Similarly, with vegetation, the cost can vary depending on the type of tree species, as it may be more or less dense.

SAVINGS - ROI

Since these are passive energy efficiency measures, it is difficult to establish a specific percentage of cost savings or the payback period.

OTHERS

PHASE

Design and Renovation.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

It is possible to install a shutter for each window, add an awning, or place vegetation near the façade.

REFERENCES

[1] BIU. *Arquitectura y paisaje. La vegetación reduce la temperatura junto a los edificios.* Retrieved from <https://biuarquitectura.com/2012/04/13/la-vegetacion/>

[2] Akira Hoyano. (1988). Climatological uses of plants for solar control and the effects on the thermal environment of a

building. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378778888900357>

LED LIGHTING

ID #19

Change incandescent, fluorescents or halogen lamps by LED lamps and replacement of concert lights/spotlights.

APPLICATION

This is a measure feasible regardless the level of protection of the building and with low technical requirements.

MEASURE GROUP

Lighting system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

Pillar 2: Resource & Circularity.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Installations.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

It is important that the electrical installation is in good condition and that the lamps do not have a significant cultural value.

ADVANTAGES

- Reduce energy consumption.
- Reduce economic costs.
- Increase visual comfort.

DISADVANTAGES

Cost of initial investment.

LIMITATIONS

The original lamp may not be compatible with LED fixtures.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

VISUAL IMPACT

Low.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

Low.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

High.

PHOTO ^[1]

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES ^{[2][3]}

Efficacy [lm/W]	[70 - 150]
Colour temperature [K]	[2700 – 8000]
Colour rendering [Ra]	[65 -93]
Efficiency (%)	≈ 80

INSTALLATION DATA

Installation time [h]	≈ 0.5 [h/lamp]
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MAINTENANCE DATA ^[3]

Type of maintenance	Cleaning and visual inspection
Lifespan [h]	[25000 – 75000]

OPERATION DATA

In order to perform this measurement, it is necessary to have an electrical installation.

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Total energy intensity	KPIs
Lighting Energy Intensity	[kWh/m ² /year]

Visual Comfort	KPIs (%)
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PILLAR 2 KPIs: Resource Efficiency, Circularity and LCC

Global Warning Potential	KPIs [kgCO ₂ eq/m ² /year]
Life Cycle Cost	KPIs [€/m ² /year]

COSTS ^[4]

INVESTMENTS

The final cost of the investment depends on the power of the luminaire, the brand and the number of units. Additionally, if they are to be installed at a considerable height, it may be necessary to utilise equipment such as cranes. The estimated cost of the equipment is between €2.8 and €4.7 per LED light bulb.

SAVING

The average savings in energy consumption by using LED lights instead of fluorescent lights can range from 50% to 80%.

ROI

The payback period varies according to the initial investment and savings. However, it is generally stipulated between 2 and 3 years.

OTHERS

PHASE

Monitoring, Operation and Management.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Installation can be carried out at different levels: only in some rooms, on specific floors or in the whole building.

REFERENCES

[1] Lyco. (2021). *What is LED? A beginner's guide to LED lighting*. Retrieved from

<https://www.lyco.co.uk/advice/what-is-led-a-beginners-guide-to-led-lighting/>

[2] U.S. Department of Energy. *LED basics*. Office of Energy Efficiency & Renewable Energy. Retrieved from <https://www.energy.gov/eere/ssl/led-basics>

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[4] European Commission, Joint Research Centre. (2020). *Energy-efficient lighting – JRC Science for Policy Report*. Retrieved from <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC122760>

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LIGHTING SENSOR

ID #20

A lighting sensor monitors the number of lumens in a room to verify compliance with regulations and ensure uniform, indirect lighting.

APPLICATION

It is a measure feasible regardless the protection level of the building and with low technical requirements.

MEASURE GROUP

Lighting system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

Pillar 2: Resource & Circularity.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Installations.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

It requires access to the building's electrical system.

ADVANTAGES

Possibility of integration with a lighting control system for:

- Reduce energy consumption.
- Increase visual comfort.
- Extended lamp life.

DISADVANTAGES

Need for regular adjustment and calibration.

LIMITATIONS

Compatible with existing electrical systems, especially older installations or complex building automation systems.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

VISUAL IMPACT

Low.

PHOTO ^[1]

PHYSICAL IMPACT

Low.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

High.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES ^[2] ^[3]

Type of sensor	Photoresistor / Photodiode / Phototransistors
Measurement Range [lux]	[0.1 - 100.000]
Types of daylighting	Switched / Bi-level / Continuous
Control strategy	Manual switching/ Presence - Occupant detection / Daylight harvesting / Constant illuminance.

INSTALLATION DATA ^[4]

It depends on the complexity of the electrical installation. The typical installation time is 0.26h/sensor.

MAINTENANCE DATA

Type of maintenance	Regular basic cleaning, visual inspection.
Lifespan [Years]	Typical sensor lifetime: 10-15

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Lighting energy intensity	KPIs [kWh/m ² /year]
Energy performance & operation	KPIs (SRI score)
Response to the needs of occupants	
Energy flexibility assessment	KPIs (%)
Visual comfort	

PILLAR 2 KPIS: Resource Efficiency, Circularity and LCC

Global Warming Potential	KPIs [kgCO ₂ eq/m ² /year]
Life Cycle Cost	KPIs [€/m ² /year]

COSTS

INVESTMENTS ^{[4][5]}

Due to the wide range of models and brands available, it's difficult to determine an exact average price. However, the cost per sensor typically ranges between 30 and 60 euros.

SAVINGS - ROI

This technology is utilized for the measurement of lux, thus not being associated with direct savings or a payback period. However, should a lighting control system be implemented that regulates the power based on this measurement, it could generate significant savings.

OTHERS

PHASE

Monitoring, Operation and Management.
Design and renovation.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Installation can be carried out at different levels: only in some rooms, on specific floors or in the whole building.

REFERENCES

- [1] Blebox. *LuxSensor*. Retrieved from <https://blebox.eu/en/product/luxsensor/>
- [2] Kaminska, A., & Ozadowicz, A. (2018). Lighting control including daylight and energy efficiency improvements analysis. *Energies*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.3390/en11082166>
- [3] Brambley MR, et al. (2005). Advanced sensors and controls for building applications: Market assessment and potential R&D pathways. Pacific Northwest National Laboratory: prepared for U.S. Department of Energy.
- [4] Generador de Precios. Interruptor crepuscular. Retrieved from https://generadordeprecios.info/obra_nueva/Instalaciones/Iluminacion/Sistemas_de_control_y_regulacion/Interruptor_crepuscular.html
- [5] El Instalador Electricista. Sensor de luz vía Wi-Fi. Retrieved from <https://www.elinstaladorelectricista.es/domotica-facil-para-profesionales-/4498-sensor-de-de-luz-via-wi-fi-.html>
- [6] Lutron. Daylight sensor design and application guide.

OCCUPANCY SENSORS

ID #21

It is a device that detects the presence or movement of people or objects within a defined area. It is commonly used in security systems, automated lighting, and home automation. Its primary function is to trigger a response—such as turning on a light or activating an alarm—upon detecting motion. Occupancy sensors can be installed in specific areas to control lighting and HVAC systems based on the number of occupants, improving energy efficiency and comfort.

APPLICATION

It is a measure feasible regardless of the protection level of the building and with low technical requirements.

MEASURE GROUP

Control system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

Pillar 2: Resources & Circularity.

Pillar 4: Accessibility & Inclusiveness.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Installations.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

It requires access to the building's electrical and HVAC system. Installation should be done by qualified personnel with knowledge of building automation and control systems.

ADVANTAGES

Possibility of integration with a lighting and HVAC control system:

- Reduce energy consumption.
- Enhanced convenience and comfort for occupants.
- Potential for integration with other building management systems.

PHOTO

DISADVANTAGES

- False positives or negatives, incorrectly activating or deactivating systems.
- If it is not connected to any control system, it is practically a movement detector.

LIMITATIONS

Compatibility with existing electrical and control systems.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

VISUAL IMPACT

Low.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

Low.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

High.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

Type of sensor	PIR / Ultrasonic / Dual
Detection Area [°]	90-360°
Detection Distance [m]	5-20
Delay time	Adjustable (10s - 30 min)
Connection	Wired/Wireless

INSTALLATION DATA

It depends on the complexity of the electrical installation. Typical installation time is 0.2 [h/sensor].

MAINTENANCE DATA

Type of maintenance	Cleaning, visual inspection.
Lifespan [Years]	10-15

OPERATION DATA

- Requires continuous power supply.
- Regular monitoring of sensor performance.

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Total Energy Intensity	KPIs [kWh/m ² /year]
Heating Energy Intensity	
Cooling Energy Intensity	
Lighting Energy Intensity	
Visual Comfort	KPIs (%)

PILLAR 2 KPIS: Resource Efficiency, Circularity and LCC

Global Warming Potential	KPIs [kgCO ₂ eq/m ² /year]
Life Cycle Cost	[€/m ² / year]

PILLAR 4 KPIS: Accessibility & Inclusiveness

Accessibility level	KPIs (%)
Inclusiveness and openness level	KPIs (-)
Public perception	KPIs (%)

COSTS

INVESTMENTS ^[2]

The investment in occupancy sensors depends on the type of sensor and the systems they control (HVAC, lighting). In the case of lighting control by occupancy sensor, the cost is 81.40 - 250 [€ / sensor].

SAVING ^[3]

The energy saving for the use of occupancy sensors to control lighting system is approximately 25-50% for lighting consumption (depending on the type of space).

ROI ^[3]

Depending on the size of the installation and local energy costs, the payback period is typically between 1 and 3 years.

OTHERS

PHASE

Monitoring, Operation and Management.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Installation can be carried out at different levels: only in some rooms, on specific floors or in the whole building.

REFERENCES

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<https://azollasoftware.com/occupancy-management-iot-sensors-for-facilities-management/>

LIGHTING CONTROLS

ID #22

Lighting controls are systems designed to optimise energy use by enabling features such as adjustable intensity, scheduling, and occupancy sensors to automate lighting. These controls enhance energy efficiency and provide greater flexibility in managing lighting to suit the needs of the space.

APPLICATION

Applicable to all protection levels with minimal technical requirements.

MEASURE GROUP

Lighting system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

Pillar 2: Resource & Circularity.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Functional behaviour.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

It requires access to the building's electrical system.

ADVANTAGES

- Lighting energy savings.
- Increased luminaire life.
- Increase visual comfort.

DISADVANTAGES

Specialized knowledge for installation, programming and maintenance.

LIMITATIONS

Users may override or manipulate settings.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

VISUAL IMPACT

Low.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

Low.

PHOTO ^[1]

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

High.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

At least one of the following:

- Occupancy sensor.
- Lighting sensor.
- Schedule control.

INSTALLATION DATA

It depends on the complexity of the electrical installation. Typical installation time for sensor is:

Occupancy sensors (h / sensor)	0.20 ^[2]
Lighting sensors (h / sensor)	0.26 ^[3]

MAINTENANCE DATA

Type of maintenance	Cleaning, inspection and calibration.	visual and
Control Lifespan [Years]	There is no precise information on this. But it may be around 10 - 15 depending on the manufacturer.	

OPERATION DATA

- Centralized control via BMS or standalone apps.
- Real-time tracking integrated with BMS.

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Lighting intensity	energy	KPIs [kWh/m ² /year]
Energy performance & operation		KPIs (SRI score)
Response to the needs of occupants		
Energy flexibility assessment	flexibility	
Visual comfort		KPIs (%)

PILLAR 2 KPIS: Resource Efficiency, Circularity and LCC

Global Warming Potential		KPIs [kg CO ₂ eq/m ² /year]
Life Cycle Cost		KPIs [€/m ² /year]

COSTS

INVESTMENT

Depending on several factors: climatic conditions, orientation building, shading, the complexity of the installation and the type of control: use of light/occupancy sensors:

- Occupancy sensor: 81.4 – 250 €/sensor^[2]
- Lighting sensor: 55.75 €/sensor^[3].

SAVINGS

Sensor technology can reduce lighting consumption by 20–30%. Light sensors alone achieve savings of over 20% in 39% of cases, while only 8% exceed 30%, showing varying effectiveness based on conditions. Combining lighting and occupancy sensors enhances efficiency, ensuring savings above 20% in all cases and over 30% in 74% of cases. This highlights the advantages of

integrating multiple sensors to optimize energy use.

ROI
N/A.

OTHERS

PHASE

Monitoring, Operation and Management.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Installation can be carried out at different levels: only in some rooms, on specific floors or in the whole building.

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DISTRICT HEATING SYSTEM

ID #23

District heating networks offer great potential for efficient, cost-effective and flexible large-scale use of low-carbon energy for heating.

APPLICATION

The main components are heat exchanger station, primary heat network connection, internal distribution system, control and regulation systems, and monitoring and metering devices.

MEASURE GROUP

HVAC system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Installations.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

It is necessary to notify the construction works or obtain a building permit based on the connection project to the network. The project should be prepared in accordance with the connection conditions received from the network operator.

ADVANTAGES

- Energy efficiency.
- Environmental benefits.
- Cost savings.
- Reliability and stability.
- Reduced maintenance.
- Space savings.
- Increased comfort.

DISADVANTAGES

- Initial investment costs.
- Dependence on the supplier.
- Limited control.
- Heat loss in distribution.

PHOTO ^[5]

DISADVANTAGES

- Potential for price increases.
- Complexity of system changes.

LIMITATIONS

- Availability of infrastructure.
- Dependence on the provider.
- Infrastructure limitations.
- Regulatory and administrative barriers.
- Technical compatibility.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

VISUAL IMPACT

Low.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

High.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

Low.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES ^[1]

	Low scale	Large scale
Supply Temperature [°C]	[70 - 90]	[80 - 130]
Operating Pressure [bar]	[4 - 10]	[16 - 25]
Heat Loss in Pipes [%]	[8 - 15]	-

INSTALLATION DATA

Installation time	Depending on the scale of the system, installation times may range from several weeks to several months
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MAINTENANCE DATA

Type of maintenance	Inspections, servicing, repairs, condition and data monitoring
Useful life	As the system consists of multiple components, it is difficult to determine an exact service life. However, it is estimated to last over 20 years.

OPERATION DATA

In order to perform this measurement, it is necessary to have required permits.

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Total energy intensity	KPIs [kWh/m ² / year]
Heating energy intensity	
Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	KPIs (%)

COSTS

INVESTMENTS

- Small Connection (single - family home): 2,000 - 10,000 €.
- Medium Connection (multi - family building): 10,000 - 50,000 €.
- Large Connection (commercial or industrial complex): 50,000 - 500,000 € or more.

SAVING

The savings associated with the installation of this measure are unknown.

ROI

Each case should be considered individually. Too many variables to estimate the payback time.

OTHERS

PHASE

Design and renovation.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

The system can be implemented at a small scale, with capacities ranging from 1 to 5 MW, targeting building blocks or neighborhoods. At a large scale, exceeding 10 MW, it is designed to serve entire cities.

REFERENCES

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- [4] Schmidt, D., Kallert, A., Blesl, M., Svendsen, S., Li, H., Nord, N., & Sipilä, K. (2017). Low temperature district heating for future energy systems. *Energy Procedia*, 116, 26–38.
- [5] Izquierdo, D. (2019) District Heating urbano como alternativa de calefacción. Retrieved from <https://www.construction21.org/espana/articles/h/district-heating-urbano-como-alternativa-de-calefaccion.html>

HEATPUMP – DIRECT EXPANSION

ID #26

Climate control system based on heat pump technology. The refrigerant directly exchanges heat with the indoor and outdoor air, without an intermediate hydraulic circuit. It supports both heating and cooling modes.

APPLICATION

Suitable for individual climate control in residential units, offices, retail spaces, and light commercial environments. Ideal for projects requiring quick installation, localized air treatment, and systems with limited space or no access to water-based infrastructure. Compatible with air-to-air direct expansion heat pump systems in split, multisplit, or compact configurations.

MEASURE GROUP

HVAC system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

Pillar 2: Resources & Circularity.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Installations.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

Approval of the administrative unit supervising the CH building. Only possible if it does not disturb the former appearance of the façade.

ADVANTAGES

- Energy efficiency.
- Environmentally friendly.
- Heating and cooling in one system.
- Low maintenance.
- Long lifespan.

DISADVANTAGES

- High initial cost.

PHOTO

- Efficiency drops in cold climates.
- Electricity dependence.
- Lower heating output.
- Noise.
- Space requirement.

LIMITATIONS

- Lack of space.
- Bad technical condition of the building.
- Legal regulations.
- For bigger system: available capacity on the electrical grid.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

VISUAL IMPACT

Medium.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

High.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

Medium.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

These are highly dependent on the building size and the choice between a centralized or room/floor-level system. For example the model Daikin 4MXXM52A:

Coefficient of Performance	≈ [4.53 - 4.28]
Seasonal Coefficient of Performance	4.61
Heating Capacity [kW]	6.8
Power Consumption [kW]	≈ [1.5 – 1.59]
Noise Level [dB]	47

GEOMETRY DATA

Hot Water Tank Capacity [l]	150 - 300
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INSTALLATION DATA

Installation time [h]	≈ 8 - 80
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MAINTENANCE DATA

Type of maintenance	Inspections, cleaning and repairs
Useful life [Years]	≈ 10-25

OPERATION DATA

In order to perform this measure, it is necessary to have the required permits.

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Total energy intensity	KPIs [kWh/m ² / year]
Heating energy intensity	
Cooling energy intensity	
Energy autonomy	KPIs (%)
Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	KPIs (%)
Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	KPIs (%)

PILLAR 2 KPIS: Resource Efficiency, Circularity and LCC

Global Warming Potential	KPIs [kg CO ₂ eq/m ² /year]
Operational Energy Costs	KPIs [€/m ² /year]
Life Cycle Cost	
Energy Circularity Indicator	KPIs (%)

COSTS

INVESTMENTS ^[1]

In commercial systems, costs typically range from €5,000 to €15,000, while residential units usually cost between €1,500 and €5,000.

SAVING

Although there are no sources that specify the exact savings, it is estimated that energy consumption can be reduced by approximately 30%, resulting in corresponding cost savings.

ROI

Each case should be considered individually. Too many variables to estimate the payback time.

OTHERS

PHASE

Design and renovation.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

It can be implemented in residential units, offices, retail spaces, and light commercial environments.

REFERENCES

[1] Energian. (n.d.). *Daikin air-to-air heating, cooling and hot water heat pump system for 2-bedroom houses/bungalows*. Retrieved from <https://www.energian.co.uk/>

[2] Intuis. *What is the price of a heat pump?* Retrieved from <https://intuis.fr/en/info/what-is-the-price-of-a-heat-pump>

RECONSTRUCTION OF THE HEATING SYSTEM AND THERMOSTAT FOR CONTROL OF HEATING ACCORDING TO SYSTEM SCHEDULING

ID #29

Complete reconstruction of the heating system. Replacing all radiators and considering the possibility of building an infrared heating system, so that the entire volume of the room does not have to be heated. Possibilities to create heating in different zones with effective adjustment options. Control Thermostat system scheduling.

APPLICATION

System assessment and upgrade, thermostat installation, schedule automation, energy savings, remote control.

MEASURE GROUP

HVAC system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

Pillar 2: Resources & Circularity.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Functional Behavior.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

Technical compatibility, possibility to create effective zoning due to building conditions and obtaining necessary permits or certifications.

ADVANTAGES

- Energy efficiency.
- Cost savings.
- Automation and convenience.
- Environmental benefits.

PHOTO

DISADVANTAGES

- High initial costs.
- Complex installation.
- System compatibility issues.
- Maintenance and repairs.
- Security concerns.

LIMITATIONS

- Dependence on Internet Connectivity.
- Limited Zone Control.
- Sensor Limitations.
- Software Dependence.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

VISUAL IMPACT

Low.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

High.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

Medium.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

Temperature Control Range [°C]	5-30
Efficiency [%]	≈ 100

INSTALLATION DATA

Installation time [h]	≈ 12 -24h
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MAINTENANCE DATA

Type of maintenance	Regular inspections, monitoring, firmware updates, app management, calibration and system optimization.
Useful life [Years]	≈ 5-20

OPERATION DATA

To perform this measurement, it is essential to install appropriate sensors and monitoring devices throughout the heating system, ensuring accurate data collection and real-time analysis of temperature, energy consumption, and system performance.

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Total energy intensity	KPIs [kWh/m ² /year]
Heating energy intensity	
Energy performance and operation	KPIs (-)
Response to the needs of occupants	
Energy flexibility assessment	
Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	KPIs (%)

PILLAR 2 KPIS: Resource Efficiency, Circularity and LCC

Total Water Consumption	KPIs Residential: [m ³ /occupant/ year] Non-residential: [m ³ /m ² /year]
Operational Energy costs	KPIs [€/m ² /year]

COSTS

INVESTMENTS ^{[1] [2]}

The total cost of implementing a heating panel system typically ranges from approximately €3,000 to €20,000, depending on the scale and specific requirements of the installation. Heating panels themselves are priced between €120

and €600 per unit. Installation costs are estimated at around €90 per square meter. Additionally, a control thermostat system ranges from €140 to €270, depending on the make and model selected, with installation costs for the thermostat system varying between €40 and €100.

SAVING

Although there are no sources that specify the exact savings, it is estimated that energy consumption can be reduced by approximately 10–30%, resulting in corresponding cost savings. Infrared heaters are highly efficient, converting nearly 100% of the electricity they consume into usable heat, which contributes significantly to these reductions.

ROI

Each case should be considered individually. Too many variables to estimate the payback time.

OTHERS

PHASE

Design and renovation.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

The classification of system scale is typically based on the size and type of the building:

Small Scale	Residential
Medium Scale	Larger Residences or Small Commercial
Large Scale	Commercial and Institutional

REFERENCES

- [1] Checktrade. (2023). *Infrared heating cost*. Retrieved from <https://www.checktrade.com/blog/cost-guides/infrared-heating-cost/>
- [2] Checktrade. (2024.). *Cost of a smart thermostat in 2024*. Retrieved from <https://www.checktrade.com/blog/cost-guides/cost-smart-thermostat/>

HEAT RECOVERY

ID #31

Heat recovery is a system that recaptures heat from exhaust air and uses it to precondition incoming air during ventilation. This reduces the energy needed for cooling and heating, enhancing overall efficiency.

APPLICATION

Heat recovery systems are installed between exhaust and supply air stream in HVAC set-ups to enhance energy efficiency and indoor air quality. They are typically placed upstream of any heating or cooling components that condition the air. They can be integrated into the air handling unit (AHU), installed as standalone heat or energy recovery ventilator (HRV or ERV) units, or added to ductwork, depending on the building design and energy goals.

MEASURE GROUP

HVAC system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Installations.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

It may not apply to some CH buildings with high protection level.

ADVANTAGES

- Energy Efficiency enhancement.
- Cost savings.
- Versatility.

DISADVANTAGES

- Initial Cost.
- Possibility of frost formation.

LIMITATIONS

- Space Requirements.

PHOTO ^[2]

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

Medium.

VISUAL IMPACT

Low - Medium.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

High.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

Low.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES ^[1]

	FIXED PLATE	ENERGY WHEEL
Airflow Arrangements	Counterflow Cross flow	Counterflow Parallel flow
Equipment size range [L/s]	25 and up	25 to 35 000 and up
Typical sensitivity effectiveness [%]	50 to 75	65 to 80
Typical latent effectiveness [%]	0	50 to 80
Total effectiveness [%]	20 to 70	55 to 80
Face velocity [m/s]	1 to 5	2.5 to 5
Pressure drop [Pa]	100 to 1000	100 to 300

GEOMETRY DATA ^[2]

This depends on the type of heat recovery unit and the air flow rate for which it is required.

INSTALLATION DATA

Installation time [h] | 1 - 3

MAINTENANCE DATA

Energy recovery segments should be removable and easily cleanable outside the cabinet using detergent or an alkaline coil cleaner with water. Regular cleaning ensures optimal system efficiency and longevity.

OPERATION DATA

Heat recovery systems operate automatically once installed.

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Total energy intensity	KPIs [kWh/m ² / year]
Heating energy intensity	
Cooling energy intensity	
Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	KPI (%)
Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	KPI (%)

COSTS

INVESTMENT ^{[2][3]}

The cost of energy recovery systems typically ranges from 900 € to 1,800 € for the unit and 1,000 € to 2,500 € for installation, depending on the system size and complexity. Total investment averages 1,900 € to 4,300 €.

SAVINGS

Savings will depend on ventilation airflow, weather conditions and energy costs. When energy is expensive, there is a tendency to save more.

ROI ^[1]

Well-designed energy recovery systems typically have a payback period of less than 5 years and often less than 3 years. Payback periods of less than 1 year are not uncommon in comfort-to-comfort applications in hot, humid climates, mainly

because of the reduced size of the cooling equipment required.

OTHERS

PHASE

Design and Renovation.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Air conditioning system.

REFERENCES

[1] ASHRAE. *Air-to-air energy recovery equipment*. Retrieved from https://www.ashrae.org/file%20library/technical%20resources/covid-19/si_s20_ch26.pdf

[2] Airxchange. *Energy recovery plates: Performance products & reliable energy recovery*. Retrieved from <https://www.airxchange.com/performance-products-reliable-energy-recovery/energy-recovery-plates/>

[3] Attainable Home. (2024). *Is an energy recovery ventilator worth it?* Retrieved from https://www.attainablehome.com/is-an-energy-recovery-ventilator-worth-it/?utm_source=chatgpt.com

MECHANICAL VENTILATION WITH HEAT RECOVERY (MVHR)

ID #32

It is a controlled ventilation system that, through extraction and supply units, ensures a continuous exchange of fresh and stale air in enclosed buildings. The system uses a heat exchanger to transfer thermal energy from the extracted air to the incoming fresh air, reducing energy losses associated with conventional ventilation.

APPLICATION

It is primarily applied in high-energy-efficiency buildings, such as residential buildings, offices, schools, and hospitals. This system is ideal for environments where the goal is to maintain optimal indoor air quality, control humidity, and reduce energy consumption.

MEASURE GROUP

HVAC systems.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

Pillar 2: Resources & Circularity.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Installations.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

MVHR works best in buildings that are relatively airtight, such as new-build buildings or buildings that are being fully renovated

ADVANTAGES

- Increase indoor comfort.
- Reduce energy consumption.
- Reduce humidity and prevent mold.

DISADVANTAGES

- Space required for ducting and the unit.
- Cost of initial investment.

PHOTO [1]

- Regular maintenance costs, including cleaning and replacing filters.

LIMITATIONS

Space requirements and installation could be very challenging in protected interiors.

SOCIAL ACCEPTATION

High.

VISUAL IMPACT

Medium (depends on design).

PHISICAL IMPACT

High.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

Medium.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

The required amount of air to be provided is determined by the national standards. Recommended values can be found in EN 15251.

GEOMETRY DATA

- Ductwork dimensions must be planned to minimize pressure drops and noise.
- The placement of the unit should allow easy access for maintenance and filter replacement.
- Ensure adequate space for air intake and exhaust terminals to avoid recirculation and contamination.

INSTALLATION DATA

- MVHR requires careful HVAC design and professional installation.
- The system requires proper sealing to prevent air leakage.
- Coordination with other building systems (e.g., plumbing, electrical) is essential to avoid conflicts.
- Electrical connections must comply with local regulations.
- Adequate space should be allocated for the ductwork and main unit, particularly in buildings with protected interiors.

MAINTENANCE DATA

- Filters should be checked and replaced regularly to maintain air quality and system efficiency.
- Fans and heat exchangers need periodic cleaning to prevent dust accumulation and ensure effective operation.

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Total energy intensity	KPIs [kWh/m ² /year]
Heating energy intensity	
Cooling energy intensity	
Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	KPIs (%)
Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	KPIs (%)

PILLAR 2 KPIS: Resource Efficiency, Circularity and LCC

Global warming potential	KPIs [kg CO ₂ eq/m ² /year]
Life cycle cost	KPIs [€/m ² /year]

COSTS

INVESTMENTS ^[2] ^[3]

The cost of this system may vary depending on the unit's size and technical features. However, the price for a wall-mounted model ranges from €1,200 to €3,000.

SAVING

Reduces energy consumption by recovering up to 90% of heat from exhaust air. Overall system efficiency varies based on the specific system and initial ventilation losses.

ROI

The payback period varies according to the initial investment and savings. However, potential ROI within 5-10 years.

OTHERS

PHASE

Design and Renovation.
Monitoring, Operation and Management.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Suitable for different kind of buildings and various sizes. Adaptable to both new constructions and retrofits, though retrofits may require more planning and space considerations.

REFERENCES

[1] Pure Ventilation. Retrieved from <https://www.pureventilation.com.au/>

[2] BPC Ventilation. *Nuair MRXBOXAB-ECO2B Wall Mounted*. Retrieved from <https://bpcventilation.ie/products/nuair-eco-2>

[3] SiberZone. *Sistema de ventilación con recuperación de calor*. Retrieved from <https://www.siberzone.es/>

VARIABLE AIRFLOW FANS

ID #33

Variable airflow fans adjust their speed and air flow to match the system's real-time demands, optimising energy use and reducing operating costs. They enhance efficiency while maintaining occupant comfort by ensuring a consistent and adequate air supply.

APPLICATION

Suitable for a wide range of buildings, including heritage sites, though installation may be complex in space-constrained or protected interiors. Can be an upgrade to existing AHUs.

MEASURE GROUP

HVAC systems.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

Pillar 2: Resource & Circularity.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Installations.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

Fans are major electricity consumers in HVAC systems, but variable airflow fans reduce energy usage by adapting speed and air flow to system needs. It is possible to retrofit existing or install new HVAC systems with variable speed fans.

ADVANTAGES

- Reduces energy consumption and energy costs.
- Reduces maintenance of mechanical equipment such as belts and bearings due to reduced operating speeds.
- Maintains good comfort level.
- Ease to maintain low noise levels.

PHOTO ^[1]

DISADVANTAGES

- Cost of initial investment.
- Need to develop a control algorithm to ensure good comfort in building.
- Reduced fan speeds can lead to condensation and freezing and therefore should be closely monitored.

LIMITATIONS

Higher initial costs and complexity in system integration and control.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

VISUAL IMPACT

Low - Medium (depends on the design).

PHYSICAL IMPACT

High.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

Medium.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

HVAC system would need control algorithms for dynamic airflow adjustment, compatibility with other building systems, for example BMS and protocols for seamless communication between fan units and HVAC controllers.

GEOMETRY DATA

- Allow sufficient space for the variable airflow fans, ensuring clear paths for

both air intake and exhaust to prevent recirculation and maintain clean air distribution.

- Avoid interference with other components.

INSTALLATION DATA

- Selection of a fan type and size.
- Ensure professional installation with careful HVAC design.
- Implement a control strategy to enable the fan to adjust airflow based on demand.
- Electrical connections must meet local building code requirements and be inspected for safety and compliance.

MAINTENANCE DATA

- Filters should be checked and replaced regularly to maintain air quality and system efficiency.
- Conduct periodic cleaning of fans and heat exchangers to prevent dust buildup, which can compromise airflow and reduce the system's overall performance.

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Total energy intensity	KPI [kWh/m ² /year]
Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	KPI (%)
Air quality	KPI (%)

PILLAR 2 KPIS: Resource Efficiency, Circularity and LCC

Global Warming Potential	KPIs [kg CO ₂ eq /m ² year]
Life cycle cost	KPI [€/m ² /year]

COSTS

INVESTMENT

This type of technology is integrated into the HVAC system, making it difficult to estimate a standalone cost.

SAVINGS ^[3]

Variable airflow fans can significantly reduce energy consumption by adjusting airflow to

match demand, potentially saving up to 30-40% on HVAC electricity energy use. Overall savings will depend on system efficiency and initial ventilation requirements.

ROI

The payback period varies according to the initial investment and savings. However, potential ROI within 3-7 years.

OTHERS

PHASE

Monitoring, Operation and Management

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Suitable for different kind of buildings and various sizes. Adaptable to both new constructions and retrofits, though retrofits may require more planning and space considerations.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ebmpapst. Retrieved from www.ebmpapst.com
- [2] Lu, Daniel B. Warsinger, David M. (2020). "Energy savings of retrofitting residential buildings with variable air volume systems across different climates". *Journal of Building Engineering*.
- [3] New York Engineers. *Ventilation system comparison: CAV and VAV*. Retrieved from <https://www.ny-engineers.com/blog/ventilation-system-comparison-cav-and-vav>
- [4] Aktaçir, M. A., Büyükalaca, O., & Yılmaz, T. (2006). Life-cycle cost analysis for constant-air-volume and variable-air-volume air-conditioning systems. *Applied Energy*, 83(6), 606–627.
- [5] Pacific Northwest National Laboratory. *Variable air volume systems – OM best practices guide*. Retrieved from <https://www.pnnl.gov/projects/om-best-practices/variable-air-volume-systems>

HIGH-EFFICIENCY FILTERS

ID #34

The use of high-efficiency filters in heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) systems helps to improve indoor air quality by trapping smaller particles and pollutants.

APPLICATION

Install a high efficiency filter in the air conditioning system.

MEASURE GROUP

HVAC system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Installations.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

Filter must be sized appropriately for HVAC unit and the size of air ducts.

ADVANTAGES

- Improve indoor air quality therefore health benefits.
- Trap smaller particles and pollutants.

DISADVANTAGES

- Initial cost.
- Increased air flow resistance.
- Regular maintenance.

LIMITATIONS

Not all systems are designed to handle high efficiency filters.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

Medium – High.

VISUAL IMPACT

Low.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

Low.

PHOTO ^[1]

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

Low - Medium.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES ^{[2] [3]}

It depends on the manufacturer and the type of high-efficiency filter, but there are standards that regulate certain technical parameters, such as UNE-EN 1822 and ISO 29463.

Efficiency (%)	95 - 99,7
Captured particle size [microns]	0,1 - 0,3

GEOMETRY DATA

It depends on the manufacturer and the model.

INSTALLATION DATA

Installation time [h]	0.5 - 1
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MAINTENANCE DATA ^[4]

Type of maintenance	Regular inspection every 3 months or by pressure sensor alarm, with cleaning if reusable and annual replacement if disposable.	
Lifespan [Months]	Reusable	24 - 60
	Disposable	3

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Air quality		KPIs (%)
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COSTS

INVESTMENTS ^[5]

The price may vary depending on the size of the particles captured, as well as the dimensions of the system. Additionally, brand and model can influence the cost. It is estimated that the price range could be between €1,900 and €4,700.

SAVING

Implementing this measure will not result in direct savings.

ROI

It should be noted that this measure will not provide a return on the investment made in its installation.

OTHERS

PHASE

Design and Renovation.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

This measure has been implemented in the HVAC system of a building.

REFERENCES

[1] INSPARE INDUSTRIES. *Filtros de alta eficiencia*. Retrieved from <https://inspamex.com/FILTROS%20DE%20ALTA%20EFICIENCIA%20.html>

[2] International Organization for Standardization. (2011) ISO 29463: *High-efficiency filters and filter media for removing particles in air*.

[3] Asociación Española de Normalización. (2019–2020). *UNE-EN 1822: Filtros absolutos (EPA, HEPA y ULPA)*.

[4] Allergy & Asthma Network. (2025). *HEPA: Help or Hype?* Retrieved from <https://allergyasthmanetwork.org/news/health-help-hype/>

[5] Angi. (2024). *Whole-house air purifier cost*. Retrieved from <https://www.angi.com/articles/whole-house-air-purifier-cost.htm#purifier-type>

[6] Alavy, M., Li, T., & Siegel, J. A. (2020). Energy use in residential buildings: Analyses of high-efficiency filters and HVAC fans. *Energy and Buildings*, 209, 109697. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2019.109697>

STORAGE SYSTEMS

ID #36

A thermal energy storage system is a mechanism designed to capture and conserve energy in the form of heat or cold for later use. These systems allow the storage of excess thermal energy generated during periods of low demand or high production and release it when demand is higher or production is insufficient. Depending on the technology employed, storage can be achieved through sensible heat, latent heat, or thermochemical reactions.

APPLICATION

The installation of hot/cold water tanks in an air conditioning system can significantly improve the energy performance of the installation.

MEASURE GROUP

HVAC system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Functional Behaviour.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

- Sufficient space for the installation of the storage tanks.
- Integration with existing HVAC systems and compatibility with the pipework.

ADVANTAGES

- Reduces peak energy demand and energy costs.
- Enhances a stable temperature supply.
- Energy and capital cost savings.
- System capacity extending.

DISADVANTAGES

- Requires space for installation.
- Don't necessarily save energy.

PHOTO ^[1]

LIMITATIONS

- Limited by the available space.
- Requires careful planning and design to integrate with existing HVAC system.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

VISUAL IMPACT

Medium.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

Medium.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

Medium.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

Thermal storage types	Water / Ice
Storage types	Full storage / partial storage
Function	Heating / Cooling

GEOMETRY DATA ^[4]

Aspect Ratio (AR)	Tank height / Tank diameter
Capacity [L]	50 - 1000

INSTALLATION DATA

Installation time [h] | 0.25 - 1.5

MAINTENANCE DATA

Type of maintenance	Interior and exterior cleaning (Decennial)
Lifespan [years]	15 - 25

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Total energy intensity	KPIs [kWh/m ² / year]
Heating energy intensity	
Cooling energy intensity	
Energy performance & operation	KPIs (%)
Energy flexibility assessment	
Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	

COSTS

INVESTMENTS ^[5]

Depends on size, material, insulation, and installation complexity, ranging between €500 - €5000 (for small / medium tanks of 50 – 1000 [L])

SAVING ^[2]

Studies have shown that implementing fully integrated chilled water storage systems can reduce peak electrical demand for cooling by up to 80–90% compared to conventional cooling systems. While these solutions do not necessarily lead to a reduction in total energy consumption, they enable more efficient energy management by shifting loads away from peak demand periods. Specifically, full ice thermal storage systems have demonstrated up to a 5% reduction in overall system energy consumption.

ROI

The return on investment period has not been determined.

OTHERS

PHASE

Design and Renovation.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Depending on the building and demand, it is possible to store only cold or hot water or to store both.

REFERENCES

[1] HVAC Eng. (n.d.). *Thermal storage (HVAC)*. Retrieved from <https://hvac-eng.com/thermal-storage-hvac/>

[2] Vakiloroyaya, V., Samali, B., Fakhar, A., & Pishghadam, K. (2014). A review of different strategies for HVAC energy saving. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 77, 738-754. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2013.10.023>

[2] Karim, A.; Burnett, A.; Fawzia, S. (2018). Investigation of Stratified Thermal Storage Tank Performance for Heating and Cooling Applications. *Energies*. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en11051049>

[3] AA Tanks. *Specialty/HVAC tanks*. Retrieved from <https://www.aatanks.com/products/specialty-hvac-tanks.html#:~:text=AA tanks%20specialty%20tanks%20are%20designed,tanks%2C%20primary%20and%20secondary%20headers.>

[4] Helioakmi. *Tanques de almacenamiento*. Retrieved from <https://www.helioakmi.com/es/tanques-de-almacenamiento/>

[5] Generador de Precios. *Acumulador para calefacción y climatización*. Retrieved from https://generadordeprecios.info/obra_nueva/calculaprecio.asp?Valor=3|0_0|1|ICS065|ics_065:0_0_25_0_0_0_0

TEMPERATURE SENSORS

ID #41

These sensors are used to measure the ambient temperature in different areas of a building or space and provide feedback to the HVAC system to regulate the temperature efficiently.

APPLICATION

It is a measure feasible regardless the protection level of the building and with low technical requirements.

MEASURE GROUP

Control system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Installations.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

- Requires compatible HVAC systems with control capabilities.
- Calibration and initial setup for accurate readings.

ADVANTAGES

Possibility of integration with and control of HVAC systems:

- Enhances energy efficiency by providing temperature control, reducing energy consumption.
- Improves occupant comfort.
- Integrated with other smart systems.

DISADVANTAGES

Initial costs.

LIMITATIONS

Dependence on HVAC system compatibility.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

VISUAL IMPACT

Low.

PHOTO ^[3]

PHYSICAL IMPACT

Low.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

High.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES ^[3]

Sensing range [°C]	- 30 to 100
Accuracy	± 0.5°C to ± 1°C
Response time (s)	1 - 5
Communication	Analog, digital or wireless

INSTALLATION DATA

Installation time of 0.3 - 1 [h] depending on system and location.

MAINTENANCE DATA

Type of maintenance	Calibration checks every 6-12 months.
Lifespan [years]	10 - 15

OPERATION DATA

Must be installed in areas with minimal obstructions for accurate readings.

It makes no sense to add more than one sensor for a specific controlled zone.

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Heating energy intensity	KPIs
Cooling energy intensity	[kWh/m ² /year]
Response to the needs of occupants	KPIs (SRI score)
Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	KPIs (%)

COSTS

INVESTMENTS ^[2]

The estimated cost per sensor ranges from €150 to €300, including connection and setup expenses.

SAVINGS - ROI

This technology is utilised for the measurement of temperature, thus not being associated with direct savings or a payback period. However, should a control system be implemented that regulates the power of the HVAC based on this measurement, it could generate significant savings.

OTHERS

PHASE

Design and Renovation.
Monitoring, Operation and Management.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Applicable to all building types.

REFERENCES

[1] King, J. and Perry C. (2017) *Smart Buildings: Using Smart Technology to Save Energy in Existing Buildings*. ACEEE.

[2] CYPE Ingenieros. *Flush-mounted room thermostat*. Generador de Precios. Retrieved from <https://generadordeprecios.info/>

[3] TEquipment. *Comet T3111P - Compressed Air RH+T+Tdp Sensor with 4-20mA Output*. Retrieved from <https://www.tequipment.net/Comet/T3111P/Humidity-Temperature-Sensors/>

SYSTEMS FOR REMOTE MEASUREMENT OF ENERGY CONSUMPTION – ELECTRICITY

ID #43a

Installation of systems for remotely monitor electricity consumption. These systems typically include three main components: an electricity meter, a safety mechanism and communication equipment.

APPLICATION

This measure is feasible for any building, regardless of its protection level, and has low technical requirements.

MEASURE GROUP

Control system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

Pillar 2: Resources and Circularity.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTION

Installations.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

To install, commission, and test the remote measurement system, the electricity meter must either have an integrated telemetry system or be compatible with additional equipment for communication integration.

ADVANTAGES

- Encourages behavioural reductions in electricity consumption.
- Enables real-time monitoring.
- Increase awareness of energy usage.
- Provides insights into building operations.

DISADVANTAGES

- High initial investment cost.
- Requires stable communication.

PHOTO

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

VISUAL IMPACT

Low.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

Low.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

High.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

- Communication protocol: NB-IOT.
- Communication with devices: Impulse.
- Power – option 1: via cable (230 VAC).
- Power – option 2: battery (Li 3,6V).
- Type of SIM card: mini-SIM.
- Working temperature range: -25 / +70.
- Measurement interval: 15 min – 1 month.

GEOMETRY DATA

High [mm]	65,5
Width [mm]	25,5
Large [mm]	150

INSTALLATION DATA

Installation time [h/device] | ≈ 0.5

MAINTENANCE DATA

Type of maintenance	Device calibration each 2 years.
Useful life [h]	≈ 5 years (battery)

OPERATION DATA

For full operation, it is necessary to connect communication equipment of this system to a central system for gathering measurement data.

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Total energy intensity	KPI [kWh/m ² /year]
Energy performance and operation	KPI (SRI score)
Response to the needs of occupants	
Energy flexibility assessment	

PILLAR 2 KPIS: Resource Efficiency, Circularity and LCC

Operational Energy Costs	KPI [€/m ² /year]
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COSTS

INVESTMENT

The final cost of the investment depends on type of electricity meter.

- If electricity meter is adequate and only a communication equipment needs to be installed = 300 - 500 €.
- If a new electricity meter needs to be installed as well = 600 – 800 €.

SAVINGS

All energy savings are related only to indirect savings due to behavioural changes. According to EU standards, average savings are 5-10%.

ROI

This measure is not installed to achieve great energy savings, but to gain insights about consumption and increase awareness of users.

However, the payback period varies according to the initial investment and savings. It is generally stipulated between 3 and 5 years.

OTHERS

PHASE

Monitoring, Operation and Management.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Installation can be performed at various levels: in specific rooms, on particular floors, or throughout the entire building, with the potential to add more meters as needed.

REFERENCES

- [1] E. Barakat, N. Sinno, C. Keyrouz, A Remote Monitoring System for Voltage, Current, Power and Temperature Measurements, Physics Procedia, Volume 55, 2014, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1875389214001230>

SYSTEMS FOR REMOTE MEASUREMENT OF ENERGY CONSUMPTION – HEAT

ID #43b

Installation of systems for remotely monitor heat energy consumption. These systems typically include three main components: a calorimeter, flow sensors and communication equipment.

APPLICATION

This measure is feasible for any building, regardless of its level of protection, and has low technical requirements.

MEASURE GROUP

Control system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

Pillar 2: Resources and Circularity.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Installations.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

To install, commission, and test the remote measurement system, heat meter must either have an integrated telemetry system or be compatible with additional equipment for communication integration.

ADVANTAGES

- Encourages behavioural reductions in heat consumption.
- Increase awareness of energy usage.
- Provides insights into building operations.

DISADVANTAGES

- High initial investment cost.
- Requires stable communication.

LIMITATIONS

- Compatibility with existing heat meter (calorimeter).

PHOTO

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

VISUAL IMPACT

Low.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

Low.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

High.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

- Communication protocol: M-BUS, RS 232, supercom, relay, LON, analog (0,4 – 20 mA).
- Communication with devices: Impulse.
- Power – option 1: via cable (230 VAC).
- Power – option 2: battery (Li 3,6V).
- Applicable for flow: qp 0.6 – qp 2.5.
- Measurement interval: ≥ 10 s.
- LC screen.
- IP65 protection.

GEOMETRY DATA

Length [mm]	110 – 190
Diameter [“]	½ - ¾

INSTALLATION DATA

Installation time [h/device]	≈ 1
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MAINTENANCE DATA

Type of maintenance	Device calibration each 2 [years]
Useful life [h]	≈ 6 years (battery)

OPERATION DATA

For full operation, it is necessary to connect communication equipment of this system to a central system for gathering measurement data.

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Total energy intensity	KPI [kWh/m ² /year]
Heating energy intensity	
Energy performance and operation	KPI (SRI score)
Response to the needs of occupants	
Energy flexibility assessment	

PILLAR 2 KPIS: Resource Efficiency, Circularity and LCC

Operational Costs	Energy	KPI [€/m ² /year]
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COSTS

INVESTMENT

The final cost of the investment depends on type of heat meter.

- If heat meter is adequate and only a communication equipment needs to be installed = 300 – 500 €.
- If a new heat meter needs to be installed as well = 500 – 700 €.

SAVINGS

All energy savings are related only to indirect savings due to behavioural changes. According to EU standards, average savings are 5 -10%.

ROI

This measure is not installed to achieve a great energy savings, but to gain insights about consumption and increase awareness of users.

However, the payback period varies according to the initial investment and savings. It is generally stipulated between 3 and 5 years.

OTHERS

PHASE

Monitoring, Operation and Management.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Installation can be carried out at different levels: only in some circuits, on specific floors or in the whole building.

REFERENCES

[1] E. Fabrizio, M. Ferrara, V. Monetti, *Chapter 10 - Smart Heating Systems for Cost-Effective Retrofitting*, Editor(s): Fernando Pacheco-Torgal, Claes-Göran Granqvist, Bjørn Petter Jelle, Giuseppe Peter Vanoli, Nicola Bianco, Jarek Kurnitski, *Cost-Effective Energy Efficient Building Retrofitting*, Woodhead Publishing, 2017, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/B9780081011287000101>

SYSTEMS FOR REMOTE MEASUREMENT OF ENERGY CONSUMPTION – NATURAL GAS

ID #43c

Installation of systems for remotely monitor natural gas consumption. These systems typically include four main components: a natural gas meter, a signal splitter, a “zener” barrier and communication equipment.

APPLICATION

This measure is feasible for any building, regardless of its level of protection, and has low technical requirements.

MEASURE GROUP

Control system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

Pillar 2: Resources and Circularity.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Installations.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

To install, commission, and test the remote measurement system, the natural gas meter must be compatible with additional equipment for communication integration. Otherwise, a new meter should be installed.

ADVANTAGES

- Encourages behavioral reductions in natural gas consumption.
- Increase awareness of energy usage.
- Provides insights into building operations.
- Together with the heat consumption measurement provides information on the efficiency of the heating system/DHW.

PHOTO

DISADVANTAGES

- High initial investment cost.
- Requires stable communication.

LIMITATIONS

- Compatibility with existing natural gas meter.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

VISUAL IMPACT

Low.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

Low.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

High.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

- Communication protocol: NB-IOT
- Communication with devices: impulse
- Power – option 1: via cable (230 VAC)
- Power – option 2: battery (Li 3,6V)
- Type of SIM card: MFF2

- Working temperature range: -25 / +55
- IP65 protection
- Measurement interval: ≥ 1 min

GEOMETRY DATA

High [mm]	145
Width [mm]	54
Large [mm]	56

INSTALLATION DATA

Installation time [h/device]	≈ 1
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MAINTENANCE DATA

Type of maintenance	Device calibration each 2 [years]
Useful life [years]	≈ 5 (battery)

OPERATION DATA

For full operation, it is necessary to connect communication equipment of this system to a central system for gathering measurement data.

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Total energy intensity	KPI [kWh/m ² /year]
Energy performance and operation	KPI (<i>SRI score</i>)
Response to the needs of occupants	
Energy flexibility assessment	

PILLAR 2 KPIS: Resource Efficiency, Circularity and LCC

Global Warming Potential	KPI [Kg CO ₂ eq./m ² /year]
Operational Energy Costs	KPI [€/m ² /year]

COSTS

INVESTMENT

The final cost of the investment depends on type of natural gas meter.

- If natural gas meter is adequate and only a communication equipment needs to be installed = 300 – 500 €.
- If a new gas meter needs to be installed as well = 450 – 650 €.

SAVINGS

All energy savings are related only to indirect savings due to behavioural changes. According to EU standards, average savings are 5-10%.

ROI

This measure is not installed to achieve a great energy savings, but to gain insights about consumption and increase awareness of users.

However, the payback period varies according to the initial investment and savings. It is generally stipulated between 3 and 5 years.

OTHERS

PHASE

Monitoring, Operation and Management

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Installation can be carried out at different levels: for individual equipment or for the consumption of the whole building.

REFERENCES

[1] Berry, B. & Bauer, E. (2006). Remote natural gas measurement and automation systems.

SYSTEMS FOR REMOTE MEASUREMENT OF INNER AIR QUALITY

ID #43d

Installation of systems for remotely monitor inner air quality, which typically includes temperature, humidity and CO₂ concentration.

APPLICATION

This measure is feasible for any building, regardless of its level of protection, and has low technical requirements.

MEASURE GROUP

Control system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Installations.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

No specific conditions. A device is simply installed in any room by attaching it to a wall.

ADVANTAGES

- Increase awareness of air quality.
- Provides insights into building operations.

DISADVANTAGES

- High initial investment cost.
- Requires stable communication.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

VISUAL IMPACT

Low.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

Low.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

High.

PHOTO

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

- Communication protocol: NB-IOT
- Power: via cable (230 VAC)
- Temperature range (°C): -20 / 70 ± 0.3
- Humidity range (%): 0-100 ± 2
- CO₂ range (ppm): 0 – 5000 ± 50
- Type of SIM card: mini-SIM
- Measurement interval: ≥ 2 min

GEOMETRY DATA

High [mm]	125
Width [mm]	67
Large [mm]	43

INSTALLATION DATA

Installation time [h]	≈ 0.5 [h/device]
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MAINTENANCE DATA

Type of maintenance	Device calibration each 2 years
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OPERATION DATA

For full operation, it is necessary to connect communication equipment of this system to a central system for gathering measurement data.

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	KPI (%)
Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	
Air quality	KPI (SRI score)
Energy performance and operation	
Response to the needs of occupants	
Energy flexibility assessment	

COSTS

INVESTMENT

The estimated cost per device ranges from €400 to €500 per unit.

SAVINGS

All energy savings are related only to indirect savings due to behavioural changes.

ROI

This measure is not installed to achieve energy savings, but to gain insights about indoor air quality and increase awareness of users.

OTHERS

PHASE

Monitoring, Operation and Management.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Installation focused on room level.

REFERENCES

- [1] Dimitrios Bousiotis, Leah-Nani S. Alconcel, David C.S. Beddows, Roy M. Harrison, Francis D. Pope, *Monitoring and apportioning sources of indoor air quality using low-cost particulate matter sensors*, Environment International, Volume 174, 2023, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0160412023001800>

SYSTEMS FOR REMOTE MEASUREMENT OF WATER CONSUMPTION

ID #44

Installation of systems for remote water consumption measurement which consists of four main components: a water meter, impulse emitter, impulse splitter, and communication equipment.

APPLICATION

This is a measure feasible regardless the level of protection of the building and with low technical requirements.

It enables accurate monitoring and control of water consumption, contributing to resource saving and more efficient water management.

MEASURE GROUP

Control system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 2: Resources and Circularity.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Installations.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

To install, commission, and test the remote measurement system, the water meter must be compatible with the installation of additional equipment for integration of communication equipment. Otherwise, a new meter should be installed.

ADVANTAGES

- Indirect (behavioural) reduction of water consumption.
- Increase water consumption awareness.
- Gain insights into the operation of the building.

DISADVANTAGES

- Cost of initial investment.
- Stable communication must be ensured.

PHOTO

LIMITATIONS

- Type of existing water meter.
- It may not be compatible with the system

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

VISUAL IMPACT

Low.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

Low.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

High.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

- Communication protocol: NB-IOT.
- Communication with devices: impulse.
- Power battery (Li 3,6V).
- Type of SIM card: MFF2.
- Working temperature range: -25 / +55.
- IP65 protection.
- Measurement interval: ≥ 1 min.

GEOMETRY DATA

High [mm]	145
Width [mm]	54
Large [mm]	56

INSTALLATION DATA

Installation time [h/device] | ≈ 1

MAINTENANCE DATA

Type of maintenance	Device calibration each 2 years
Useful life [years]	≈ 5 (battery)

OPERATION DATA

For full operation, it is necessary to connect the communication equipment of this system to a central system for gathering measurement data. A stable internet connection must be provided.

IMPACT

PILLAR 2 KPIs: Resource Efficiency, Circularity and LCC

Total water consumption	KPIs Residential: $\text{m}^3/\text{occupant}/\text{year}$ Non-residential: $\text{m}^3/\text{m}^2/\text{year}$
Water circularity indicator	KPIs (%)

COSTS

INVESTMENTS

The final cost of the investment depends on the type of water meter. If it is adequate and only communication equipment needs to be installed, the cost range is 300 - 500 €.

SAVINGS

All energy savings are related only to indirect savings due to behavioural changes. According to EU standards average savings are 5-10%.

ROI

This measure does not aim to achieve large water savings, but to gain insights about

consumption and increase awareness of users.

The payback period varies according to the initial investment and savings. It is generally stipulated between 3 and 5 years.

OTHERS

PHASE

Monitoring, Operation and Management.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Installation can be carried out at different levels: only in some rooms, on specific floors or in the whole building.

REFERENCES

[1] Rui Liang, Arwa A. AL-Huqail, H. Elhosiny Ali, Joffin Jose Ponnore, Tamim Alkhalifah, Fahad Alturise, Hamid Assilzadeh, Wireless water consumption sensing system for building energy efficiency: A visual-based approach with self-powered operation, Energy and Buildings, Volume 301, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2023.113584>. (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378778823008149>)

PV (+/- STORAGE)

ID #45

An electric energy production system will be incorporated by means of photovoltaic panels typically placed on the roofs or parking canopies. Incorporating a photovoltaic system reduces a building's electricity consumption from the grid and improves its overall environmental performance.

APPLICATION

Normally, this type of installation is carried out on roofs with good orientation or on the ground. If it is to be installed on the roof of a cultural heritage building, it is necessary to consider whether it affects its cultural value.

MEASURE GROUP

RES integration.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort

Pillar 2: Resource & Circularity.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Installations.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

It may not apply to some CH sites with high protection level. The installations risk damaging the cultural heritage value of the building and/or its surroundings.

ADVANTAGES

- Clean and inexhaustible energy source.
- Reduction of the cost of the energy cost.
- Low maintenance.
- Flexibility of application.

DISADVANTAGES

- Initial cost High.
- Dependence on sunlight.
- Potential aesthetic degradation of the building.

PHOTO ^[1]

LIMITATIONS

- Space.
- Energy storage.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

Medium.

VISUAL IMPACT

Medium – High.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

Low.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

Low – Medium.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

Monocrystalline ^[4]

Power [W/m ²]	[180 - 230]
Efficiency [%]	[18 – 23]
Area [m ² /panel]	[1 – 2.2]

Polycrystalline ^[5]

Power [W]	[160 – 220]
Efficiency (%)	[15 – 18]
Area [m ² /panel]	[1 - 2]

INSTALLATION DATA

Installation time [day]	[1 – 3]
-------------------------	---------

MAINTENANCE DATA

Type of maintenance	Cleaning of the solar panels and a visual inspection should be carried out every 6 months. Inverter maintenance should be done every 5-10 years.
Useful life [Years]	25 - 30

OPERATION DATA

Receiving sufficient solar radiation on the collector and ensuring proper system installation.

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Energy autonomy	KPIs (%)
Energy performance & operation	KPIs (SRI score)
Energy flexibility assessment	

PILLAR 2 KPIS: Resource Efficiency, Circularity and LCC

Global Warming Potential	KPIs [kg CO ₂ eq/m ² /year]
Operational Energy Cost	KPIs [€/m ² /year]
Life cycle cost	KPI [€/m ² /year]
Energy Circularity Indicator	KPIs [%]

COSTS

INVESTMENTS ^[2]

PV installation costs can vary considerably depending on country, incentive policy, labor costs and other region-specific factors. The estimated cost is between 1 and 1.6 euros per watt.

SAVING

The annual savings when installing a photovoltaic (PV) panel system depend on several factors, including the size of the system, energy consumption, local electricity rates, and the amount of solar energy available at your location.

To estimate the energy generation of the system, you can use the PVWatts tool ^[3]. To determine energy consumption, simply review your electricity bills.

ROI

In order for a photovoltaic installation to be considered cost-effective, the payback period must be between five and eight years.

OTHERS

PHASE

Design and Renovation.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Implementation can be at residential, community or industrial scale.

REFERENCES

- [1] Church Times. (2024, December 20). US Episcopal Church quits fossil fuels. Retrieved from <https://www.churchtimes.co.uk/articles/2024/20-december/news/world/us-episcopal-church-quits-fossil-fuels>
- [2] Forbes. (2024). How much do solar panels cost?. Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com/home-improvement/solar/cost-of-solar-panels/>
- [3] National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL). PVWatts Calculator. Retrieved from <https://pvwatts.nrel.gov/>
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- [7] Lucchi, E. (2022). Integration between photovoltaic systems and cultural heritage: A socio-technical comparison of international policies, design criteria, applications, and innovation developments. Energy Policy, Volume 171, 113303. Retrieved from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0301421522005225>
- [8] EnergySage. (2025). Community solar. Retrieved from <https://www.energysage.com/community-solar/>

EV CHARGERS

ID #47

Installation of infrastructure for charging electric vehicles.

APPLICATION

This is a measure feasible regardless the level of protection of the building and with medium technical requirements.

MEASURE GROUP

RES integration.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

Pillar 2: Resources & Circularity.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Installations.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

To install this equipment, a connection to the electricity grid is necessary via adequate cables. If it is a wall-box solution, appropriate position on wall is needed (to be allowed by conservatory office), while if it is a stand-alone solution, additional construction works are necessary in terms of foundations and mounting near parking spaces.

ADVANTAGES

- Provide the possibility to charge electric cars on-site and promote electromobility.
- Reduction of greenhouse gas emissions in transport.
- If equipped with monitoring system, gain insights in energy consumption for charging of EVs and direct energy/financial savings in comparison to ICE vehicles.
- Increased Property Value.

DISADVANTAGES

- EV charger needs to be connected to the grid.

PHOTO

- Limited space to position EV chargers – has to be in range of parking.
- Hidden cost in terms of construction works, especially lay down cables from EV charger to the grid connection.
- RFID card, mobile app or any other means of login to use the charger.

LIMITATIONS

- Maximum power of EV charger depends on connection power of a building where the charger is installed.
- Limited to installation near parking lots.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

VISUAL IMPACT

Medium.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

Medium.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

High.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES^[3]

Conductive charging involves an electrical connection between the charging inlet and the vehicle and is categorized into three levels, based on power output, as shown in the next table:

LEVEL 1	
Charging Power	1.44 – 1.9 [kW]
Charger time	200 [km]: ± 20 [h]

Charge Location	Residential
Power supply	120 / 230 [Vac]
	12 - 16 [A]
	Single phase
Supply Interface and protection type	Convenience outlet (breaker in cable)
LEVEL 2	
Charging Power	3.1 - 19.2 [kW]
Charger time	200 {km}: ± 5 [h]
Charge Location	Private and commercial
Power supply	208 / 240 [Vac]
	12 - 80 [A]
	Single phase/Split phase
Supply Interface and protection type	Dedicated EV supply equipment (breaker in the cable and pilot function)
LEVEL 3	
Charging Power	20 - 350 [kW]
Charger time	80% of 200 [km]: 30 [min]
Charge Location	Commercial
Power supply	208 / 240 [Vac]
	250 - 500 [A]
	Three phase
Supply Interface and protection type	Dedicated EV supply equipment (communication and event monitoring between EV and charging station)

GEOMETRY DATA

Various data based on type of EV charger.

Example:

Wallbox [mm]	228.5 x 228.5 x 100
Stand-alone [mm]	830 x 459 x 1686

INSTALLATION DATA

Wallbox [h/device]	≈ 0.5
Stand-alone [h/device]	≈ 24

MAINTENANCE DATA ^[5]

Regular maintenance is essential to ensure optimal performance and extend the service life of the chargers, with annual costs estimated between €190 and €480.

For smart charging systems, annual software subscription fees range from €95 to €480.

OPERATION DATA

For full operation, it is necessary to install the EV charger and connect it to the power grid, as well as to any platform that will be used to monitor operation (either central platform of the building or commercial platform provided by manufacturer). To use aN EV charger, it is necessary to log-in (RFID/mobile app/other).

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Total energy intensity	KPIs [kWh/m ² /year]
Energy performance and operation	KPIs (-)
Response to the needs of occupants	

PILLAR 2 KPIS: Resource Efficiency, Circularity and LCC

Operational energy costs	KPIs [€/m ² /year]
Life-cycle costs	

COSTS

INVESTMENTS ^[4]

According to the DEA, the investment cost for this type of solution depends on the level of charger installed. The following table presents the equipment and installation costs:

	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3
Equipment [€]	[0 - 850]	[360 - 3 300]	[35 800 - 85 000]
Installation [€]	[380 - 570]	[1 230 - 2 350]	[18 800 - 56 500]

SAVINGS ^[6]

Savings largely depend on variables such as the price of diesel or petrol for internal combustion engine (ICE) vehicles, the driving range, and the cost of electricity used to charge electric vehicles (EVs).

Fuel cost comparison:

- Diesel price: €2.00 per liter

- Average ICE vehicle consumption: 8 L/100 km
- Cost per kilometer (ICE): €0.16/km
- Electricity price (grid): €0.12 per kWh
- Average EV battery capacity: 50 kWh
- Average range per charge: 400 km
- Energy consumption per kilometer (EV): 0.125 kWh/km
- Cost per kilometer (EV): €0.02/km

This results in an approximate 50–60% reduction in fuel costs, with EVs being up to 8 times more cost-effective per kilometer compared to ICE vehicles.

ROI

Savings highly depends on price of diesel / petroleum used in ICE cars, driving range (mileage), price of electricity which is used to charge cars via EV charger.

To simply, if car is being driven 20 000 km per year, savings achieved by using EV (and EV charger) are around 3 000 €. This results in a ROI of less than one year.

OTHERS

PHASE

Design and Renovation.
Monitoring, Operation and Management.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Any type of building.

REFERENCES

- [1] North-West Croatia Regional - Energy Climate Agency
- [2] Various technical factsheets and commercial material from EV charger manufacturers
- [3] Acharige, S. S. G., Haque, M. E., Arif, M. T., Hosseinzadeh, N., Hasan, K. N., & Than Oo, A. M. (2019). *Review of electric vehicle charging technologies, standards, architectures, and converter configurations.*

Deakin University & RMIT University. Retrieved from <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/10102467>

[4] Alternative Fuels Data Center. (n.d.). *Electricity infrastructure development*. U.S. Department of Energy. Retrieved from <https://afdc.energy.gov/fuels/electricity-infrastructure-development>

[5] Universal EV Chargers. (2024). *The Economics of Universal EV Chargers: Cost Savings and ROI for Consumers and Businesses*. Retrieved from <https://universalevcharging.com/>

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MODELLING AND SIMULATION ENVIROMENT

Modelling and simulation environment is a service that aims to assess the energy saving potential of different energy efficiency measures in buildings and to offer recommendations for improving their energy performance.

APPLICATION

It simulates the energy performance of the buildings considering their characteristics (e.g., climate conditions, area of walls and windows, heating and cooling technologies used, etc.). The results are calibrated using also real data from sensors and bills, in order to create a realistic baseline of their energy usage. Afterwards users select which measures they would like to explore for their building and the service simulates the different energy efficiency scenarios and recommends potential actions based on their energy saving potential.

MEASURE GROUP

Digitalization system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

Pillar 2: Resources & Circularity.

Pillar 3: Climate & Human Hazard Resilience.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Functional Behaviour.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

Familiarity with a simple user interface where the indication of the building characteristics takes place, and the selection of the actions is done. Access to data related to the building features and real data related to energy consumption.

ID #48

PHOTO

**For the moment: architecture of the service.
Photo will be updated later in the Project.*

ADVANTAGES

- Energy savings.
- Data-driven insights.
- Customized feedback and recommendations.
- Higher energy efficiency.

DISADVANTAGES

- Complexity in data management
- Dependence on user compliance

LIMITATIONS

- Data availability and quality.
- Difficulty balancing energy efficiency and preservation of the building.
- Complex energy calculations.
- Energy saving assessment software can usually be operated only by specialists.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

VISUAL IMPACT

Low.

PHISICAL IMPACT

Medium.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

High.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

- Internet connection required.
- Local or cloud data storage as a backup in case of network disruptions.

GEOMETRY DATA

Location of building and climate data.

INSTALLATION DATA

Sensor placement and coverage.

MAINTENANCE & OPERATION DATA

N/A.

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Total energy intensity	KPIs [kWh/m ² / year]
Heating energy intensity	
Cooling energy intensity	
Lighting energy intensity	
Appliances energy intensity	
Energy performance & operation	KPIs (SRI score)
Response to the needs of occupants	
Energy flexibility assessment	
Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	KPIs (%)
Thermal comfort in terms of humidity	

PILLAR 2 KPIS: Resource Efficiency, Circularity and LCC

Global Warming Potential	KPIs [kg CO ₂ eq/m ² /year]
Operational Energy Costs	KPIs [€/m ² /year]
Life Cycle Cost	
Energy Circularity Indicator	KPIs (%)

PILLAR 3 KPIS: Resilience to Climate and Human-Made Hazards

Risk Impact assessment	KPIs (-)
Risk impact Level evaluation	

COSTS

INVESTMENT

Development costs for the service are covered by the INHERIT project. Post-

project usage costs will be determined through a collaborative exploitation strategy involving participating municipalities and additional interested stakeholders.

SAVINGS – ROI

N/A.

OTHERS

PHASE

Monitoring, Operation and Management.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

Medium (cutting-edge technology, evolving with data-driven advancements)

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Web-based application - Building level.

REFERENCES

- [1] Stavarakas, V., Flamos, A., 2020. A modular high-resolution demand-side management model to quantify benefits of demand-flexibility in the residential sector. *Energy Convers. Manag.* 205, 112339. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2019.112339>
- [2] Galbiati, G., Graf, F., Marino, G., Fürbringer, J.M., 2023. A modelling framework for modern heritage buildings energy simulation. *J. Build. Eng.* 80, 107973. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JOBE.2023.107973>
- [3] DigiBUILD project, 2024. D3.2: “Second wave” of DigiBUILD AI-based data-driven services for the built environment.

IEQ AND THERMAL COMFORT OPTIMISATION

ID #49

The service aims to enhance occupant comfort in CH buildings by using data-driven models to measure thermal, visual, and acoustic comfort, along with indoor air quality, and to offer recommendations for improving IEQ.

APPLICATION

The service evaluates IEQ across key building areas, detect anomalies, identify poor practices, and suggest adjustments to occupant behaviour and building settings to balance health, safety, and energy use. User feedback will also be incorporated when available to refine the insights provided. It is a measure feasible regardless the protection level of the building and with low technical requirements.

MEASURE GROUP

Digitalisation system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

Pillar 2: Resources & Circularity.

Pillar 3: Climate & Human Hazard Resilience.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Functional Behaviour.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

Provided with a set of operating sensors measuring IEQ variables in key areas of the building and a properly programmed control system, this is a ready-to-use service. Nevertheless, data safety and proper firewall configuration must be ensured.

ADVANTAGES

- Enhanced occupant comfort and well-being.
- Data-driven insights.

PHOTO

**For the moment: architecture of the service. Photo will be updated later in the Project.*

- Customized feedback and recommendations.
- Energy Efficiency.
- Fulfils upcoming obligations from the EPBD

DISADVANTAGES

- Dependence on user compliance.
- Possible disruptions from sensor failure.
- Sustainability of the system, especially on the software part and the control components.

LIMITATIONS

- Possible sensor inaccuracies and miscalibration.
- Data quality and completeness issues
- Challenges in balancing occupants' comfort and energy efficiency.
- Dependence on occupants' behaviour.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

VISUAL IMPACT

Low.

PHISICAL IMPACT

High.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

High.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

- Internet connection required.
- Local or cloud data storage as a backup in case of network disruptions.

GEOMETRY DATA

Location of sensors and smart energy meters.

INSTALLATION DATA

1. Installation of sensors.
2. Configure communication interface.
3. Set up functionalities.
4. Launch and test system.

OPERATION DATA

- Corrective: Sensor repairs and replacements.
- Preventive: Log reviews, predictive model updates, firmware and software maintenance.

MAINTENANCE DATA

The tool operates as an online service that allows the user to have access to monitoring rooms and the relevant monitored data. .

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Total energy intensity	KPIs [kWh/m ² /year]
Heating energy intensity	
Cooling energy intensity	
Lighting energy intensity	
Energy performance & operation	KPIs (-)
Response to the needs of occupants	
Energy flexibility assessment	
Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	KPIs (%)
Thermal comfort in terms of humidity	

PILLAR 2 KPIS: Resource Efficiency, Circularity and LCC

Global Warming Potential	KPIs [kg CO ₂ eq/m ² /year]
Operational Energy Costs	
Life Cycle Cost	KPIs [€/m ² /year]
Energy Circularity Indicator	KPIs (%)

PILLAR 3 KPIS: Resilience to Climate and Human-Made Hazards

Risk Impact assessment	KPIs (-)
Risk impact Level evaluation	KPIs (-)

COSTS

INVESTMENT

Determining the investment cost for implementing this service is complex, as it varies depending on the building's level of complexity and the amount of the sensors that are needed. Additionally, costs can vary significantly between countries. However, the cost typically ranges between €10 and €15 per square meter.

SAVINGS – ROI

Real-time monitoring of a building's Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ) enables the identification of specific areas that require improvement to ensure better living or working conditions. In some cases, achieving thermal comfort may not align with minimizing energy use, while in others, improvements can lead to greater energy efficiency. By understanding these dynamics, more informed and balanced decisions can be made to enhance both comfort and sustainability.

OTHERS

PHASE

Monitoring, Operation and Management.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

Medium.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Web-based application - Building level.

REFERENCES

- [1] Tsolkas, C., Spiliotis, E., Sarmas, E., Marinakis, V., Doukas, H. (2023). Dynamic energy management with thermal comfort forecasting, *Building and Environment*, 237, 110341.
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- [4] Skaloumpakas, P., Sarmas, E., Mylona, Z., Cavadenti, A., Santori, F., Marinakis, V. Predicting Thermal Comfort in Buildings With Machine Learning and Occupant Feedback," 2023 IEEE International Workshop on Metrology for Living Environment (MetroLivEnv), Milano, Italy, 2023, pp. 34-39.
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- [6] European Union. (2024). *Directive (EU) 2024/1275 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 April 2024 on the energy performance of buildings. Official Journal of the European Union*, L, 202, 9–61. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=OJ:L_202401275

ENERGY FORECASTING AND INTELLIGENT MANAGEMENT

ID #50

The service aims to optimize energy usage in buildings by leveraging data-driven models to predict energy demand and guide energy management decisions, focusing on load shifting.

APPLICATION

This service monitors energy consumption, forecasts future needs, and optimizes operational settings to balance energy efficiency with occupant comfort. It detects inefficiencies, enabling proactive adjustments, and provides energy-saving recommendations to occupants, supporting sustainability and reducing costs.

MEASURE GROUP

Digitalisation system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

Pillar 2: Resources and Circularity.

Pillar 3: Climate & Human Hazard Resilience.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Functional Behaviour.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

Provided a set of operating sensors, measuring IEQ variables in key areas of the building and energy consumption (total and/or per energy use), this is a ready-to-use service.

ADVANTAGES

- Energy savings.
- Data-driven insights.
- Customized feedback and recommendations.
- Higher energy efficiency.

PHOTO

**For the moment: architecture of the service. Photo will be updated later in the Project.*

- Fulfils upcoming obligations from the EPBD (for non-residential CH).

DISADVANTAGES

- Complexity in data management.
- Dependence on user compliance.
- Possible disruptions from meters failure.

LIMITATIONS

- Possible sensor inaccuracies and miscalibration.
- Data quality and completeness.
- Difficulty balancing comfort and energy efficiency.
- Dependence on occupants' behaviour.
- Low adaptability to building design and structure.
- Can be expensive for small buildings compared to their size.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

VISUAL IMPACT

Low.

PHISICAL IMPACT

Medium.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

High.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

- Internet connection required.
- Local or cloud data storage as a backup in case of network disruptions.

GEOMETRY DATA

Location of sensors and smart energy meters.

INSTALLATION DATA

1. Sensors' installation.
2. Configure communication interface.
3. Set up functionalities.
4. Launch and test system.

OPERATION DATA

- Corrective: Sensor repairs and replacements.
- Preventive: Log reviews, predictive model updates, firmware and software maintenance.

MAINTENANCE DATA

The tool operates as an online service that allows the user to have access to monitoring rooms and the relevant monitored data.

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Total energy intensity	KPIs [kWh/m ² / year]
Heating energy intensity	
Cooling energy intensity	
Lighting energy intensity	
Energy performance & operation	KPIs (-)
Response to the needs of occupants	
Energy flexibility assessment	
Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	KPIs (%)
Thermal comfort in terms of humidity	

PILLAR 2 KPIS: Resource Efficiency, Circularity and LCC

Global Warming Potential	KPIs [kg CO ₂ eq/m ² /year]
Operational Energy Costs	
Life Cycle Cost	KPIs [€/m ² /year]
Energy Circularity Indicator	KPIs (%)

PILLAR 3 KPIS: Resilience to Climate and Human-Made Hazards

Risk Impact assessment	KPIs (-)
Risk impact Level evaluation	KPIs (-)

COSTS

INVESTMENT

Determining the investment cost for implementing this service is complex, as it varies depending on the building's level of complexity and the amount of the sensors that are needed. Also the different cost in different countries. However, the cost typically ranges between €6 and €10 per square meter.

SAVINGS – ROI

Real-time monitoring of a building's energy consumption provides valuable insights that enable the optimization of energy usage across various systems and spaces. By continuously tracking consumption patterns, inefficiencies can be identified and addressed promptly, resulting in significant cost savings, reduced energy waste, and enhanced overall energy efficiency. This proactive approach not only supports sustainability goals but also contributes to smarter building management and long-term operational benefits.

OTHERS

PHASE

Monitoring, Operation and Management

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

Medium (cutting-edge technology, evolving with data-driven advancements)

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Web-based application - Building level.

REFERENCES

[1] T. Testasecca, M. Lazzaro, E. Sarmas and S. Stamatopoulos (2023). Recent advances on data-driven services for smart energy systems optimization and pro-active management, 2023 IEEE International Workshop on Metrology for Living Environment (MetroLivEnv), Milano, Italy, 2023, pp. 146-151.

[2] Sarmas, E., Spiliotis, E., Dimitropoulos, N., Marinakis, V., Doukas, H. (2023). Estimating the Energy Savings of Energy Efficiency Actions with Ensemble Machine Learning Models, *Applied Sciences*, 13, 4: 2749.

[3] Sarmas, E., Marinakis, V. & Doukas, H. (2022). A data-driven multicriteria decision making tool for assessing investments in energy efficiency. *Operational Research*, 22, 5597–5616.

[4] Tsolkas, C., Spiliotis, E., Sarmas, E., Marinakis, V., Doukas, H. (2023). Dynamic energy management with thermal comfort forecasting, *Building and Environment*, 237, 110341.

DIGITAL TWIN FOR HERITAGE FACILITIES: REAL TIME MONITORING, OPERATION & MANAGEMENT

ID #51

A digital twin is a virtual replica of a cultural heritage building designed to enhance its operation and management, particularly in terms of energy performance and indoor environmental quality. It provides valuable insights to building users and maintenance managers, supporting informed decision-making for conservation and efficiency.

The digital twin integrates a broad range of elements, combining static data from BIM models (capturing the building's architectural, structural and system details) with dynamic data from real-time monitoring systems. Advanced data processing transforms this information into performance indicators and scores, offering a comprehensive assessment of both building conditions and user interactions. Additionally, energy performance models enable scenario simulations and "what-if" analyses, allowing stakeholders to evaluate the impact of potential energy conservation measures before implementation.

APPLICATION

It is a low intrusive measure. Therefore, it is feasible regardless of the protection level of the building.

MEASURE GROUP

Digitalization system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

Pillar 2: Resources & Circularity.

Pillar 3: Climate & Human Hazard Resilience.

Pillar 4: Accessibility & Inclusiveness.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Functional Behaviour.

PHOTO

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

It requires full access to detailed building information, it demands strong technical expertise and dedicated support, and it needs staff training in digital twins' technologies and data interpretation.

ADVANTAGES

- Provides in-depth insights into building performance and condition.
- Identifies inefficiencies in energy use, comfort and maintenance.
- Enhances user awareness and engagement.
- Improves data management and decision-making.
- Enables real-time monitoring and analysis.

DISADVANTAGES

- High complexity of implementation.
- Requires specialised technical knowledge.

LIMITATIONS

- Need of staff training and skill development.
- Possible resistance to technological change.
- Dependence on an accurate BIM model and reliable real-time data.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

VISUAL IMPACT

Low.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

Low.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

High.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

- BIM model viewer.
- Sensor integration.
- Data analysis from sensors.
- Web Interface.

GEOMETRY DATA

The BIM files of the elements to be displayed in the digital twin are required.

INSTALLATION DATA

Steps:

1. Obtain BIM model.
2. Develop energy models.
3. Install sensors.
4. Configure communication interface.
5. Set up functionalities.
6. Launch and test system.

MAINTENANCE DATA

- Corrective: Sensor repairs and replacements.
- Preventive: Log reviews, predictive model updates, firmware and software maintenance.

OPERATION DATA

The tool operates as an online service that allows the user to access building information.

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Total energy intensity	KPIs [kWh /m ² /year]
Heating energy intensity	
Cooling energy intensity	KPIs [kWh/m ² /year]
Lighting energy intensity	
Appliances energy intensity	

Energy autonomy	KPIs (%)
Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	KPIs (%)
Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	KPIs (%)

PILLAR 2 KPIS: Resource Efficiency, Circularity and LCC

Global Warming Potential	KPIs [kg CO ₂ eq/m ² /year]
Operational Energy Costs	KPIs [€/m ² /year]
Life Cycle Cost	
Energy Circularity Indicator	KPIs (%)
Water Circularity Indicator	
Material Circularity Indicator	

PILLAR 3 KPIS: Resilience to Climate and Human-Made Hazards

Inventory of relevant Hazards	KPIs (%)
Hazards Identification	KPIs (-)
Risk impact Level evaluation	KPIs (-)

PILLAR 4 KPIS: Accessibility & Inclusiveness

Accessibility level	KPIs (%)
Public perception	KPIs (%)

COSTS

INVESTMENT

Determining the investment cost for implementing this service is complex, as it varies depending on the building's level of complexity. However, the cost typically ranges between €10 and €15 per square meter.

SAVINGS

Real-time monitoring reduces resource consumption and helps prevent damage, leading to long-term cost savings.

ROI

N/A.

OTHERS

PHASE

Monitoring, Operation and Management.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

Medium.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

It can be applied to specific rooms, floors or the entire building.

REFERENCES

[1] CEMOSA. *Projects portfolio*.

[2] Dang, X., Liu, W., Hong, Q., Wang, Y., & Chen, X. (2023). Digital twin applications on cultural world heritage sites in China: A state-of-the-art overview. *Journal of Cultural Heritage*, 64, 228–243. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.culher.2023.10.005>

REAL-TIME INSIGHTS ON ACTIVITY AND MOBILITY PATTERNS

Real-time data and analytics regarding visitor activity, mobility and crowd flow patterns as well as correlation with indoor environmental quality (IEQ).

APPLICATION

By leveraging advanced tracking technologies and data analytics, this web application (microservice) will offer valuable real-time insights into visitor behaviour, crowd flow patterns, and more.

MEASURE GROUP

Digitalization System.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

Pillar 4: Accessibility & Inclusiveness.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Functional Behaviour.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

Sensors installed in premises.

ADVANTAGES

Provides pilot administrators and staff with valuable insights derived not only from real-time data regarding mobility but also from their correlation with the IEQ.

DISADVANTAGES

Cost of initial investment; prompt to errors and misleading insights due to low accuracy of sensors installed.

LIMITATIONS

Availability of infrastructure.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

ID #52

PHOTO

VISUAL IMPACT

Medium.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

High.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

High.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION¹

TECHNICAL FEATURES

People Count [persons]	0 to inf.
Humidity [%]	0 to 100
Temperature [°C]	-20 to 60
CO ₂ concentration [ppm]	400 to 5000

GEOMETRY DATA

Height [mm]	65
Width [mm]	20.5
Length [mm]	68

INSTALLATION DATA

Installation time [days]	Simple connection to a building; Depends on size of building (approx. 1-30)
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MAINTENANCE DATA

Type of maintenance	Change batteries
Lifespan [years]	~ 3

OPERATION DATA

Required to have permits to install sensors in premises.

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Total energy intensity	KPIs [kWh/m ² / year]
Heating energy intensity	
Cooling energy intensity	
Lighting energy intensity	
Appliances energy intensity	
Energy autonomy	KPIs (%)
Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	KPIs (%)
Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	KPIs (%)

PILLAR 4 KPIS: Accessibility & Inclusiveness

Accessibility level	KPIs (%)
Inclusiveness and openness level	KPIs (%)

COSTS

INVESTMENTS

Determining the investment cost for implementing this service is complex, as it varies depending on the building's level of complexity. Development costs for the service are covered by the INHERIT project. Post-project usage costs will be determined through a collaborative exploitation strategy involving participating municipalities and additional interested stakeholders.

SAVING

N/A.

ROI

N/A.

OTHERS

PHASE

Monitoring, Operation and Management.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

Medium.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Can be implemented either on specific rooms/floors or even in the whole building.

REFERENCES

[1] ShopIoT. (2025). *Milesight AM307 LoRaWAN® indoor ambience monitoring sensor EU868*. Retrieved from https://shopiot.eu/products/copy-of-milesight-am307-lorawan%C2%AE-indoor-ambience-monitoring-sensor-eu868?srsId=AfmBOopftS8jwqNGbB2D7GFljZTLNwY-q4nlsx_ClzygBc1ZQt4Q0z01

PREVENTIVE MAINTENANCE WITH H- BIM

ID #53

A methodological service approach for preventive maintenance in Cultural Heritage buildings, supported by a digital ecosystem based on Heritage Building Information Modelling (H-BIM). It enables proactive condition assessment and risk-based planning by integrating geometric data, historical records, and Technical Inspection (TI) results. This approach supports long-term decision-making and sustainable conservation.

APPLICATION

Applicable in Cultural Heritage buildings requiring systematic and proactive maintenance strategies. Through the methodological integration of H-BIM and TI, this service enables structured data management, long-term asset planning, and optimization of conservation workflows.

MEASURE GROUP

Digitalization system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

Pillar 2: Resources & Circularity.

Pillar 3: Climate & Human Hazard Resilience.

Pillar 4: Accessibility & Inclusiveness.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Functional Behaviour.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

- Request a suitable H-BIM model with adequate LOD.
- Data access (Historical + TI).
- Requires Revit or similar tool.

ADVANTAGES

- Enhances maintenance planning.
- Decision-making support.

PHOTO

- High understanding of current building conditions.
- Centralises building's data.
- Enables risk anticipation and cost optimisation

DISADVANTAGES

- Requires training in using BIM tools.
- High dependency on the availability and quality of existing BIM data.

LIMITATIONS

- Restrictive for small organizations without access to Revit.
- Limited to buildings with existing or developed H-BIM model.
- High implementation cost if no H-BIM model is available

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

Medium.

VISUAL IMPACT

Low.

PHISICAL IMPACT

Low.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

High.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

The system requires an active internet connection for data synchronisation and remote access. In addition, it is necessary to

install Autodesk Revit in order to access this service.

GEOMETRY DATA

An accurate H-BIM model including geometric and material data is required. Model creation can be resource-intensive due to heritage-specific complexity.

INSTALLATION & MAINTENANCE DATA

Local installation of Revit or equivalent software is required.

MAINTENANCE DATA

The digital model must be updated periodically following inspections. Maintenance includes reviewing condition states, incorporating new records, and verifying element attributes.

OPERATION DATA

Users interact with the H-BIM model to plan, register, and visualize maintenance tasks. Access is granted through desktop environments with licensed software.

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

N/A. This service does not directly affect physical energy-related systems.

PILLAR 2 KPIS: Resource Efficiency, Circularity and LCC

Payback period	KPIs [year]
Life Cycle Cost	KPIs [€/m ² /year]

PILLAR 3 KPIS: Resilience to Climate and Human-Made Hazards

Inventory of relevant Hazards	KPIs (%)
Hazards Identification	KPIs (-)
Risk Management Plan	
Risk impact Level evaluation	

PILLAR 4 KPIS: Accessibility & Inclusiveness

Inclusiveness and openness level	KPIs (-)
Increased property value	KPIs (%)
Number of local jobs created	
Cultural Enrichment	
Public perception	

COSTS

INVESTMENTS

The cost estimation presented here is indicative and based on hypothetical implementation scenarios. Development costs are currently covered by the INHERIT project, and post-project usage costs will be defined through an exploitation strategy in collaboration with the participating and interested municipalities.

The implementation cost of this service is highly dependent on the availability and adequacy of an existing H-BIM model.

Scenario	Description	Estimated Cost
Existing H-BIM model	<i>Minor updates and TI integration</i>	15–30 €/m ²
No H-BIM model	<i>Full model creation</i>	50–70 €/m ² or more

Key cost drivers:

- High geometric complexity of Cultural Heritage assets
- Limited availability of standard BIM object libraries
- Need for custom parametric families and historical detail
- Qualified personnel for HBIM modelling and technical inspections

- Software licensing and platform integration

Interreg SUDOE – CAREEN. <https://careen-sudoe.eu/>

SAVING

Return on investment is expected through:

- Avoidance of major structural or material failures
- Better eligibility for public funding and CH programmes
- Increased operational efficiency and preservation value
- Asset valorisation through digital enablement

ROI

Return based on the reduction of corrective interventions and prolongation of heritage lifespan.

OTHERS

PHASE

Preservation and maintenance.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

Medium.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Digital application. Building-level deployment. Adaptable to different scales according to the needs of the heritage asset (from an element to a room to the whole building).

REFERENCES

[1] T3.1 INHERIT Technical Inspection. CARTIF

[2] buildingSMART Spain. (2022). Guía del Usuario BIM. Documento 14: BIM aplicado al Patrimonio Cultural. buildingSMART Spain. <https://www.buildingsmart.es/documento-14-bim-aplicado-al-patrimonio-cultural/>

[3] CAREEN Project. (2023). Recomendaciones para el modelado H-BIM aplicado al diagnóstico y conservación preventiva del patrimonio arquitectónico.

GIS-BASED SOLUTION FOR SUSTAINABLE HERITAGE MAINTENANCE

ID #54

The objective of the service is to assist heritage managers, engineers, architects, and building operators in developing effective maintenance plans for CH buildings based on the characteristics and similarities of the latter.

APPLICATION

The service offers a GIS-based interface that visualizes CH buildings on an interactive map, summarizing key information about each building's architectural style, design, use, and overall condition. By utilizing advanced algorithms, the service categorizes CH buildings into clusters based on their similarities, facilitating targeted maintenance strategies and informed decision-making.

MEASURE GROUP

Digitalisation system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

Pillar 2: Resources & Circularity.

Pillar 3: Climate & Human Hazard Resilience.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Functional behaviour.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

- Ready-to-use service with no specific conditions.

ADVANTAGES

- Informed decision-making.
- Efficiency in maintenance planning.
- Visual representation.

DISADVANTAGES

- Complexity of implementation in new areas due to high data requirements.

PHOTO

**For the moment: Service in progress. Photo will be updated later in the Project.*

LIMITATIONS

- Variability in building characteristics in different areas.
- Regulatory constraints.
- Technological barriers.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

VISUAL IMPACT

Low.

PHISICAL IMPACT

Low.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

Medium.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

- Interactive GIS map viewer.
- Spatial clustering algorithms for building classification.
- Metadata visualization
- Filtering and search capabilities.
- Web-based user interface.

GEOMETRY DATA

- Geolocation (coordinates) of each CH building.
- Building metadata

INSTALLATION DATA

- Gather and standardize building data (geometry + metadata).

- Import datasets into the GIS platform.
- Configure spatial clustering parameters.
- Customize user interface (e.g., branding, language).
- Launch the service and provide user access.

OPERATION DATA

- Visualize CH assets on a map.
- Analyze building similarities for maintenance prioritization.

MAINTENANCE DATA

- Fixing errors in data input or GIS layers.
- Regular updates of database content, algorithmic model tuning, UI improvements.
- Periodic validation and enrichment of building metadata.

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Total energy intensity	KPIs [kWh/m ² / year]
Heating energy intensity	
Cooling energy intensity	
Lighting energy intensity	
Appliances energy intensity	
Energy autonomy	KPIs (%)
Energy performance & operation	KPIs (-)
Response to the needs of occupants	
Energy flexibility assessment	
Thermal comfort in terms of air temperature	KPIs (%)
Thermal comfort in terms of humidity	

PILLAR 2 KPIS: Resource Efficiency, Circularity and LCC

Global Warming Potential	KPIs [kg CO ₂ eq/m ² /year]
Operational Energy Costs	KPIs [€/m ² /year]
Life Cycle Cost	
Energy Circularity Indicator	KPIs (%)

PILLAR 3 KPIS: Resilience to Climate and Human-Made Hazards

Vulnerability and Exposure	KPIs (-)
Severity of consequences and Likelihood of occurrence	

COSTS

INVESTMENT

The total cost of the service is primarily related to the development and maintenance of the digital platform, as most geospatial and heritage data are available through open-source repositories at no cost. An estimated cost for the development and ongoing maintenance is €7,000 – €10,000 per 500-building dataset, depending on the specific requirements and features implemented.

SAVINGS – ROI

N/A.

OTHERS

PHASE

Preservation and maintenance.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

Medium.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Web-based application - City level.

REFERENCES

- [1] Sánchez-Aparicio, L.-J., Masciotta, M.-J., García-Alvarez, J., Ramos, L.F., Oliveira, D.V., Martín-Jiménez, J.-A., González-Aguilera, D., Monteiro, P. (2020). Web-GIS approach to preventive conservation of heritage buildings, *Automation in Construction*, 118, 103304.
- [2] Fabbri, K., Zuppiroli, M., Ambrogio, K. (2012). Heritage buildings and energy performance: Mapping with GIS tools, *Energy and Buildings*, 48, 137-145.
- [3] Malaperdas, G., Grethe, R., Zacharias, N. (2023). Depicting the past: The value of old maps and topographic diagrams in cultural heritage through GIS, *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports*, 52, 104276.
- [4] Santos, B., Gonçalves, J., Martins, A.M., Pérez-Cano, M.T., Mosquera-Adell, E., Dimelli, D., Lagarias, A., Almeida, P.G. (2021). GIS in Architectural Teaching and Research: Planning and Heritage, *Education Sciences*, 11, 307.

REINFORCEMENT OF LOAD – BEARING STRUCTURE

ID #65

This measure involves reinforcing the load-bearing structure of a building by repairing cracks or weaknesses that could compromise the building's structural stability, ensuring safety and longevity.

APPLICATION

The cracks will be repaired using materials identical to those originally used in construction and techniques like fiber-reinforced polymers or steel supports.

MEASURE GROUP

Structural system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 3: Climate & Human Hazard Resilience.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Foundations and Structure.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

- Bureaucratic requirements.

ADVANTAGES

- Preserves the building.
- Enhances safety and security.
- Increases the value of the building.
- Extends the building's functional lifespan.

DISADVANTAGES

- Potential loss of historical authenticity.
- High implementation cost.

LIMITATIONS

Technical complexity of the repair process.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

Medium.

VISUAL IMPACT

High.

PHOTO

PHYSICAL IMPACT

High.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

High.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

A materials study of the structural element must be conducted before reinforcement to ensure compatibility.

GEOMETRY DATA

Accurate documentation of the building's geometry is essential, using tools like laser scanning or photogrammetry to guide reinforcement design.

INSTALLATION DATA

Reinforcement involves assessing structural integrity, selecting compatible materials and applying appropriate techniques like fiber-reinforced polymers or steel supports. Installations should be made in the right environment or weather conditions (ideally when it is not raining, and temperatures are neither too high nor too low).

MAINTENANCE DATA

Type of maintenance | Visual inspection

OPERATION DATA

No operation is required after implementation.

IMPACT

PILLAR 3 KPIS: Climate & Human Hazard Resilience.

Hazards Identification	KPI (-)
Risk Management Plan(s)	
Risk Impact assessment: Vulnerability and Exposure	
Risk impact Level evaluation: Severity of consequences and Likelihood of occurrence	

COSTS

INVESTMENT

Costs depend on building size, required reinforcement and materials, typically involving significant investment due to specialized work.

SAVINGS

Prevents future structural deterioration and costly repairs while preserving the building's value and functionality over time.

ROI

Though initial costs are high, benefits include extended building lifespan, enhanced safety and cultural heritage preservation.

OTHERS

PHASE

Design and Renovation.
Preservation and maintenance.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

Medium - High

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Only on items require intervention.

REFERENCES

[1] CEMOSA portfolio.

[2] Kruszka, L. (2018). Reinforcement of brick historic buildings threatened by structural damages or by failure. MATEC Web of Conferences, 175, 03013. https://www.matec-conferences.org/articles/mateconf/pdf/2018/33/mateconf_ece2018_03013.pdf

MOISTURE PROTECTION

ID #66

Moisture can severely damage building materials such as concrete, wood and brick, leading to mould, fungi and bacteria that pose health risks. It also accelerates metal corrosion, weakens joints and seals, reduces energy efficiency, and, in cold climates, causes freeze-thaw damage that worsens structural cracks. Proper waterproofing and maintenance are essential to preserving the durability and habitability of cultural heritage buildings.

APPLICATION

Injection of epoxy resins on both sides of the wall at the lowest possible level, combined with mortar replacement up to one meter using draining, fungicidal mortar. Interior surfaces should be finished with silicate paint. Additional protective measures include drainage systems, waterproof barriers, and moisture-resistant finishes.

MEASURE GROUP

Structural system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 1: Energy & Comfort.

Pillar 3: Climate & Human Hazard Resilience.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Foundations and Structure.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

It requires an assessment of aesthetic impact and must be carried out by professionals.

ADVANTAGES

- Effective waterproofing.
- Repairs cracks and fissures.
- Prevents mould and mildew.
- Long-lasting protection.

PHOTO

DISADVANTAGES

- High cost.
- Invasive application.
- Potential chemical hazards.
- The waterproofing effect may be limited in time.

LIMITATIONS

Epoxy resin may not be sufficient for large cracks, requiring additional structural repairs. It also does not address the underlying moisture issues like poor drainage or inadequate waterproofing in other areas.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

Medium.

VISUAL IMPACT

Low – Medium.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

Medium.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

Low.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

Waterproofing efficiency (%)	95-100
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INSTALLATION DATA

Installation time [days]	6-9
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MAINTENANCE DATA

Type of maintenance	- Annual visual inspections - Reapplication of one coat every 5 - 10 years
Useful life [years]	20 - 30

OPERATION DATA

Needs of minimal operation, periodic inspections and reapplication is required.

IMPACT

PILLAR 1 KPIS: Energy Performance and IEQ

Thermal comfort in terms of indoor humidity	KPIs (%)
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PILLAR 3 KPIS: Climate & Human Hazard Resilience.

Risk Impact assessment: Vulnerability and Exposure	KPI (-)
Risk Management Plan	KPI (-)

COSTS

INVESTMENT

The initial investment depends on the location and the particularities of the project. The estimated costs range from approximately €80 to €195 per square metre.

SAVINGS - ROI

N/A.

OTHERS

PHASE

- Design and Renovation.
- Preservation and maintenance.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Begin with a small test application to assess compatibility with the building materials. If successful, proceed with the full-scale implementation across the structure.

REFERENCES

- [1] CEMOSA. *Projects portfolio*.
- [2] INHERIT. *Internal references of INHERIT*.
- [3] TSA conservacion. *Control of moisture by capillarity and condensation in buildings*. Retrieved from <https://tsaconservacion.com/control-de-humedades-por-capilaridad-y-condensacion-de-edificios-gipuzkoa/>

HERITAGE BUILDINGS ENVIRONMENTAL CLIMATE SCENARIOS

ID #70

A web-based tool that assesses the impact of climate change on CH buildings at the city level. It evaluates key hazards (extreme temperatures, flooding and wind risk) and calculates risk KPIs across various climate change scenarios to support informed preservation and maintenance.

APPLICATION

Used for city-level climate risk assessment of CH buildings, applying scenario analysis, risk modelling and KPI calculation. The tool integrates climate data sources, hazard models and city-specific building information.

MEASURE GROUP

Digitalization system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 3: Climate & Human Hazard Resilience.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Functional behaviour.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

Ready-to-use service with no specific conditions.

ADVANTAGES

- Informed decision-making.
- Promotes local climate adaptation.
- Comprehensive risk analysis.

DISADVANTAGES

- Data dependency.
- Requires climate scenarios understanding.

LIMITATIONS

- Data granularity.
- User skill requirement.

PHOTO

*Mock up of the service showing the risk to flood hazard in Jastrebarsko pilot.

- Scope restriction (focus on three specific hazards).

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

Medium.

VISUAL IMPACT

Low.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

Low.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

High. It can be applied to any CH city, regardless the level of protection.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

The system requires an active internet connection for data synchronization and remote access.

GEOMETRY DATA

N/A.

INSTALLATION DATA

No installation needed, as it is a web-based service.

MAINTENANCE DATA

Timely updates would be needed to ensure quality (to be agreed, e.g., once a year).

OPERATION DATA

The tool operates as an online service accessible via the INHERIT Platform. It requires user input for the selection of hazards and scenarios, and the different features and options.

IMPACT

PILLAR 3 KPIS: Climate & Human Hazard Resilience.

Inventory of relevant hazards	KPIs (%)
Hazards identification	KPIs (-)
Risk impact assessment: Risk impact Level evaluation	

COSTS

INVESTMENTS

The development costs of the service are covered by the INHERIT project. Post-project usage costs will be determined through an exploitation strategy in collaboration with participating and further interested municipalities.

SAVINGS

By providing risk assessment, the service can help municipalities prevent or reduce costly damage to CH buildings, leading to potential savings in emergency repairs and long-term maintenance. Additionally, using climate adaptation measures on these insights may reduce insurance costs and protect economic and cultural value.

ROI

The service's return on investment lies in its ability to support data-driven decision-making, which can enhance the longevity and resilience of CH buildings. Municipalities and CH managers can prioritise cost-effective, proactive preservation actions, potentially reducing the need for more expensive interventions over time. Quantifying ROI depends on factors like risk levels, projected damage

prevention and the specific financial and cultural value of the assets protected.

OTHERS

PHASE

Preservation and maintenance.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

Medium (cutting-edge).

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

Web-based application. City-level decision-making.

REFERENCES

- [1] ARCH Decision Support System (DSS): <https://savingculturalheritage.eu/solutions/tools>
- [2] CLIMATE-ADAPT Urban Adaptation Support Tool (UAST): <https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/knowledge/tools/urban-ast>
- [3] IPCC AR6 Working Group II Report – Chapter 8: Urban Systems and Human Settlements: <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg2/>

ELEVATOR

ID #71

Installing an elevator as an alternative to stairs aims to ensure accessible vertical circulation for people with reduced mobility. This intervention can be addressed either by installing a single-person lift attached to an existing wall, or through a larger-scale construction that allows the installation of a higher-capacity elevator suitable for multiple passengers.

APPLICATION

Conservators often prefer the external placement of the elevator to avoid damaging the interior. However, even an external solution must be carefully designed to blend with the façade's style.

MEASURE GROUP

Accessibility.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 4: Accessibility & Inclusiveness.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Accessibility.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

It is necessary to request approval from the conservation authorities. They will assess how the elevator could impact the building's preservation.

ADVANTAGES

- Improved accessibility.
- Reduces the risk of falls (on stairs).
- Increased property value.

DISADVANTAGES

- High cost.
- Impact on the preservation of original elements.
- Additional bureaucracy.
- Structural challenges.
- Visual impact.

PHOTO ^[1]

**Photographs of the construction of an elevator at the Cathedral of Santa María, in Vitoria-Gasteiz (Spain), integrated within a tower. This cylindrical tower, built with sandstone masonry, was designed to blend visually with the monument.*

LIMITATIONS

- Design and placement restrictions.
- Space limitations.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

VISUAL IMPACT

High.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

Medium – High.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

High.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

Power [kW] | 4 - 15

GEOMETRY DATA ^[2]

Standard cabin dimensions (wheelchair accessible):

Height [mm]	2100 – 2300
Width [mm]	1100 – 1400
Depth [mm]	1400 – 1600

INSTALLATION DATA

Installation time [h] | 500 - 1000

MAINTENANCE DATA

Routine inspections, lubrication and cleaning, control system calibration, emergency, and safety tests.

Lifespan [years] | 20 - 30

OPERATION DATA

Operational needs: energy efficiency and power supply, access control and security, temperature and humidity control, vibration and noise reduction, user accessibility and interface, routine maintenance scheduling.

IMPACT

PILLAR 4 KPIS: Accessibility & Inclusiveness

Accessibility level	KPIs (%)
Inclusiveness and openness level	KPIs (-)
Public perception	KPIs (%)

COSTS

INVESTMENTS

Investing in an elevator for a CH building is a significant financial commitment that requires careful planning, heritage-compatible design, and collaboration with conservation experts. The total cost can range from € 100.000 to over € 1 million, depending on the complexity of the project

and the building's structural and heritage needs.

SAVINGS - ROI

There are no direct energy savings or payback period associated with this measure, as it does not lead to a reduction in consumption. However, it does contribute to the increased value of the property, allowing for an indirect return on investment.

OTHERS

PHASE

Design and Renovation.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

The scale of implementation is influenced significantly by the type of building, with residential buildings typically requiring smaller solutions and commercial or institutional buildings needing larger, more complex systems.

REFERENCES

[1] Fundación Catedral Santa María. (2010). *Communications in the Canton of Santa María*. Retrieved from <https://www.catedralvitoria.eus/es/restauracion-patrimonio/25/comunicaciones-en-canton-de-santa-maria-2010>

[2] UNE. (2022). UNE-EN 81-70:2022: Safety rules for the construction and installation of lifts.

HAINDRAIL

ID #73

The installation of handrails on stairs and ramps will facilitate access to heritage buildings for users with mobility impairments.

APPLICATION ^[1]

Double handrails shall be installed on flights of stairs and ramps. On flights wider than 4.00 m, a double handrail shall be fitted in the central area. The handrail shall be stable, rigid and firmly fixed.

MEASURE GROUP

Accessibility.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 4: Accessibility & Inclusiveness.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Accessibility.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

It is a measure feasible regardless the protection level of the building and with low technical requirements.

ADVANTAGES

- Safety and security.
- Ease of ascent and descent.
- Provision of additional support to individuals with mobility impairment.
- Enhances user comfort.

DISADVANTAGES

- Collisions with other architectural elements.
- Difficulties in adapting the design to CH buildings.

LIMITATIONS

In confined spaces, handrails can take up extra space and make the area appear smaller.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

PHOTO ^[3]

VISUAL IMPACT

Medium.

PHISICAL IMPACT

Medium.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

Low.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

N/A.

GEOMETRY DATA ^[1]

Grip width diameter [cm]	[4,5 – 5]
Vertical separation with clamping system [cm]	4
Lower handrail [m]	[0,65 - 0,75]
Upper handrail [m]	[0,95 - 1,05]

MATERIAL DATA ^[2]

Wood	Elegant and traditional
Metal	Durable and resistant
Glass	It bring light and transparency to the space.

INSTALLATION DATA

For its installation, supports and anchors will be required to secure it to the surface.

MAINTENANCE DATA

Continuous cleaning will be required.

OPERATION DATA

N/A.

IMPACT

PILLAR 4 KPIS: Accessibility, Inclusiveness, Openness and Socioeconomic Sustainability

Accessibility level		KPIs (%)
Inclusiveness and openness level		KPIs (%)

COSTS

INVESTMENTS

Depends on the type of material and the length of the section.

SAVINGS - ROI

There is no direct energy savings or payback period associated with this measure, as it does not lead to a reduction in consumption. However, it does contribute to the increased value of the property, allowing for an indirect return on investment.

OTHERS

PHASE

Design and Renovation.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

High.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

All the building.

REFERENCES

[1] Orden VIV/561/2010. Retrieved from BOE:
<https://www.boe.es/boe/dias/2010/03/11/pdfs/BOE-A-2010-4057.pdf>

[2] Solo escaleras. Retrieved from <https://soloescaleras.es/2024/02/19/usuarios-y-tipos-pasamanos-de-escaleras/>

[3] TUR4all. *Accessible tourism – Palacio de Velázquez*. Retrieved May 8, 2025, from <https://www.tur4all.com/es/home>

ISA SIGNAL

ID #76

The ISA (International Signal of Access) sign is a symbol that indicates the accessibility of a place for people with disabilities.

APPLICATION

Accessible entrances to the building, accessible routes, accessible parking spaces and accessible restrooms (toilet, changing room and accessible shower) shall be marked with ISA, supplemented, if necessary, with directional arrows.

MEASURE GROUP

Accessibility.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 4: Accessibility & Inclusiveness.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Accessibility.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

It is a measure feasible regardless the protection level of the building and with low technical requirements.

ADVANTAGES

- Facilitates the identification of areas, services and equipment accessible to people with disabilities, promoting their inclusion and autonomy.
- As a globally recognized symbol, it removes linguistic and cultural barriers, allowing anyone, regardless of language, to understand its meaning.

DISADVANTAGES

Visual Overload.

LIMITATIONS

Limited Physical Space.

SOCIAL ACCEPTATION

High.

PHOTO

VISUAL IMPACT

Medium.

PHISICAL IMPACT

Medium.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

High.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

N/A.

GEOMETRY DATA ^{[1] [2]}

Small size [cm]	15 x 15
Medium size [cm]	30 x 30
Large size [cm]	45 x 45
Installation height [cm]	80 -170

COLOUR DATA ^[1]

Background	Dark Blue
Figure and edges	White

MATERIAL DATA

- Aluminium.
- High - density plastic.
- Reflective materials.

IMPACT

PILLAR 4 KPIS: Accessibility & Inclusiveness

Accessibility level	KPIs (%)
Inclusiveness and openness level	KPIs (%)

COSTS

INVESTMENTS ^[3]

The cost of an accessibility sign varies according to size, material, quantity and personalization. For example, a 30x30 cm sign in reflective aluminium costs around 20 euros.

SAVING - ROI

There is no direct energy savings or payback period associated with this measure, as it does not lead to a reduction in consumption. However, it does contribute to the increased value of the property, allowing for an indirect return on investment.

OTHERS

PHASE

Design and Renovation.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

N/A.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

All the building.

REFERENCES

[1] ISO 7001. (2023).

[2] Polaris Sign. Retrieved from <https://xn--sealizacionaccesible-46b.com/senalizacion-sia/>

[3] PUNTODIS. Retrieved from Accesible solutions:

<https://puntodis.com/producto/simbolo-internacional-de-accesibilidad-sia-braille/>

[4] Simbolo de accesibilidad para la movilidad. (2002). Retrieved from UNE 41501.

[5] SUA 9: Accesibilidad. (2022). Retrieved from Ministerio de Transportes, Movilidad y Agenda Urbana: <https://www.codigotecnico.org/pdf/Documentos/SUA/DcmSUA.pdf>

INTERACTIVE SCREEN USE & AR-VR INTERFACES

ID #79

This service uses AR/VR to support the maintenance and renovation for CHs.

APPLICATION

Used for supporting on-the-job training, providing different maintenance and renovation scenarios in the virtual environment to reduce time and cost, and improving work quality.

MEASURE GROUP

Digitalisation system.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 3: Climate & Human Hazard Resilience.
Pillar 4: Accessibility & Inclusiveness.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Functional Behaviour.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

It requires full access to the building information and strong technical support and staff with knowledge of VR/AR.

ADVANTAGES

- Increased efficiency.
- Time and cost savings.
- Improved maintenance & renovation.
- Immersive training and simulation.

DISADVANTAGES

Complexity of implementation due to detailed building model and high data requirements.

LIMITATIONS

Technological limitations as current VR/AR technology may struggle to replicate highly detailed or complex environments.

PHOTO

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

VISUAL IMPACT

Medium.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

Medium.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

Medium.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION

TECHNICAL FEATURES

VR EQUIPMENT

- Dual AMOLED 3.5-inch diagonal screen.
- 1440 x 1600 pixels per eye.
- 90 Hz refresh rate.

AR EQUIPMENT

- 2048 x 1080 pixels per eye.
- 1080p video.
- 2 IR cameras.
- Gesture recognition and voice command features.

OTHER INFORMATION

Field of view	110 degrees
Eye tracking	Yes
Integrated audio	Yes
High- resolution display	Yes
Gesture recognition	Yes

GEOMETRY DATA

N/A.

INSTALLATION DATA

Setup time for VR environment [h]	2 - 3
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MAINTENANCE DATA

N/A.

OPERATION DATA

Depending on the kinds of the sensors installed in the building.

IMPACT
PILLAR 3 KPIS: Climate & Human Hazard Resilience.

Inventory of relevant Hazards	KPIs (%)
Hazards Identification	KPIs (-)
Risk Management Plan	
Risk Impact assessment	
Risk impact Level evaluation	

PILLAR 4 KPIS: Accessibility & Inclusiveness

Accessibility level	KPIs (%)
Inclusiveness and openness level	KPIs (-)
Cultural Enrichment	KPIs (%)
Public perception	

COSTS
INVESTMENT

The estimated cost for implementing the service includes both hardware and software components. For hardware, a standard AR device such as the Microsoft HoloLens 2 costs approximately €3,100 per unit. However, the service is designed to be compatible with a broader range of AR/VR-enabled devices, allowing flexibility based on user preferences and available resources.

As for the software, implementation costs are minimal. The core system is already developed and can be deployed without

additional licensing fees. Future customization or integration may incur marginal costs depending on specific use cases, but the base software is ready for immediate use.

SAVINGS

Utilizing an AR/VR environment can enhance the efficiency of maintenance and renovation strategies, potentially leading to long-term cost savings.

ROI

N/A.

OTHERS
PHASE

Preservation and maintenance.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

Medium.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

It can be applied to specific rooms, floors or the entire building.

REFERENCES

- [1] Casini, M. (2022). Extended reality for smart building operation and maintenance: A review. *Energies*, 15(10), 3785. <https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/15/10/3785>
- [2] Bitnamic. (n.d.). *Microsoft HoloLens 2: Features and improvements*. <https://bitnamic.net/en/microsoft-hololens-2-features-and-improvements/>

SOCIAL LABS

ID #82

Social Labs aim to establish a co-creation and collaboration framework that integrates approaches from Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) to address societal challenges and promote resilience. This is achieved through the implementation of interdisciplinary and co-design-oriented workshops with adjacent methodological activities (such as world café, mapping walk etc.). The Social Labs serve as platforms for engaging diverse stakeholders in participatory activities, fostering collective intelligence, and leveraging cultural heritage as both subject and catalyst for positive transformation.

APPLICATION

Implementation of a Social Science Framework that integrates transdisciplinary and multi-stakeholder perspectives through socially engaging inclusive and participatory approaches. By conducting stakeholder consultations and tailor-made co-creation processes within INHERIT pilots, the labs facilitate real-world experiments that promote mutual learning and leverage local tacit knowledge tied to specific sites and buildings.

MEASURE GROUP

Inclusiveness & Openness.

INHERIT PILLAR

Pillar 4: Accessibility & Inclusiveness.

HEADING OF TECHNICAL INSPECTIONS

Accessibility.

GENERIC INFORMATION

IMPLEMENTATION CONDITIONS

Social labs, as a series of in-person meetings, are easy to implement, irrespective of the protection level of the CH site; Social labs are not affecting the

PHOTO

physical/built environment of the CH site, thus can be implemented also in highly protected areas. As a means of interdisciplinary and co-creative discussion and collaboration between stakeholders, social labs help to co-design ideas and visions for possible interventions at the CH site. Only the actual implementation of these ideas or visions may take the form of constructional changes etc.

ADVANTAGES

- Foster Collaboration and Inclusivity.
- Drive Innovation through Co-Creation.
- Ensure Social Acceptance and Relevance.

DISADVANTAGES

Risk of little or no understanding of the social lab methodological approach at the side of lab attendees; In connection to that, risk of mismatch between the objectives related to the co-design approach and the expected outcomes of the social lab workshop.

SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE

High.

VISUAL IMPACT

High.

PHYSICAL IMPACT

N/A.

CH PROTECTION LEVEL

Medium.

TECHNICAL INFORMATION
TECHNICAL FEATURES

N/A.

GEOMETRY - INSTALLATION – OPERATION DATA

N/A.

MAINTENANCE DATA

Stakeholder engagement.

IMPACT

PILLAR 4 KPIS: Accessibility, Inclusiveness, Openness and Socioeconomic Sustainability

Accessibility level	KPIs (-)
Inclusiveness & openness level	KPI (-)
Cultural enrichment	KPI (%)
Public perception	

COSTS
INVESTMENTS – SAVINGS – ROI

N/A

OTHERS
PHASE

Applicable in all rounds of the social labs, including round 1, 2, 3, 4.

TECHNOLOGY MATURITY

N/A.

SCALE OF IMPLEMENTATION

The Social Labs are designed to address challenges specific to the communities or sites involved while also generating insights and solutions that can be scaled up or replicated in other contexts.

REFERENCES

ISO. (2010). *ISO 26000:2010 - Social responsibility*. International Organization for Standardization.